

**Exploring Value Creation Mechanisms In Enterprise Architecture: A Realist
Evaluation Of Healthcare Organisations Evidenced In The UK**

Joshua Asoeweh Tadam

Thesis

Doctor of Business Administration (Research)

Banner ID: B00354904

UWS
UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

Table of Contents

1	CHAPTER ONE: OVERVIEW OF THE THESIS.....	26
1.1	INTRODUCTION.....	26
1.2	ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE (EA) AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	29
1.3	HIGH FAILURE RATE OF EA	29
1.3.1	<i>Why is EA a hard sell despite the potential rewards it can bring to Organisations?</i>	<i>32</i>
1.4	MOTIVATION FOR THE RESEARCH EVALUATION (GAP)	34
1.4.1	<i>Motivations For Research into The Mechanisms of EA Management</i>	<i>35</i>
1.5	THE AIM, OBJECTIVES, QUESTIONS AND FOCUS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY	36
1.5.1	<i>Research Aim</i>	<i>36</i>
1.5.2	<i>Research Questions.....</i>	<i>36</i>
1.5.3	<i>Research Objectives.....</i>	<i>37</i>
1.5.4	<i>Significance Of the Study.....</i>	<i>38</i>
1.5.5	<i>Research Focus.....</i>	<i>38</i>
1.6	SCOPE OF THE STUDY	38
1.6.1	<i>Axioms.....</i>	<i>39</i>
1.7	THE ORGANISATION OF THE THESIS	41
1.7.1	<i>Chapter One: Introduction</i>	<i>41</i>
1.7.2	<i>Chapter Two: Literature Review.....</i>	<i>41</i>
1.7.3	<i>Chapter Three: Conceptual Framework.....</i>	<i>42</i>
1.7.4	<i>Chapter Four: Methodology.....</i>	<i>42</i>
1.7.5	<i>Chapter Five: Analysis</i>	<i>42</i>
1.7.6	<i>Chapter Six: Findings and Summary of Findings.....</i>	<i>42</i>
1.7.7	<i>Chapter Seven: Conclusion.....</i>	<i>43</i>
1.8	SUMMARY	43
2	CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	44
2.1	INTRODUCTION.....	44
2.2	SCOPING THE LITERATURE	45

2.3	WHAT IS ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE (EA)?.....	46
2.4	OVER TWO DECADES OF NATIONAL HEALTH IT: EXPLORING STRATEGY, STRUCTURE, AND SYSTEMS IN THE ENGLISH NHS.	50
2.5	THE IMPACT OF THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON EA AND THE RESEARCH	53
2.6	ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE CHALLENGES AND LESSONS FROM NHS DIGITAL’S TRANSFORMATION PROGRAMMES.....	53
2.7	BACKGROUND OF CULTURE, RELATIONS AND AGENCY, FUNDING, TECHNOLOGY AND STRUCTURE OF HEALTH AND SOCIAL CARE IN ENGLAND	57
2.7.1	<i>About NHS England</i>	57
2.7.2	<i>Structure of NHS Digital</i>	58
2.7.3	<i>NHS Digital – Assuring Technology and Funding in the NHS</i>	60
2.7.4	<i>Vision and Strategy for Technology</i>	62
2.7.5	<i>The Health and Social Care Act 2012 (HSCA)</i>	62
2.7.6	<i>From the Five-Year Forward View of the NHS to the Long-Term Plan</i>	63
2.7.7	<i>Sustainability and Transformation Plans (STPs)</i>	63
2.7.8	<i>The NHS Long-Term Plan</i>	64
2.7.9	<i>Duties of Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs) An Agency of NHS England</i>	64
2.7.10	<i>NHS Improvement</i>	65
2.7.11	<i>NHS Providers</i>	65
2.7.12	<i>The Care Quality Commission</i>	66
2.7.13	<i>Accountability To the Public, Government and The Parliament of the United Kingdom</i>	67
2.7.14	<i>Access of Service Users to Treatment Services</i>	67
2.7.15	<i>Education and Training of Service Providers</i>	68
2.7.16	<i>Safety of Patient Care</i>	68
2.7.17	<i>Culture of The NHS about Patient Safety and Implications for EA.</i>	69
2.7.18	<i>Integration with Health and Social care Services</i>	70
2.7.19	<i>Technology and Data in the NHS</i>	71
2.7.20	<i>The function of the NHS National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE)</i>	72
2.7.21	<i>Integrated Care Systems (ICSs) functions</i>	72

2.7.22	<i>Sources of Funding and the Related Performance Mandate of NHS England</i>	73
2.7.23	<i>Technology funding in the NHS</i>	73
2.8	CRITICAL REALISM	75
2.8.1	<i>Mechanisms in Critical Realist Evaluation</i>	77
2.8.2	<i>Some Criticisms and Rival Theories of Critical Realism</i>	78
2.9	THE SOCIAL REALITY OF EA PROGRAMMES, SOCIAL CAUSATION, AND SOCIAL CHANGE.....	80
2.9.1	<i>The Embeddedness of social reality in EA Programmes</i>	81
2.9.2	<i>Underlying Mechanisms of EA Programmes</i>	82
2.9.3	<i>Context Dependency of EA Programme Mechanisms</i>	84
2.9.4	<i>Demi-Regularities in EA Programmes</i>	85
2.9.5	<i>EA Programmes as Social Change Agent</i>	87
2.9.6	<i>How Realist Evaluation of EAs Cumulate to Create Aligned Outcomes</i>	90
2.10	THE OPEN GROUP ARCHITECTURAL FRAMEWORK (TOGAF)	92
2.11	IMPLEMENTING EA UNDER COMPLEXITY.....	96
2.12	MECHANISMS OF EA PROGRAMMES.....	96
2.13	ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE FRAMEWORKS OVERVIEW	98
2.14	THE TOGAF ARCHITECTURE DEVELOPMENT METHOD (ADM)	101
2.14.1	<i>Preliminary Phase (PP)</i>	103
2.14.2	<i>The Main Building Blocks and Process Specification of the ADM</i>	104
2.14.3	<i>Initiation of the TOGAF Framework</i>	106
2.14.4	<i>Current/Baseline State Architecture Description</i>	106
2.14.5	<i>Target Architecture and Transition Architectures</i>	107
2.14.6	<i>Opportunities and Solutions Architecture</i>	107
2.15	MODELLING IN EA DEVELOPMENT: DEVELOPING CONTEXT.....	108
2.15.1	<i>Modelling in EA Development; Developing Context.</i>	108
2.15.2	<i>Phase A: Architecture Vision (AVP)</i>	109
2.15.3	<i>Phase B: Business Architecture (BAP)</i>	109
2.15.4	<i>Phase C: Information Systems Architectures (ISAP)</i>	111
2.15.5	<i>Phase D: Technology Architecture (TAP)</i>	112

2.15.6	<i>Phase E: Opportunities and Solutions (OSP)</i>	112
2.15.7	<i>Phase F: Migration Planning (MPP)</i>	113
2.15.8	<i>Phase G: Implementation Governance (IGP)</i>	113
2.15.9	<i>Phase H: Architecture Change Management (ACMP)</i>	113
2.15.10	<i>ADM Architecture Requirements Management (ARMP)</i>	114
2.15.11	<i>TOGAF Deliverables</i>	114
2.15.12	<i>Architecture Iterations within the ADM</i>	114
2.15.13	<i>Review of TOGAF research and applicability and generalizability to EA practice</i>	115
2.16	BUSINESS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ALIGNMENT	118
2.17	COMPLEXITY THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE OF EA.....	122
2.18	NETWORK THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE OF EA.....	123
2.19	THE CONCEPT OF VALUE IN EA	123
2.19.1	<i>The value of EA promotes effectiveness and stakeholder satisfaction.</i>	135
2.19.2	<i>Technology Architecture Roadmaps as Output to EA Development</i>	137
2.20	SOCIO-TECHNICAL THEORY	138
2.21	CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS FOR EA MANAGEMENT	139
2.21.1	<i>Social-Technical Perspective as Critical Factors (CSF) For EA Intervention Success</i>	140
2.21.2	<i>EA Improves IT Investment Decisions</i>	143
2.21.3	<i>Transforming and Transactional Factors for the Successful Implementation of EA in the Public Sector</i> 146	
2.22	CRITICAL FAILURE FACTORS FOR ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE MANAGEMENT.....	147
2.23	SUMMARY	150
CHAPTER TWO PROVIDES A REVIEW OF THE RELEVANT EXTANT LITERATURE RELIED ON FOR THE HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION OF THE THESIS. CHAPTER TWO ALSO PROVIDES AN EXPLANATION FOR CONCEPTS AND ABSTRACTIONS USED TO INFORM THE BACKGROUND OF THE THESIS.		
		150
3	CHAPTER 3: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	151
3.1	INTRODUCTION.....	151
3.2	THE TAXONOMY OF CONTRIBUTIONS TO THEORY	153

3.3	ABSTRACT AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS IN THE SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT CONTEXT	154
3.4	RETRODUCTIVE THEORISING IN THE EA CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	154
3.5	DEALING WITH THE SOCIAL REALITY OF EA PROGRAMMES	156
3.6	THE AESTHETIC VALUE OF EA OUTCOMES.....	157
3.7	OPEN SYSTEMS AND AMBIGUITY IN THE CONTEXT ACTION OF EA IMPLEMENTATION IN PROGRAMMES	159
3.8	ESSENTIAL BUILDING BLOCKS FOR THE ABDUCTIVE THEORISING APPROACH USED TO FORMULATE THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK.....	161
3.9	THE CONTEXT MECHANISM OUTCOME CONFIGURATION (CMOC) HEURISTIC APPLIED TO THE RESEARCH.....	161
3.9.1	<i>Context</i>	162
3.9.2	<i>Mechanisms</i>	164
3.9.3	<i>Outcome</i>	165
3.9.4	<i>CMO Configuration</i>	166
3.9.5	<i>The Scientific Realist Perspective on EA Programme Outcomes</i>	167
3.9.6	<i>The Implications of the Longitudinal critical realist EA Programme</i>	168
3.9.7	<i>Ontological Depth of the EA Research</i>	168
3.9.8	<i>Inference Sufficiency of the Investigation of The EA Case Study</i>	169
3.9.9	<i>Mechanisms Latency and Activation in The Context of Programme Action</i>	171
3.9.10	<i>Context-Mechanism Interaction is Necessarily Present in EA Management Action</i>	172
3.9.11	<i>Outcomes Dependency on the Approximation and Accumulation of Triggered Mechanisms in EA Implementations</i>	174
3.10	SOCIAL-TECHNOLOGICAL CONFLATION OF SOFTWARE-INTENSIVE AND SOCIAL-INTENSIVE SYSTEMS IN EA MANAGEMENT.....	176
3.11	TRANSFORMATIONS IN SOCIAL SYSTEMS AND HOW THEY ARE SITUATED IN EA TRANSFORMATIONS.....	181
3.12	THE EA CONTEXT-MECHANISM-OUTCOME CONFIGURATION CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK.....	183
3.12.1	<i>Building the Conceptual Framework for the EA Programme Intervention</i>	187
3.12.2	<i>Hypothesis</i>	189
3.12.3	<i>Boundary Conditions: The TOGAF ADM, Mechanisms-Context-Outcome configuration (CMOC) and The Social Context of Culture, Relations, Agency, Funding, Technology and Structure (CRAFTS)</i>	190
3.12.4	<i>The Realist Paradigm as a Programme Theory for EA Management</i>	245

3.12.5	<i>Retroduction in the development for development of EA vision</i>	191
3.12.6	<i>Retroduction develops foresight for the EA Programme outcomes</i>	192
3.12.7	<i>The Hidden Reality of EA Outcomes in a Realist Ontology</i>	192
3.12.8	<i>Realist Causal Explanation for EA Programme Implementation</i>	193
3.12.9	<i>The Impact of Context on EA Mechanisms and Outcomes</i>	193
3.13	THE CONTEXT-MECHANISM-OUTCOME (CMO) CONFIGURATION OF THE PROGRAMME	194
3.13.1	<i>The Archery Analogy of EA Programme Implementation CMO configuration</i>	198
3.13.2	<i>The TOGAF ADM Mechanisms of EA In the Context-Mechanism-Outcome Configuration</i>	199
3.13.3	<i>Socio-Technological Conflation in EA: TOGAF ADM Mechanisms in Social Context of Action</i>	202
3.13.4	<i>Propositional Formulations of a Conceptual CMO configuration For the EA Programme</i>	205
3.13.5	<i>Culture as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms</i>	208
3.13.6	<i>Relations as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms</i>	209
3.13.7	<i>Agency as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms</i>	210
3.13.8	<i>Funding as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms</i>	214
3.13.9	<i>Technology as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms</i>	217
3.13.10	<i>Structure as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms</i>	219
3.13.11	<i>Elaborating Context for EA Programme Theories</i>	223
3.13.12	<i>Mechanisms and Emergence in The Context of EA Management</i>	224
3.13.13	<i>Structuration Theory and Implications for the Implementation of EA Programmes</i>	232
3.13.14	<i>Emergence In the Context of EA Mechanisms</i>	233
3.13.15	<i>Outcomes of Generative Mechanisms of EA in Context</i>	236
3.14	A CRITICAL REALIST APPROACH TO ELABORATING THE CMOC CONFIGURATION IN EA PROGRAMME IMPLEMENTATIONS	237
3.15	ELABORATING THE CMO CONFIGURATION ON CRITICAL SUCCESS AND CRITICAL FAILURE FACTORS OF EA MANAGEMENT	238
3.15.1	<i>Critical Success Factors of the CMOC of EA Programmes</i>	239
3.15.2	<i>Critical Failure Factors of the CMOC of the EA Programme Intervention</i>	239
3.16	SUMMARY	240

4	CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY	242
4.1	INTRODUCTION.....	242
4.2	THE ENVIRONMENT SURROUNDING THE EVALUATION.	243
4.3	THE RATIONALE FOR USING REALIST EVALUATION IN THE RESEARCH	245
4.3.1	<i>Critical realist perspective of EA Programme Mechanisms</i>	<i>247</i>
4.3.2	<i>The rationale for adopting a critical realist perspective for the research design.....</i>	<i>253</i>
4.4	THE CRITICAL REALIST INTERVIEW APPROACH IN THE EA PROGRAM INTERVENTION	253
4.5	THE REALIST EVALUATION INTERVIEWING OF EA MANAGEMENT	256
4.6	THE REALIST INTERVIEWING APPROACH IN DETERMINING THE CRITICAL FAILURE FACTORS AND CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS IN EA MANAGEMENT.....	257
4.7	QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS.....	260
4.8	VALIDITY AND GENERALISATION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS	261
4.9	RECRUITMENT PROCESS AND SAMPLING STRATEGY.....	263
4.9.1	<i>Ethical Approval.....</i>	<i>266</i>
4.9.2	<i>Sampling, Access, and Recruitment Strategy.....</i>	<i>267</i>
4.9.3	<i>Selection Of Participants</i>	<i>269</i>
4.9.4	<i>Internet-mediated Access.....</i>	<i>270</i>
4.10	RETRODUCTION: A CONCEPTUAL CONFIGURATION APPROACH EA RESEARCH AND GENERATIVE MECHANISMS	271
4.11	THE TOGAF ADM IN EA PROGRAM MANAGEMENT AND THE PHASES IN THE REALIST INTERVIEW APPLIED TO THE RESEARCH.	273
4.11.1	<i>Phase 1 of the study interview: The EA programme theory gleaning.</i>	<i>274</i>
4.11.2	<i>Phase 2 of the study interview: The EA Program theory refinement</i>	<i>279</i>
4.11.3	<i>Phase 3 of the study interview. The EA Program theory Consolidation interview</i>	<i>282</i>
4.11.4	<i>Conjecturing the CMO Configurations as programme theories and findings</i>	<i>285</i>
4.12	EXPLANATION OF THE ANALYSIS	285
4.13	TRUSTWORTHINESS	287
4.14	ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS	288
4.15	SUMMARY	288

5	CHAPTER FIVE: ANALYSIS	289
5.1	INTRODUCTION.....	289
5.2	QUALITATIVE RESEARCH DESIGN – ANALYSIS APPROACH.....	290
5.3	GENERATING THE CMO CONFIGURATIONS.....	293
5.3.1	<i>Approach to Analysis Process.....</i>	<i>293</i>
5.3.2	<i>Step One of the Analysis</i>	<i>298</i>
5.3.3	<i>Step Two of the Analysis</i>	<i>304</i>
5.3.4	<i>Step Three of the Analysis.....</i>	<i>305</i>
5.3.5	<i>Step Four of the Analysis</i>	<i>306</i>
5.3.6	<i>Step Five of the Analysis</i>	<i>308</i>
5.3.7	<i>Step Six of the Analysis</i>	<i>308</i>
5.3.8	<i>Reliability.....</i>	<i>311</i>
5.4	SUMMARY.....	312
6	CHAPTER SIX: RESULTS AND FINDINGS	313
6.1	INTRODUCTION.....	313
6.2	DETAILS OF PARTICIPANTS	313
6.3	RESULTS	314
6.4	MAIN FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH.....	317
6.5	CRITICAL FAILURE FACTORS (MECHANISMS) TO EA IMPLEMENTATIONS.....	317
6.5.1	<i>Cultural Barriers</i>	<i>318</i>
6.5.2	<i>Relations Barriers.....</i>	<i>321</i>
6.5.3	<i>Individual and Institutional Agency Barriers</i>	<i>325</i>
6.5.4	<i>Funding Barriers</i>	<i>328</i>
6.5.5	<i>Technology Barriers</i>	<i>332</i>
6.5.6	<i>Structural Barriers.....</i>	<i>335</i>
6.6	CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS TO EA ARE EXPRESSED AS CONTEXT-MECHANISM-CONFIGURATIONS (CMOC). 339	
6.6.1	<i>Cultural Enablers</i>	<i>340</i>
6.6.2	<i>Relations Enablers.....</i>	<i>343</i>

6.6.3	<i>Individual and Organisational Agency Enablers</i>	347
6.6.4	<i>Funding Related Enablers</i>	350
6.6.5	<i>Technology Enablers</i>	354
6.6.6	<i>Structural Enablers</i>	357
6.6.7	<i>Summary of Findings</i>	361
6.7	DISCUSSION	361
6.7.1	<i>CMO Configurations preponderance and distributions in CMO configuration in Mechanisms contributing to Alignment of outcomes.</i>	362
6.7.2	<i>CMO Configurations preponderance and distributions in CMO configuration in Mechanisms contributing to Misalignment of outcomes.</i>	363
6.7.3	<i>Comparing CMO configurations for failure outcomes and Success outcomes</i>	365
6.7.4	<i>Critical Success Factors of EA</i>	366
6.7.5	<i>Critical Failure Factors Of EA</i>	369
6.7.6	<i>How an EA Program Might be Reconfigured in the Context of Triggering Mechanisms Antecedent Conditions In an action context</i>	376
6.7.7	<i>EA Mechanisms and Emergence in the Context of Programme Action</i>	377
6.7.8	<i>Constructive Ambiguity of EA Frameworks</i>	378
6.7.9	<i>Recurrent Patterns in CMO Configurations and Demi-regularities in EA Mechanisms</i>	379
6.7.10	<i>Strengths</i>	380
6.7.11	<i>Limitations</i>	381
7	CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	383
7.1	CONTRIBUTION OF THIS RESEARCH TO ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE	383
7.2	RECOMMENDATIONS	384
7.2.1	<i>Future Directions</i>	384
7.2.2	<i>Using Artificial Intelligence to Configure Context-Mechanisms-Outcomes in EA Programmes</i>	385
7.3	FUNDING AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST.....	402
8	REFERENCES	403
9	APPENDIX A: ETHICAL APPROVAL FORM	478

10	APPENDIX B: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET	481
	RESEARCH PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET	481
11	APPENDIX C: THE TOGAF ADM ARCHITECTURE DELIVERABLE.....	484
12	APPENDIX D: TOGAF ARCHITECTURE DELIVERABLES DESCRIPTIONS	485

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1.1. List of Abbreviations	17
Table 1.2. Glossary of Terms	19
Table 2.2. Certified TOGAF Practitioners up to 2018	93
Table 2.3 Structure of the TOGAF Framework. Source: (The Open Group, 2018).	95
Table 2.4. Classification of EA frameworks (Goethals, 2005)	100
Table 4.1. Tendencies of the stratified domains of reality. Source: (Bhaskar, 1978)	250
Table 4.2. Some illustrative sample sizing for qualitative research.....	265
Table 4.3. Participants’ selection criteria	268
Table 4.4. Expert Participants' Profiles.	269
Table 4.5 defines the EA programme theory's relevant CMO configuration terms and coding frames. Source: (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Mukumbang et al., 2020).	278
Table 4.6. Interview questions and prompts for participants.	281
Table 5.1. analysis and synthesis process for generating the CMO configuration of the study. Adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).	296
Table 5.2. shows the distribution of CMO configuration elicited from Participant Interview scripts into critical success and failure factors.	299
Table 5.3. Formulating the Failure Factors CMO configuration process. Adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).	302
Table 5.4. Formulating the Success Factor CMO configuration process, adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).	303
Table 6.1. TOGAF ADM Phases represented by letters	315
Table 6.2. Shows the Distribution of CMO configurations and Program theories elicited from Participant interview scripts.....	316
Table 6.3. CMO Configurations for Critical Failure Factors related to the cultural context and as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	318
Table 6.4. CMO configurations of critical failure factors in the Relations context as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	321
Table 6.5. CMO configurations of Critical failure factors in the individual and organisational agency context as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	325
Table 6.6. CMO configurations of critical failure factors in the funding context and as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	329
Table 6.7. CMO configuration of critical failure factors in the Technology context.....	332

Table 6.8. CMO configuration of critical failure factors in the structural context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	336
Table 6.9. CMO configurations of Critical success factors in the cultural context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	340
Table 6.10. CMO configurations of Critical success factors in the Relations context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	344
Table 6.11. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the individual and organisation agency context.....	347
Table 6.12. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the funding context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	351
Table 6.13. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the technology context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	354
Table 6.14. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the structural context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).....	357
Table 6.15. Distribution of Critical Success Factors in the CRAFTS Model	362
Table 6.16. Distribution of Critical Failure Factors in the CRAFTS Model.....	363
Table 6.17. A bubble chart view of the Distribution of Critical Failure Factors CMO configurations in the CRAFTS Model.	364
Table 6.18. Distribution of CMO configurations in the context of The CRAFTS model.	365

List of Figures

Figure 2.1. above shows the integrated Care Systems of the NHS and Local Government—source: (House of Commons Library, 2020).....	57
Figure 2.2 Functional Structure of NHS Digital (NHS Digital, 2021a)	59
Figure 2.3. The regularity of context mechanisms in EA programmes is abstracted from Bhaskar (2009; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; The Open Group, 2018; de Souza, 2013).....	87
Figure 2.4 Illustrative Realist Model of EA Transformation in Social Programmes.	88
Figure 2.5. Shows The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) Capability. (The Open Group, 2018).....	92
Figure 2.6. shows the ADM Elements, interactions, and its iterations, adapted from The Open Group (2018).....	103
Figure 2.7. The essential Phases/steps of the ADM where the Architecture building blocks are specified and evolve during the programme implementation. Source: (The Open Group, 2018).	106
Figure 2.8. Strategic alignment model showing how The TOGAF ADM interacts with its components (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999; The Open Group, 2018).....	119
Figure 2.9. Criticality percentage for Socio-Technical factors critical to EA Implementation Success (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2015).....	142
Figure 3.1. The volcanic eruption analogy illustrates how hidden and observable mechanisms of EA are triggered in context to create EA programme outcomes.....	169
Figure 3.2. High-Level Conceptual Framework of Context (CRAFTS, ADM), Mechanism and Outcome Configuration of EA development. Theoretically elicited from Archer (1995), Bhaskar (1978), Dalkin et al. (2015), de Souza (2013), Jagosh et al. (2015), Pawson and Tilley (1997) and The Open Group (2018).	173
Figure 3.3 The realist evaluation of the EA programme depicting the Mechanism-Context-outcome configuration of the EA programme theory, adapted from Pawson and Tilley (1997), Pawson (2006), Gilmore, McAuliffe, et al. (2019), and Jagosh (2020b).....	184
Figure 3.4. Generative Causal Pathways of EA Mechanisms in the Context of Social Action. Abstracted from Archer (1995), Bhaskar (1978), Dalkin et al. (2015), de Souza (2013); Jagosh et al. (2015), NHS Digital (2021a), NOA (2020a), Pawson and Tilley (1997) and The Open Group (2018).....	186
Figure 3.5. A high-Level view of the Components of the Conceptual Framework. Mechanisms are triggered in context to create programme outcomes.	193

Figure 3.6. Conceptual Framework, abstracted from Archer (1995), de Souza (2013), Pawson and Tilley (1997), and The Open Group (2018).....	195
Figure 3.7. shows a detailed programme theory or conceptual Framework of CMO configuration for Implementing EA based on the TOGAF ADM.	201
Figure 3.8. The CMO configuration programme theory of EA Implementation.....	202
Figure 3.9. Socio-Technological Enactment of Complexity in EA Using the TOGAF ADM Mechanisms, inspired by de Souza (2013), Archer (1995), The Open Group (2018), and reports from NHS Digital.....	204
Figure 3.10. Shows the Propositional formulations ‘network of outcomes’ for CMO configurations of the case study, adapted from Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012, p.181).....	206
Figure 3.11. illustrates the emergent properties of EA for the context-sensitive mechanism of the Organisations.	234
Figure 4.1. The methodological approach to critical evaluation is used in the research.	243
Figure 4.2 shows the critical contributors to the conceptual framework development.	246
Figure 4.3. The objectivism-subjectivism multidimensional continuum. Source: (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2019, p. 129).	248
Figure 4.4. Stratified ontology (Empirical, Actual and Real) of Critical Realism (Bhaskar, 1978; Saunders, 2109, p.139) is depicted within a Volcanic Eruption Metaphor. Mechanisms are triggered in context to produce Outcomes.	250
Figure 4.5. The Realist Interview Approach to EA Program Intervention was abstracted from Pawson and Tilley (1997), Bhaskar (2009), TOGAF (2018), de Souza (2013), and Mukumbang et al. (2020).	259
Figure 4.6. The realist research interview phases of the EA Programmes Interview Process. Reference: (Mukumbang et al., 2020; Yin, 2018).	274
Figure 4.7. Phase 1: The Theory Gleaning Interview Process. Source: (Mukumbang et al., 2020).	275
Figure 4.8. Building Blocks of the Context-Mechanisms-Outcome Configuration Roadmap of The EA Program Theory, abstracted from Archer 1995; Pawson and Tilley (1997), de Souza (2013), The Open Group (2018), Bhaskar (2009), and Jagosh (2020a).	277
Figure 4.9. The EA program theoretical framework is the subject of the phase 2 interview, theory Gleaning. Mukumbang et al. (2020).	280
Figure 4.10. The EA program theoretical framework is the subject of the phase 3 interview, theory Refinement and Consolidation. Mukumbang et al. (2020).	282

Figure 5.1. Extracting the CMO Configuration from participant interviews. Source: Format adapted from (Gilmore et al., 2019, p.7).	293
Figure 5.2. A summary of the analysis and synthesis process of the Case Study is adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).	296
Figure 5.3. Distribution of Critical Failure Factors and Critical Success CMO Configurations from Participant Interviews.	300
Figure 6.1. A bubble chart view of the Distribution of Critical Success Factors CMO configurations in the CRAFTS Model.	363
Figure 6.2. Distribution of CMO configurations related to Critical success factors and Critical failure factors in Radar view in the context of the CRAFTS Model.	366
Figure 6.3. shows how the EA CMO configurations for successful outcomes might be reconfigured to align with the organisation's objectives and goals, with agility with ongoing stakeholders' concerns as input.	376
Figure 7.1. shows an illustrative Framework for uncovering contexts, Mechanisms and likely outcomes from Stakeholder perspectives.	386
Figure 13.1. Superimposing the Transformational Model of Social Action in EA programme action, the Morphogenetic/static cycle, the Context-Mechanism-Outcome Configuration, The TOGAF ADM and the Strategic Alignment Model.	492

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Table 1.1. List of Abbreviations

EA	Enterprise Architecture
IT	Information Technology
TOGAF	The Open Group Architecture Framework
ADM	Architecture Development Method
CRAFTS	Culture, Relations, Agency, Funding, Technology, Structure
CMO	Context Mechanism Outcomes
CMOc	Context Mechanism Outcomes configuration
HIC	Hierarchical culture
BITA	Business-IT alignment
ATUTIT	Aligned Transformation, Unaligned Transformation, Invariant Transformation
CSF	Critical Success Factors
CFF	Critical Failure Factors
NHS	National Health Service
ISO	International Standard Organisation
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
NAO	National Audit Office
HSC	Health and Social Care
DHSC	Department of Health and Social Care
CRS	Care Record Service
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission

EAM	Enterprise Architecture Management
KIIs	Key Informants Interviews

Table 1.2. Glossary of Terms

Terms	Definition
Environment	<i>“Context determines the setting and circumstances of all influences upon a [architecture] system” (ISO, 2011, 3.1.21).</i>
Design	<i>The “[process] defines the architecture, system elements, interfaces, and other characteristics of a system or system element” (ISO, 2011, 3.1.17).</i>
Design phase	<i>(1) “The period in the software life cycle during which definitions for architecture, software components, interfaces, and data are created, documented and verified to satisfy requirements” (ISO, 2011).</i>
	<i>(2) “the period in the software life cycle during which the designs for architecture, software components, interfaces, and data are created, documented and verified to satisfy requirements” (ISO, 2011)</i>
Integration	<i>(1) The” process of combining software components, hardware components, or both into an overall system” (ISO, 2011).</i>
	<i>(2) The “activities of combining several implemented system elements and activating the interfaces to form a realised system (product or service) that enables interoperation between the system elements and with other systems to satisfy system requirements, architecture characteristics and design properties components, or both into an overall system” (ISO, 2019).</i>
Architect	<i>(1) A” person, team, or organisation responsible for systems architecture” (ISO, 2011).</i>
Architecting	<i>(1) “process of conceiving, defining, expressing, documenting, communicating, certifying proper implementation of, maintaining, and improving an architecture throughout a system's life cycle.</i>

	<i>The entity to be architected can be of several kinds: system, enterprise, solution, business, data, application, information technology, mission, product, service, software” (ISO, 2011, 3.1).</i>
Architecture System	<i>(1) A "man-made and may be configured with one or more of the following: hardware, software, data, humans, processes (e.g., processes for providing service to users), procedures (e.g., operator instructions), facilities, materials and naturally occurring entities" (ISO, 2019).</i>
Software-intensive systems	<i>“Any system where software contributes essential influences to the design, construction, deployment, and evolution of the system as a whole” to encompass “individual applications, systems in the traditional sense, subsystems, systems of systems, product lines, product families, whole enterprises, and other aggregations of interest” (ISO, 2019).</i>
Architecture	<i>(1) Architecture “{system} refers to the "fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution” (ISO, 3.3).</i>
	<i>(2)"The structure of components, their inter-relationships, and the principles and guidelines governing their design and evolution over time" The Open Group (2018, 2.2).</i>
	<i>(3) “(system) fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution” (ISO, 3.2).</i>
	<i>(4) “set of rules to define the structure of a system and the interrelationships between its parts” (ISO, 2019).</i>
Enterprise Architecture	<i>“An enterprise architecture is either the architecture of an enterprise or the architecture of an entity from an enterprise point of view. In both cases,</i>

And Systems Architecture	<i>it has a defined overall business objective and may include one or more participating organisations” (ISO, 2019, E.4.1.2).</i>
Identification and Stakeholders and Concerns.	<i>An “architecture description shall identify the system stakeholders [are]having concerns considered fundamental to the architecture of the system-of-interest; users, operators; acquirers; owners; suppliers, developers, builders, and maintainers” (ISO, 2011, 3.1).</i>
Stakeholder	<i>“A system individual, team, organisation, or classes thereof, having an interest in a system.” (ISO, 2011, 3.10).</i>
System	<i>“man-made and may be configured with one or more of the following: hardware, software, data, humans, processes (e.g., processes for providing service to users), procedures (e.g., operator instructions), facilities, materials and naturally occurring entities” (ISO, 2011, p.3).</i>
Architecture View/View	<i>“Work product expressing the architecture of a system from the perspective of specific system concerns” (ISO, 2011, 3.5).</i>
Architecture Viewpoint/View point	<i>“Work product establishing the conventions for the construction, interpretation and use of architecture views to frame specific system concerns” (ISO, 2011, 3.6).</i>
	<i>(2)” <architecture> conventions for the construction, interpretation, and use of architecture views to address specific concerns about the architecture entity” (ISO, 2019, 3.25).</i>
System design	<i>“Process of defining the hardware and Software architecture, components, modules, interfaces and data for a system to satisfy specified requirements” (ISO, 2011).</i>
Architecture Description (AD)	<i>“Work product used to express an architecture” (ISO, 2011, 3.3).</i>

Architecture framework	<p>(1) <i>“conventions, principles and practices for use by architecture-related activities that have been established within a specific domain of application or community of stakeholders” (ISO, 2019, 3.7).</i></p>
	<p>(2) <i>“conventions, principles and practices for the description of architectures established within a specific domain of application or community of stakeholders” (ISO, 2019, 4.1.6).</i></p>
Social System	<p><i>A Social system is "the interplays of individual and institution, of agency and structure, and of micro and macro social processes". Pawson & Tilley, p.63).</i></p>

Acknowledgement

The author would like to sincerely thank Dr Justin Jagosh, the Director of the University of Liverpool Centre for Advancement in Realist Evaluation and Synthesis (CARES), for his guidance and mentoring in applying realist evaluation to this research.

The author acknowledges Dr Javad Izadi for his guidance and supervision.

To my wife, Professor Prospera Tadam, and sons Joel and Kevin, for their support and patience as I took time out of family business to passionately work on this research.

ABSTRACT

There is a preponderance of evidence for the impact of Enterprise Architecture (EA) mechanisms on programme outcomes. However, little research has explored the context sensitivity of these mechanisms in a socio-technological context in digital transformations in healthcare organisations.

The study explains EA outcomes' critical failure and success factors through the lens of mechanism-context interaction to create outcomes. The study proposes a socio-technological initial programme theory for eliciting Context-Mechanisms-Outcome (CMO) configurations concerning the strategic alignment of the organisation's strategic objectives and goals; on the one hand, its Information Technology (IT) from an EA perspective. It proposes the Culture, Relations, Agency, Funding, Technology, Structure (CRAFTS) context model as a significant trigger for EA mechanisms.

Twelve key informants and experts informed a large UK Healthcare Organisation's initial programme theory or conceptual Framework through semi-structured qualitative data collection and retroductive theorisation. Next, the CMO configurations were elicited, refined, and consolidated into critical failure and critical success factors of EA outcomes.

The research found that the organisation's culture, the effectiveness of human agency and their attitude towards technology are critical to the success of the EA implementation, one that aligns the organisation's vision, objectives, and goals with IT. The findings suggest that the mechanisms of EA are context-sensitive. Applying mechanisms for EA development without due regard to context creates uncertain outcomes. Social interactions are complex, and EA outcomes are emergent on socio-technological consideration because of the unpredictability of agency and social systems. The relationships between stakeholders are also a determining factor in EA outcomes. Where relationships have not been favourable, EA tended to be perceived as unsuccessful. Funding of technology programmes is critical to EA's failure or success. With funding constraints, EA outcomes tend to be assessed as unfavourable.

Where the organisation's affinity for technology has been poor due to cultural aversion, or lack of funding, EA outcomes have been perceived not to be successful. Digital non-native may also slow the pace of adoption. The study has identified preliminary support for context-sensitive EA mechanisms and outcomes in Enterprise Architecture. A new socio-technological model has been identified with culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure playing critical roles in determining alignment in EA outcomes. A significant contribution to EA is supporting context-mechanism-outcome configurations as enablers and barriers to EA outcomes.

Keywords: *Critical Success Factors, Critical Failure Factors, critical realism, EA Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) Configuration, TOGAF ADM, CRAFTS Model.*

1 CHAPTER ONE: OVERVIEW OF THE THESIS

1.1 Introduction

This introductory chapter summarises the thesis, aiming to explore the "value creation" mechanisms in UK healthcare organisations' Enterprise Architecture (EA) programs. The UK National Health Service (NHS) implements EA to ensure that its technology supports operational services provided to users locally and nationally.

According to NHS Digital (2017), to support its services to healthcare service users, there is a need for systems and local services to be designed under the appropriate governance conditions to allow the services to operate effectively. The need for local and national health systems to interoperate is key to supporting critical care models in the NHS.

EA, therefore, will enable NHS Digital to have a *"more detailed understanding of architecture – the way technology is used, and the way data flows around the health and care system"* (p.9).

NHS Digital further argues that EA is critical in promoting consistent, complete, and interoperable technology systems to ensure robust investment decision-making and remove technology resource duplication. EA initiatives within the NHS are underway to design new services that work across healthcare systems in the UK.

"This will be an important piece of the system-level governance arrangements, working through the EA Board. (p.9)"

One rationale for selecting TOGAF as an Architecture framework in this research is its acceptance as a standard in architecting healthcare technology in the NHS. According to The Open Group (2001), *"the NHS is testing TOGAF for use as a standard framework for IT architectures. It is hoped to provide a formal case study in the near future, explaining the use of TOGAF in the NHS"* ((The Open Group, n.d., para.7). The researcher worked for NHS Digital as a Solution Architect, and the pervasive adoption and use of TOGAF are confirmed.

Gartner (2021) argues that EA delivers value to the organisation by providing business and IT decision-makers with "signature-ready" guidance for adapting policies and projects to achieve selected business outcomes that exploit relevant technology disruptions relevant to their business.

Although there has not been a shared definition of what constitutes EA, which may have affected the progress of EA research in finding business solutions (Gerow, Grover, Thatcher & Roth, 2014), its concepts, processes, mechanisms, and models have evolved since its inception in 1987 (Simon, Fischbach, & Schoder, 2013).

Healthcare organisations are increasingly turning to technology to realise the value creation inherent in their business strategies (Burn & Szeto, 2000). This trend underscores the growing significance of technology in enhancing operational efficiency and achieving strategic objectives within the healthcare sector. As such, it is becoming increasingly critical for healthcare institutions to effectively integrate and leverage technology to optimise value creation and overall performance. Accordingly, the practice of EA is the process of planning, designing, and representing information technology resources of the organisation and their interactions. EA is often defined as a prescriptive framework that can guide and constrain the subsequent development of businesses and IT systems (Foorthuis et al., 2012, p.46). It can create synergies among diverse business processes (Gerow, Grover, Thatcher & Roth, 2014) and provides *"a structured and aligned collection of plans for the integrated representation of the business and information technology (IT) landscape of the enterprise, in the past, current, and future state"* (Simon et al., 2013, p.2). These definitions point to the significant role of information technology in sustaining strategic advantage for organisations (De Vries & van Rensburg, 2009) and explain why most healthcare organisations may be increasingly adopting EA in their business processes and strategies.

Recent research has shown that firm commitment can promote EA value creation. According to Gartner (2009), 66% of EA interventions fail due to the opportunities and constraints of the researcher's specific environment and culture. The need for EA has grown. Membership had grown

to 70,000 certified EA Practitioners worldwide as of July 2017 (Josey, 2017). The Open Group has an Organisational membership of six hundred members worldwide due to the increasing significance of aligning Information Technology and Business Strategy (The Open Group, 2018).

"As digitisation becomes pervasive, many organisations struggle to drive value from the growing number of IT-related opportunities. We show how the drivers of IT value creation can be framed as firm-wide commitments to a set of IT capabilities" (Quaadgras, Weill & Ross, 2014, p.114).

However, despite the promising features of EA, its value is still not being realised. The reason for value realisation concerns could be a result of the misconception of EA as a "value" by itself instead of *"an instrument that can enable the creation of value"* (Gong & Janssen, 2019, p.1).

Gong and Janssen (2019) analysed "various EA value claims and compared them with the empirical evidence to identify myths" (p.1) and gain deeper insight into EA value. Their findings suggested that EA has been misconstrued "as an instrument that can solve almost any kind of enterprise problem [instead of] ... an instrument that can enable the creation of value" (p.1). Therefore, Gong and Janssen (2019) concluded that although EA is an essential concept in the enterprise world, its value cannot be understood without examining the context-based mechanisms on which the value of EA can be based. This notion calls for a further review of how value creation can be a critical success or failure factor in implementing EA. This focus is crucial as what constitutes 'value' in EA and how this value is measured is contestable.

As a critical success factor in EA implementation, it is essential to note the EA aspects that result in value creation (Foorthuis et al., 2012; Gong & Janssen, 2019). According to Foorthuis et al. (2012), EA *"provide decision-makers with a clear and comprehensive description overview of the organisation and provide a prescriptive framework that guides and constraints subsequent development of business and IT solutions"* (p.46). In other words, EA informs the structure on which organisations base their systems and assets; hence, EA implementation is expected to add value to the organisation's processes. This added value is the primary motivation for investing in EA and [in]

establishing an architectural function within an enterprise (Gong & Janssen, 2019, p. 1). However, organisations cannot rationalise their EA investments due to a lack of a clear understanding of EA value mechanisms (Tamm et al., 2015).

1.2 Enterprise Architecture (EA) And Digital Transformation

According to Parviainen et al. (2017), Digital transformation changes an organisation's functions, roles, responsibilities, and value proposition when it embraces digital technology.

EA, therefore, is the process of planning, designing, and representing information technology resources and their interactions during the changes enabled by digital transformation. EA outlines the orchestration between the organisation's objectives and goals for digital transformation and the information technology resources and interactions (van de Wetering et al., 2021).

"EA maps out and orchestrates business and IT assets and processes and their interconnections and is, therefore, a crucial ingredient for firms to drive digital transformation" (p.1).

According to Gartner (2021, p.1), *"Digital transformation can refer to anything from IT modernisation (for example, cloud computing), to digital optimisation, to the invention of new digital business models."* Gartner further suggests that public-sector organisations commonly use digital transformation to enable online digital services or legacy IT modernisation.

Bhattarai (2020, p.1) defines digital transformation as *"an effort to enable existing business models by integrating advanced technologies"*. Whereas EA concerns the strategic alignment between organisational objectives and IT resources, digital transformation enables its capabilities.

1.3 High Failure Rate of EA

According to Kohansal, Rolland & Khodambashi (2022), the primary factors contributing to the failure of Enterprise Architecture Management (EAM) are fundamentally tied to issues of legitimacy. Their research suggests that the lack of adequate legitimacy, reflected in insufficient shared understanding, stakeholders' engagement, and crucial financial and managerial support, often leads to the failure of EAM initiatives.

Furthermore, the authors suggest that while pragmatic legitimacy may confer some initial advantage, the sustained success of EAM is inextricably linked to the acquisition of regulatory legitimacy. Their study also highlights the detrimental impact of intra-organisational complications, such as conflicting viewpoints and bureaucratic impediments, which pose significant barriers to attaining normative and cultural-cognitive legitimacy.

According to Gartner (2009), derived from the opportunities and constraints of the researcher's specific environment and culture, 66% of EA interventions fail. According to Josey (2017) and The Open Group, the need for TOGAF has driven the demand for EA has grown with a membership in 2019 to 70,000 certified EA Practitioners worldwide as of July 2017 (Josey, 2017). The Open Group has an organisational membership of six hundred members worldwide due to the increasing significance of the need to align Information Technology and Business strategy. Pasaribu, Hakiki, Situmorang, Sfenrianto, and Kaburuan (2019) argue that implementations fail in healthcare organisations because of a lack of alignment with the goals of independent organisations forming part of the core implementing organisations.

In a company report published, LeanIX argues that a collaborative culture with continuous support from top-level management can help create EA implementation success (LeanIX, 2019).

EA is not sustainable without due recognition of its role in determining the strategic direction of the implementing organisation, a primary reason why 66% of EA initiatives fail to reach expected outcomes. The company suggest that failure is due to the lack of endorsement from top leadership. It is also because modelling in the EA implementation process is commenced before understanding the need of the organisation's information systems and information technology needs (Kreizman and Bittler, 2005; Lange, Mendling, & Recker, 2016; Simon, Fischbach & Schoder, 2013). Failure often results in cost overruns and unexpected and disappointing organisation performance as they cannot fulfil the expected value of EA. According to Kreizman and Bittler (2005), in a report authored for Gartner, they predicted that 40% of EA implementations would fail.

Achieving IT and business alignment is a continuous process sensitive to changing market conditions and emerging technological innovation influencing its strategy. Organisations, however, pay little attention to the changing market conditions. Instead, the focus of top management has been on IT structuring and business goals (Luftman, 2003; Gerow et al., 2014; Coltman et al., 2015; Cram, Brohman, & Gallupe, 2015).

EA has been widely accepted to improve IT and business alignment (Löhe & Legner, 2014; Tamm et al., 2011; Wu & Lu, 2007). Despite the wide acclaim regarding the benefits of EA, failures have been prevalent across several countries (Banaeianjahromi, 2018).

In a case considered by Banaeianjahromi, a lack of clear organisational strategy led to the chief information officer rejecting the EA initiative and labelling it as a failure. *"The EA project with difficulties as it took much longer than expected" to finish and "almost failed" (p.4).*

Several researchers have used the terms 'socio-technological' and 'socio-technical'. For instance, Caprario and Finotti (2019), Nesari, Gonzalez, Naghizadeh, Ghazinoori, and Manteghi (2022), Eccles and Groth (2006) and Alfoudari, Durugbo, and Aldhmour (2021) used the term 'socio-technological'. Hope (2015) and Nesari et al. (2022) used socio-technical. These terms are used interchangeably in this thesis, but the subtle differences have been highlighted in later sections of this thesis.

Korhonen and Poutanen (2013) identify Socio-technical architecture as an integral part of the design and building of architecture work. Korhonen and Poutanen argue that Socio-technical architectures are *"self-contained and self-regulated with its paradigmatic function, methods, and tools" (p.351).*

They argue that social-technical consideration facilitates a holistic view of balancing tactics versus changing business requirements. In their adaptive and maladaptive EA model, clutching to "best practices" with little regard for Socio-technical factors causes a disconnect with strategy. The disconnect may result in a potentially curtailed view of the reach of architecture in promoting alignment with strategy.

Löhe and Legner (2014) argue that the EA initiative fails because of low patronage of EA-related documentation to inform technology decision-making. They argue further that Enterprise Architects responsible for the management of EA lack authority.

According to Morganwalp and Sage (2004), implementing EA requires much effort, which drains the implementing organisation leading to inertia and subsequent failure. Seppanen, Heikkila, and Liimatainen (2009) and Winter and Schelp (2008) argue that the lack of governance, inadequate support for the EA implementation from the managers of the business and IT, and suboptimal resource and skills support hinder strategic alignment of organisational objectives with Information technology using EA implementations.

The value of EA to organisations is inferred and not directly measurable. The benefits of EA are longitudinally realisable (Schmidt & Buxmann, 2011). Implementation issues have motivated this research, explicitly considering Socio-Technical approaches that have received little attention in EA Research (Hope, 2015; Hope, Chew, & Sharma, 2017). Therefore, this research aims to identify Socio-Technological critical success and failure that may promote or hinder EA implementations in healthcare organisations.

1.3.1 Why is EA a hard sell despite the potential rewards it can bring to Organisations?

On the 1st of June 2018, this researcher surveyed to gauge opinions from EA Practitioners regarding scepticism surrounding the value of EA to organisations (the researcher sampled opinions of EA experts on a LinkedIn.com EA Practitioners network (LinkedIn.com, 2018). Note that their profiles, as stated on LinkedIn.com, are as given.

One hundred seventy-one thousand nine hundred thirty-six members of the EA Network on LinkedIn.com were asked about their opinion on why there is organisational inertia about the value of EA to their strategic alignment interventions. In the LinkedIn.com poll, this research invited comments on why EA is a hard sell; Thirty-two respondents posted their comments on LinkedIn.com

relating to the poll. Most respondents alluded to the difficulty in demonstrating the value of EA to organisations that implement them (LinkedIn.com, 2018).

Two of the 32 respondents disagreed that demonstrating EA value is hard to justify, representing 6%, while 30 agreed, representing 94%.

One contributor argued that EA programmes are costly to the organisations, time-consuming, lack clear benefits, and have poor communication, affecting confidence. The LinkedIn comment for RespondentMT (LinkedIn.com, 2018) says:

"The reasons are in failure to name a few - very expensive, time-consuming, seldom having clear business benefits defined, poor communication on progress to the organisation, lack of experience of EA personnel in the understanding of business strategy etc. ...All of these do not generate much confidence to business as time passes by on a transformation programme. More focussed business transformation capability-based programmes have more chances to be successful if they have potential business reuse. We all know it is important, and lack of it can cause a death 🧠 blow to company sustainability to trade."

A senior Enterprise Architect in a higher education institution suggests that EA falter at the development stage. He argues that Enterprise Architects tend to reject project decisions and may be perceived as a hindrance instead of a catalyst.

The LinkedIn comment for RespondentMG says, *"I see some EA stumble at the development of digital approaches. I am now outside the core EA team because there is a need to provide architecture/capability context around mode 2 type projects (ones with an appetite for failure, speed, and throw-away work). Some EAs struggle badly with this, even though EA should be even more useful at this point (LinkedIn.com).*

I also witnessed EA folk adopt "no" thinking; the answer is "no" to your idea, and I don't need to listen to it because I need to be seen to lead. In digital (or agile), all ideas need to be engaged with,

and the first response needs to be "let's explore that"; otherwise, the digital teams will see EA as a block to cool stuff" (LinkedIn.com).

The survey conducted on the EA Practitioners network on LinkedIn regarding the scepticism surrounding the value of Enterprise Architecture (EA) to organisations revealed several key lessons. Most practitioners (94%) agreed that demonstrating the value of EA to organisations is a significant challenge, attributing this to several factors. These included the high cost and time-consuming nature of EA programmes, the difficulty in defining clear business benefits, poor communication regarding progress, and a lack of understanding by EA personnel about business strategy. These elements lead to losing confidence over time in the transformation programme. Another observation from the feedback was that Enterprise Architects are often seen as obstacles rather than facilitators, particularly in digital or agile environments. They tend to reject project ideas rather than explore them, creating an impression of hindering innovation. It is suggested that improving the perception and effectiveness of EA requires focusing on business transformation and adopting a more exploratory, open-minded approach to new ideas.

1.4 Motivation For the Research Evaluation (Gap)

The failure rate of the EA initiative is high and well documented in practice and theory, as already discussed. EA initiatives have failed to meet expectations (Hope et al., 2017, p.21).

The researcher's radar of appreciating EA drives this research. As the CEO and Director Of EA, Tadam Technology Services Ltd, the UK, an EA and technology strategy firm registered in England and Wales. The researcher has ten years of professional experience as a Strategic Enterprise Architect and a Senior Manager in the NHS. The researcher is also a Certified TOGAF Practitioner, the industry certification for EA, and previously implemented five EA Initiatives, mainly in the healthcare sector. From experience as a Strategic Enterprise Architect in NHS, the value of EA is subjective among the various stakeholder decision-makers within the organisation. Since the works of Henderson and Venkatraman (1993, 1999) on the strategic Alignment of EA, using their strategic alignment model,

the evolution of EA has been embraced by organisations culminating in inter-organisational collaboration to enhance and realise the value of EA. Notably, The Open Group has been a leading source of the organisational affiliation of EA standards. The researcher is a member of the Open Group.

The researcher served on the National programme IT, later NHS Digital, for over 15 years as a Lead Solution Architect implementing EA using The Open Group Architecture Framework. The plan's scope involved managing and implementing a Nationwide integrated Electronic Health Record system for the NHS. As a practitioner, the researcher has not encountered the difficult hurdles external researchers have to overcome, such as negotiating research access (Saunders et al., 2016, p.208).

As an internal researcher, having worked at the senior management level within the NHS for over 15 years, the researcher is aware of the complexity of activities in healthcare organisations.

However, the researcher is conscious of the biases and perceptions of being an internal researcher. Saunders et al. (2016) argue that bias is *"an inevitable consequence of knowing the organisation well and can prevent you from exploring issues that would enrich the research"* (p.208).

As an internal researcher, there is a recognition of how this affects the research approach to the design and conduction. The researcher's role as an internal researcher has emotional and measurement implications on the research, which is acknowledged and managed. The tasks of analysis, interpretation, and theorising concerning the research data collected may render *"strange the all-too-familiar"* (Tietze, 2012, p.68). Therefore, the researcher is aware of the researcher's impact because of the proximity to the research setting.

1.4.1 Motivations For Research into The Mechanisms of EA Management

Extant literature has identified some weaknesses in the field of EA research. Notably, while there is agreement that EA delivers value, the mechanisms governing such success need further attention (Ahlemann et al., 2020).

"While there is a relative consent that these benefits may be the outcome of successful EAM, the mechanisms that lead to their realisation are widely unexplored. However, extending the current understanding of the mechanisms of EAM benefit realisation is highly worthwhile both from practical

and theoretical viewpoints. In practice, EA programs have very often turned out to struggle in realising these benefits” (Ahlemann et al., p.2). The research considers mechanisms for Enterprise Architecture development within digital transformation programmes in social systems, specifically healthcare organisations.

According to Pawson and Tilley (2008), the characteristics of mechanisms reflect the program's inseparability from the differentiated nature of social reality. Mechanisms form propositions explaining general and specific processes that create the programme. They explain how programme outcomes arise from the stakeholders' personal or collective decision and their ability to implement these.

1.5 The aim, objectives, questions and focus of the research study

1.5.1 Research Aim

The research study explores how healthcare organisations implement EA interventions in the context of the Socio-Technological mechanisms prevalent. The perspectives of EA experts in the healthcare sector and archival documents, the organisation's EA documents, were elicited to investigate what constitutes EA mechanisms in healthcare organisations and identify the factors that promote success or impede EA implementation. The research aims to provide an evaluative and planning approach to determining critical success and critical failure factors of EA mechanisms in digital transformation programmes in healthcare. The research explores the critical failure and success factors of the mechanisms under which EA implementation is managed.

1.5.2 Research Questions

The research questions answered in this research are:

1. **Research question 1 (RQ1):** What are the Mechanisms for managing EA programs in healthcare organisations?
2. **Research question 2 (RQ2):** What critical factors and challenges (critical failure factors) impact EA programme delivery in healthcare?

1.5.3 *Research Objectives*

- To **evaluate** EA mechanisms in healthcare organisations.
- To **explain** the lack of perceived value in EA in healthcare.
- To **identify** the factors that facilitate the EA Management success or failure in healthcare organisations.

The research aims to explain the causal mechanisms and outcomes of the [EA] programs in the context of healthcare technology implementation. The research is concerned with the participants' capacities, reasoning, and choices, which influenced the outcome of the EA programme. Therefore, the research explanation aims to uncover the potential to change EA's technology EA programme mechanisms. This evaluative research is based on the notion that all knowledge is fallible (Pawson & Tilley, 2004; Wong et al., 2013; Emmel, 2013; Manzano, 2016).

"It steers a course between disregard for stakeholders on account of their self-interested biases and their craven treatment as omniscient and infallible on account of their inside knowledge. Stakeholders are treated as fallible experts whose understanding needs to be formalised and tested" (Pawson & Tilley, 2004, p.22).

"Central to the research question dealing with the change of the programme mechanisms are the following realism axioms: the ability to reconfigure the existing chains of reasoning and resources, which are fundamental factors that have led to the outcome of the EA program that the research seeks to explain. Pawson and Tilley argue that the critical realist evaluation research question must address the following:

- The mechanisms for change activated by the program and how these hidden and unhidden mechanisms counteract the existing organisation's social activities.
- The social and cultural circumstances are essential for the change mechanisms to work and be distributed across the [EA] program contexts.
- EA implementation in healthcare organisations is social programs or social systems, the interaction of individuals, the organisation's agency, structure, and social processes. *"Social*

programs are undeniably, unequivocally, unexceptionally social systems" (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63).

1.5.4 Significance Of the Study

The study is a realistic evaluation of the management of EA programs in a healthcare organisation. It explores how mechanisms within EA programs, in context, influence the outcomes paying particular attention to how practitioners act, why, by whom, and in what circumstances these outcomes are implemented. The mechanisms of EA and how they affect the outcomes of Architecture programme intervention require further research. Particularly how agency, structural, cultural, and relations factors affect the outcomes of the EA program intervention. The study explores how to successfully manage EA programs by identifying EA programs' critical success and failure factors.

1.5.5 Research Focus

The lack of in-depth research into the Mechanisms of EA has not been adequately researched Ahlemann, Legner & Lux (2020). Hope (2015) argues for the significance of Socio-Technical factors in determining EA success. This research focuses on the impact of EA Mechanisms on the outcome of EA implementations within a Socio-Technological context. [EA] Mechanisms are activated in program implementation to produce outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh, 2020b). Mechanisms of program implementations in a social context may be hidden or opaque. However, they contribute to the context of programs to produce a transformation that may be aligned or unaligned with organisational expectations. Therefore, the configuration of such EA mechanisms is of interest in determining the EA program's critical success or critical failure factors.

1.6 Scope Of the Study

This research offers an explanatory abductive reasoning approach to how and why the mechanisms of EA can affect outcomes of related programmes with specific emphasis on healthcare implementation as a social programme. The research combines the Open Group's Architecture Framework Architecture development method (ADM) theories (The Open Group, 2018). The study

proposes a mechanisms-context-output configuration as the central theme in evaluating EA programmes drawing on theories from social science research and EA framework from industry experts. The embedded mechanisms, the context-mechanism-outcome configuration, social-technical mechanisms, and the environmental context, such as culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure, form a unified and superimposed Socio-Technological perspective of how and why EA programmes may or may not work.

The study also aims to contribute to the theoretical and practical knowledge about the critical success and failure factors that affect EA programme outcomes. The study aims to understand why EA programs work or do not work by understanding the action of mechanisms. *"While much has been written about the factors influencing the success of EA programmes, there are few empirical investigations of the role of critical success factors (CSFs) in the success of EA programmes" (Hope et al., 2017, p.1)*

1.6.1 Axioms

It is imperative to provide the philosophical underpinnings of the implementation of this research to explain the high failure rate of EA initiatives. The research adopts the critical realist perspective (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Bhaskar, 2009), interwoven with strategic alignment models of EA (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999; The Open Group, 2018), on the logic of critical realist explanation of why and how EA programmes in the social programmes work, regularities are socially significant.

"The basic task of social inquiry is to explain interesting, puzzling, socially significant regularities (R). Explanations take the form of [postulating] some underlying Mechanisms (M) which generates the regularity and thus consists of propositions about how the interplay between structures and agency has constituted the regularity. With the realist investigation, there is also an investigation of how the working of such mechanisms is contingent and conditional and thus only fired in particular local, historical, and institutional contexts (C)" (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p71).

In this thesis, ‘organisation’ and ‘institutions’ are used interchangeably to refer to the workplace as “*a company or other group of people that work together for a particular purpose*” (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.).

Mechanisms of EA programmes may be hidden and unhidden. Mechanisms have causal pathways that lead to change, contingent on social and cultural factors, and are triggered by the programme to create outcomes aligned with the institution's strategic objectives.

"Research has to answer the questions: what are the mechanisms for change triggered by a program, and how do they counteract the existing social process?" (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.75).

Mechanisms have generative causal pathways, and the created outcomes are not predictable but are constrained by context. The research question also addresses contingent conditions for mechanisms to operate in the context of EA programmes. *"What are the social and cultural conditions necessary for change mechanisms to operate, and how are they distributed within and between contexts?" (p.77).*

Various authors have used the term implementation, initiative or management to qualify the use of Enterprise Architecture. In this thesis, EA implementation, EA management or EA initiative are used interchangeably to guide significant organisational digital transformation changes towards achieving business goals, aligning IT and business strategies, ensuring effective communication among stakeholders, and facilitating strategic decision-making processes.

Enterprise Architecture Management is a key strategic instrument that allows for the holistic analysis, management, and development of the information systems architecture in an organisation. It aids in aligning IT and business strategies, ensuring effective communication among stakeholders, and facilitating strategic decision-making processes. Its success can be measured by various factors, including stakeholder satisfaction, decision-making impact, and financial impact (Lange, Mendling, & Recker, 2016).

The process of Enterprise Architecture Implementation involves the practical application of enterprise architecture principles to guide the organisation's systems towards achieving business goals. It includes systematically structuring enterprise architectures, introducing effective tools and models, and balancing IT and business considerations (Rood, 1994; Veltman-Van Reekum et al., 2006).

Enterprise Architecture Initiatives involve the application of enterprise architecture concepts to guide significant changes in the organisation. They play a crucial role in organisational transformation, enabling a structured approach to evaluate, design, and implement changes in the organisation's structure, processes, and systems. The success of these initiatives can be influenced by various factors, including cultural aspects (Shanks et al., 2000; Simon, Fischbach, & Schoder, 2013).

1.7 The Organisation of the Thesis

The section is a brief overview of the organisation of the thesis.

1.7.1 Chapter One: Introduction

Chapter One is an overview of the thesis. It establishes the research question, aims and objective, explaining the need to further research in the field of EA, primarily on mechanisms in social programmes. It also provides the rationale and motivation for this research.

1.7.2 Chapter Two: Literature Review

Chapter two is the literature review section. It provides the research context, discusses relevant details about its location and structure, and highlights relevant issues and stories in understanding the research context. The chapter discusses the critical realist paradigm and touches on a brief Context-mechanism outcome configuration, the TOGAF ADM and some concepts on EA value. Other concepts relevant to the research have also been discussed, including the socio-technical approaches to EA. The literature review is a significant part of the research as it helps the research adjudicate between theories from the extant literature and relevant organisation reports. Insights will be used to develop the theoretical Framework in Chapter 3.

1.7.3 Chapter Three: Conceptual Framework

Chapter Three formulates and discusses the conceptual Framework drawing on the literature discussed in chapter one and explaining the key concepts and theories. Chapter Three proposes the CRAFTS model, a context-mechanism-outcome heuristic framework used for collections, analysis, and research findings in later sections. The chapter also includes proposed concepts on socio-technological approaches to EA. A significant part of release evaluation in theory development seeks an explanation rather than a simple description (Wong et al., 2016).

1.7.4 Chapter Four: Methodology

Chapter Four is the methodology chapter. It discusses the key concepts and methods used for the research, including qualitative data collection and analysis, retroductive theorisation approaches, critical realist approach to semi-structured interviewing, how participants are sampled, and how the Context-mechanism-outcome configuration of the programme is conjectured.

1.7.5 Chapter Five: Analysis

Chapter Five is the analysis chapter. It discusses how the data collected from participants are analysed, including how the CMO configurations are elicited in line with the conceptual framework proposed in chapter three. The CMO configuration provided the answers to the research questions, specifically the CMO configurations for the critical failure and critical success of factors of the study programme.

1.7.6 Chapter Six: Findings and Summary of Findings

Chapter Six presents the research study's findings, ostensibly answering the research questions in chapter two. The findings synthesised are linked with the CMO configurations elicited from participants and analysed in chapter five. The summary of findings directly focuses on the research questions, the critical success factors and failure factors in EA implementations in healthcare organisations, and the intended audience of EA Practitioners and programme implementers.

1.7.7 Chapter Seven: Conclusion

Chapter seven is the conclusion chapter. It provides a summary of what has been done in this research.

1.8 Summary

Chapter One outlines the research aim, objectives, and questions. It also outlines the significance of the study to the field of EA in healthcare, an introduction to EA and the current state of EA implementations with digital transformation programmes.

2 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Chapter two aims to review what is currently known about EA implementation in healthcare. It draws from literature within and outside the healthcare sector to discuss and identify the factors critical to the success of EA implementation. The discussion in section 1.5 shows that UK healthcare organisations need an improved business strategy and Information Technology solutions, especially in this era of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the COVID-19 pandemic has become a "new normal" worldwide, health organisations face challenges integrating their business vision and IT solutions for better patient outcomes. Therefore, it is essential to review what is already known, claimed, and described in the literature about EA mechanisms and their application to identify potential critical success factors and critical success failures for EA implementation in the NHS.

The first section explains how the literature was scoped and describes the search strategy used in scoping the literature. The section outlines the inclusion and exclusion criteria used to set the literature reviewed. It also explains how the literature drawn from other EA contexts could offer insight into what may be considered a successful EA implementation in the UK health sector. The second section explores the various EA frameworks and their mechanism. The section also aims to identify the gap(s) in the literature about the EA frameworks, which the recent study aimed to address. The idea is to review multiple debates on EA frameworks and methodologies to locate the current study in a suitable framework.

The third broadly explores the debates around the vision and benefits of EA implementation. It discusses the various conceptions of value, benefits, and challenges of EA. This discussion is critical in the context of this study because *"before one can start drawing up ADs (Architectural Descriptions¹), the scope of the architecture activity should be determined"* (Goethals, 2005, p.2).

The fourth section explores the various EA context. The focus is on understanding how EA is implemented in each context and exploring the multiple factors that aid the implementation. The contexts were reviewed in their culture, agency, relations, funding, technology, and structure.

2.2 Scoping the literature

This literature review was done to understand that any literature that provides valuable insight into EA is considered if it meets the inclusion criteria. Diverse perspectives each have unique contributions to make, and understanding these contributions requires an appreciation for the distinctiveness of each paradigm. This aligns with principles of pluralism and integrative approaches in many fields (Repko, Szostak, & Buchberger, 2019; Jackson, Keys, & Cropper, 2016; Kuhn, 2012). The primary focus was to review diverse literature, both local (UK) and international literature on EA, to explore the EA frameworks, benefits, and mechanisms. The idea was to identify factors that had made EA implementation successful or challenging. The Information Technology process is irrespective of its context (Goethals, 2005); hence, there was no limitation on the country or industry from which the reviewed literature emerged. Nevertheless, some inclusion/exclusion criteria were used to limit the currency and ensure the reviewed literature's integrity. The requirements include all reviewed literature.

- It must be written in the English language.
- Recent publications are used where available. However, older literature was consulted when necessary as they provided insights into some background information for EA.
- The journal must be ranked at three stars and above when published as a journal article. However, lower-ranked papers were considered necessary.
- Journal articles must be peer-reviewed.
- Both research articles and review papers were considered.
- Published reports and articles about the technology programme
- Publicly available documents about the programme

In terms of the search strategy, the search for relevant literature started with a keyword search in online journals such as the MIT Journal of Information Management Review and the Harvard Business Review. Literature searches were also done on the University's online library; online databases (for example, Scopus and Web of Science); web searches such as Google Scholar; official reports such as TOGAF white papers and some recommendations from the supervisory team. The researcher also searched for relevant literature from the reference list of the resultant articles or books. The resulting references were organised in Mendeley. The main keywords for the search were "EA", "healthcare organisation", "EA framework", "EA value", "EA scope", "Architecture descriptions", "implementation", "critical failure factors", and "critical realism". Various search strategies such as phrase searching, truncations and adjacency were employed, and operators (e.g., "OR", "and") were used in extracting relevant literature. Moreover, "the document type" and "the publication date" were used as filters to narrow down the resulting references.

2.3 What is Enterprise Architecture (EA)?

The ISO, IEC and IEEE define architecture in several ways. Enterprise Architecture has several definitions, some of which have been adopted as standard definitions. The ISO, IEC and IEEE define a system as *"man-made and may be configured with one or more of the following: hardware, software, data, humans, processes (e.g., processes for providing service to users), procedures (e.g., operator instructions, facilities, materials and naturally occurring entities"* (ISO, 2011, p.3).

According to the ISO/IEC/IEEE standard, *"environment [system] context determining the setting and circumstances of all influences upon a system"* (ISO, 2011, 3.1.21).

The Open Group describes an enterprise as *"... any collection of organisations that has a common set of goals"* (TOGAF, 2018, p. 5). The ISO (2011) defines an enterprise as *"a group of interrelated and interacting elements that form a complex whole"* (Enterprise).

Architecting is the “*process of conceiving, defining, expressing, documenting, communicating, certifying proper implementation of, maintaining and improving an architecture throughout a system's life cycle*” (ISO, 2011, 3.1).

An architect is the person, team, or organisation responsible for systems architecture (ISO, 2011). According to the ISO, Architecting occurs within the framework of a company, a programme, or a project. The entity to be architected might be of several types, as shown in the examples below: system, enterprise, solution, business, data, application, information technology, mission, product, service, and software. Certifying the appropriate execution of a design is occasionally recorded as a formal declaration by the architect to the client or user that the system, as-built, fulfil the requirements for being ready for use.

ISO (2011) identifies two features of architecture:

First, Architecture is “a formal description of a system” (ISO, 2011) or a thorough component-level blueprint that guides its implementation. Secondly, Architecture is described as a component structure, interrelationships between components, and the concepts and criteria that govern their design and evolution across time. When a qualifier is prefixed to the word architecture, it indicates that the architecture applies to that entity; System Architecture indicates that the architecture applies to a system; **Enterprise** Architecture indicates that the architecture applies to an enterprise or organisation (ISO, 2011).

The organisational logic for business processes and information technology infrastructure that reflects the institution's integration and standardisation needs is known as enterprise architecture. The operational model represents the ideal degree of integration and standardisation of business processes to deliver [socio-technological] products and services to stakeholders (Weill, 2007).

“The entity to be architected may be a system, an enterprise, a solution, an organisation, data, an application, information technology, mission, a product, a service, or Software” (ISO, 2011, 3.1).

According to The Open Group (2019), Architecture is *"the structure of components, their inter-relationships, and the principles and guidelines governing their design and evolution over time"* (The Open Group, 2018, Part I). The Open Group confirms that TOGAF supports but does not strictly conform to the nomenclature used in the ISO standard definition of architecture. See glossary of terms.

According to The Open Group (2018), EA "is used in many contexts. [EA] can denote both the architecture of an entire enterprise, encompassing all its information systems and the architecture of a specific domain within the enterprise. In both cases, the architecture crosses multiple systems and multiple functional groups with the enterprise" (p.1).

According to Gartner (2021, p.1), EA *"is a discipline for proactively and holistically leading enterprise responses to disruptive forces by identifying and analysing the execution of change toward desired business vision and outcomes."*

According to Tamm et al. (2015, p142), "Enterprise Architecture is the definition and representation of a high-level view of an enterprise's business processes and IT systems, their interrelationships, and the extent to which these processes and systems are shared by different parts of the enterprise (organisation)."

According to Tamm et al., EA's primary objective is to define the desirable, aspirational future state of the organisation's business processes and information technology objectives referred to as target 'architecture'. The goal of EA is also to provide a strategic technology roadmap to enable the organisation to achieve the stated target architecture from its current state of EA, often referred to as the 'baseline architecture'.

Two principal attributes of EA are the definition of the planning process for creating the target state architecture and the tangible and intangible outcomes of that planning process in the form of EA documentation: roadmaps, architecture diagrams and other related process-driven artefacts.

EA aims to serve as an alignment mechanism between the organisation's strategic objective and information technology. Some aspects of EA focus on delivering project technology solution architecting or 'system architecting'.

"The task of EA is to translate the broader principles, capabilities, and goals defined in the strategies into systems and processes that enable the enterprise to realise these goals. In this regard, EA is a step towards enacting strategy" (p.142).

ISO (2011) and ISO (2019) define a service as a “**means of delivering value for the customer by facilitating results (or outcomes) the customer wants to achieve**”, and ISO (2011) defines it as “**a set of capabilities that a component provides to another component via an interface**”.

Accordingly, by the ISO definitions, Enterprise Architecture may therefore be considered a service through its role as a process for strategic alignment between the organisation's needs and its IT (Hope et al., 2017; Lange, Mendling, & Recker, 2016; Niemi & Pekkola, 2017; Tamm et al., 2015; The Open Group, 2018).

One of the widely used frameworks, Zachman (1987), adopted the concept of Enterprise Architecture Management (EAM) from the conceptual modelling technique of engineering and architecture from construction science to aid in the planning the design of organisational information management systems (Lankhorst, 2013; Bernard, 2012; Ross, Weill, & Robertson, 2006).

Knowledge of the related generative mechanisms and the circumstances in which they are triggered is crucial for the successful outcomes of programmes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The prerequisites associated with these mechanisms are indispensable for decision-makers, as they assist in comprehending and undertaking suitable measures for the effective execution of the intended goals (Niemi & Pekkola, 2017; Schmidt & Buxmann, 2011; Tamm et al., 2011).

As an engine of organisational performance, it uses the modelling technique through an integrated mediation of the organisation's mandate and its technology assets to provide alignment that enables performance improvement (Lange et al., 2016; Tamm et al., 2011). In their finding, Boucharas, van

Steenbergen, Jansen and Brinkkempe (2010), conducted within contemporary research of EAM, argue that organisations have gained. These gains are about how EAM affects the management and project portfolios, compliance with business regulations, mitigating organisational risk and cost reduction of business operations.

EAM has also become popular in steering digital business transformation initiatives towards successful completions to improve firm performance (Bērziša et al., 2015; Röglinger, Bolsinger, Haeckel, & Walter, 2016; Tamm et al., 2015). Niemi and Pekkola (2020) argue that planning and steering digital transformation can be arduous as complexity has increasingly been built into the organisation. EA has been commonly used as a planning and governance perspective to manage the complexity and evolution to align its IT and objectives. Niemi and Pekkola further argue that realising EA benefits involves a longitudinally interconnected chain of the undertaking, from the EA initiation phase, until several years later, when measurable outcomes, such as cost efficiency, are achieved.

2.4 Over two decades of National Health IT: exploring strategy, structure, and systems in the English NHS.

The focus of NHS IT management in the '70s and '80s was on providing reports for the NHS for strategic use in healthcare delivery. Due to changes in healthcare needs, further strategic initiatives were taken in the '90s and 2000s to improve better use of available information to deliver 21st-century information technology support for the NHS (DHSC, 2018).

The challenges of implementing information technology programmes have been researched.

According to Hendy et al. (2007), information technology programmes have several serious concerns. These apprehensions span a variety of issues, including financial shortfalls, delays in the implementation of patient administration systems that align with the implementing organisation's vision, and inadequate communication between the agencies executing the programmes and the user managers. Each of these issues represents potential obstacles that could impede the successful execution and overall efficacy of the programme.

In the following recommendations of their findings, Hendy et al. (2007) argue that organisations need to set a realistic timetable and take proactive measures to procure interim systems to enable the continuity of services while delays occur. Transition Architecture must incorporate temporary solutions as interim measures for the delay in achieving programme outcomes.

Pouloudi, Currie, and Whitley (2016) argue that there is an increase in healthcare technology's pervasiveness, complexity, and challenges in the healthcare environment. In their research using stakeholder theory, they argue that favourable and unfavourable several stakeholder group viewpoints have a causal link with entanglement during the adoption of the UK NHS N3 network. Such entanglement, they argue, exists because competing viewpoints undermine the uptake of the health network.

The NHS IT management organisations, from 2010 to 2018, have enabled digital services for better healthcare (DHSC, 2018). The strategic focus of the NHS IT management organisations has, over the period, moved from technical and data standards, connectivity, and applications to consolation and support. Relationship with local NHS organisations continues to be centralised in providing resources and guidance (Price, Green & Suhomlinova, 2019).

It is challenging for organisations to align their objectives with their information systems. The NHS continues to report such difficulties in its implementations. Without a specific conceptual framework for evaluating, the outcomes of longer-term interventions are overlooked (Price et al., 2019).

The alignment of organisational objectives with information systems has practical implications for the functioning of Enterprise Architecture (EA). This alignment facilitates agility within EA operations and enables an ongoing evaluation of longitudinal implementation. This evaluation, in turn, supports the continuous strategic alignment necessary for an organisation's adaptability and sustained success in its operations. Hospitals are one of the most complex stakeholders, with much interaction between everyone who works there (patients, nurses, doctors, and staff). In the running of a hospital, the use of IT has been shown to make things more effective and efficient (Girsang &

Abimanyu, 2021). Girsang and Abimanyu argue a *"lack of alignment between business strategy and IT strategy"* (p.305) in healthcare organisations. The concepts of structuration and context have gained significant importance in shaping the action context of programmes. This shift is a consequence of changes in the structural framework to accord with national strategy, coupled with the dynamic context of the healthcare system. The evolutionary nature of these elements necessitates their thoughtful consideration in the planning and execution of healthcare programmes, ensuring their relevance and efficacy within a fluctuating environment. The NHS assessed the impact of the evolving NHS's multifaceted organisational structure by researching the relationship between progressive national strategy and an actively evolving healthcare system.

According to Price et al. (2019), The NHS must adopt an M-form structure approach that adopts centralised governance with multiple semi-autonomous subsidiaries to pursue set mutual goals.

In healthcare systems, the design and efficacy of networks, in conjunction with the principles of autonomy and control, are paramount. The balance and interplay between these elements fundamentally shape these systems' operational effectiveness, patient outcomes, and overall success. These aspects warrant meticulous attention and careful management in healthcare systems planning, implementation, and ongoing operation. They are social and hierarchical, with interconnected subsystems, formal structures, and basic components. Other industries, including healthcare, investigate autonomy and control in complex hierarchical systems to discover issues within and among organisations via local autonomy. Price et al. argue that the association between strategy and structure has long been a subject of interest in management but faces planning and implementation challenges. NHS decision-makers must pursue a consistent assessment of the impact of the system's restructuring.

Achieving integrated national IT systems requires understanding, optimal management of complexity and organisational and structural dynamics irrespective of its implementation strategy. Archer's morphogenetic approach to changing social reality on structure, culture, relation, and agency is

discussed. It constitutes part of the foundation for the Socio-Technological theoretical approach of this thesis (Archer, 1995, 1996, 1998).

2.5 The Impact of the Coronavirus Pandemic on EA and the Research

Healthcare delivery in the NHS has been transformed radically by the coronavirus pandemic. The Coronavirus pandemic, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus and leading to the disease known as COVID-19, began in the year 2019. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared it a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on January 30, 2020, and subsequently recognised it as a pandemic on March 11, 2020 (WHO, 2020). It is like leaving a long-term impact on the health and well-being of crucial staff and on strategies to improve clinical outcomes and tackle workforce planning issues (Powell, 2020).

Technology alignment with organisation strategies through EA becomes necessary because of the pervasive and indispensable use of digitally enabled services in the NHS. The existing trend in workforce configuration is a convergence towards online working. Responses to the covid-19 Pandemic have accelerated these reconfigurations of systems and working structures. New ways of working, such as out-of-office working audio-visually enabled meetings, have been introduced throughout the NHS in response to the "new normal".

The impact of structural, agential, relational, and cultural changes has become too apparent because of the coronavirus pandemic. Way of workings, new EAs for working under social distancing, and reconfiguring the safety culture to prevent virus transmission have led to digital transformations requiring the realignment of strategy and technology (Powell, 2020).

2.6 Enterprise Architecture Challenges and Lessons From NHS Digital's Transformation Programmes.

The National Audit Office (NOA) has voiced concerns over digital transformation performance within the National Health Service (NHS). Historically, such initiatives have delivered poor value,

with significant obstacles cited, including legacy IT systems, complex governance, and a myriad of stakeholders (NOA, 2020a).

The NOA has evaluated the NHS's past digital transformation attempts, such as the failed endeavour to transition to a paperless system by 2018 (NOA, 2020a). This initiative, among others, suffered from a lack of progress, thereby demonstrating the need for robust changes in IT investment management and stakeholder behaviour.

There is concern over the projected funding for future digital transformations. The NHSE&I anticipates requiring around £8.1 billion to realize its digital objectives by 2024, including up to three billion pounds from NHS Trusts up until 2029. However, the NOA has questioned the viability of these budgets, emphasizing the scarcity of cost data and the potential unwillingness or inability of trusts to provide the necessary funding (NOA, 2020a).

Despite incremental improvements in trusts' digital maturity since 2016, the capacity to leverage technology in patient care is still a significant issue. According to the NOA, only 54% of trusts believe they can rely on digital records for timely information, with 16% considering their digital maturity as 'low' (NOA, 2020a).

The NOA has pointed out that the NHS needs to acknowledge and learn from past mistakes for a more successful digital transformation. Key to this is ensuring interoperability, efficient governance, consistent strategy, sufficient investment, and better data on costs and benefits.

Despite a clear vision for digital transformation, the NHS faces notable discrepancies between its objectives and the current state of its Enterprise Architecture. Systemic discord is not confined to software systems but also involves the organizational culture, including stakeholder interests and strategic directions. The DOH (2018) calls for a socio-technical approach to digital transformation that accounts for these social and technological complexities.

The Department of Health (DOH, 2018) underscores the need to improve the technology used by those delivering health and care services to achieve improved technological capabilities and better

health outcomes. Despite excellent practice in some areas, many health and care providers still grapple with these fundamentals.

The DOH (2018) stipulates several guiding principles for future digital transformations, including managing legacy technology, risk-averse culture, underinvestment, and maintaining public trust. Strategic requirements include ensuring data security, addressing technology incompatibilities, and improving accessibility for all.

Adopting an open ecosystem of user experience designers, the DHSC aims to create better service provision while reducing internal tensions (DOH, 2018). The department plans to prioritize user demands, privacy, security, interoperability, and inclusivity while continually adopting the latest cybersecurity standards.

The NOA report highlights several key lessons about the challenges of digital transformation in the NHS. The key lessons from the report revolve around the importance of planning, funding, improving digital maturity, workforce training, learning from past failures, and focusing on user needs in any future digital transformation initiatives:

- **Digital Transformation Difficulty:** Digital transformation is inherently difficult due to aged ('legacy') IT systems, complex governance, numerous stakeholders, and existing commercial arrangements. The need for large-scale process and behavioural change, substantial IT investment, and improving digital maturity across all Trusts make the process complex.
- **Progress Evaluation:** The NHS has failed to achieve its expected digital transformation progress since 2014. It includes the objective of becoming a 'paperless' NHS, which demonstrates the issues of setting ambitious goals without adequate support and infrastructure.
- **Funding Issues:** The report suggests that the NHS needs approximately £8.1 billion to achieve its digital transformation goals. However, funding has been insufficient, and plans are

based on limited cost data. There is a significant risk that trusts may be unable or unwilling to fund the £3 billion expected.

- **Digital Maturity Disparity:** The report highlights the mixed picture of digital maturity across different trusts. While some trusts are digitally mature, digital capacity remains an issue for many, with 16% of NHS Trusts rating their digital maturity as 'low'.
- **Poor Governance and Planning:** The report criticizes the lack of national oversight and governance of digital transformation at the local level. It also highlights the complexity and fragmentation of the NHS's technology solutions and the frequent changes to digital programmes, plans, and leadership tenure.
- **Workforce Skills Gap:** The NHS faces a shortage of digital and data skills among its workforce. This gap must be addressed to ensure the success of digital transformation efforts.
- **Cybersecurity Vulnerabilities:** The NHS's legacy IT systems are particularly vulnerable to cyber-attacks and data losses. This risk can undermine public trust in the NHS's digital transformation efforts.
- **Learning from Past Failures:** The report suggests that the NHS has not adequately learned from past digital transformation failures and recommends systematically learning and implementing lessons from previous efforts.
- **Focus on Stakeholder Needs:** The report argues that user needs, privacy, security, interoperability, and inclusivity should guide the development of digital technologies.

The DHSC established a data layer of registers and APIs to facilitate data management and discovery. Regarding patient records management, the department will enhance its procurement process by establishing preferred contracts and systemising patient records systems (DOH, 2018). This strategy should facilitate seamless updates and reduce the need for bespoke technologies, leveraging the UK's digital expertise to benefit the NHS.

2.7 Background of Culture, Relations and Agency, Funding, Technology and Structure of Health and Social Care in England

2.7.1 About NHS England

Healthcare in England is funded, planned, and delivered by NHS England. The non-departmental agency funds CCGs and the DHSC. Commissions dental, optical, pharmacy and general practitioner initiatives for the local service user community. It also provides uncommon illness intervention, screening, and immunisation programmes. Among these obligations is maintaining CCG efficiency. NHS England provides extensive assistance and guidance to CCGs in its supervisory function—notably the Cancer Drug Fund (NHS Commissioning, 2021; NHS England, 2019a). The integrated care systems (ICSs) aspirational integrated care providers (ICPs) contract covers NHS and local government services. Figure 2.1 shows the functional structure of NHS England; how ICSs (and future ICP contracts) cross the NHS and local government.

Figure 2.1. above shows the integrated Care Systems of the NHS and Local Government—source: (House of Commons Library, 2020).

NHS England, created in April 2019, and Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs) are England's two central NHS bodies, according to the House of Commons (Powell, 2020). While the former oversees

NHS leadership via joint national and regional teams, the latter oversees local services. Patient safety is provided by the Care Quality Commission (CQC), workforce planning, skills development, and education by Health Education England, and public health by Public Health England (PHE). The NHS constitution and the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence are also part of its responsibilities (NICE). It highlights critical concerns in health policy, including the NHS's performance, financing, and personnel. Also considered are redesigning and integrating services, changing competition regulations, and advancing the use of technology and data in healthcare.

The House of Commons (Powell, 2020) highlighted significant policy concerns in NHS England, including performance, workforce pressures, service reform and integration, and technology and data development and usage. According to Powell (2020), the UK government adopted the Social Care Act of 2012 to address these challenges.

Forty-two Sustainability and Transformation Partnerships (STPs) were established across England to enhance services, promote health, and allow a more financially sustainable delivery mechanism for NHS England's responsibility to service consumers. The STP unifies regional health and social care plans. The UK health department established Integrated Care Systems (ICSs) in 14 English regions to improve STP collaboration, allowing NHS organisations to collaborate with local councils and other partners. The ICSs oversee population health and resource management.

According to Powell (2020), since April 2019, STPs and ICSs have been responsible for enhancing service delivery across the NHS. In January 2019, they issued a 10-year strategy plan and a long-term NHS plan outlining how the NHS is funded. The 10-year strategy outlines how healthcare access improves patient outcomes. The five-year plan reconciled the NHS's health strategy from a commissioning/provider division. The NHS is now structured on this single approach (Powell, 2020).

2.7.2 Structure of NHS Digital

The Strategy, policy and governance function of NHS Digital is responsible for strategy and planning, technology, policy and architecture, clinical governance, privacy, transparency and ethics, and

communications. Its vision is to empower and enable sustainable delivery through organisation-wide specialist functions which ensure alignment to the health and social care system (NHS Digital, 2021a), a system that enables UK care receivers to 'live more independent, healthier lives for longer. The technology, policy and architecture function sit within the strategy, policy, and governance. It takes responsibility for providing digital services to the NHS digital, underpinned by a common architecture practice and appropriate technologies for health care delivery by defining the organisation's vision and technology implementation strategies and aligning technology resources with its business needs.

Figure 2.2. shows the functional structure of the digital NHS.

Figure 2.2 Functional Structure of NHS Digital (NHS Digital, 2021a)

As of the 1st of February, 2023, NHS England and NHS Digital have officially consolidated their operations in a landmark merger. This confluence marks the inaugural phase of a strategic move towards forming a unified entity to guide the National Health Service in England. The fundamental aim of this integration is to enhance service delivery quality across the board, ensuring a universally high standard of care. Despite the recent merger between NHS England and NHS Digital, the core

function of NHS Digital remains consistent. It remains the centre for data and technology expertise within the NHS, playing a critical role in collecting and analyzing data to enhance patient outcomes. Its pivotal role was exemplified through the facilitation of the National Booking Service, which was integral in administering nearly 145 million doses in the NHS Covid vaccination programme (NHS England, 2023, February 1).

2.7.3 NHS Digital – Assuring Technology and Funding in the NHS

Schedule 18 of the Health and Social Care (HSC) Act 2012 is outlined in an Accounting Officer Memorandum delivered to its Chief Executive by the DHSC Principal Accounting Officer (DHSC, 2019). Through its boards, NHS Digital is accountable to the UK Parliament for its performance and financial integrity (NHS Digital, 2021a).

The Health and Social Care (HSC) board is crucial in bolstering robust financial management and enhancing value by endorsing the business strategy, operational plans, and financial accounts. Assuring appropriate financial and performance risk governance and internal assurance methods are among the board's duties. This ensures that NHS Digital complies with all applicable rules and regulations (NHS Digital, 2021a).

NHS Digital full-time employees earn less than the UK public sector median of 10.7% and the statistical mean of 12.1%, according to October 2019 ONS preliminary statistics (NHS Digital, 2021a). The main reason for the pay gap is that men have more seniority than women. Men also earn more significant role-specific recruiting, retention, and on-call compensation (NHS Digital, 2021a). BAME persons make up 12.3% of the UK workforce. As of 2018-19, over 12.7 per cent of our employees were BAME. Approximately 38% of our employment applications were BAME, up from 21% last year, and approximately 25% of NHS Digital staff were BAME. Disabled employees were 4.8%, up from 4.8% last year. 18% of working-age Britons and 9.2% of employed Britons are disabled (NHS Digital, 2021a).

The NHS Digital workforce comprises 2.7% LGBT+ and 69.8% heterosexual. 27.5 % of workers refuse to share. Ages vary from 46 to 65 at NHS Digital. The number of employees aged twenty-six and thirty-five had fallen as of 2016 (NHS Digital, 2021a). Approximately 33% of NHS Digital employees have not declared their faith. Historically, this proportion has been steady. Around 34% are Christians, 13% are from other religions, and 19% are atheists (NHS Digital, 2021a).

NHS Digital faces significant challenges (NHS Digital, 2021b). NHS Digital's responsibility includes assisting the NHS with the coronavirus response and preventing data or service loss. In 2019, digital solutions to boost system responsiveness were focused on, including data services, technical IT, and product support (NHS Digital, 2021a).

Assure NHS Digital has the skills and flexibility to address future healthcare and digitalization demands. These included a new People Plan, revising the NHS Digital brand promise, employment reviews and succession planning. Controls, such as business continuity plans, assure high availability, integrity, and confidentiality of essential systems and services (NHS Digital, 2021a).

Due to budget issues, NHS Digital successfully delivered significant health and care reform programmes. NHS Digital improved programme resourcing and governance controls in 2019 by prioritising essential programmes (NHS Digital, 2021b).

According to King's Fund (2019), two organisations and NHS Digital have agreed on new responsibilities, roles, accountability, governance structures, and working methods for corporate and IT system governance. NHS Digital has also improved NHS Digital clinical governance system to ensure sufficient clinical safety, quality, and patient experience. In continuing to help the health and social care sector, patients, and the public, NHS Digital faced exceptional difficulties in 2020-21, mainly due to funding constraints (NHS Digital, 2021b).

2.7.4 Vision and Strategy for Technology

The NHS's vision is "to provide care and services that we and our families would want to use" (DOH, 2018, para.3). Its ambition is to use the best technology available for the NHS and social care sector to Improve health and communities.

According to the DOH, to reach this capability, they need to focus on getting the 'basics right', implying a '**Digital Architecture**' are the building block of the health and care system. *"Open standards, secure identity and interoperability are critical to the safe and successful use of technology, ensuring that systems talk to each other and that the right data gets to the right place at the right time" (para.7).*

The NHS needs modular IT systems that can be quickly swapped out to establish a market where providers compete and are rewarded for excellence. They will also guarantee that patients and care service users have trust in the security and responsible use of their data (DOH, 2018).

The NHS hopes to use the UK 'healthtech' as the world's premier healthtech organisation, delivering breakthroughs and increasing the worldwide reputation of their scientific and research basis. The NHS wishes to capitalise on the chance to develop an ecosystem that consistently produces the finest healthtech - technology, innovative approaches, and insights that contribute to global health outcomes for export (DOH, 2018). According to the DOH, there is a growing gap between the NHS vision and its digital architecture's current state, requiring a radically new approach to technology across systems devoid of the portrayal that it is arduous to 'do it right' in health and care.

2.7.5 The Health and Social Care Act 2012 (HSCA)

The Health and Social Care Act included critical structural changes to reduce central control, give clinical staff more responsibility in commissioning health services, and involve patients more in their care (HSCA, 2012). The social care act was implemented in April 2013, with CCGs commissioning services, local authorities overseeing public health, and Healthwatch replacing strategic health authorities and primary care trusts (Powell, 2020).

The Health and Social Care Act (TNA, 2012) completely restructured the NHS. It affects the new structure and its relationships, the NHS culture, and the agential arrangements for safe patient care. The social care act also established Health Education and Health Research Authorities to oversee health and social care education and research, raising standards and performance.

2.7.6 From the Five-Year Forward View of the NHS to the Long-Term Plan

The five-year plan sets several priorities, among others, to pay a more significant focus on Technology and innovation and the related skills and workforce requirements to bring them to fruition. These priority areas will enable the NHS to provide better care and promote its service users' self-care.

The plan Improves emergency care and widens participation in urgent and emergency care systems. As demand for services grows, the need to improve the flow of patients across health delivery institutions within the NHS has become another priority area.

Strategic alignment of this new structure requires far more radical approaches to EA programmes that incorporate mechanisms that span beyond the technical to those that tackle the dynamic social context such restructuring creates (NHS England, 2019a).

According to Archer (1995), outcomes of actions such as those planned by the Social Care Act occur within a social context. Archer further suggests that outcomes are context-dependent. Programme actions such as the plan to bring the Health and social care act may merely reproduce the pre-existing action context, leading to invariant transformation or transformations that modify the existing action context.

2.7.7 Sustainability and Transformation Plans (STPs)

The sustainability and information plans published a sweeping change across forty-four agencies in England in 2016 (England & Improvement, 2019a). 42 Sustainability and Transformation Partnerships (STPs) were established across England to address improvements in the steps taken to prevent ill health and tackle challenges such as workforce shortages facing health and social care

systems. The STP was created to improve the efficiency of service delivery in hospitals, communities, mental health, and primary care services. They have been concerns about the lack of transparency and a reduction in the service capacity of NHS England from stakeholders (NHS England, 2017, March).

2.7.8 The NHS Long-Term Plan

In June 2019, NHS England's responsible body, the NHS Improvement, published a delivery framework for its five-year plan (King's Fund, 2019). The plan outlines measures of assurance that the national implementations were realistic, deliverable and in line with the budgetary allocation.

According to King's Fund (2019), NHS England (2019a), and The House of Lords Committee on the Long-term Sustainability of the NHS commented on the STP planning process. The Long-term plan proposed amendments to the existing system architectures to improve the coordination of services through the development of Sustainability and Transformation Plans. According to King's Fund (2109), by 2021, the STPs would be developed further into 14 integrated Care Systems that advance local partnerships networks, given their responsibility to them and improve the health and care systems for their respective local service populations.

2.7.9 Duties of Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs) An Agency of NHS England

The service commission roles are split between the Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs) and NHS England. Whilst the former commissions most of the NHS services, including in-hospital admissions and treatment, the latter primarily provides direct commissioning of regional and national services primary care services such as specialised services, including treatments for rare conditions, secure mental health care General Practitioner Services (GPs), dentists and opticians. Some primary medical services (GPs) have devolved most CCGs via the primary care co-commissioning framework (NHS England, 2021). However, there is an increasing allocation of services to the CCGs.

According to NHS England (2021b), as a mandated statutory duty under the Social Care Act 2012, the CCGs and NHS England have oversight responsibilities promoting the NHS constitution. They

are also responsible for securing continuous improvement in service quality delivery, reducing inequalities of access to care, and enabling and promoting patient engagement in their services. These agencies are also responsible for securing structural, agency, cultural and relations integration and promoting innovative research to improve quality and efficiency. Technology is at the core of service improvement. There is an increasing drive to digitise service and reduce paper-based care with the ambition to fully rid the services of it and adopt digital technology.

2.7.10 NHS Improvement

Part three of the HSCA (2012) sets the framework that promotes competition and choice in providing NHS services to patients. Part three empowers the DHSC to regulate, through NHS Improvement, health services anticompetitive behaviour and procurement malpractices from CCGs or NHS England. The Long-term Plan of 2019 established changes to the system architecture of the NHS to increase care coordination, departing from a market-based transformation of the HSCA and significantly amalgamating the commissioner/provider split into a single entity (NHS England, 2019a).

2.7.11 NHS Providers

NHS Foundation Trusts (FTs) and NHS Trusts provide most of the NHS's hospital, community, mental health, ambulance, and specialist care. Whilst FTs are self-governing with more extraordinary financial powers to generate revenue to invest in the services and operational freedom, the NHS Trusts have fewer powers than the CCGs. The Chief Executives, management boards, and board of governors of the FTs are responsible for improving the service offered to users and are ultimately accountable for NHS improvement.

Independent providers under a single national contract are responsible for providing General Practitioners, dentists, optometrists, and pharmacies. Some non-NHS bodies also provide NHS-funded services, including charities, voluntary sector bodies and private companies under the regulation of the CQC (House of Commons Library, 2020, April).

2.7.12 The Care Quality Commission

The Care Quality Commission (CQC) is responsible for registering, monitoring, and inspecting health and adult social care providers under a mandate granted by the Health and Social Care Act 2012 (HSCA, 2012). The CQC regulates disease treatment, disorder and injury, surgical procedures, personal care, nursing care, and assessing persons detained and receiving care under the mental health act 1983 (HSCA, 2012). All providers offering such 'regulated activities' must register with the CQC and demonstrate that they meet the standards for safe care delivery (House of Commons Library, 2020, April).

The CQC has undergone structural changes by introducing a chief inspector for hospitals, primary medical services, integrated care and adult and social care. Following recommendations from the Francis review that highlighted failures in care at the Mid Staffordshire NHS Foundation Trust, the CQC made fundamental changes in 2013 in how it regulates providers (DHSC, 2018). The fundamental standard has been introduced, including assuring safe, effective, and caring delivery of services that are responsive to the needs of patients (DHSC, 2018).

In April 2015, the CQC introduced new policies that enhance the power to act where poor care and regulatory breaches have occurred (DHSC, 2018). There is an extraordinary measure framework to tackle 'major' failures in the safe delivery of quality care or identified financial inefficiencies. Structural, agential, relations and agential changes continue to be applied with changes in the social context when outcomes are not expected.

In January 2020, the CQC introduced regulatory changes following the Whorlton Hospital review, an independent provider of care offering treatment and assessment to patients with learning disabilities and those with complex needs. The review's recommendation includes introducing an internal whistleblowing process and improving the regulation of services where the risk of abuse and harm is prevalent (House of Commons Library, 2020).

2.7.13 Accountability To the Public, Government and The Parliament of the United Kingdom

In the HSCA (2012), apart from setting the strategic direction of the NHS in England, reforms have meant the removal of political interference in the regulation and management of the NHS in England, with full power given to NHS England and its partner agency, NHS improvement (England & NHS Improvement, 2019a).

The accountability Framework to the UK government, parliament and the public explains how they set the direction for NHS England and NHS Improvement *"to underpin the initial implementation of the Long-Term Plan. It sets out shared delivery objectives for both NHS England and NHS Improvement for 2019-20, as the NHS transitions into full plan delivery. It also confirms their budgets"* (NHS England, 2019a, p.6).

The executive committee of The House of Commons on Health and social care scrutinises the administration and spending of the DHSC, making inquiries into the area of policy in line with the duty of accountability. Local Healthwatch organisations are responsible for representing the views of service users on the local authorities' Health and wellbeing boards. They also advocate for complaints management and report quality-related concerns via Healthwatch England to the CQC for the appropriate interventional measures.

2.7.14 Access of Service Users to Treatment Services

The NHS Constitution was introduced in 2009 and updated latterly in July 2015, setting out the principles and benefits of the NHS guiding how patients should access treatment (DHSC, 2018).

A comprehensive service should be provided to service users regardless of paying. Aspiring to the highest quality standard of care, the NHS places the patient at the centre of what it does through the highest standard of professionalism and excellence. They are partnering with other organisations to fulfil the interest of patients, local communities, and the population while delivering a fair, effective, sustainable, and best value for taxpayers' money acknowledging finite resources (NHS England, 2019a).

2.7.15 Education and Training of Service Providers

This non-departmental entity of the DHSC was established in 2013 to support the workforce needs of healthcare providers, commissioners, and consumers (DHSC, 2019). The Health Education England (HEE) workforce plan covers the demand and supply for physicians, nurses, pharmacists, and other NHS workforce requirements.

The HEE oversees the education and training of NHS clinicians and non-clinicians through four Local Education Trust Boards (LETBs). Local provider committees govern the LETBs, helping to match education and training results with the patient, public, and provider demands. LETBs also consult with professional regulating authorities, including the Nursing and Midwifery Council and the General Medical Council, to develop their policies.

These professional regulating agencies create quality standards and criteria for education and training and approve and verify training providers. Professional regulating agencies develop expertise, competence, and experience (Health Education England, 2020).

Concerns over the UK's withdrawal from the EU have increased attrition rates. NHS England has struggled to recruit enough nurses, GPs, and other healthcare specialists. Despite the increased number of experts hired, worker morale has dipped owing to increased pressure from inadequate personnel. NHS England faces difficulty in retaining the people necessary to offer high-quality care. Growth and assistance for the NHS staff have been proposed. A new operational model for staff following developments in the quality of care for the 21st century is also proposed. Among the measures to address nursing shortages is easing entry into NHS nursing. (Powell, 2020)

2.7.16 Safety of Patient Care

Agencies of NHS England, such as hospitals, general practitioner services and other care delivery agencies, are responsible for the safety of the care they give to their patients. The CCGs, ICSs and STPs ensure evidence-led quality provision of safe care to their service users, NHS England, NHS Improvement, Care Quality Commission, and the National Institute for Clinical Excellence. Other

national agencies are responsible for setting safety standards. Published in July 2019, The NHS Patient safety strategy aims to bring national and regional patient safety improvement initiatives under one plan (NHS England, 2019a).

2.7.17 Culture of The NHS about Patient Safety and Implications for EA.

The NHS's culture shapes how it serves its users. Strategy cannot change culture, but its impact on quality is indisputable (England & Improvement, 2019b). *"However, the significance of culture in influencing safety cannot be overlooked. Fear and blame frequently obstruct 'just cultures' in the NHS. The dread of becoming involved in patient safety events was a recurring theme in the consultation replies "* (p.7).

The NHS's digital health and safety infrastructure has changed dramatically. Systematic surveillance of new and unknown dangers, significant accidents and patient education are now possible across the NHS. *"The digital arm of a fundamental shift in the way we understand, structure, collect and use patient safety information across the NHS"* (p.21).

NHS Improvement, a partner agency of NHS England, creates digital methods to address patient safety concerns in primary care. These digital solutions increase service continuity, minimise referral delays, and enable the NHS to build successful multimorbidity management plans. Digital techniques also improve communication between staff, patients, and primary and secondary care services.

Primary care providers can digitally obtain the NHS summary care record of care episodes. According to NHS Improvement, combining GPs and community pharmacists via an electronic prescription service decreases drug prescription mistakes. They also claim that providing care in the community, where multidisciplinary teams oversee care, has become more complicated.

Better EAs might improve patient safety and IT systems like risk management. NHS England's current EA contains various IT solutions to support patient safety. These include treating adverse drug responses and tracking patient medication history.

The GP IT Futures Digital Care Services Framework includes a patient safety architecture, according to England & Improvement (2019b). The safety architecture integrates with GP IT operational paradigms to ensure digital enablement. Digital enablers include GPCs and CCGs. Digital enablers include the technical infrastructure needed to support the NHS's Long-term plan for primary care intervention.

The 'keeping general practise safe' operational model's criteria for digital changes and EAs may enable safe and secure care delivery.

"The operational model's 'keeping general practise safe' component includes standards for digital innovations such as video consultations and patient access to medical records. Artificial intelligence (AI) will assist detect patients whose medical data exhibits troubling tendencies " (England & Improvement, p.20). High-profile investigations like Gosport, Mid Staffordshire, and Morecombe Bay have changed the NHS's patient safety culture. A culture of denial and defensiveness among caregivers and staff regarding shortcomings uncovered by the probes: individual blunders are poorly controlled.

2.7.18 Integration with Health and Social care Services

Before the HSCA of 2012, health and social care were administered and funded independently. Access was also done independently, with health provided free at the point of access whilst local authorities provided means-tested social care interventions. Changes in the social structure, such as demographic trends and an ageing population, necessitated the integration of health and social care. NHS England (2020) argues that integration reduces costs apart from improving the patient experience and minimises delayed discharges.

Integration requires reconfiguring culture, relations, agency, funding, technology and structure brought on by the changes. Archer (1995) argues that such structural changes impact social action outcomes because they influence the generative mechanisms that deliver such programmes in which transformations occur.

Nevertheless, the EA framework, TOGAF, which most healthcare institutions adopt, does not provide core mechanisms that are sensitive to the social context, with developments methods to ensure a ‘Socio-Technological’ (see description in a later section) reconfiguration of the technology to support these social systems.

NHS England set up health and well-being boards and local strategic plans to strengthen the integration drive. In 2019, the UK government and NHS England jointly established a review of the existing Better Care Fund with a budgetary allocation of £7.8 bn as of 2018/2019, following concerns regarding the complexity of funding mechanisms and doubts about its return on investment (NHS England, 2020).

2.7.19 Technology and Data in the NHS

According to the House of Commons, technology and data can significantly improve the health and care delivery system and hope for new and innovative treatments. Aspects of the NHS Long-term plans of January 2019 outline an approach to upgrading technology and its use for digital access to services to improve clinical care delivery and the service user population (Powell, 2020).

In addition to implementing security standards for care organisations and local healthcare providers, the UK Government introduced a new strategy for using data beyond individual direct care in May 2018, requiring the service user to opt out with opt-in as default. The office of a National Data Guardian was introduced in April 2019 with powers to publish guidance that provides advice, assistance, and guidelines on how data is used in health and social care in England.

In October 2018, the DHSC published a Technology vision for the future of healthcare provision.

"Our vision for digital, data and technology in health and care. In July 2019, NHSX became operational as a joint unit between NHS England, NHS Improvement and the Department of Health and Social Care" (House of Commons Library, 2020, p.35).

The NICE technology appraisal process evaluates approximately 40% of drugs new to the UK market annually.

Technology appraisals aim to assess evidence of the efficacy of medicines and treatments and the impact of the intervention on mortality and quality of life. While appraisals are not obligatory, they also evaluate cost-effectiveness evidence and incorporate the perspectives of clinicians, patients, and stakeholders as potential change agents. The EA programme programmes are critical to these assessments as they are designed to align the programme objectives of the technologies with the overall strategies of the NHS, including cost.

Technology implementation in the NHS may be complex because of turbulence in the operational environment. According to Kaivo-oja and Lauraeus (2018), turbulence is a critical component of the operational environment in today's market circumstances of organisational foresight. Turbulence is encapsulated by the fashionable management acronym "VUCA" to mean volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity.

2.7.20 The function of the NHS National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE)

NICE is an agency of NHS England that provides evidence-backed, underpinned by its constitution, guidelines on how health, social care and public health should be delivered for quality impact.

The institute sets out recommendations through technology appraisals on the clinical and cost-effectiveness of Technology use in the delivery of patient care (NICE, 2021).

2.7.21 Integrated Care Systems (ICSs) functions

As the King's Fund detailed, the Long-Term Plan proposes alterations to the existing system designs to enhance the cohesion between health and social care services. By 2021, the Sustainability and Transformation Partnerships (STPs) are set to merge into fourteen distinct Care Systems. This reorganisation aims to enhance service provision for their respective local populations, as the King's Fund (2019) stated. The NHS's Integrated Care Systems (ICSs) show financing and accountability links between the NHS and local government—involvement of non-NHS health and care providers in ICS and STP debates (Powell, 2020). The DHSC directs around 70% of NHS money to Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs).

The NHS is working on a long-term plan to improve service planning and delivery. With major health and social care partners, it updates current technology to provide digital NHS access (Powell, 2020). NHS Improvement's role is to provide safe and compassionate treatment while ensuring local health systems are financially viable. Healthcare provider and commissioner performance, care transformation and funding will be combined in NHS England (Powell, 2020).

2.7.22 Sources of Funding and the Related Performance Mandate of NHS England

According to NHS England (2020), the responsibility for funding health services falls within the remit of the health department. In 2019/20, the total budgetary allocation for England was £138 billion, with most of it, £121 billion, transferred to NHS England, the remainder divided across other agencies such as the Care Quality Commission, NHS Improvement and NICE and other related programmes. According to NHS England, the rising cost of new and innovative treatment, and the need to safeguard staff level and patients' access to care, the NHS has experienced significant financial challenges resulting in declining performance in the set target, such as the waiting times' directives for emergency and diagnosis and delayed discharges from hospitals. The impact of an ageing and growing service user population has compounded the adequacy of provision due to funding shortfalls. *"For a number of years, NHS Trusts and Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs) have ended the financial year with an overall deficit"* (Powell, 2020).

2.7.23 Technology funding in the NHS

The NHS is primarily supported by general taxation and National Insurance payments. Since 1951, patients have been obliged to subsidise some services (King's Fund, 2019). Exemptions exist for many patients, including those under 16 and over 60.

King's Fund claims the NHS has the most prolonged and severe financing volatility. As the UK's population ages and illness trends change, the NHS confronts financing issues.

The NHS budgeting process is political and pushes governments to balance health and other public expenditures. This ability to manage expenditure has both benefits and drawbacks. Underfunding

issues are widespread in tax-funded systems (McKee & Stuckler, 2018; Dixon & Mays, 2018; Appleby, Galea & Murray, 2014; Savedoff, 2004). Capital budgets are under strain to fund technology. Several obstruct the use of technology in the NHS. They include the NHS's strategic and technical knowledge and funding capacity in each area. Historically, new technology has cost money. The NHS estate requires substantial cash. However, technology-related costs like licence fees are rising (Wenzel & Evans, 2019).

Technology is financed internally and externally. Specific policy or technological efforts can also be funded (Wenzel & Evans, 2019). They claim that from 2015 to 2016, GPs seeking technology funding might apply to NHS England's Technology Transformation Fund (for both capital and income). The Global Digital Exemplar programme awarded 12 acute trusts up to £10 million in capital and income matching in 2016. Four other NHS Trusts were invited in 2018 (Wenzel & Evans, 2019).

It suggested £10 billion for NHS estates investment in 2017: £5 billion for backlog maintenance and £5 billion to help STPs achieve Forward View goals (Naylor, 2017). The NHS has faced financing shortfalls. Transfers from Capital to revenue budgets have lowered capital investment from £5.8 billion in 2010/11 to a projection of £5.3 billion in 2019/20 (Kraindler et al., 2018).

Kraindler et al. estimate that NHS backlog maintenance will cost £6 billion, with £300 million at risk. The NHS CSR promised £1 billion for new technology over five years in 2014. 2016 the government pledged £1.8 billion toward a paperless NHS (Illman, 2016). Despite the UK government's pledges, this funding has been inconsistent and opaque. The capital component was questioned (Heather, 2018). The existing capital budget does not fulfil the DHSC's Future technology plan, say Kraindler et al. So how much of this is new money, and how will it be invested? (Honeyman et al., 2016).

A 3.4% annual increase in real-term finance from 2019/2020 to 2023/2024 was announced in 2018, but no commitment to capital spending. The NHS Long-Term Plan states that new CT and MRI scanners will be funded in 2019. (NHS England 2019a).

Funding dispersion poses a challenge to providers. Financial uncertainty may hinder investment in the NHS, according to Wenzel and Evans (2019). Transparency and finance have also been criticised in the capital regime. In 2017, money identified by stakeholders went wasted (Carding, 2019). The Local Health and Care Record Exemplar, Technology Transformation Fund, and Global Digital Exemplar Program all fund technology (Wenzel & Evans, 2019).

Rarely has estate and technology funding been combined. Both sectors benefit from the Estates and Technology Transformation Fund. However, technological and real estate investment priorities differ (McDermott et al., 2018). NHS estate planning, technology policy, and investment are generally generated in silos, according to McKenna et al. (2017). Taking an integrated approach to planning and finance may become increasingly difficult when funding for technology ventures shifts from financial capital to revenue.

2.8 Critical Realism

Realism is a philosophy that explains a social action in which social structure and agency play a role (Mingers & Standing, 2017; Archer, 2013b; Bhaskar, 1975). Critical realism acknowledges the presence of autonomous structures that impact the conduct of actors in a specific environment while admitting the significance of these actors' subjective knowledge (Sobh & Perry, 2006).

Throughout this research, *“realism is a methodological orientation, or a broad logic of inquiry that is grounded in the philosophy of science and social science”* (Wong et al., 2013b, p.5).

According to McEvoy and Richards, the interaction (relations) between these social structures, mechanisms, and human agencies creates outcomes or effects (McEvoy & Richards, 2003; Byrne, 2013; Fletcher, 2017; Mingers & Standing, 2017).

In critical realist theory, the world is 'layered' into different domains of reality. In a closed experimental setting, a directly observable pattern of behaviour (the empirical domain) can be explained by investigating linear causal relationships between variables (the actual domain) (Jagosh, 2020b; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Roberts, 2014).

Researchers may also be interested in discovering how a causal power produces this pattern of behaviour or causal mechanism that is not immediately apparent at the level of appearances and can only be investigated thoroughly in open systems (the 'real' domain) (Bhaskar, 1975, p.13; Easton, 2010; Elder-Vass, 2012; Mingers & Standing, 2017).

Exploration of causality is qualitative, as we study causal mechanisms within the social context through real, dynamic scenarios. These processes often interact in ways that depend on frequency and are unpredictable. Critical realists believe in knowledge's fallibility since the world's complexity suggests our understanding of it may be inaccurate or misleading. Thus, social scientists seek information regarding causal processes in various study scenarios (Benton & Craib, 2001, p.120).

"And it is fallibilism that ensures "responsible rationality" in research" (Roberts, 2014, p.2).

Roberts argues that critical realism is appropriate for developing a qualitative theory of causality.

To understand how people assess their lives via their beliefs and meanings, qualitative researchers believe that social scientists must understand the human behaviours and meanings that individuals and groups assign to their everyday lives, objects, and social interactions. Quantitative approaches may undoubtedly make similar assertions, but they typically push social scientists to make broad generalisations based on dubious and constrained causal hypotheses.

Qualitative interviews can be considered a purposeful discourse (Yin, 2018). Thus, an 'emic' (insider) perspective on society enables the qualitative researcher to elicit detailed contextual information on a case study and the symbolic behaviours, meaningful beliefs, and everyday emotions that pervade everyday encounters (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Geertz, 1993; Morse, 2015; Patton, 2023; Liamputtong, 2016). For example, qualitative interview techniques allow respondents to speak openly about emotionally charged subjects to understand how people feel and reason about a research issue. Thus, they can delve deeper into specific everyday situations than standardised quantitative interviews (Oppenheim, 1992; Silverman, 1989). Thus, qualitative methods are perhaps more attuned to

everyday society's messiness and 'openness', which inevitably alter respondents' outlooks in their daily lives (Alvesson, 2002; Tracy, 2010; Denzin & Lincoln, 2011; Flick, 2018).

2.8.1 Mechanisms in Critical Realist Evaluation

Chen and Rossi were among the pioneering evaluators to introduce the term “mechanism” in theory-driven evaluation to explain the causal mechanisms that theoretically arbitrate between programme activities and their outcomes (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010), arguing that ‘*the theory-driven approach avoids the pitfalls of black-box evaluation and provides a better understanding of the causal mechanisms underlying the relationship between treatment and effects*’ (Chen & Rossi, 1989, p. 102). Throughout this thesis, mechanisms refer to the realist philosophical understanding of mechanisms. They are usually hidden/unobservable, have generative causal properties and create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Mediating or moderating causal mechanisms may underlie programmes. The former is a program component that intervenes in the relationship between two other elements, and the latter is the relationship between programme components that are enabled or conditioned by a third feature.

According to Bhaskar, the critical realism-classified stratified reality is mediated by 'non-identity.' Causal powers develop from other causal powers. However, they retain a high degree of autonomy, i.e., they share a non-identity with the powers from whence they emerged (Bhaskar 1994). Bhaskar elaborates on his argument by asserting that non-identity is a state of 'absence.' Causal powers, even if we cannot directly observe a mechanism in action, is still ontological object that may affect us. Scientists create discoveries by understanding causal mechanisms about which they were unaware or had little information, i.e., by gaining knowledge about what was previously 'absences' (Morais, 2011). Indeed, since the universe is intricately interwoven and tiered, some form of absence will always affect us.

Furthermore, they erase faults in scientific comprehension by 'absenting' this omission from their knowledge (Bhaskar 1993, p.14-28). Bhaskar uses the term 'diffraction' to characterise and

contextualise these processes. Thus, mechanisms aid in describing what causes non-random patterns between objects and explain why (Hedstrom & Swedberg, 1998; Mayntz, 2004).

Pawson and Tilley (1997) used the concept of mechanisms distinctly as an approach to program theory based on the principles of causal explanation put forward by early researchers affiliated with the realist philosophy of science, such as Roy Bhaskar's realist theory of science issued in 1975.

One of the main implications of Pawson and Tilley's realism assessment viewpoint is that it is not enough to adduce programmes as a cause of results; the processes linking causes and their effects must be recognised. Programs only function or provide positive results when they present relevant ideas, opportunities, or processes to stakeholders in the circumstances or settings.

According to Weiss (1997), mechanisms differ from 'implementation theory' or 'logic model'. Realism deals with the mechanisms that intervene between the delivery of programme services and the incidence of outcomes of interest. Mechanisms rely on participants' responses to programme activities. *"Regardless of methodological or disciplinary traditions, most scholars who write about mechanisms offer a conceptualization that has been influenced to some extent by realist accounts of causation"* (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010, p.368). Astbury and Leeuw describe the realist philosophy characterisation of mechanisms as often hidden, sensitive to context variations, and generating outcomes.

2.8.2 Some Criticisms and Rival Theories of Critical Realism

while critical realism is vital for avoiding some of the difficulties associated with simply using a quantitative theory of causation in social research, it has encountered several objections from individuals sympathetic to its objectives. (Carchedi, 2005; Elder-Vass, D. (2010; Lawson, 2012; Fleetwood, 2014) argue that critical realism takes a dualist view, in which causal processes relate to 'closed' systems while actual concrete occurrences occur in 'open' systems. From this perspective, closed and open systems appear parallel but ultimately distinct, making it difficult to appreciate how they interact. Bhaskar (2009), Elder-Vass (2010), Archer (2013a) and Fleetwood (2014) argue against

the distinctness of open and closed systems. The authors assert that causal mechanisms must be contextualised within a dialectically related whole, encompassing historical processes and specific experiences. In other words, rather than understanding structure and history as separate entities that interact via 'process,' structures and history are dialectically intertwined. Bhaskar outlines three opportunities for further theoretical growth in his prior work on critical realism: 'absence', 'contradiction', and 'completeness'. These three incidents are linked to Bhaskar's eventual attempt to define and grasp how structures are 'diffractions' of the same historical system, which he refers to as a 'totality'. Bhaskar recognises that earlier forms of critical realism require a dialectical supplement to acquire and develop the necessary theoretical tools for comprehending and explaining certain aspects of historical totalities.

Sayer (2000, p.165-168) argues that critical realism has not always effectively established a normative framework considering ordinary life's complexity. Abstract normative pronouncements made by some critical realists frequently fail to grasp the complex character of the conflicts at work in people's lives under these circumstances (Nicola et al., 2020; Cowling et al., 2020; Haleem, Javaid & Vaishya, 2020). For instance, in the Covid-19 Pandemic, people's priorities may frequently be complicated and contentious. They face daily challenges when confronted with concerns during empirical occurrences (Nicola et al., 2020; Chatterjee & Bhanja, 2020; Cowling et al., 2020; Haleem et al., 2020). When people consider such issues, they begin to reason through generally held beliefs and sift through the many justifications for making decisions in response to the challenges (Billig et al., 1988).

Therefore, qualitative researchers should seek to elucidate the conflicting causal forces at work in a particular context and how these contradictory causal powers are governed, or not regulated, by the setting's many structural and strategic relationships. In other words, refracted concrete research settings serve as a conduit for organising people's daily social experiences by conflicting social interactions and regulating systems (Bakhtin & Medvedev, 1978; Nicolini, Mengis & Swan, 2012; Minniti & Van Audenhove, 2017; Langley, 2018).

A typical rebuttal to critical realism is that critical realists must first depend on their prior understanding of the social system in issue to describe it. According to critical realists' theory, it is required to establish hypotheses about hypothetical structures that might account for the interaction of observable components of a concrete event in an open system. These hypotheses are derived from previously held knowledge about structures. Kemp and Holmwood argue *that "an occurrence must be interpreted in terms of current knowledge about structures, their causal effect, and the conditions under which they operate"* (Kemp & Holmwood, 2003, p.169). An open world will have several causal processes interacting, resulting in multiple structural explanations for the same social phenomena. Kemp and Holmwood find this problematic because it implies that critical realists rely on a priori knowledge about how structures work in an open system. Furthermore, critical realists' frequent argument that the social world is 'open' suggests that several researchers can employ a realism technique while producing opposing causal interpretations of the same social occurrence.

To some degree, dialectical critical realists agree with Kemp and Holmwood's argument that critical realists work with pre-existing structural knowledge. However, dialectical critical realists argue that this only pertains to prior knowledge about the determinants of a historical totality, not information about a specific collection of concrete structures and causal processes operating in a specific social context (Robbers, 2010; Nicolini, Mengis & Swan, 2012; Minniti & Van Audenhove, 2017; Langley, 2018).

2.9 The Social Reality of EA Programmes, Social Causation, and Social Change

Misunderstanding regarding the nature of change inherent in 'EA' programme initiatives stems from oversimplifying how they are constituted. Social programmes are embedded in social systems, involving actors, organisations, agencies, structures, and social processes (Pawson & Tilley, 2008). EA initiatives are not different since they are intended to deliver organisations' vision, strategy, and objectives for which human agency is embedded.

This research aims to explain the social-technical impact on programme outcomes, an area that Hope (2015) identified as insufficient depth within the EA implementations.

Pawson and Tilley (2008) identified five characteristics for explaining programmes embedded in social systems: ‘embeddedness’, ‘mechanisms’, ‘contexts’, ‘regularities’ and ‘change’. In Archer’s morphogenic approach to social change, Archer (1995) supports this view. Archer contends that a proactive approach to social activities precipitates transformation. Consequently, the impact of social activities on Enterprise Architecture (EA) in social programmes, including healthcare, should not be overlooked due to the pivotal role of inherent programme social mechanisms in shaping programme outcomes. However, our understanding of EA mechanisms is limited and needs further research (Ahlemann, Legner & Lux, 2020; Goethals, 2005).

The notion of EA as change agents for strategic alignment of organisational strategy have been discussed in the strategic alignment model proposed by Henderson and Venkatraman (1993, 1999). This research does not seek to preclude the preponderance of natural mechanisms of a technical nature in EA programmes. Social mechanisms, which have received little attention in research (Hope, 2015) in determining outcomes, help promote better and wholistic understanding by explanatory and generative causal powers of social mechanisms following the realist philosophy holistic view.

2.9.1 The Embeddedness of social reality in EA Programmes

According to realist philosophy, all human action occurs within social processes, the “*stratified nature of social reality*” (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.64). Human action is understood within a location of various layers of social reality. Causal powers are embedded in organisational structures and social relations of individuals and objects (Archer, 2015; Bhaskar, 2016; Sayer, 2011; Cruickshank & Sassower, 2017; Danermark et al., 2019; Elder-Vass, 2016). Causation is not merely a relationship between cause and effect or discrete events but a cascading regularity of events (Archer, 2015; Bhaskar, 2016; Sayer, 2011; Cruickshank & Sassower, 2017; Danermark et al., 2019; Elder-Vass, 2016). Based on regular events, EA programmes can be argued to activate a complex sequence of

activities and events to produce EA outcomes. Therefore, an action within the EA programme has a cascading effect on the social system within which the programme exists because of the embeddedness of the action. This realist principle underpins the lens through which this research is conducted.

Programs are about people, and so are EA programmes in the context of social action. EA Practitioners have experiences and backgrounds that mediate the nature and success of exchanging ideas that affect the programme outcomes. The reception of these ideas is cultural and social circumstances in which the [EA] programme is embedded (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

According to Pawson and Tilley (1997), all social programmes are embedded in social action, “a program is its personnel, its place, its pas and its prospects” (p.65).

2.9.2 Underlying Mechanisms of EA Programmes

Mechanisms are hidden, have explanatory power within the realist research strategy, and are metaphorically underlying. They explain how things work by delving into the inner workings beyond the limits of observability (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Whereas physical science explanations are based on powers and the potential of molecular action, the laws of nature and social regularities in social science allow for causal powers of social mechanisms. Individual action and social constraints, therefore, affect programme action outcomes. Social mechanisms, therefore, involve choices that people make and the capacities derived from group membership (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Dalkin et al., 2015; Lacouture, 2015; Marchal, Kegels, & Van Belle, 2018; Emmel et al., 2018).

Structure and agency are applied across social explanations; therefore, similar explanations can be employed in dialectical reasoning and the available collective resources. The TOGAF mechanisms, which are Socio-Technological but with greater detail on the technical development of EA programmes, have already been discussed in chapter two. Mechanisms are embedded in programmes within the stratified nature of social reality regarding the propositional constituent of micro and micro-processes. Mechanisms also demonstrate how programmes are derived from reasoning and

resource availability. However, the exploration of mechanisms in EA programmes remains to be explored. According to Zhang, Chen, and Luo (2018), the set of governance mechanisms in business-IT alignment, for instance, the rationale for EA programmes, has not been explored and calls for sustainable governance mechanisms to be embedded in the evolutionary process of EA.

Gong and Janssen (2019) argue that mechanisms that result in value are often not mentioned and propose that further research is required.

Decomposing EA processes and their related activities into value-creation mechanisms can help manage EA complexity. According to realist philosophy, programmes always work as a weaving of processes that binds reasoning and resources together (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Pawson et al., 2005; Westhorp, 2014; Mukumbang et al., 2016a; Wong et al., 2016; Dalkin et al., 2019). For instance, in EA programmes teams, communication between IT and business departments has been identified as essential in promoting success (Alaeddini, Asgari, Gharibi, & Rashidi Rad, 2017). According to Pawson and Tilley (1997), this social mechanism could impact people's reasoning by promoting mutual trust.

“Identifying mechanisms involves the attempt to develop propositions about what it is within the program which triggers a reaction from its subjects” (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.66).

Social mechanisms and mechanisms used in natural science explanations are distinct; invoking different layers of reality in social explanation has implications on how causation is perceived. Social mechanisms explain the regularity as located at different levels of reality, implying a distinct and generative idea of reality. A generative mechanism is not the association of variables and how they correlate but how they are formed. The generative mechanisms in themselves form a regularity.

A mechanism is a theory with the potential for human reasoning and resources (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

“A mechanism is thus not a variable but an account of the make-up, behaviour and interrelationships of those processes which are responsible for the regularity” (p.68).

2.9.3 Context Dependency of EA Programme Mechanisms

According to social realist theory, context is an irreducible set of factors that impact when and how an intervention is provided and how mechanisms are engaged. Thus, understanding the contextual variables that permit or obstruct processes is crucial for realism appraisal (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Pawson et al., 2005; Westhorp, 2014; Mukumbang et al., 2016a; Wong et al., 2016; Dalkin et al., 2019).

Pawson and Tilley (2004) describe contextual variables as follows:

- Individual capacities of influential actors and stakeholders, such as interests, attitudes, knowledge, and skills
- The lines of communication, management, administrative assistance, professional relationships, and contracts are all necessary to support the intervention.
- The institutional setting in which the programme is implemented, such as the implementing body's culture and norms, leadership, and governance
- The more extensive infrastructure, structural, and welfare systems include political backing, funding availability, and conflicting policy priorities and influences (Pawson & Tilley, 2004, p.7–8).

According to Sayer (1992), Dalkin et al. (2015) and Emmel et al.(2018), the relationship between causal mechanisms and their generated effects is flexible but contingent on context. Contextual conditioning of generative causal mechanisms can turn but sometimes fail, causal potential into a causal outcome. By the notion of contextual contingency, EA programme mechanisms are not fixed. However, they may vary due to contextual conditioning and thus affect the outcome of EA programmes in unpredictable ways.

Social contexts refer to the prior collection of rules, norms, values, and the interconnectedness of institutions, locations and geographies that tend to limit the efficacy of social programmes. All socially-oriented programmes involving the preponderance of social systems (Pawson & Tilley, 1997) necessarily challenge contextual conditions. Such programmes are usually embedded in pre-existing social contexts and become essential determinants in explaining their outcomes, failure, or success. However, these contexts are anonymous in experimental evaluations.

“We have no hesitation in pointing to this lack of attention to the social conditions which pre-exist and endure through programs as one of the great omissions of evaluation research” (p.70).

Programmes work through the cross-pollination of ideas, resources, and reasoning into a set of social relationships of experts, decision-makers and feedback from user needs of the services the programmes are designed to support.

The extent to which pre-existing institutional and cultural structures enable or disable programmes to trigger change mechanisms in the context of action should, therefore a critical concern for investigative evaluation of how programmes work (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh, 2020b; de Souza, 2013). In her morphogenic approach to social systems, Archer (1995) supports such a notion. In social action, mechanisms function as catalysts that mediate and modify pre-established conditions. This interaction precipitates two potential outcomes: either a perpetuation of the initial state through an invariant transformation, thus leading to a reproductive cycle or an alteration that ushers in a variant transformation. Indeed, the purpose of EA is to create a target Architecture outcome aligned with the organisational objectives in transforming the current architecture state of the organisation’s technology (Saint-Louis & Lapalme, 2018; & The Open Group, 2018).

2.9.4 Demi-Regularities in EA Programmes

According to Pawson and Tilley (1997), most explanatory paradigms aim to establish regularity. Regularity is the summation of mechanisms and context; regularity = mechanisms + contexts. These

regularities form outcomes, patterns, rates of change, and associations in and within mechanisms and their related contexts in social programmes. Demi-regularities are often used to indicate the fact that human choice or agency appears in a semi-predictable way because variances in patterns of behaviour may be traced in part to contextual differences from one set to the next (Wong et al., 2013; Jagosh et al., 2012).

For instance, Banaeianjahromi and Smolander (2019, p.877) argue that the lack of communication and collaboration is one of the challenges facing practitioners in developing EA programmes. Their finding showed that in the context of governance of EA programmes, social communication and collaboration mechanisms hinder personnel distrust, stifle innovation, and prevent a shared understanding, leading to ineffective outcomes. **Figure 2.3** below illustrates how regularity might be present in the context of EA mechanisms to create outcomes. The Causal factors are the vision and strategy, objectives and goals of the organisation, and trigger mechanisms within the EA programmes to generate outcomes in the form of business capabilities. The mechanisms are elicited within the TOGAF ADM but may include other mechanisms within the programme outside of the framework. Outcomes may be relinquishing of value and thus constitute failure or enduring of benefits constituting successful alignment with the intended goals of the organisation. **Figure 2.3** shows the CMO configuration conceptual framework, a continuation between explanation in social science and natural science, and emphasises the need to combine the three elements of the realist paradigm of the causal powers of triggered mechanisms in context to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

The framework disables extraneous mechanisms. It acknowledges that other circumstances external to the programme may impact its mechanisms (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Triggered mechanisms occur within the programme's circumstances, culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure to create regular outcomes. The outcomes result from the Programme activities that create business capabilities (The Open Group, 2018). When these capabilities are aligned with the organisation's

objectives and goals, the associated mechanisms are success factors. Conversely, misaligned outcomes are a result of failure mechanisms.

Figure 2.3. The regularity of context mechanisms in EA programmes is abstracted from Bhaskar (2009; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; The Open Group, 2018; de Souza, 2013).

2.9.5 EA Programmes as Social Change Agent

EA initiatives in social programmes occur through the act of people. Stakeholder decision and policy governs the implementation. Regularity is distinct in realist physical explanation and realist social explanation. Realist social explanations have a morphogenic character, according to Archer (1995). Bhaskar (1979) supports this argument and describes this as an ‘open system’. In open systems, programme social order is sustained by the balance of mechanisms, contexts, and regularities. These attributes are susceptible to infinite and self-generated reconfiguration. In the empirical scientific explanation of social programmes, people exist as external and peripheral to experimentalists. In the realist social explanation, people are central to the effects of mechanisms, contexts, and regularities through conditions they have no control over. In social systems, people are aware of choices, prioritising activities, patterns and regularities, and their social forces limiting their opportunities but

lack control of how this shapes their lives (Pawson & Tilley, 2007; Wong et al., 2013b; Jagosh et al., 2015; Salter & Kothari, 2014; Mukumbang et al., 2018a).

This awareness catalyses change, not because the change is necessarily desired. Programmes may not have the resources to effect the change, or their effort may be constrained by other influences that are overbearing. Because of imperfect knowledge of contextual conditions, limiting peoples’ actions, unpredictability is created. Moreover, the initiated change mechanism may produce unanticipated ramifications. The causal pathway remains unforeseen as social regularities have self-transforming properties.

Figure 2.4 is an illustrative realist model of how EA in Social Systems may be transformed. It depicts a confluence of arguments and frameworks from the industry and practice of EA. (Archer, 1995; Bhaskar, 2009; Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; The Open Group, 2018, Zachman, 1987).

Figure 2.4 Illustrative Realist Model of EA Transformation in Social Programmes.

The realist model of EA transformation in social programmes in Figure 2.4 can be illustrated through an example of healthcare change in the United Kingdom and others worldwide because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Before the Coronavirus COVID-19 pandemic, in digital healthcare technology, “clinical workflows and economic incentives have been developed for a face-to-face

model of care which, during this pandemic, contributes to the spread of the virus to uninfected patients who are seeking medical care” (Golinelli et al., 2020, p.13).

The legal framework and ICT infrastructure and payment structure for telemedicine, a technology that has become essential for healthcare, were inadequate for the covid-19 pandemic conditions (Golinelli et al., 2020, p.13). Pre-pandemic Socio-Technological transformation (T1) regularities of the healthcare institutions have changed significantly compared with transformative social systems post-pandemic (T2).

Comparing the organisational objectives of healthcare organisations in meeting patient needs R1 pre-pandemic and R2 post-pandemic, significant changes occur in how digital technologies are designed and used. Diagnostic artificial intelligence tools, big data analytics and contact tracing for surveillance and prevention, and telehealth have not only emerged as innovative technologies. However, they have become essential requirements for the post-pandemic social system, T2 (Golinelli et al., 2020). In post-pandemic transformative social systems in the healthcare ecosystem, technologies proven to be implementable, scalable, and agile are more aligned with the T2.

For instance, at T1, more resources are directed at a face-to-face model of healthcare institutions (M1). At T2, more resources are directed at legal frameworks and technology alignments that support the telehealth system (M1). The social systems at T1 may even be detrimental to T2, as in the case of this illustration, where the mechanism M1 face-face workflows in T1 contribute to the spread of the coronavirus on the uninfected patient seeking medical intervention.

*“The prevailing social and cultural contexts may also be said to have shifted markedly”
(Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.73).*

Thus, before the Covid-19 pandemic, healthcare organisations' resources, skills, and reasoning were directed toward face-to-face healthcare delivery in C1. The organisation's culture was building relationships with patients and improving employee face-to-face behaviour and attitudes. In C2, during the coronavirus pandemic, more resources, skills, and reasoning are directed towards patient

confidentiality, data protection against cyberattacks, and a workforce more prepared to exploit AI diagnostic tools.

Realist evaluation is about change involving social programming that starts with identifying regularities (R1) suspected to represent a problem requiring strategic alignment that fits into the scope of EA. The EA transformation then shifts the pattern of behaviour to cause a transformation of the organisation's EA to a more acceptable level (R2).

In Social systems, programs and policymaking involve people (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Digital transformation of health care where EA activities are embedded is quintessentially about change].

Outcomes or outcome patterns constitute the explanatory objective of realist evaluation research. A mechanism-context-outcome configuration in EA development results from the change in rate (R1-R2) over a given time. R1 is analogous to the Current state Architecture, and R2, the Target state architecture, is used in the Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF).

The set of mechanisms, M1, sustains the problem of the current state that the programmes intend to change. The most crucial explanatory resource is to assess the potential for change of the programme mechanisms (M2), transforming the current state architecture into a future state architecture, T2.

2.9.6 How Realist Evaluation of EAs Cumulate to Create Aligned Outcomes

EA initiatives implemented via The Open Group Architecture framework ADM cumulate via a series of iterative steps as shown in section 2.11 and figure 2-7 section 2.10.2 as iterations. Such iteration is transitional architecture intended to continually align the organisation's EA vision with the target state Architecture (The Open Group, 2018).

In social systems, using the realist approach to evaluate EA programmes, such iteration can be achieved through iterations that may be achieved through an iterative review of regularities, mechanisms, context, and outcomes until alignment is achieved. However, Pawson and Tilley (1997) argue that evaluation studies usually appear as one-offs. Evaluation is neither retrospective nor forwards looking to future evaluations. Target EA must remain a work in progress as a continual

iterative process building on previous and future findings of EAs of the organisation to achieve the desired alignment of the outcome of the organisation's strategic objective.

They further argue that evaluating social programmes must be cumulation oriented to improve policy, strategy, and practice. Accordingly, EA implementations must cumulate through iteration of regularity, mechanism, context, and outcome configurations to achieve the expected outcome.

Delivering valuable insight into social programmes determines their ineffective value policy and program design. Despite the meticulous design and execution of research programmes, deriving dependable knowledge remains elusive due to the inherent unpredictability and the vast diversity embedded within social phenomena. The multiplicity of facets in social life introduces an element of variability that invariably complicates our efforts to comprehend these phenomena reliably. The causal process of mechanisms and context in programmes is time and place-sensitive with no order of significance. An EA programme that works in one organisation under certain conditions may be less effective under different organisations with different circumstances. The ability to accumulate best practices across several domains of social systems to inform programmes becomes crucial (Cook et al., 1993).

“The accumulation of results and the gradual convergence on [the] information of high quality is one hallmark of progress in any science, but it is particularly key in social science, where there may be no single, uniform answers to a given question, but rather a family of answers, related by principles that emerge only over the course of much research. Traditionally, this process of distilling reliable generalisations from the history of research on a given problem has been considered something of an art” (p.VII).

Thus, EA programmes in social systems must accumulate to deliver effective and sustained value.

2.10 The Open Group Architectural Framework (TOGAF)

Figure 2.5. Shows The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) Capability. (The Open Group, 2018).

The TOGAF standard is a conceptual framework for EA developed by the Open Group in 1995 through industry collaboration (TOGAF, 2018). The Open Group founded TOGAF in 1995, and by 2016, it was used by 80 per cent of Global fifty companies and 60 per cent of Fortune 500 companies. TOGAF is free to use internally by institutions but not for commercial purposes (The Open Group, 2018).

The research focuses on the mechanisms of TOGAF contained in Part 2 in **Figure 2.5** of the capability standard. Part II of the TOGAF framework describes the method for developing Enterprise Architecture (The Open Group, 2018). TOGAF is an IT tool used to "design, evaluate, and build the right architecture for [an] organisation. It helps to 'demystify' the architecture development process, enabling IT users to build genuinely open systems-based solutions to their business needs" (The Open Group, 2001). Urbaczewski and Mrdalj (2006) noted that TOGAF uses open systems building blocks

to specify their EA development mechanisms. These building blocks are called the Architecture Development Method (ADM). Alaeddini et al. (2017) argue that TOGAF is widely used for *"enabling the true perspective on IT capabilities that business units need for identification, planning, execution and management of the right project interventions or requirements to maximise the benefits for the enterprise"* (p.75).

TOGAF was founded in 1995 and has become the most widely used EA framework (TOGAF, 2018; Goepf & Petit, 2017). It illustrates the increasing interest and influence of the TOGAF in determining alignment between organisational objectives and strategies and IT. The Open Group reported that, as of the 21st of April 2020, the 10,1787 TOGAF architects registered in their database had been certified as TOGAF-certified practitioners on the TOGAF framework across 149 countries (TOGAF, 2018). Table 2.1 summarises the total number of TOGAF 9.2 accredited individuals. Urbaczewski and Mrdalj (2006) also describe (TOGAF) as "one of the most comprehensive [frameworks] with regards to the actual process involved" (p. 21). Unlike the other EA frameworks, TOGAF "explains rules for developing good principles, rather than providing a set of architecture principles" (Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006, p.19). It supports stakeholders' decision-making, guides IT resources, and helps design and evaluate EA development and implementation. See Table 2.1. Table 2.1 Summary of Certified Individuals: TOGAF 9 Certification. Source: The Open Group (2018).

Table 2.1. Certified TOGAF Practitioners up to 2018

Conformance Requirements	Total Certified up to 2018
TOGAF 9 Foundation	30081
TOGAF 9 Certified	71706
Total of all TOGAF 9 Certifications	101787

The popularity and influence of TOGAF in the practice of EA are pervasive. Several researchers have confirmed the pervasiveness of TOGAF both in practice and research.

"Several dedicated frameworks have been created, such as the Zachman Framework (Zachman, 1987) in the earlier stage and The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF), which has gathered the most attention for its contributions" (Guo, Li, & Gao, 2019, p. 2). "It is today a widely accepted open standard for modelling EA, with a large user base and a variety of modelling tools that support it" (Mayer, Grandry, Feltus, Goettelmann, & Wieringa, 2019, p. 2287).

"TOGAF, a standard established and maintained by The Open Group providing a detailed method and a set of supporting tools for developing an EA. The TOGAF Content Metamodel and its associated glossary are the references used for the conceptual alignment" (Mayer et al., 2019, p. 2289).

"TOGAF is the best for developing an Integrated Health Information System compared to Zachman because of the lack of step-by-step processes and more taxonomy. On the other hand, TOGAF provides verified methods, shared vocabulary to understand the information in organizations, knowledge of organizations to enable managers or systems to make better decisions and improve data sharing, improve the reliability of solutions and easier maintenance" (Pasaribu, Hakiki, Situmorang, Sfenrianto, & Kaburuan, 2019, p.864).

The first version of the TOGAF standard (version 1) was developed in 1995 and *"was based on the Technical Architecture Framework for Information Management (TAFIM), developed by the US Department of Défense (DoD)" (TOGAF, 2018, introduction.)*. The primary purpose of developing TOGAF was *"to support the technology architecture" (Jin et al., 2010, p.294)*. Since then, a succession of TOGAF standards has been developed and published into a complete framework and methodology, with the latest version being version 9.2. Version 9.2 of the TOGAF standard is structured in six parts: the introduction, Architecture Development Method (ADM), Guidelines and Techniques, Architecture Content Framework, Enterprise Continuum and Tools, and Architecture

Capability Framework. This standard reflects the structure and content within an enterprise" (TOGAF, 2018). **Table 2.2** briefly describes the six parts of the TOGAF version 9.2 standard document.

Table 2.2 Structure of the TOGAF Framework. Source: (The Open Group, 2018).

Part	Name	Description
I	Introduction	Part I provides a high-level introduction to the key ideas of EA, focusing on the TOGAF method of architecting. It includes the definitions of terminology found in this standard.
II	Architecture Development Method (ADM)	This section represents the foundation of the TOGAF architecture. It outlines a step-by-step procedure for creating an EA.
III	ADM Guidelines and Techniques	This section includes a set of guidelines and approaches for implementing the TOGAF methodology and the TOGAF ADM. The TOGAF Library contains additional policies and techniques.
IV	Architecture Content Framework	This section presents the TOGAF content framework, which includes a structured metamodel for architectural artefacts, reusable Architecture Building Blocks, and an overview of common architecture outputs.
V	Enterprise Continuum and Tools	Part V describes the taxonomies and tools necessary for categorising and storing the outputs of architectural work inside an organisation.
VI	Architecture Capability Framework	This section addresses the organisation, procedures, skills, roles, and responsibilities necessary to build and run an organisation's architectural function.

This review focuses on "Part II", the Architecture Development Method (ADM) of the TOGAF standards. The reason is that ADM is the only part that describes the approach to developing and implementing EA. Therefore, ADM forms the basis for this review and the entire study.

2.11 Implementing EA under complexity

EA programmes are complex and longitudinal (Makiya & Lyytinen, 2011; Braun et al., 2005; Haki & Legner, 2021). The limitation of data to analyse EA management mechanisms in longitudinal studies is a reality. Data is often based on hindsight, which may not model the future state significantly because of transient conditions of context mechanisms interactions and bias in collecting the related data (Lyytinen & Newman, 2008; Saldaña & Omasta, 2016). Complex programmes' emergent and dynamic behaviour create foresight fuzziness (Haki, Aier & Winter, 2016).

Unforeseen effects of longitudinal programmes remain unobserved and erroneously attributed to the programmes. Unforeseen context effects create context insensitivity, which may lead to the unreliable explanation of EA outcomes and conclusions about the cause of such outcomes, albeit positive or negative. Attributing the organisation's resources to observable outcomes in longitudinal programmes is difficult, leading to the inaccuracy of attribution and rendering decision-making weak (Jagosh, 2018). In a longitudinal study of the impact of outer dynamics and the assimilation of digital transformation, Wang (2008), Ostrom et al. (2015), and Hanelt et al.(2019) argue that a multiplicity of causal factors are gained significantly over a time horizon of the implementation.

2.12 Mechanisms of EA Programmes

The research focuses on the impact of the mechanism of EA in determining the outcomes in the context of programme outcomes, a gap identified in the extant literature. Chen and Chen (2005) argue that there are two types of Mechanisms; A mediating causal mechanism that intervenes in the relationship between two other components of a programme and moderating mechanism, a relationship between program components based on the influence of a third factor.

EA approaches, and mechanisms are multifaceted but are primarily organised around EA frameworks to improve the practice and align technology and organisational goals (Saint-Louis & Lapalme, 2018; Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999). The lack of consensus and a unified understanding (Simon, Fischbach & Schoder, 2013) creates several ways to achieve Alignment. The centre of which is context and the associated mechanism for achieving such Alignment (Lapalme, 2012).

"The lack of common understanding in EA can create misunderstandings and conflicts regarding the role and responsibility of professionals practising EA" (Saint-Louis & Lapalme, 2018, p.17).

Various perspectives, therefore, have taken hold to address the fragmented viewpoints (Saint-Louis & Lapalme, 2018) of the concept of EA.

"Mechanisms are underlying entities, processes, or structures which operate in particular contexts to generate outcomes of interest." (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010, p368). Mechanisms in the realist paradigm are broken-down into resources and reasoning and are mutually constitutive. Such disaggregation is important in operationalising mechanisms as a separate concept from context (Dalkin et al., 2015). Accordingly, An EA mechanism is the underlying resources, processes or structures and reasoning, emotional and cognitive, which operate contexts of the EA programme to generate outcomes of interest to align business objectives and information technology.

Mechanisms are fundamental to EA value, yet there has been a poor understanding of their impact on programmes. There is also inattention to how these EA mechanisms create value for the organisation. Gong and Janssen (2019) argue that EA is a complex process requiring that the related creation activities be broken down into 'value-creation mechanisms. *"The significant practitioner interest in EA and a poor understanding of the EA value-creation mechanism were the drivers of this study into the value of and myths about EA" (p.1). "Although the value is often described in the literature, the mechanisms that result in the creation of value are often not mentioned" (p.4).*

According to Zhang, Chen, and Luo (2018), EA mechanisms have explored *"dynamic EA governance" (p.18936)* to maintain business and information technology alignment. Zhang et al.

further argue that these governance-related mechanisms have not been explored thoroughly, stating that EA governance mechanisms should be an integral part of the EA evolutionary process.

Schilling, Haki and Aier (2018) have also argued that mechanisms are essential in EA portfolio control, the dyadic process of regulating and fine-tuning the behaviour of EA implementers. They argue that EA portfolio control mechanisms are required for successful outcomes in aligning individual reasoning and reaction to EA resources with organisational objectives.

2.13 Enterprise Architecture Frameworks Overview

Every EA must clearly define its deliverables – in terms of benefits and values – and the mechanisms that produce them (TOGAF, 2018; Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006; Hauder et al., 2012; Simon, Fischbach & Schoder, 2013). Hence, having an appropriate framework or methodology is critical to the success of every EA project. An EA framework is a tool for *"developing a broad range of architectures [and] for capturing, organising, and displaying the needed information in an enterprise"* (Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006, p.19). The EA framework should describe a method for designing an information system *"in terms of a set of building blocks, and for showing how the building blocks fit together"* (TOGAF, 2018, p.300).

Goethals (2005), Buckl, Matthes and Schweda (2010), and Buschle et al.(2012) advised that all TOGAF mechanisms should be defined and understood to work correctly with any EA framework. A well-defined EA framework guides the EA artefacts and determines the quality of the EA. Using an architectural framework will speed up and simplify architecture development, ensure complete coverage of the designed solution, and ensure that the architecture selected enables future growth in response to organisations' requirements, objectives and goals (Winter et al., 2010; TOGAF, 2018; Vargas et al., 2019).

John Zachman EA pioneered EA in 1987, and several other EA frameworks have emerged (Goethals, 2005; Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006). *These EA frameworks differ in scope, mechanism, context, and the issues they address. Some EA frameworks have a "specific application or development methodology and are truly enterprise-oriented, while others are specific to the development of the IT system only"* (Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006, p.19). Hence, it may be challenging to directly compare

all the existing EA frameworks (Goethals, 2005). Nevertheless, the literature has attempted to review and compare the various EA frameworks. For instance, Urbaczewski and Mrdalj (2006) analysed the "views²" and "abstractions" in five EA frameworks. These five frameworks include the Zachman framework, The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF), the Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF), the Federal EA Framework (FEAF) and the Treasury EA Framework (TEAF).

The analysis suggested that Zachman's framework presented a comprehensive framework through which "views" can be represented. Urbaczewski & Mrdalj (2006) argue that the Zachman framework is not designed to guide the sequence, process, or implementation [of EA]; instead, [it] focuses on ensuring that all views are well established and ensures a complete system regardless of the order in which they were established (p. 18).

Various EA peer-reviewed publications apply different EA methodologies to organise EA practice (Bernard, 2005; Spewak & Hill, 1992). According to The Open Group (2018), TOGAF is currently the most popular EA methodology and has been since 2011 (TOGAF, 2018; Cameron & Mcmillan, 2013; Obitz & Babu, 2009)

However, the elementary usage of EA methodologies usually creates significant practical issues (Löhe & Legner, 2014). Moreover, the strict adherence to a recommendation of EA methodologies and frameworks is recognised as one of the worst EA implementation practices (Makadok, Burton, & Barney, 2018).

"Companies typically adapt existing EA methodologies to their specific needs or even use them only as idea contributors " (Kotusev, 2018, p. 322).

On the other hand, TOGAF is said to be designed in a way that it *"explains [the] rules for developing good principles, rather than providing a set of architecture principles"* (Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006, p.18). Urbaczewski & Mrdalj noted that TOGAF is ideal for business and technical architecture and

is the most comprehensive framework for EA implementation as it *"provides guidance towards principles for decision making, the guidance of IT resources, and architecture principles"* (p. 21).

Goethals (2005) classed EA frameworks into two main groups: classic and federated (see **Table 2.3**).

This classification was based on the frameworks' deliverables and scope. The classic EA frameworks were those frameworks that *"mostly implicitly focused on one centralised enterprise"*. [In contrast], *the 'federated EA frameworks focus on "describing enterprises that are linked by a kind of umbrella organisation"* (Goethals, 2005, p. 3).

Table 2.3. Classification of EA frameworks (Goethals, 2005)

Classic EA frameworks	Federated EA frameworks
<p>Zachman framework</p> <p>Kruchten's 4+1 view model of architecture</p> <p>Soni, Nord and Hofmeister framework</p> <p>Tapscott and Caston framework</p> <p>The ISO/IEEE Reference Model of Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP)</p> <p>The Model Driven Architecture (MDA)</p>	<p>The Federal EA Framework (FEAF)</p> <p>C4ISR Architecture Framework</p> <p>Treasury EA Framework</p>

The analysis of these frameworks positioned the Zachman framework as the most coherent. Goethals (2005) argued that the *"soundness of the foundations of other frameworks is unclear"* (p. 17). He argues that many frameworks focus only on "software architecture" instead of the entirety of EA; hence, those who employ the framework in their projects seldomly detail the mechanism. Goethals (2005) compared these frameworks to TOGAF's four-dimensional architecture description. This viewpoint justifies the robustness and comprehensiveness of TOGAF in EA.

Furthermore, Guo et al. (2019) identified TOGAF as the most used EA framework since its inception. They argued that even though the Zachman framework was the first to emerge, *“TOGAF has garnered the most attention for its contributions in EA management”* (Guo et al., p. 39). Although the criteria by which Guo et al. (2019) based their claim was not described, Mayer et al. (2019) noted that TOGAF has a broad *“user base and a variety [of] modelling tools that support it”* (p. 2287). This makes it suitable for EA implementation (Urbaczewski & Mrdalj, 2006). Although it can be argued that the Zachman framework presents a comprehensive framework for identifying viewpoints, it lacks a systematic process for understanding organisational information. Pasaribu et al. (2019) argue that TOGAF is the *“best for developing an Integrated Health Information System [as it] provides verified methods, shared vocabulary to understand the information in organisations, knowledge of organisations to enable managers or systems to make better decisions and improve data sharing, improve the reliability of solutions and easier maintenance”* (p.864).

2.14 The TOGAF Architecture Development Method (ADM)

Information systems are the bedrock of modern organisations, supporting business processes to enable strategic advantage. TOGAF has various components: the Architecture development framework, Architecture Development Method (ADM), Architecture Content Framework, and the Enterprise Continuum. (Goepf & Petit, 2017; Lankhorst, 2005; The Open Group, 2018).

This research focuses on the mechanisms of ADM, the core of TOGAF because it provides a *“way of working”* (Goepf & Petit, 2017, p. 1178) for Architects. The TOGAF ADM mechanisms are the most representative process for alignment (Goepf & Petit, 2017). EA is one such process for enabling organisations to align their business objectives with investment in IT.

The architecture development method (ADM) describes the development and management of the lifecycle of EA interventions. It is the foundation of the TOGAF standard by integrating components and other available architectural assets to meet the organisation's business needs (The Open Group, 2018). EA is about restructuring the organisation to cause alignment with its business strategy. It is

less about IT system implementation actions and more about people, mechanisms, processes, and contexts.

The ADM is the point of conjecture between technology and sociology. Since the ADM contains developmental processes, the research examines the mechanism underpinning such development. Therefore, within these mechanisms, the core impact of context is felt most.

In their finding, Hope et al. (2017) argue for a Socio-Technical essence that the skills of the various actors, such as Architects within the organisational context, enable them to attend to the organisational context that assures the EA intervention towards successful outcomes.

"Methodological skills of architects need to be supplemented with process (or social) skills so that architects might be able to attend to key aspects of the organisational context to assure the success of EA programmes as well as their own success, rather than be the victims of circumstances" (p.25).

Although the ADM's primary emphasis is the creation of enterprise-specific architecture, it is also considered the process of stocking the enterprise's architecture repository with essential reusable 'building blocks' and, over time, adding additional material to the organization's architecture repository (The Open Group, 2018a).

The ADM employs an enterprise's business needs to determine the appropriate definitions and choices in the foundation architecture. The ADM is also viable for populating an organization's foundation architecture. The ADM is supported by a comprehensive collection of guidelines, templates, checklists, and other technical documents (The Open Group, 2018).

Throughout the Architecture Development Method (ADM) cycle, it is vital to validate outcomes against the preliminary assumptions of intervention mechanisms regularly. The initial execution of the ADM is often the most difficult. The required architectural assets must be reused, making future performances more accessible when more architectural assets are identified. They are saved in the organisation's architectural repository and may be reused. The architecture capability, transiting

planning, development, and governance are managed iteratively as the programme unfolds. Figure 2.6 shows the iterative phases of the TOGAF ADM (The Open Group, 2018).

Figure 2.6. shows the ADM Elements, interactions, and its iterations, adapted from The Open Group (2018).

2.14.1 Preliminary Phase (PP)

The preliminary phase (PP) entails doing any required work to launch and adjust the ADM to develop an organizational-specific framework. The general scope and aims of the architectural project determine the preliminary phase's precise scope. The preliminary phase component determines the intended method to separate and provide the framework for implementing the chosen route to architecture (The Open Group, 2018).

It aims to determine and establish the desired architecture capability with architectural and non-architectural inputs, including business and strategies. This phase orders the governance framework components sequence for formal commencement and completion. The PP series includes scoping the enterprise organisations impacted, confirming governance and support frameworks, defining and establishing the EA team and organisation, identifying and establishing architecture principles, and

tailoring TOGAF. Creating a tool strategy and execution plan, and courses of action is the final step if any other selected architecture frameworks are scoped (The Open Group, 2018).

The preliminary phase's outputs include an organisational model for EA, a tailored architecture framework, an initial architecture repository, a restatement of the organisation's principles, goals and objectives, and motivations, an optional request for architecture effort, and an architecture governance framework in the form of a catalogue (The Open Group, 2018).

The ADM's preliminary phase defines the 'where, what, why, who, and how we do architecture' of the organisation concerned. The primary outcomes of the mechanisms include defining the enterprise and identifying key drivers, required architecture work, principles, and framework; considering the connections between management frameworks during the preliminary phase, the EA maturity is assessed.

The preliminary step of ADM establishes the organization's targeted architectural capabilities and its key to establishing these capabilities. This phase's primary inputs include Governance Board strategies and business plans, IT strategy, organisational principles, goals and objectives, and business drivers (Goepp & Petit, 2017).

2.14.2 The Main Building Blocks and Process Specification of the ADM

This section describes the 'Architecture Building Blocks' (ABB) as key to Architecture development using the TOGAF framework approach. The basic units of the ADM are the ABB (The Open Group, 2018). The ABB are the depiction of a model and associated specification, their connectedness, and how they align to fulfil the information systems requirements of the organisation. The ABB is a specification of services the organisation needs for specific systems. The organisation determines the system boundaries (The Open Group, 2018).

The TOGAF Framework employs specific usage design principles of architectures for the ABB. Firstly, the EA contains only the building blocks for the needed services. Secondly, building blocks

such as new applications should be subject to development. Finally, the ABB must comply with the service standards of the specific architecture implementation (The Open Group, 2018).

The ADM process involves identifying and capturing the EA's Architecture Building Blocks (ABB). These building block components are a collection of the functions required to integrate and differentiate ADM stages. The categories of these building blocks include the following (The Open Group, 2018):

- The ADM building blocks are a collection of reusable legacy resources, such as building blocks of the organisation's technology assets. The consolidation also includes building blocks for consideration in the architecture development, such as new applications and those earmarked for procurement, such as commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) digital solutions.
- The ADM Combines functions into building blocks at the desired degree of integration, for example, by defining distinct categories for old infrastructure.

During the initial stages of the development of the ADM, the ABB maintains a broad level of integration. The early stages are best for viewing the organisation's service definitions. At the latter stages of the ADM development, further enhancement of the ABB's more detailed views addresses implementation decisions, focusing on critical decisions and assessing the impact of the development on value creation and future standards and reusability (The Open Group, 2018). The main stages of the ADM process, the specification, and the ABB evolution are summarised in **Figure 2.7** below.

The specification of the ABB is evolutionary and iterative. The ABB definition is done gradually through steps 1 to step 4.

Figure 2.7. The essential Phases/steps of the ADM where the Architecture building blocks are specified and evolve during the programme implementation. Source: (The Open Group, 2018).

2.14.3 Initiation of the TOGAF Framework

Discussed in additional detail in the subsections that follow is the initiation of the TOGAF architecture development method (ADM) commences with an abstract definition of the Architecture building blocks (ABB) (The Open Group, 2018). In Step 1, the initiation step identifies a list of the candidate ABBs for the business process view. Created is a model of these candidate-views of the organisation's architecture and building blocks depicting their relationships (The Open Group, 2018).

2.14.4 Current/Baseline State Architecture Description

Secondly, in step 2, a description of the baseline or current state of the organisation's architecture building blocks is created with an additional list of candidate architecture building blocks generated from the analysis. These outputs, the candidate building blocks and the refined baseline architecture

building blocks constitute the architecture of the existing systems in use, with the potential for reusability, within the organisation (The Open Group, 2018).

2.14.5 Target Architecture and Transition Architectures

Transition Architecture is created as the target architecture is being developed. These are milestone transitional architectures the organisation might choose to establish as the architecture evolves towards the target architectures, as shown in step 3.0 in **Figure 2.7** above. Step 3.1 of the Target architecture development produces a high-level description and an associated model of the target system ABBS, including its justification (The Open Group, 2018). In step 3.2, a target is developed with input from the baseline architecture building blocks listed in step 2. The creation of the target state architecture of the organisation is an evolutionary and iterative process (The Open Group, 2018). Each ABB of the target state architecture produces a set of the non-conflicting portfolio of services in Step 3.3. These service descriptions are tested for functional fit with application requirements (The Open Group, 2018).

The next step, step 3.4, develops the complete target state ABBs and a fully defined and specified list of all the standards required for implementation. The Open Group recommends that the target state ABB is depicted in the diagrammatic form at the level of the organisation's needs. These diagrammatic descriptions should be consistent with the strategic and implementation perspective of the organisation's architecture (The Open Group, 2018).

2.14.6 Opportunities and Solutions Architecture

Step 4 discussed the descriptions of the opportunities and solutions building blocks elsewhere in this section. Developing the Solutions building blocks (SSB) is the final stage in the TOGAF framework. The implementation of the ABB is implementation-specific, along with the detailed architecture specification of interfaces to other supporting building blocks of the organisation's architecture. The output ABB of step 4, opportunities and solutions, is a set of product-specific solutions with their defined functions (The Open Group, 2018).

2.15 Modelling in EA Development: Developing Context.

The TOGAF ADM models the context of the ABB in two technical levels for the definition and development of the organisation's Architecture (The Open Group, 2018). However, it does not consider Socio-Technological aspects of the social context of the programme activities in the ADM where the mechanisms reside.

The Business process level, the highest level, deals with the organisation's business process implementation. Secondly, the technical functions and constraints that deal with the supporting activities form part of the business process. Activities that cannot be supported are also assessed at this model level (The Open Group, 2018).

Defining and developing the ABB itself also take two iterative levels. The architectural model level identifies the relationships between building blocks and architecture components that implement the technical functionality. Secondly, the architecture model's solution building blocks are where specific products and components implement the candidate architecture (The Open Group, 2018).

2.15.1 Modelling in EA Development; Developing Context.

The TOGAF ADM models the context of the ABB in two technical levels for the definition and development of the organisation's Architecture (The Open Group, 2018). However, it does not consider Socio-Technological aspects of the social context of the programme activities in the ADM where the mechanisms reside.

The Business process level, the highest level, deals with the organisation's business process implementation. Secondly, the technical functions and constraints that deal with the supporting activities form part of the business process. Activities that cannot be supported are also assessed at this model level (The Open Group, 2018).

Defining and developing the ABB itself also take two iterative levels. The architectural model level identifies the relationships between building blocks and architecture components that implement the technical functionality. Secondly, the solution building blocks of the architecture models are the

stage where specific products and their components implement the candidate architecture (The Open Group, 2018).

2.15.2 Phase A: Architecture Vision (AVP)

The AVP is the first step in the architectural development procedure (The Open Group, 2018). The AVP aims to create a high-level vision of the organization's capabilities and business value. The AVP includes establishing the scope, identifying stakeholders, generating the architectural vision, and gaining intervention clearances. In addition, AVP detects and handles any practical limits.

The AVP then seeks permission for a statement of architecture work, which describes the work to create and implement to utilise architectural and non-architectural inputs. Further stages may be modified to the context following the established architectural governance. (The Open Group, 2018).

The outputs of the AVP are stakeholder map matrices, business model diagrams and value chain diagrams, an approved statement of architecture work, and refined business strategy reports. AVP outcomes include architecture principles, capability assessment, customised architecture, architecture vision, a drafted architecture definition document, communications plan, and more information filling the architecture repository that may be utilised to produce a single architecture vision. The approach is to request architecture work from the sponsoring organisation and ensure proper recognition and endorsement from the relevant decision-makers (The Open Group, 2018).

Phase A, architecture vision, enables the organisation to define the scope of the architecture effort and the constraints that must be resolved for strategic alignment. This phase of the ADM identifies the relevant stakeholders and business domain, such as its mission, strategic vision, and operating strategy. The organisation's goals are confirmed and refined for consistency and commitment (Goepff & Petit, 2017).

2.15.3 Phase B: Business Architecture (BAP)

The BAP's purpose is to create the target business architecture, which outlines how the organisation should run to fulfil the objectives outlined in the architectural vision. The BAP allows the organisation

to handle architecture work and stakeholder issues and identify chosen architectural roadmap pieces based on gaps between the baseline and target business architectures. The BAP focuses on business outcomes (The Open Group, 2018).

All actions launched in the phases are concluded at the finality of the business architecture step with the required architectural and non-architectural inputs. The BAP requires publicly publishing the documentation developed in the last stage (build the architectural definition document) for outputs that are updated versions of the deliverables from the architecture vision phase.

Business architecture represents holistic, multi-dimensional capabilities, end-to-end value delivery, information, and organisation structure. The BAP establishes the relationships among the organisational ideas and strategies, products, policies, initiatives, and stakeholders.

Business architecture connects business components to organisational objectives and attributes. Understanding business architecture is essential for other types of architectural work (data, application, technology). As a result, it is the first architectural work that must be completed if it has not already been handled in other organisational processes.

According to Goepf and Petit (2017), phase B of the ADM, the business architecture, has two main goals. First, it sets out to create the organisation's target business architecture to describe how it needs to operate to align with its business goals. Secondly, the BAP identifies possible architecture roadmap components in line with the gaps between the baseline and target architectures. The BAP outlines the service strategy and the business environment's organisational, functional, operational, informational, and geographical aspects. The BAP also addresses the external business domain constraints by redefining the organisation's mission, vision, strategy, and objectives.

Goepf and Petit (2017) suggest that the ADM business architecture phase aims to develop its target business architecture to help it achieve its goals. The stage also helps the organisation identify a candidate architecture roadmap derived from the baseline and target architecture gaps.

2.15.4 Phase C: Information Systems Architectures (ISAP)

The ISAP specifies information system architectures for architectural interventions, including data and application architectures (The Open Group, 2018). The ISAP aims to develop the target information systems architectures by demonstrating how the organization's information systems architecture supports the business architecture and architectural vision. The ISAP addresses architecture work and stakeholder challenges and identifies potential architecture roadmap components based on gaps between the organization's baseline and desired information systems architectures. The ISAP incorporates some data and application architecture. According to The Open Group (2018), Steven Spewak's EA planning (EAP) takes a data-driven approach, while major application systems like enterprise resource planning (ERP) and customer relationship management (CRM) often employ an application-driven approach. The application-driven approach recognises select essential apps as the basic foundations of mission-critical business operations, making these core applications the central focus of architectural work.

The ISAP must define existing and new data or application building blocks in detail per the formal steps identified to determine; whether it is appropriate to conduct target architecture development.

The outputs of data architecture may be catalogues, matrices, and diagrams of the upgraded form of the architecture vision phase deliverables, data, and application interoperability requirements.

According to Goepf and Petit (2017), ISAP aims to enable the organisation to develop the target information system architecture (data and application architectures) and identify candidate architecture roadmap components. Critical considerations for data architecture include data management, migration, governance, and the relevant data architecture repository for the available data models. For the application architecture, reviews for appropriate resources in the architecture repository must be given to high-level business functions.

2.15.5 Phase D: Technology Architecture (TAP)

The TAP aims to evolve the target technology architecture that warrants the architecture vision, target business, data, and application building blocks to be implemented through technology components and services (The Open Group, 2018). The TAP solves architectural issues as well as stakeholder concerns. It detects architectural roadmap components based on gaps between baseline and targeted technology architectures. The TAP also identifies Architectural and non-architectural inputs through appropriate steps, emerging technologies, and architecture repositories to create outputs in catalogues, matrices, and diagrams.

TAP's goals are first to build the target technology architecture to realise the logical and physical application, data components, and architectural vision. The technology architecture contains technology components and their relationships to the organization's information systems, platforms, and fragmentations, demonstrating the technological combinations necessary to realise a specific technology function (Goepff & Petit, 2017). Its goal is to discover potential architectural roadmap pieces additionally.

Pasaribu et al. (2019) describe the information system architecture phase as the integration of the target data needs of the organisation and its application that enable it to meet the vision and principles of the EA. It provides how the organisation can depict its business architecture.

2.15.6 Phase E: Opportunities and Solutions (OSP)

The OSP discusses identifying projects, programmes, or portfolios that successfully provide the target architecture specified in earlier stages of the ADM and focuses on how to offer the architectural intervention (The Open Group, 2018). The goals are to create the complete version of the architecture roadmap and to choose Architecture parts from previous stages to decide if an incremental approach is needed.

The OSP also identifies and defines the overall solution building blocks to finalise the target architecture based on the architecture building blocks (ABBs). The OSP routes its inputs via suitable

phases that keep the focus on the goal while adding incremental value to the organisation. According to Nikpay et al. (2017), the ADM's opportunities and solutions phase consists of evaluation and implementation choices.

2.15.7 Phase F: Migration Planning (MPP)

The MPP bridges the gap between the baseline and target architectures by validating the architectural roadmap and assisting with implementation (The Open Group, 2018). The migration strategy guarantees that the project and portfolio managers coordinate the execution. The migration strategy also validates that key stakeholders comprehend the business value, cost of work packages, and transition architectures using different tools and procedures. During this phase, the migration planning component evaluated the numerous migration projects' dependencies, costs, and advantages to finishing the architectural development cycle. The MPP records lessons learned to allow continual process improvement inside the organisation.

2.15.8 Phase G: Implementation Governance (IGP)

The IGP oversees implementation architecture to guarantee conformity with the objective design (The Open Group, 2018). The IGP is also responsible for architectural governance and implementation-driven architecture change requests. The IGP creates a signed architecture contract, change requests, and a populated architecture repository using relevant tools and organisational processes. The Open Group suggests that the ideal approach to implementation governance is to deploy the target architecture to enable the early realisation of business value and benefits and minimise risk in the transformation and migration program.

2.15.9 Phase H: Architecture Change Management (ACMP)

The ACMP defines methods for managing modifications to the new architecture to guarantee that the architectural lifecycle is maintained and the governance framework is implemented (The Open Group, 2018). The ACMP also guarantees that the organization's architectural competence is current. It employs rigorous techniques to align diverse architectural and non-architectural inputs with the

desired results. The change management process attempts to certify that the architecture achieves its original goal business value by managing changes to the architecture cohesively and architecturally. It also enables ongoing monitoring of governance requirements, technological advancements, and changes in the corporate environment.

2.15.10 ADM Architecture Requirements Management (ARMP)

The ARMP drives the ADM cycle. The objective of the ARMP is to ensure that the implementation process is sustained and operational for all appropriate steps (The Open Group, 2018). The phase manages architecture requirements identified during any execution. It ensures that applicable architecture requirements are accessible at each stage of the intervention/implementation with all needed inputs.

TOGAF recommends using an iterative approach to architectural development. Steps are taken in the ARMP to obtain the requirements impact assessment, architecture requirements repository and updated architecture requirements specification if required. The Open Group suggests recording and managing all architectural requirements in an architecture requirements repository. Unlike the architectural requirements specification and impact assessment, it may store information from numerous ADM cycles. As a result, it enables a feedback loop across all stages of the ADM.

2.15.11 TOGAF Deliverables

The architecture intervention culminates in deliverables recommended per the TOGAF (The Open Group Architecture Framework) standard. These are detailed in Appendix D. While these specifics fall outside the scope of this study, they guide architects on how changes can be implemented to address the findings of this study.

2.15.12 Architecture Iterations within the ADM

The Architecture Capability iteration (ACI) outlines the process of building a complete Architecture Landscape across numerous ADM cycles depending on specific demands, according to The Open Group (2018). These requirements are related to the Request for Architecture Work.

Iterations of the Architecture Development Iteration (ADI) define the integrated process of building architecture. The actions mentioned in the various ADM stages interact to create a unified architecture. Transitioning planning (TPI) and Architecture governance iterations (AGI) describe the approach to managing change to the organisation's Architecture Capability.

According to Goepp and Petit (2017), the ADM regards the organisation and IT strategies as input to the preliminary stages. Still, from a Socio-Technological perspective, the ADM does not consider EA interventions' social aspects, which is perhaps a significant justification for this research.

"The ADM does not consider the skills and processes components of the IT domain" (p.11712).

Korhonen and Poutanen (2013) identify Socio-Technological architecture as an integral part of the design and building of architecture work. However, Korhonen and Poutanen argue that Socio-Technological architectures are *"self-contained and self-regulated with its paradigmatic function, methods, and tools"* (p.351).

In their adaptive and maladaptive EA model, clutching to "best practices" with little regard for Socio-Technological factors causes a disconnect with strategy. The disconnect may result in a potentially curtailed view of the reach of Architecture in promoting alignment with strategy. The proponents contend that incorporating socio-technical considerations fosters a comprehensive perspective, enabling a nuanced balance between tactical considerations and evolving business requirements. Still, the TOGAF ADM has not been explicit in factoring in the role of Socio-Technological architecture in developing EA.

2.15.13 Review of TOGAF research and applicability and generalizability to EA practice.

Can we generalise EA implementation research findings? One critical factor to note in research on value realisation in EA implementations is the variability various implementations introduce.

According to Masuda and Viswanathan (2019), The TOGAF frameworks are often customised and tailored to suit the organisation's context and requirements. As such, analysis of research finding from

a specific implementation may be difficult to generalise for other implementations situated in a different context of a customised framework with different needs and structures.

"Organisations start with an open framework like the TOGAF framework, but as it gets customised and tailored, it adapts to an organisation's culture to become their own personalised EA model. As EA matures in an organisation, the TOGAF framework is still inside and powering their EA but no longer very visible" (p. 16).

Generalising the applicability of research finding beyond the case under study is a weak proposition, according to Yin (2003). TOGAF has a doubtful historical antecedent (Kotusev, 2018). Kotusev rejects The Open Group's suggestion that the original development of version 1 of the TOGAF in 1995 was gleaned from the Technical Architecture Framework for Information Management (TAFIM) (Kotusev, 2018). Indeed, Perks and Beveridge (2003) support the view that TAFIM as a framework is incomplete and obsolete because its implementation is costly and time-consuming. This argument suggests that TOGAF has similar philosophical foundations as the TAFIM. A sound argument is that the shortfall of TAFIM heralds the creation of TOGAF. However, Kotusev argues that TOGAF advocates essentially the same ideas as TAFIM that prove ineffective in aligning the organisation's strategy with its IT.

Kotusev (2016) argues that the TOGAF framework lack documented illustrations of successful implementations. Anderson and Backhouse (2009, p.79) support such a view by suggesting that the lack of tangible evidence of successful implementation cannot be taken for granted, as a measure of TOGAF, as a viable framework for achieving EA success.

Dietz and Hoogervorst (2011) argue that TOGAF (version 9.2) is a failure because the extent to which it fulfils the indispensable requirement of unity and integration is inadequate. Dietz and Hoogervorst attribute the leading cause of these failures to a lack of a sound and appropriate theoretical foundation for the framework instead of a result of a collaborative effort from industry which may lack scientific rigours in its creation. According to Buckle et al. (2009), TOGAF is too complicated. Despite

intensive familiarisation workshops, EA practitioners have reported negative experiences with programmes implemented using the TOGAF framework.

TOGAF has no documented real-life examples of successful implementation grounded in independent and verifiable evidence-based validation and is based mainly on beliefs built on claims by the Open Group. Therefore, the Open Group's recommendation can best be described as delivering anecdotal value without evidence adduced with scientific rigour Alm and Wißotzki (2013, p. 114).

Beyond the generalizability of research findings from a case study, there are significant gains in enhancing the body of relevant knowledge and best practices in implementing EA programmes.

Agerfalk (2014, p.596) argue that findings may not be generalisable but can provide sound evidence for questioning generally accepted theoretical assumptions.

Due to its wide use and acceptability, the TOGAF is widely assumed to be suitable as a generally applicable theoretical model. Many researchers have considered TOGAF a generic conceptual portrayal of EA in practice for their studies, notably Gill (2015), Hanschke (2010), Svee and Zdravkovic (2015), and Mueller et al. (2013).

EA implementations may significantly deviate from the TOGAF method.

"EA practices based on TOGAF may essentially not even relate to the TOGAF's original prescriptions"(Kotusev, 2018a, p.20).

There is a widely held assumption among the research community that it is sound to analyse EA practices through the lens of EA frameworks (Bui, Markus, & Newell, 2015; Kotusev, 2018).

Kotusev further argues that his research finding suggests that, although EA frameworks form the basis for an organisation's implementation practice, frameworks do not necessarily determine the EA practice.

TOGAF is the most widely cited in EA publications but does not usually determine reality, according to Simon et al. (2013). The empirical fact from research findings may be valuable because they form the basis for questioning conventional wisdom and established theoretical frameworks (Kotusev,

2018). Challenging conventional wisdom may stimulate future research, contribute to the body of knowledge in EA, and significantly change the EA discipline towards more successful outcomes.

2.16 Business and Information Technology Alignment

It is argued that the *"lack of alignment within an organisation generally limits the effectiveness of the organisation's business strategies"* (Ansola et al., 2011, p. 13079). Given the pervasive growth of information technology systems across most business sectors, securing strategic alignment between information systems and the overarching business strategy is paramount. Alignment necessitates that all parts of a business, including the *"people, systems, processes and technology"*(p, 13074), are well situated to actualise the goals and vision of the business. Camponovo, Pigneur, and Lausanne (2004) suggested three business and information technology alignment levels.

"The first level corresponds to the nowadays classical internal Alignment of IS with the other constituents of the enterprise, namely its strategy, organisation and technology. The second level considers the external environment of the enterprise. It is assumed that IS have to integrate features for assessing the environment so as to facilitate the alignment of the organisation with it. Finally, the third level copes with evolution over time and emphasises the necessity to design IS that are able to evolve according to the future changes in the organisation and its environment so as to achieve an enduring alignment" (p.1).

Hence, businesses that align with IT *"achieve a better strategic match, a more efficient IT Architecture with more core competencies as well as better decision-making and foster competitive reactions"* (Alaeddini et al., 2017, p.56). In other words, the lack of IT Alignment with an organisation's objective may result in the inability of such an organisation to appreciate the value of IT as a strategic competitive resource base (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999).

Business and Information Technology Alignment (BITA) refers to the ability to "manage and utilise Information Technology in an organisation to respond to business needs, achieve business goals and acquire competitive advantages" (Alaeddini et al., 2017, p. 56). BITA is considered efficient when

strategically actioned (Alaeddini et al., 2017; Shpilberg et al., 2007). There, however, remains a lack of clarity as to how BITA can be better achieved, and this has become a significant concern currently. It is important to note that in Strategic Alignment, both IT and business strategy inform each other. In as much as IT helps in delivering business objectives, enhances business environments and fosters future business goals (Camponovo, Pigneur, & Lausanne, 2004), business strategy, on the other hand, drives the choice of IT design (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999). Accordingly, the mechanisms of action may or may not cause alignment between IT and the organisation's strategy. **Figure 2.8** shows how the TOGAF ADM may be layered within the strategic alignment framework between IT and the organisation's objectives and goals (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999; The Open Group, 2018). It is a phenomenon that is of interest to the researcher.

Figure 2.8. Strategic alignment model showing how The TOGAF ADM interacts with its components (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999; The Open Group, 2018).

In their Strategic alignment model, Henderson and Venkatraman (1993, 1999) argue that a lack of alignment between the organisation's business and IT strategies can cause the value of IT investment

challenges. They further say that administrative processes must be dynamic to continuously align with IT and the organisation's business domains.

Such analytical alignment, they argue, has four main dominant perspectives. **Figure 2.8** shows the strategic alignment model overlaid with the TOGAF to align IT and business using EA approaches.

Firstly, the organisation's business strategy drives the design options and information systems design logic. While top management decision-makers formulate organisational and IT strategies, internal information systems managers implement its strategy.

Secondly, the business strategy involves articulating a supporting IT strategy. The IT strategy must also have a supporting specification of the information systems processes and infrastructure if the potential for technology value is realised. Thirdly, strategic alignment enables the organisation to exploit its emerging IT capabilities to improve service delivery, enhance its unique core competencies and develop new and meaningful relationships. Business strategy is not regarded as given. Instead, their model enables the organisation's business strategy to be amended to continuously align with emerging IT capabilities. The role of top management consequently becomes one of forging a vision for the organisation. This vision articulates emerging IT capabilities and their related functions, changing governance patterns of IT in the business ecosystem and ensuring continuous strategic alignment. Information systems management as a support function identifies trends that assist the organisation in understanding and benefiting from opportunities and threats IT presents. Organisations rely on their EAs and related processes using available skills and competencies.

Finally, another dominant perspective, they argue, is providing world-class IT and information systems competencies within the organisation. The service level is necessary to effectively use IT resources for a responsive approach to dynamic end-user demands. While top management prioritises by allocating resources and setting operating guidelines, information systems managers lead through task execution for operational success.

One of several ways to achieve business and IT strategy alignment is using EA, including the strategic alignment model. The Open Group Framework (TOGAF) is one such approach. Embedded within the TOGAF framework is a series of iterative domains of implementation. Central these domains are a set of iterative mechanisms for implementation, The Architecture Development Method (ADM). The ADM has been discussed (The Open Group, 2018). Archer (1995) argues that context impacts social systems' transformations with human agency. These context influences are structure, agency, relations, and culture.

The Henderson and Venkatraman strategic alignment model, supports the idea that transformations occur when aligning IT and business needs (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999).

Archer and de Souza (2013) argue that structure, culture, relation, and agency must be present in organisations' social action context. Pawson and Tilley (1997) argue that mechanisms are triggered in the context of social action to produce program outcomes. However, The Open Group (2018) provides no specific guidelines on managing Socio-Technological contextual influences in the development of EA using TOGAF.

The implication of such Socio-Technological gaps in social programmes such as the healthcare IT system cannot be overlooked because of their impact on Enterprise program outcomes. Although Shpilberg et al. (2007) cautioned about the IT alignment trap, studies have explored various ways of achieving strategic alignment between business strategies and IT. One way is argued through EA (Foorhuis et al., 2012; Bhattacharya, 2018; Alaeddini et al., 2017). Bhattacharya (2018) explained that EA improves and supports strategic Alignment between business and Information Technology (IT). Alaeddini et al. (2017) analysed the questionnaire responses of 236 experts from sixty different countries for further insight into the benefits of adopting EA in the strategic alignment of business and IT. They adopted Luftman's maturity Assessment model³, PLS path modelling, 'Wilcoxon

matched-pairs signed-ranks test and Mann -Whitney U test' to identify the impacts of EA on Strategic Alignment.

The Alaeddini et al. (2017) findings suggest that large organisations (66%) are likely to adopt EA more than medium (19%) or small organisations (14%). They observed that TOGAF was the most used EA framework in business and IT Alignment, followed by Zachman at 8% and FEA/FEAF at 7%. Alaeddini et al. reiterate that EA can employ 'alignment maturity' to assess the organisations' needs for harmonising IT and business strategies. BITA maturity occurs when all the levels⁴ proposed by Camponovo, Pigneur and Lausanne (2004) are reached. However, Alaeddini et al. (2017) overgeneralised their findings. Theoretically, the study did not detail or provide a guideline on the "how" of IT and business alignment. Methodologically, there was no mention of a sample frame or strategy used for the study. The people from whom the sample was recruited were unknown. Hence, it may not be easy to assess the reliability of the findings, especially as the study claimed that it collected data from experts worldwide. No wonder the authors acknowledged that their research is limited by their inability to ask questions relating to the success factors of the business and IT Alignment. The success factors are critical for business and IT Alignment and the EA implementation process.

The case for strategic alignment is an ongoing agile process requiring a continual review of how organisations implement technology intervention to support their organisational objectives.

Their strategic alignment model highlights the importance of organisations continuously aligning business strategy with IT and lacking this process (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999).

2.17 Complexity Theoretical perspective of EA

Complexity offers a new approach that has arisen over the past decade, taking a radically new alternative paradigm for scientific analytic research. Formal scientific research involves a reductionist approach to the systematic scientific process. The phenomenon is reduced to its parts, each considered

in isolation from the whole, with a linear cause and effect of the parts (Anderson et al., 2005; Calvo, 2021; Mitchell, 2009). Healthcare Organisations have many interconnected, interdependent, and autonomous features, making them complex (Küppers, 1992). Because of this complexity, the analysis considers the phenomena as joint-up, interconnected, and interdependent. Complexity is a non-linear process by which the interdependent part combined to form a whole is greater than the sum of the parts. The interconnectedness of the components parts has synergistic effects. Such synergies may create negative or positive attributes within the system phenomena (Manson, 2001, p.13). EA is complex because of its interdependent goals and practices; and interconnected in its architecture domains (infrastructure, business processes, and applications). *“It currently lacks a robust theoretical foundation and is characterised by emergence because of the firm's objectives and technology dynamic nature that it attempts to align”* (Pascot, Bouslama, & Mellouli, 2011, p.2).

2.18 Network Theoretical Perspective of EA

Network theory is a paradigm that does not take a reductionist approach to its nodes. Organisations are social entities in a network (Kadushin, 2012). The components of the organisations, people and processes and technology are at the core of the social network that characterises organisations. With the interconnectedness of the nodes, technology is a core resource within the organisational network and creates synergies (Granovetter, 1983; Kane, Palmer & Phillips, 2019). Therefore, the characteristics and function within the corporate network can be analysed in isolation, a departure from the reductionist approach to viewing organisational elements as distinct entities. In considering the organisation's strategic Alignment, business objective, and technology assets, the significance of the synergies between them cannot be overlooked (Granovetter, 1983).

2.19 The Concept of Value in EA

Achieving the desired outcomes of EA programmes is challenging; the intended objectives are sometimes not achieved. Program Outcomes provide evidence of success or failure. They trigger

multiple mechanisms in context to produce expected and unexpected outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The value of EA programmes, therefore, lies in their outcomes.

According to Saint-Louis and Lapalme (2018), EA is a discipline that emerged to help organisations meet the challenge of meeting their information technology needs in a context of increasing dynamism and change.

"The definitions of EA vary in terms of scope and purpose. This situation can create misunderstanding and conflict regarding the role and responsibility of professionals practising EA, especially when EA team members are not thoroughly conscious of the extent of the lack of common understanding in EA" (Saint-Louis & Lapalme, 2018, p. 2).

They Carried out a systematic mapping study (SMS) of EA literature as a discipline, focusing primarily on who has published articles, where they are located, and the purpose of the studies. The authors highlight difficulties in defining EA precisely and the risks to establishing a common understanding of EA and adequate direction for future studies.

The authors use an SMS to provide a complete overview of the research area above and comment on the reliability of the research evidence. They are the first to apply the scientific method of SMS to analyse this body of literature, providing insights for future research. Another limitation is that one study excludes relevant data sources such as book chapters and conference articles.

EAF may be defined as modelling business entities aligned with the enterprise utilising the EA Framework (EAF). For each of its scopes and operations, the EAF has several models and views. The EAF produces models, documentation, illustrations, and reports, but most organisations struggle with EA adoption. Despite the vast selection of existing EA frameworks, they have not been able to translate EA solutions to meet organisational needs. According to Ansyori, Qodarsih and Soewito (2018), the most used framework is the Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) and the US Federal EA Framework (FEAF); about 32% of public sector agencies use TOGAF, and about 25% of public sectors use the FEAF framework to implement EA.

"As many as 68% of papers say that the technical development is a CSF that influences the success in the implementation of EA in the public sector, and about 50% of papers say that the framework and methodology is a CSF that influences of implementation of EA in the public sector" (Ansyori, Qodarsih & Soewito, 2018, p.49).

Ansyori, Qodarsih and Soewito (2018) observe and identifies frameworks and CSFs in EQ implementation. They identify 18 frameworks but do not go into detail about each one. Each of the 16 articles defines CSFs such as "Political Will Creation", "Legal Force or legal Power", and "Technical support and development", and the number of papers reviewed contains these.

In terms of the successful implementation of EA in the public sector, some aspects such as user motivation, information needs, and institutional support system use perspectives of the results of this study are not considered significant in the successful implementation of EA.

Simon, Fischbach and Schoder (2013) argue that EA is regarded as a *"structured and aligned collection of plans for the integrated representation of the business and information technology (IT) landscape of the enterprise, in the past, current, and future states"* (Simon, Fischbach & Schoder, 2013. p.2). They argue that while it is the case that EA research and practice have been the topic of several reviews, existing studies have not yet provided a more comprehensive image.

"First, these studies focus on only a specific fraction of the EA literature, e.g., on frameworks, or on works of specific research groups, or of those presented at certain conferences, although a complete review should generally not be confined to specific, potentially 'top' publications" (p.4).

The second critique of EA research was that the analysis of the sources considered does not address some critical aspects of EA in detail, such as architectural processes, the EA meta-model (as the conceptual scheme of EA content), and the understanding of business architecture.

Simon, Fischbach and Schoder (2013) highlight a large amount of co-authorship clustering and discuss the positive impacts of co-authorship on disseminating works on EA. They derive three main

structural patterns: EA frameworks, design and operations of EA management, and EA conception and modelling.

Fischbach and Schoder point out certain aspects that may need to be explored in future developments of these works. According to Fischbach and Schoder, future studies should include a balanced evaluation of various architectural layers, methodologies, components, EA administration activities, and lifecycle stages. It should also require greater use of applied research to reduce any gaps between theoretical underpinnings and EA management implementation. They also propose that future focus should be placed on using EA frameworks, particularly their processes. The findings of the research may also be necessary for the frameworks themselves.

Lange, Mendling and Recker (2016) provide an argument to address the lack of knowledge on how Enterprise Architecture Management (EAM) can successfully impact the organisation's strategic objectives positively. Their previous examinations focused primarily on IT-level benefits. Using a literature review and exploratory interviews, the authors examine EAM success factors and metrics and provide a theoretical model that describes the critical variables and processes of EAM success.

Lange, Mendling and Recker (2016) describe EAM as "*the management activities conducted in an organisation to install, maintain, and purposefully develop an organisation's EA. It captures all those processes, methods, tools, and responsibilities necessary to deal with the different architectural layers of an EA when attempting to build a holistic and integrated view of the enterprise*" (p.411).

Results from this study posit the impact of the four distinct EAM success factors below Lange, Mendling and Recker (2016):

- 'EAM product quality' (The documentation of the EA and associated decision-making is included in EAM products).
- 'EAM infrastructure quality' (includes EAM's formal founding) addresses governance issues such as EAM's conventional mission, the degree to which EAM-related decision-making is

centralised, and the explicitly specified governance structures for EAM-related decision-making).

- ‘EAM service delivery quality’ (EAM services are the actions and assistance that EAM provides to organisations or transformation initiatives).
- ‘EAM organisational anchoring’ (anchors are reference points that entities can draw upon when choosing a behaviour or deciding).

EAM organisational anchoring was introduced as a central idea that influenced the impact of success variables, including EAM infrastructure and service quality. Using a confirmatory study of the model, the researchers also proposed two critical EAM success measures: intentions to apply EAM and organisational and project benefits. The EAM Satisfaction construct did not seem to be a significant mediator for continuing EAM engagement or accomplishing organisational and project advantages, mainly if the system under consideration is a managerial rather than a technology tool.

A vital critique of this study is that the measurement instrument used perceptual measures as a proxy for objective criteria, as interviewees can exaggerate their views.

In a study by Levy (2019), he calls for more studies on institutional change and micro-practices that make field-level organisations a part of broader organisations, with a collective case study on EA within a US state government. The author means field-level institutions are "the taken-for-granted meanings, practices, norms, and regulations that constitute the social structures within an organisational field that *often organises around a recognised area of expertise or activity*" (Levy, 2019, p.1).

EA is an IT planning discipline that creates documentation that may serve as a blueprint for an organization's existing or future IT infrastructure and a management roadmap for moving forward. EA is a typical example of a field-level institution with various well-established frameworks built by different organisations.

Levy uses institutional theory (IS) as an analytical lens, focusing on the duality between institutions as stable schemes, norms, rules, and routines, while also challenged by the changing nature of the social activity and the institutions themselves. In this way, "*the very introduction of EA causes an institutional change in the adopting organisation, requiring well-thought strategies and practices to enable a successful EA implementation*" (p.3).

Mechanisms, as usual, play a significant role in determining the outcomes of EA programmes.

His findings suggest three change mechanisms that validate field-level organisations and act as critical success factors for EA:

- There are shared spaces for knowledge exchange between organisation members.
- Personnel shifting their roles within shared spaces to effectively engage with other organisation members.
- There is an urgent requirement to revise forms and the associated communication lexicon to facilitate more effective user engagement.
- More study is required to investigate additional legitimating strategy variations and how they may vary in IS settings against conventional organisational contexts or at various phases of the institutional reform process. Furthermore, these methodologies' meta-analyses are required to give appropriate practitioner guidance.

A resource-based viewpoint of value generation through EA management is essential.

Ahlemann, Legner and Lux (2020) propose a theory-led, empirically validated model to examine the benefits of EAM through 8 case studies. They argue that value is embedded in EAM as a firm resource enabling it to compete and be profitable.

EA management (EAM) progressed as a discipline in the late 1980s after Zachman applied architecture from construction engineering to design and plan organisational information systems (IS) (Zachman, 1987). EAM has been presumed to result in structured planning and improved decision-making, benefiting from increased organisational performance through aligned IT.

Resource-based theory (RBT) explores how value is generated using and managing IT resources and capabilities. According to RBT, a firm's power to deploy resources or so-called capability is even more critical than its resources. As a result, the RBT distinguished resource picking' (the selection and acquisition of relevant resources) and capacity building (the ability to maximise the inherent potential of appropriate resources) as essential organisational functions.

Regarding success factors, the authors discover that EAM does not provide immediate advantages but can only provide value if an organisation develops four second-order EAM capabilities: EA modelling, EA planning, EA execution, and EA governance. EAM resources only have potential when creating EAM capabilities calls into question the long-held approach of starting EAM as largely a modelling and documenting the process.

This study contributes to the research on EAM benefit realisation by providing a theory-led viewpoint on value development using EAM. The authors urge that managers and academics reconsider the responsibilities and designs of frameworks, tools, and models, which may not be flexible enough to capture the full range of EAM methods because they adhere to a one-size-fits-all philosophy.

This study relied primarily on interview data and document analysis, a very efficient way of understanding complex strategic phenomena such as EAM. There may also have been other uncovered aspects of the causal relationships and EA-related resources" importance. Ahlemann, Legner and Lux (2020) argue that future research should use this study's findings and develop techniques to measure changes in the identified EAM and IS capabilities.

In their analysis, Ahlemann and Legner and Lux (2020) acknowledge notable successes in the implementation of EAM but argue that exploring the generative mechanisms of EA, which account for these successes, is not required in enough detail necessary. They argue that research around EAM mechanisms delivers significant gains in the nascent field.

Hauder et al. (2013) and, Löhe and Legner (2014) support this review, arguing that EA programmes have the notoriety of challenges in justifying their value to organisations.

The lack of evidence to support the benefits of EAM when its resources are its capabilities casts doubt on established practices, the modelling and documentation efforts initiated by EAM, and the effectiveness of these efforts.

"EAM does not create benefits per se, but only creates value if an organisation develops four second-order EAM capabilities – EA modelling, EA planning, EA implementation, and EA governance" (Ahlemann & Legner and Lux, 2020, p.10).

The nexus of the benefits start by introducing EA intervention through a program theory of mechanisms and subsequently embedding these interventions within the organisation's operational processes.

These resources include business processes initiated by role-based human agency, competencies expressed in the taxonomy of TOGAF as Business Architecture, its technology assets - Data Architecture, Information systems Architecture" and its "Technology Architecture" commonly referred to as hardware and software (Melville et al., 2004; Bernus, Noran & Molina, 2015; Iacob et al., 2014).

Zachman (1987) adopted the concept of EAM from the conceptual modelling technique of engineering and architecture from construction science to aid in the planning the design of organisational information management systems (Ross, Weill, and Robertson, 2006).

Knowledge of their generative mechanisms is crucial for the successful outcomes of EA programmes. The conditionalities for these mechanisms are necessary for decision-makers to aid them in understanding to take appropriate action for a successful implementation. It is, therefore, imperative to grasp the intricacies of Enterprise Architecture mechanisms as a critical determinant in facilitating efficacious implementation and rational decision-making processes. (Niemi & Pekkola, 2017; Schmidt & Buxmann, 2011; Tamm et al., 2011).

As an engine of organisational performance, it uses the modelling technique through an integrated mediation of the organisation's mandate and its technology assets to provide alignment that enables it to gain performance improvement (Lange, Mendling, & Recker, 2016; Tamm et al., 2011).

Boucharas et al. (2010) argue in their contemporary research of EAM that there are gains for organisations, especially about how EAM affects how they manage their project portfolios and their compliance with business regulations in mitigating organisational risk and reducing the cost of running their business.

EAM has also become popular in steering digital business transformation interventions towards successful completions to improve firm performance (Bērziša et al., 2015; Röglinger et al., 2016; Tamm et al., 2015).

Enterprise Architecture Management (EAM) effectively manages the inherent complexity within corporate Information Systems (IS) environments. The role of organisational culture in the grounding, administration, direction, and efficacy of EA principles may impact the realistic value of an organisation. Aier (2014) analysed the mechanisms behind the EA grounding, management, guidance, principles (EAP), and organisational culture's moderating effects.

Aier argues *“that EAPs do not directly contribute to the common goals of EAM such as flexibility, efficiency, or innovation but that EAPs (like probably other EAM artefacts too) contribute to these goals indirectly via EA consistency”* (2014, p.63). This is essential in measuring EAM performance, especially in practice, where enterprise architects encounter frequent difficulties.

Although not the sole element, organisational culture may be an essential tool for better understanding the impacts of EA artefacts in each collection of organisations. The most potent moderating effects were seen with hierarchical culture (HIC), emphasising the need for grounding EA concepts within an organisation's existing structural norms and leadership frameworks. This recognition underscores the importance of aligning EA strategies with the organisation's entrenched hierarchical culture to ensure effective implementation and maximise the potential benefits of such initiatives.

The findings and recommendations might be helpful for the practitioner concerned with introducing or developing EAPs in their organisation by better recognising and understanding the dimensions of their situation and taking informed action. The value of EA is embedded in Leveraging business-IT alignment. This article contributes to conceptualising the situational parameters that influence EAM success. The study did not use a representative sample, and data collection was limited to respondents from German-speaking countries.

Alaeddini et al. (2017) conducted a worldwide survey of 236 respondents from 60 countries to understand the implications of executing EA on business-IT alignment (BITA). The primary goal of their research was to investigate these effects and offer future avenues for creative techniques.

In the increasingly volatile and competitive surroundings of the twenty-first century, IT supports a variety of corporate strategies. It may also help to design new methods to foster creativity inside organisations. Business-IT alignment (BITA) can be understood and achieved via three different approaches: architecture, governance, and relationships. BITA is *"managing and utilising IT in an organisation to respond to business needs, achieve business goals and acquire competitive advantages"* (Alaeddini et al., 2017, p.56). Gaining BITA as a long-term and assessing management problems is possible in various approaches, including EA.

Research has been conducted to investigate the link between EA and BITA. An organisation may realise BITA using EA by analysing and comprehending the following:

- Understanding the business goals and requirements of the organisation determine processes.
- The EA and BITA processes create, update, or manipulate information.
- It depends on the analysis of applications that can save or change information.
- It is about how technology can support organisational goals.
- It uses the matrices to address the relationships among the four issues above.

Because EA has a high link with BITA maturity, further research can help practitioners determine the maximum levels of maturity items that can be effectively adopted via EA initiatives. This area of

concentration is also interesting to researchers and developers of EA frameworks in healthcare, who want to perform additional research and address the present frameworks' flaws.

Various researchers have appreciated the value of EA in the Public Sector. Over time, the concept of EA has been gaining more attention from public sector stakeholders globally. EA attempts to "capture the status of an organisation's business architecture, information resources, information systems, and technologies so that the gaps and weaknesses in the processes and infrastructures can be identified, and development directions planned" (p.130). As a result, EA has become a popular strategy in the public sector for increasing efficiency and ICT use rates.

"67% of countries were implementing EA or similar programmes, and up to 93.3% of countries were planning to launch EA initiatives within a year or two. However, these initiatives turned out to be difficult to implement, despite EA providing numerous benefits" (Dang & Pekkola, 2017, p.130).

Dang and Pekkola argue that previous research has largely neglected the public sector context (particularly internationally) regarding how EA is developed, implemented, and adapted. The authors conducted a systematic literature review, identifying 71 articles over 15 years before the publication of their paper.

The EA concept has indeed been applied within diverse contexts within the public sector (Lemmetti & Pekkola, 2014; Guijarro, 2007; Hjort-Madsen, 2007; Peristeras & Tarabanis, 2000). EA has gained popularity in improving the interoperability and efficiency of inter-organisational and intra-organizational IT systems (Hiekkanen et al., 2013; Lemmetti & Pekkola, 2014).

Other applications of EA have been data consolidation and strategic planning (Boucharas et al., 2010; Hjort-Madsen, 2007; Ross, Weill, & Robertson, 2006). These interventions are usually voluntary, although legal requirements include the US, the 2002 E-Government Act, and the Finland Act on Information Management Governance in Public Administration.

Dang and Pekkola (2017) argue that case studies in industrialised nations and local contexts seem to be the foundation of mainstream EA research in the public sector. They emphasise, however, that the

public sector EA is dispersed and that there is no significant and unified research stream. It implies that information about EA creation, implementation, and adaptation and their obstacles and best practices do not accrue.

Governmental agencies are a crucial part of national EA projects within the public sector participation in all phases of the projects. As a result, it is critical to understand their role, what has happened, and why certain activities are taken. Therefore, practitioners and civil servants must be incorporated in research endeavours, as these individuals understand the root causes and causal relationships between actions, decisions, and consequences.

The authors argue that future research should focus more attention on *"EA implementation from the perspective of interoperability and integration, and alignment and strategy, to gain an understanding of pragmatic problems. This will help governments and agencies form connected governments and reduce the number of fragmented business services"* (Dang & Pekkola, 2017, p.142).

Communication and collaboration in EA development are vital to realising its value (Banaeianjahromi & Smolander, 2019).

Guest, Bunce, and Johnson (2006) referred to enterprises As living creatures; they must be continually re-architected to attain the requisite agility, alignment, and integration. Indeed, EA is seen as a "bridge" between strategy and execution, bridging the gap between the business and IT.

"Taking all of the architecture of the entire enterprise into consideration, all enterprise entities, such as systems, stakeholders, relationships, dependencies and business strategies, can be architected in an EA effort" (Banaeianjahromi & Smolander, 2019, p.878).

EA is commonly used to minimise complexity and enhance BITA. Because EA creation is a complicated profession, it is crucial to investigate practitioners' challenges when developing EAs. Banaeianjahromi and Smolander (2019) use grounded theory to investigate the challenges to EA development encountered by practitioners in fifteen big organisations.

An obstacle is "Something that blocks you, so that movement, going forward, or action is prevented or made more difficult" (Banaeianjahromi and Smolander (2019)). They argue that EA obstacles are "the factors confronting the EA project with difficulties and loss of resources that cannot be solved easily, and therefore they create risks of project failure" (p.879).

The authors explored the challenges at each step of EA development: pre-development, development, and post-development. The authors identified a lack of communication and teamwork as the primary barriers that might explain many issues. (2019, Banaeianjahromi and Smolander). They argue that other perceived EA development obstacles also harmed communication and collaboration. These include a lack of knowledge and support inside an organisation, as well as "issues imposed by external parties, hesitation in training personnel, setting too ambitious goals, constant change of management, (lack of) clarity in EA development process, lack of budget, forcing personnel to adopt EA, lack of motivation, organisational culture, and organisational structure deficiencies" (Banaeianjahromi & Smolander, 2019, p.877). To reduce issues in EA implementation, Banaeianjahromi and Smolander (2019) argue that organisations should, at the minimum, address their existing communication and collaboration problems before initiating EA interventions.

If more people were interviewed and medium-sized or small businesses were explored, Banaeianjahromi and Smolander's research would be more reliable. Furthermore, all of their interviews were from the organization's management echelons. As a consequence, generalising these findings should be done with care. Some concerns might be clarified and explained by a multidisciplinary group of stakeholders' viewpoints, such as EA consultants and people.

2.19.1 The value of EA promotes effectiveness and stakeholder satisfaction.

Large organisations increasingly use EA to manage various enterprise applications such as cloud computing, cloud storage and cloud services. Active involvement of EA stakeholders is one of the critical success factors. However, participation depends on EA's ability to help stakeholders achieve

their goals. Although EA is seen as an essential tool for solving major organisational problems, its practical use is not an easy engagement (Van Der Raadt, Bonnet, Schouten, & Van Vliet, 2010).

The role of EA enables complex solutions across multiple systems to be designed (Perks & Beveridge, 2003). EA also offers various options for using various solutions to a specific problem (Johnson, Lagerström, Närman, & Simonsson, 2007).

The alternatives selected and the EA programs' mechanisms are detailed in the target draft. The Target Blueprint (Lankhorst, 2005; Van Der Raadt, Bonnet, Schouten, & Van Vliet, 2010) thus breaks down the complexity of the organisation into comprehensible, manageable business and IT components. It allows for a clear and concise vision of a specific solution to a particular problem. It supports decision-making by management (Smolander & Päivärinta, 2002; Van Der Raadt et al., 2010).

A typical EA stakeholder is a member of an organisation with a set of goals and objectives. In a related work by Boh and Yellin (2006) and Van Der Raadt et al. (2010), EA stakeholders have been described as having specific objectives active at all levels of the organisation and centre on specific areas of interest in their respective organisations. These objectives can conflict (van der Raadt, Schouten, & van Vliet, 2008). For EA function effectiveness, collaboration amongst these stakeholders, with often conflicting objectives, must collaborate on agreed processes by considering each stakeholder's perspective in decision-making (Peterson, 2004).

Van Der Raadt et al. compared the two topics and presented their work to EA stakeholders "satisfaction and EA effectiveness. They argue that satisfaction and EA effectiveness are related issues and attempt to answer the question, to what extent does EA contribute to the collective goals of an organisation?"

The case studies found that the organisations were primarily concerned with the EA's results. At the same time, the individual stakeholders were also concerned about how the architects worked. They found a strong correlation between EA effectiveness, stakeholder satisfaction, and overall organisation satisfaction.

The findings of Van Der Raadt et al. also show that *"the EA owners of ITO's [IT and Operations] EA function mentioned more alignment indicators (39%) than agility indicators (21%)"* (Van Der Raadt et al., 2010, p.1964). Their results show that the EA owners cite several organisational targets beyond their responsibilities. According to Van Der Raadt et al., one possible cause may be that EA owners focus on goals directly related to their area of responsibility rather than purposes intended for EA features the organisation wants to achieve. Although correlation exists, inferences may be challenging to draw because of the complexity in organisations enormous organisations.

2.19.2 Technology Architecture Roadmaps as Output to EA Development

According to TOGAF (2018), as an essential outcome of technology architecting, the architecture roadmap aims to create a list of work packages that, when delivered, realises the target state architecture of the organisation. It outlines the timeline to depict the progression from the baseline architecture to the intended future state of architecture for strategic alignment with the organisation's technology capability vision. The technology roadmap provides the blueprint for the business value. It is usually embedded in the work package created to deliver the roadmap. Intermediate steps are created as transition architectures for the eventual realisation of the target architecture state. The Architecture roadmap is created progressively as the ADM progresses through stages E and F. Phase B includes the business architecture, Phase C includes the information systems architecture, and Phase D includes the technological architecture.

"The primary goal of EA is to define the [desired] future state of the organisation 's business processes and IT systems (often referred to as the —to-be|| or target architecture) and to provide a roadmap for achieving this target from the current state (—as-is|| or baseline architecture)" (Tamm. et al. 2011, p142).

Tamm et al. further argue that architecture roadmaps are essential in providing a high-quality alignment between the organisation's strategic goals and its vision, on the one hand, and its future operating technology platform. However, the TOGAF ADM is silent on the impact of context on the

mechanisms that deliver the technology roadmap. Kotusev (2016) expressed doubt about the widely accepted expression of EA as current state, future state, transition state and roadmaps as incomplete and advocates for further research.

2.20 Socio-Technical Theory

According to *Eccles and Groth (2006, p.339-340)*, “*Socio-technical systems can be considered as problem-solving systems comprising human and technical agents*”.

There is a danger of producing high costs when developing socio-technology systems with various human and technical actors. Technology might be so severely conceived or deployed that the workload cost exceeds the efficiency gains. One widely cited explanation for technological difficulties is that their design is motivated solely by technological improvements, with little regard for human qualities or human agency challenges ((Hoffman & Klepper, 2000; Orlikowski & Scott, 2015; Introna, 2016).

As a result, experts have advocated that the drive for technological innovation be shifted away from increases in technology capabilities and toward more human- and problem-centred design (Byng, Norman, & Redfern, 2005; Fichman et al., 2014; Norman & Stappers, 2015; Bødker & Kyng, 2018). Problems frequently impose expectations that cannot be accomplished given inherent human cognitive and physical resource limits. Conversely, concentrating solely on one aspect of the problem, human or technological, will inevitably yield an incomplete blueprint for technical design. This is attributed to these components' intrinsic influence on each other (Hoffman & Klepper, 2000; Leonardi & Vaast, 2017; Faraj, Pachidi, & Sayegh, 2018; Kane et al., 2014). Therefore, any attempt at effective guidance necessitates understanding this intricate interplay between human and technological elements. For the above reasons, a socio-technological approach to systems design may mitigate human or technological limitations when the social and technological aspects are combined for efficient problem-solving mechanisms.

2.21 Critical Success Factors for EA Management

In a comprehensive literature review conducted by Ansyori, Qodarsih, and Soewito (2018), it was determined that the Enterprise Architecture (EA) framework possesses the capacity to be shaped in the likeness of either a business or an Information Technology (IT) unit. This flexibility enables the framework to be adapted and moulded to suit the specific requirements of diverse organisational structures. Their study shows that organisations use the framework in various ways, such as business units, IT units, and business models. EA is implemented in this context according to the needs and objectives of the organisations implementing the intervention.

Therefore, using tools, framework conditions, and technologies determines EA deployment's success in the public and private sectors. According to Ansyori, Qodarsih and Soewito, the most used frameworks and the factors influencing their use, their literature study shows that about 32% of the public sector uses the Togaf framework in EA implementations and about 25% in business units.

The Selection Framework is among the most popular for EA rollout in the public sector. The selection system is the basis for EA implementation in private and public sectors and business units.

According to their study results, 68% of papers say technological development is the most critical factor influencing CSF implementation (Critical success factors) in the public sector.

Extending their analysis, Ansyori, Qodarsih, and Soewito (2018) contend that open-standard technologies are crucial to facilitate effective digital transformations within the public sector. These technologies, they argue, are pivotal in ensuring the successful implementation and utilisation of technology that sufficiently addresses and fulfils the unique requirements of these organisations. They also need technical assistance and development that ensures that all parties in the private sector agree on CSF and how they influence performance.

In their literature studies, as many as 50% of papers say that the framework or methodology is the most critical factor influencing the CSF in implementing EA in the public sector. The methodology or framework is used for implementation in EA, and the methodology itself is a crucial factor.

EA enables organisations to align strategic objectives with information technology architecture and needs for strategic advantage. Still, the challenge remains that most programmes fail to start, and almost half of those who start end in under five years without achieving their expected outcomes. Management of organisations seeks to derive value from EA programmes only after successful implementation and continuous use (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2017).

Out of the eight case studies of EA implementation investigated, four were successful. The denominator was the architectural thinking function of strategy and formal methodology and tools. Achieving success in EA programmes is enabled when key actors clearly understand architectural practices and their methodological skills (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2017).

Critical success factors such as having a strategy for the Development of Architecture and using a formal methodology and architectural tools are essential determinants for the success or failure of EA programme interventions.

EA interventions' ostensive and performative aspects could help explain EA outcomes by understanding key actors' behaviour in the EA implementation processes (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2017).

Hope, Chew and Sharma, however, argue that the emotional aspects of EA interventions “*have important implications for the practice of EA and suggest that the methodological skills of architects need to be supplemented with process (or social) skills so that architects might be able to attend to key aspects of the organisational context to assure the success of EA programmes as well as their success, rather than be the victims of circumstances*” (p.25). Such social skills are embedded in the mechanisms of the EA programme interventions since they are the established processes within the EA framework in question where interventions occur.

2.21.1 Social-Technical Perspective as Critical Factors (CSF) For EA Intervention Success

EA enables organisations to align strategic objectives with information technology infrastructure. Still, the challenge remains that most EA programmes fail to start, and almost half of those who start

end in under five years. Management of organisations seeks to derive value from EA programmes only after successful implementation and continuous use (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2017).

EA programmes often fail to meet the expectation of organisations that implement them.

According to Hope et al. (2017), in their research finding, out of the eight case studies of EA implementation, four were successful. The dominant factor for success is the architectural thinking function of strategy and formal methodology and tools. Hope, Chew, and Sharma (2017) posit that the success of Enterprise Architecture (EA) programmes is contingent upon the key actors' profound comprehension of architectural practices and their methodological prowess. The potential for EA programme success can be realised through this nuanced understanding and adept application of relevant methodologies.

Critical success factors such as strategy for the development of Architecture, use of a formal methodology and architectural tools can determine the success or failure of EA programme implementation. However, activity routines' ostensive and performative aspects could help explain EA's success. According to Hope, Chew, and Sharma (2017), key actors must thoroughly understand the Enterprise Architecture (EA) implementation process. The profound comprehension of this process is instrumental in effectively steering the course of EA application and achieving the desired outcomes.

Hope, Chew and Sharma (2017, p.25) argue that "the findings of this study have important implications for the practice of EA and suggest that the methodological skills of architects need to be supplemented with process (or social) skills so that architects might be able to attend to key aspects of the organisational context to assure the success of EA programmes as well as their own success, rather than be the victims of circumstances".

The failure rate for EA interventions is exceptionally high at about 95% of programmes. Forty per cent of all architecture programmes are terminated within three years, with often undesired consequences for the organisation. (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2015).

Hope (2015) compared the performance of architecture programmes with an empirical assessment of the core proposition of the CSF literature and suggested that success is linked with the preponderance of certain CSFs, while failure is associated with inadequate provision of those CSFs'. Their Purpose Driven Architecture Practice (PDAP) view is an empirical framework approach to the sociological perspective of architectural practice.

In a longitudinal analysis, they discovered the existence of CSFs in specific programmes using over 5,000 literary observations from ProQuest, Premier, the ACM Library, and Computer sources and compared their application to the results of the EA programmes. In a parallel study, almost 200 architects evaluated the CSFs collected from the literature. Only five of the examined CSFs were evaluated as critical by more than one-third of the Architects in the study, with half of the Architects evaluating only two. Furthermore, only two of the five CSFs found in their thematic analysis of the existing literature, Commitment to the Use of Architecture and Consultation and Communication, were classified as CSFs. Only 20%-30% rated the CSFs as critical by around 20% – 30%. Many technical CSFs failed to convince 20% of the Architects interviewed. The pie chart in **Figure 2.9** below depicts the percentages for the critical success factors identified in their research.

Figure 2.9. Criticality percentage for Socio-Technical factors critical to EA Implementation Success (Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2015).

Hope, Chew, and Sharma discovered a troubling propensity for anything that "sounds" rigorous or objectively assessable, such as socio-technological aspects, to be disfavored. EA frameworks, EA tools, quality control methods, maintenance, and budgetary controls are all activities that may be objectively assessed. Nonetheless, rigour is seen negatively for an intervention dealing with strategic business alignment and IT-focused on rigour.

The Architects also seem reluctant to monitor compliance, making the top six CSFs in the literature. The seventh CFS is Roles and Responsibilities. The Architects' opinions on basics contradict existing academic study results. The empirical evidence suggests that there are salient factors demonstrating a significant correlation with the success of an Enterprise Architecture (EA) intervention. These factors include rigorous monitoring and adherence to the protocols of technology implementation, stakeholder commitment towards the utilisation of architecture programmes, and efficacious consultation and communication processes with decision-makers and other pertinent stakeholders. Consequently, these variables seem to play an indispensable role in driving the success of EA interventions. The use of EA techniques, strategies, and tools did not predict success.

The consequences of this study imply that architects' scientific abilities should be supplemented with socially-oriented skills to pay greater attention to organisational behavioural circumstances to ensure the success of EA programmes. That performative adaptation is paramount to architectural success. Hope et al. (2017) argue that challenges that proposition, suggesting that the problems in architecture programmes do not fit their organisations' purpose.

So, what does this all mean? Their finding calls for a new approach to managing EA mechanisms beyond existing frameworks such as TOGAF to one encompassing a Socio-Technological paradigm.

2.21.2 EA Improves IT Investment Decisions

Another success factor in determining EA outcomes is improving information technology investment decision-making (van den Berg, Slot et al., 2019). According to van den Berg et al., data was collected through a qualitative survey of 142 participants to investigate how EA can support IT

investment decisions and what impact EA has on investment decisions. They used their data to provide a qualitative analysis of EA's impact on IT investment decisions, covering critical insights on how EA can prepare and deliver IT investments. They found that the top four organisations under the study were more mature in all areas of maturity.

They use the Dynamic Architecture Maturity Matrix (DyAMM) for this study. This model provides a model to increase EA maturity. The maturity model was developed and proposed to help organisations adopt EA best practices. In IT architecture, EA is the glue between business and IT; it links strategy and implementation through corporate integration and environmental adaptation. EA is the means of organisational innovation and Sustainability. It is an adhesive for business IT. DyAMM was developed and scientifically evaluated by Sogeti and has been expressed as one of the most effective EA models in the world (van den Berg et al., 2019).

EA is a discipline that can *“create overview and insights needed to translate strategy into execution, enabling senior management [to] take ownership of the key decisions such as procurement and contracting on the design of the future enterprise”* (Greefhorst & Proper, 2011, p.2).

Lapalme (2012) advocates for three distinct schools of thought within Enterprise Architecture (EA): maturity, using artefacts, and insights. This perspective is derived from a comprehensive critique of the fundamental EA literature, with each school distinguished by its unique strengths, weaknesses, and potential advantages. Each school is grounded in its belief system, with shared elements among its strengths and weaknesses. EA artefacts have been utilised to enhance the preparedness of IT investment decisions. Moreover, EA has endowed the top quartile organisations with a superior comprehension of their IT investments and the capacity to prepare for them, as per van den Berg, Slot, van Steenbergen, Faasse, & van Vliet (2019).

Leading companies increasingly use EA artefacts to prepare for IT in their business planning and investment decisions. Their research shows that EA can be used in various IT investment areas, from

IT infrastructure to IT operations. Their study indicates that the top four organisations stand apart from the rest due to their high overall and spatial maturity.

Business architects can gain valuable insights using Business capability models to improve their practices, processes, and products. Also, some organisations use diagnostic methods, EA artefacts to diagnose, and EA artefacts to act. As a result, EA provides a better understanding of IT investments and supports their decisions. One of EA's competencies should assess IT investments' impact on its overall business performance and financial performance (Kotusev, 2018; The Open Group, 2018). *"A business capability is a particular ability that a business may possess or exchange to achieve a specific purpose"* (van den Berg et al., 2019, p.3).

EA practices create different types of artefacts used to prepare IT investment decisions using these decisions in exchange for achieving their goals (Kotusev, 2018; The Open Group, 2018; van der Raadt, Schouten, & van Vliet, 2008; van den Berg et al., 2019).

Future state architectures, a visual blueprint of the organisation sometimes referred to as target architecture, have a significantly important business model aspect in the IT investment process. IT is often misunderstood and sometimes refers to what is targeted as architecture (van der Raadt, Schouten, & van Vliet, 2008; van den Berg et al., 2019; The Open Group, 2018; Kotusev, 2018).

Current state architectures are EA visual blueprints, a description of the current outlook of the organisation at a high level graphically.

Whereas guidelines are best practice advice that provides the best way to design and implement the solution, policies are overarching organisational standards that are usually restrictive and provide binding rules in certain areas (Kotusev, 2018; The Open Group, 2018).

EA Standards are the result of legal and regulatory obligations required by law. The purpose of these standards is to achieve compliance with the rules and regulations in the business architecture domain of the programme. Companies are then selected to adopt and organise industry standards set by industry organisations based on their entrepreneurial ambitions. Companies must comply with

organisational standards; otherwise, serious consequences are likely (Kotusev, 2018; The Open Group, 2018; van den Berg et al., 2019; van der Raadt, Schouten, & van Vliet, 2008).

Using heatmaps in different colours visualises the status of specific attributes and legal capacities. These attributes may include legal capacity, legal status, regulatory capacity, and compliance capacity (The Open Group, 2018; Roelens & Poels, 2014).

A roadmap is an abstract business and technological change plan, usually developed over several years in several disciplines. It describes a path from the current situation to the future. A landscape diagram visually represents a company's IT landscape, typically covering much of its current state. A thermal map can also visualise business processes such as planning, management, operations, and operations management (The Open Group, 2018; van der Raadt, Schouten, & van Vliet, 2008; van den Berg et al., 2019). Thermal maps can also be used with information objects, as cited in Roelens and Poels (2014).

"Project start architectures", a set of general principles guidelines that translate into concrete project guidelines, a set of guidelines for the implementation of project intervention, such as a business plan, business objective or a directive (Wagter et al., 2005; Foorthuis and Brinkkemper, 2007; van den Berg, M. et al., 2019). Artefacts in "Solution Outlines" can also represent a high-level organisational IT solution blueprint of the proposal designed to meet their specific business requirements (Kotusev, 2018).

2.21.3 Transforming and Transactional Factors for the Successful Implementation of EA in the Public Sector

Zachman (1987) and Lee, Oh, and Nam (2016) characterize Enterprise Architecture (EA) as a conceptual blueprint aimed at managing the risks associated with rapidly evolving information systems, particularly those about data management and analysis. This suggests that the extant determinants of EA success or failure should be considered from the vantage point of organisational change, given that the outcome hinges on the specific change event.

Therefore, success factors for EA must be viewed from the organisational change perspective. Therefore, EA implementation focuses not only on meeting the needs of individual employees but also on optimising the organisation's overall needs.

Lee, Oh, and Nam (2016) further argue that EA is one of the most critical and influential tools for providing citizens with high-quality e-government services. Their study used the organisational change theory to determine the factors contributing to the successful implementation of EA; transformative, transferable, and transactional.

To discern these factors, they collected survey data from the public sector in Korea. These organisations had been employing Enterprise Architecture (EA) for a period exceeding one year. Their results show that performance is affected by EA organisation laws and regulations that indirectly affect performance. This data, therefore, provided valuable insights into the elements that significantly influence the success of EA interventions in a real-world operational context.

Besides, they further show that top management's support, directly and indirectly, impacts EA's performance. Ultimately, the results of their study have important implications for governments and institutions that want to implement EA.

2.22 Critical Failure Factors for Enterprise Architecture Management

Several researchers and technology firms have reported the high failure rate of EA. According to Gartner (2009), 40% of all enterprise architecture efforts globally may be discontinued due to a failure to show good economic value.

According to Stanley (2010), most Federal EA projects in the United States of America have failed to deliver outcomes aligned with the organisation's objective, with some producing any positive impact. Pasaribu et al. (2019) suggest that there is frequently a failure of IT (Information Technology) deployment due to a lack of alignment with the organisation's objectives, with each hospital remaining autonomous. Enterprise architecture is one approach for organisations to overcome the failure of IT implementation, Pasaribu et al. further argue.

Kotusev (2018) argues that due to the adaptability and tailoring of prescriptive EA methodologies, EA practices frequently deviate significantly from the prescriptions provided by prominent EA techniques. Unsurprisingly, even with the existence of a thorough EA methodology, effectively implementing EA remains a difficult task for many businesses, with up to “66 per cent, ..., 80 per cent ..., or even more than 90 per cent ” (p.20) of them failing to realise the anticipated benefits of EA.

Kotusev points out that other EA frameworks are widely criticised as lacking demonstrable success and have well-documented failures; notably, DoDAF and FEAF have well-documented failures. He challenges TOGAF as a framework created based on sound scientific evidence.

"One cannot consider The Open Group's non-validated claims about TOGAF's practical value as reliable scientific evidence" (p.20).

Kreizman and Bittler (2005), in a report composed for Gartner, postulated that approximately 40% of Enterprise Architecture (EA) implementations are unsuccessful. They attribute this failure to a premature initiation of modelling in the EA implementation process before achieving a thorough understanding of the organisation's information systems and information technology needs. This assertion underscores the importance of comprehending an organisation's requirements before embarking on the EA implementation process.

Achieving IT and business alignment is a continuous process sensitive to changing market conditions and emerging technological innovations that influence its strategy. Organisations, however, pay little attention to the changing market conditions. Instead, the focus of top management has been on IT structuring and business goals (Gerow et al.,2014; Chan and Reich, 2007; Lutfman, 2003).

Several EA studies have been conducted to identify essential elements for effective EA implementation. For example, Ylimaki (2006) categorised EA's crucial success factors (CSFs) into twelve areas. Similarly, Nikpay et al. (2013) developed twenty CSFs from a study of the relevant literature. *"The authors failed to empirically validate these factors" (Lee, Oh & Nam,2016, p.3).*

The authors provided the failure factors identified with emphasis on contextual settings.

Despite the failure rate of EA and the reliance on frameworks, there is a gap in research about how mechanisms and contexts impact the outcome of EA implementation. This research intends to address these gaps.

There is a growing trend among organisations struggling to rationalise their investments in Enterprise Architecture (EA), as reported by Aziz & Obitz (2007), Obitz & Babu (2009), Tamm et al. (2011) and Aier, Gleichauf & Winter (2011). Enterprise architecture (EA) is attracting significant attention and investment, as seen by the proliferation of EA-related professional bodies, consulting services, frameworks, and techniques and the rising prevalence of full-time EA teams. Organisations frequently experience challenges justifying their EA investments, and anecdotal data shows that the EA function's existence and financing rely on the existing management team's opinions rather than demonstrable benefits (Tamm et al., 2011). Thus, it may seem unexpected that the usefulness of EA is still little appreciated in this setting.

Tamm et al. (2011) claim that the quality of the methodology may also judge the quality of EA planning and approaches adopted, primarily dependent on the quality of available resources and funding. *"A skilled EA team that has access to sufficient on-going funding appears likely to make use of the best methodologies and tools available"* (p.151).

Guo, Li, and Gao (2019) propose that the *"lack of sufficient funding" continues to create stakeholder reluctance to use EA* (p.41).

Flowers (1996) describes a technology system failure when it does not operate as expected, and its overall performance is deficient. The technology systems may also fail when its implementation does not perform as originally intended or is so user-hostile that users and underutilised reject it.

The technology programme may also the cost of development outweighs any benefits the system may bring throughout its useful life; when, due to problems with the system's complexity or how the programme is managed, the technology programme is abandoned prior to completion. Flowers further

suggest that events that may influence failure include organisational, financial, technical, social, and political factors and their interactions.

Yeo (2002) proposes four types of technology programme failure: correspondent when the objective of the design is not met; processive when the budgetary allocations and time schedules cannot sustain the related technology programme interactive; when usage is surrogate to agreed with key performance indicators; and expective, when stakeholder expectations, requirements or value perception have not been fulfilled.

Al-Emran et al. (2018) and Marnewick & Labuschagne(2011) argue from the perspective of the technology acceptance model, which includes aspects of unmet objectives, budget overruns, key performance indicators not being met, and unfulfilled stakeholder expectations. Genus & Jha (2018) suggest a processive failure in budgetary and time constraints and interactive failure in misaligned key performance indicators.

Yeo further reported that technology programmes fail because of inappropriate programme estimates, indeterminate objectives and goals, senior management disapproval and lack of engagement, unrealistic deadlines and schedules, scope creep, indeterminate requirements and scope and ineffective communication. Flowers and Yeo, however, have not provided the circumstances under which these failure events may occur.

2.23 Summary

Chapter two provides a review of the relevant extant literature relied on for the hypothesis formulation of the thesis. Chapter two also explains concepts and abstractions used to inform the background of the thesis.

3 CHAPTER 3: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Introduction

This section discusses the conceptual framework, the initial programme theory of the research, drawing on the TOGAF ADM framework for mechanisms from practice (TOGAF, 2018), and the Mechanism-Context-Outcome configurations presented. de Souza (2013) proposes the Mechanism-Context-Outcomes as an amplification of *the "trio of explanatory components"* (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.7) as a suitable underlying theoretical framework for researching mechanisms within a critical realist perspective. In this research, ‘program theory’ and ‘programme theory’ are used interchangeably to mean *“theory about what a program, [programme] or intervention is expected to do and in some cases, the theory about how it is expected to work”* (Wong et al., 2013, p.10).

The conceptual framework, a Socio-technological evaluative framework for EA, embeds TOGAF within a CMO configuration and the CRAFTS model (cultural, relational, agential, funding, technological and structural) contexts. The CRAFTS model is a propositional approach to theorising the researched cases based on elicitation from relevant theoretical literature, and organisation reports about reprogramming. The ontological foundation of the framework is based on realist philosophy, *“What works for whom under what circumstances”* (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63; Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012, p.177).

The conceptual framework theorises what Enterprise Architecture mechanisms work for stakeholders under what circumstances and in what phases of the TOGAF ADM.

‘Technological’ here is distinguishable from ‘Technical’.

‘Technical’ refers to *“involving the sorts of machines, processes, and materials that are used in industry, transport, and communications”* (Collins English dictionary, 2022b, Technical).

Technological, as used in this framework, means *“relating to or associated with technology”*, and *“Technology refers to methods, systems, and devices which are the result of scientific knowledge being used for practical purposes”* (Collins English Dictionary, 2022a, Technology).

The realist evaluation approach suggests a deeper understanding of *"the effects of social programmes and to explain the change, and there has to be a deeper understanding of pre-existing contexts and the mechanisms in operation before the introduction of any social program"* (de Souza, 2013, p.142).

Extending the realist evaluation, de Souza proposes a social context as relatively enduring and aimed to *"transform (rather than reproduce) by activating various structural, cultural, agential and relational mechanisms to produce various outcomes"* (p.142).

As this research takes a Socio-Technological ontological approach, the proposed framework provides a point of divergence from a purely social program. It focuses on the relevant participant context of socially contingent action on the EA program being researched and the EA program mechanisms embedded in the EA management initiative. The concept that context impacts social action is supported by Bhaskar's model of transformative social action and Archer's morphogenetic approach Archer (1995). They complement the realist evaluation approach Pawson and Tilley (1997) proposed.

The Enterprise Architecture (EA) mechanisms stand at the heart of this research, given their substantial influence on EA management. Their functional intricacies and operational modalities are integral to the successful execution and administration of EA, making them a focal point of investigation in this study. The preponderance of gaps, lacking understanding and extensive research in EA mechanisms has been established in the literature review section. Mechanisms play a vital role in explaining what is experienced about EA programmes and the underlying structures that shape their implementation. *"Critical realism focuses on explaining what we see and experience, in terms of the underlying structures of reality that shape the observable events"* (Saunders et al., 2016, p.138).

Managing large and complex systems needs good governance policies, which usually depend on a statistical analysis of the data collected on the number of factors in the composite system (de Souza, 2013).

Sager and Anderegg (2012) make a case for a systematic review of complex causality devoid of holistic policymaking in program implementation. Heinrich (2007) argues that evidence-based policy

attempts to improve the effectiveness of programmes by developing and utilising a much broader and more comprehensive platform of information and scientific evidence. Such a platform guides decisions about the program's design and implementation. Policy decisions are faster than the research findings; real-time evaluation has little impact on policymaking. Sager and Andereggen (2012) point out the generally acknowledged problem of the systematic review of traditional statistical analysis leading to unsatisfying results for political decision-makers. Pawson (2002a) considers the importance of singularity and the holistic effect of each case as some of the vital explanatory contents of the programmes get squeezed out in action making the comparisons less comprehensive than the mathematical findings on paper. Sager and Andereggen (2012) argue for a holistic approach that may address various factors in policymaking. There is a need for a suitable method that can consider complex causalities and is not limited only to mono causalities.

Studies made by Sager (2007) and Treib, Bähr, and Falkner (2007) refer to the fundamental aspects of governance comprising of 3Ps (Polity, Politics and Policy). Pawson and Tilley (1997) pointed out that these studies do not account for the context essential for realistic evaluation. Sager and Andereggen (2012) developed a comprehensive scheme to integrate the context with the three Ps for Governance.

3.2 The Taxonomy of Contributions to Theory

The conceptual framework relaxes the Mechanism-Context-Outcome configuration for a broader application to EA program implementation in a social context, including healthcare institutions. It is a necessary abstraction and simplification of reality in organisation interventions of EA. It, therefore, represents an initiative to capture, within an acceptable degree of accuracy, the salient aspects of the purpose of EA while remaining parsimonious Makadok et al. (2018).

3.3 Abstract and Conceptual Frameworks in the Social and Management Context

According to Bak (2004), several theoretical frameworks exist, and according to May, Johnson, and Finch (2016), *“One such way is to enable the researcher to interpret and appreciate findings and make sense of the information they gather” (p.20).*

Three are broad categories of research frameworks; theoretical, conceptual, and practical (Eisenhart, 1991). Theoretical frameworks are commonly used interchangeably with conceptual frameworks (Anfara Jr & Mertz, 2006). However, social and management sciences research does not have explicit distinctions between conceptual and theoretical frameworks (Ngulube, Mathipa, & Gumbo, 2015). This research uses a conceptual framework called the programme theory, postulated as suitable for critical realist evaluation research (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Wong et al., 2016; Jagosh, 2020b). Ngulube, Mathipa and Gumbo (2015) argue that conceptual frameworks are primarily *“used in qualitative research and mixed methods research”(p.66).*

3.4 Retroductive Theorising in the EA Conceptual Framework

Jagosh (2020b) makes a case for the importance of retroduction, sometimes called abduction, unearthing causal mechanisms behind the observable and empirical world. He argues retroduction to be the 'antidote to ignorance. Retroductive questions are phrased in the following ways: *“What is it about "x" that matters?” (Tilley, 1993, p.3),* why do objects appear as they do?' (Olsen 2010) Alternatively, *“What properties do societies possess that might make them possible objects of knowledge for us?” (Bhaskar, 2015, p.25).* Questions like the above can encourage examining how things become observably/empirically manifested.

Closely related to the concept of abductive theorising is retroductive theorising, which generates a theory of qualitative observations retroductively, using inferences to theorise and test hidden mechanisms. Jagosh (2020b) argues that retroduction and abduction are two sides of the same coin.

"Abduction is a creative reframing of a phenomenon of interest into a conceptualisation that leads inquirers to explore the empirical world in new and innovative ways...retroduction is ontological in the sense of unearthing mechanisms that are part of manifested reality" (p.122).

Jagosh methodically implemented Pawson and Tilley's (1997) scientific research paradigm for research and assessment. Pawson and Tilley emphasise how realism principles might be used in intervention evaluation. According to their ideology, mechanisms are programme resources and how individuals react to those resources. These resources might be physical, financial, social, or emotional. Furthermore, systems are thought to be engaged or triggered in favourable settings to achieve results. This is known as the 'context-mechanism-outcome' arrangement (CMOc).

Mechanisms operate in contexts in the same way a seed germinates in soil. (Use my volcanic eruption scenario and illustration) Pawson and Tilley (1997) suggest that social mechanisms activate depending on how social, economic, geographic, and technical settings support such activation. Activating mechanisms in their empirically exhibited form indicate that they are linked to a specific setting (Jagosh, 2020a).

The literature has already discussed the inherent complexity of EA implementation in social action. Overcoming the deficiencies of the logic of induction and deduction can offer a causal explanation. In line with the pragmatic goals of Pawson and Tilley's realist methodology, retroduction strengthens knowledge to trigger deeply informed thinking necessary for addressing complex entrenched problems (2004).

Retroduction as a technique of inference is not a standalone action. It does, however, collaborate with inductive and deductive reasoning. As a result, retroduction research issues are classified as either deductive-reproductive or inductive-retroductive (Jagosh, 2020a).

Scientific discoveries are never identical to the whole of reality's 'empirical', 'actual', and 'real' characteristics. Realism accentuates the disparity between observable reality and our perceptions. Perfect alignment between these two facets is inherently unattainable. As such, the notion of

'approximation' becomes crucial within the paradigm of scientific realism. Through approximations, we endeavour to bridge the gap and cultivate a more accurate understanding of the complexities of reality. According to Pawson and Tilley (2004), Processes, for example, resist empirical capture; therefore, research needs proxy measurements that mimic actual mechanisms. Because of this dedication to approximation, the results of scientific realism investigation must accrue over time. The findings of one study must be considered theoretical and tested in succeeding rounds of research (Jagosh, 2020b).

Because EA management is complicated, retrodution may help solve difficulties resulting from this complexity. Applying retroductive theorising to realist assessment starts with evaluating effects and then moving backwards to explore the reality conditions required for such effects to appear. Realist programme theories should be built as assertions that either different contrast ways a programme may operate or present a collection of complementary propositions that form a complete picture of a situation.

According to Jagosh (2020b), retroductive theorising inspires research to distinguish between the intrinsic working of things and the conditional modifications always present in manifestation. In this way, knowledge can be improved by achieving ever closer approximations of the truth about how and why the empirical world manifests in the way it does.

3.5 Dealing with the social reality of EA programmes

Archer (1995, p.166) argues that organisational processes change or elaborate complex systems environments. These processes may preserve (morphotactic) the system's state or transform them (morphogenesis).

To make sense of the distinction between transformation and reproduction that preserve the system state, Archer proposes that these states exist in a pre-existing social form, a transformational stage when the change is in motion, and an after state when transformation has occurred. The transformed state may serve as an input starting point for other new social processes in an infinite chain of cycles

where the output of one function becomes the input. Therefore, the implications for social programme intervention should not ignore the impact of input baseline conditions and their relations.

The degree to which observed outcomes of programmes in social systems may be attributable to the input. A baseline that considers the pre-existing cultural, relational, agential, and structural circumstances must be established (Byng et al.,2005; p.89; Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012; p.183; de Souza, 2013; p.148).

By beginning with the context component in their context-mechanism-outcome configuration theory, Pawson and Tilley (1997) are consistent with the notion that: *"a 'position-practice system' pre-exists for subjects to slip into to engage in [activities] that transform or reproduce social structures"* (Bhaskar, 1978; 44; de Souza, 2013; p.147).

The practical implications for EA interventional programmes create a necessary condition for establishing critical success factors since they provide a process of 'knowing' whether the desired transformational state has been achieved. Conversely, critical failure factors may indicate that the EA program intervention merely reproduced or preserved the current state leading to unfulfilled outcomes.

3.6 The Aesthetic Value of EA Outcomes

Verstegen (2006) argues for aesthetic value considering the ideas of critical realism, and proposes ontological reflection relating to value. Verstegen quotes relativistic statements from Bourdieu (2005), Thompson (1979), and Wolff (1983) to explore a set of principles surrounding questions of beauty and artistic taste. They all explore how the nature of taste is historically and socially contingent. However, Verstegen notes.

"What was thought to be value turns out to be social effects wrought by conditioning. According to a critical realist perspective, however, this is a presumptuous step to take, for it might confuse the ontology with the epistemology of value. Even if we understand value imperfectly in the epistemological or transitive realm, it still might exist in the ontological or intransitive dimension"

(p.235). Versteegen discusses critical realism concerning ontology- the philosophical study of being. These two ideas are linked by MacLennan (1998), who conceptualised aesthetics by categorising absence as a supplement to presence.

Versteegen introduces the methodological principle of 'eliminative realism', which identifies and removes false causes of relativism, which is seen as judgemental. According to this principle, the purpose of studies that discuss the value is to “*attempt to eliminate sources of realism*” (p.324). He attempts to avoid the "epistemic fallacy" of analysing being in terms of our knowledge of being.

'Art' is meaningless unless we know what is expected of individual works and how they fit in their native contexts; broad categories comprise interdependent representations and practices. Thus, for example, when art exists in a society, it is sustained by real-world artistic practices with some compatibility.

Versteegen argues that judgment based on aesthetics risks being false given what is possible within a particular body of evidence or knowledge, which can be termed 'epistemically false'.

We continuously re-evaluate new or forgotten art forms in the Western art world; their reputation grows, and they become more valuable pieces to acquire and compose collections (i.e., the canon). It is helpful to approach these resurrections with scepticism, but we may identify particular themes if we consider the ontology of scarcity (p.342).

Using input from the actual world, these theories assist in investigating whether particular objects seem to have worth but do not have a specific value for one purpose but not another. According to Versteegen, this process of questioning entails critical realism since the so-called critical theory has progressively cut off the possibility of this inquiry.

Versteegen argues that we cannot do without a value category. It is best to apply value intuitively, naturally, and cognitively to be normative and guide understanding debates about aesthetics.

For example, Bourdieu's criticism of high culture becomes much more entertaining when we can root, even if imperfectly, the fabricated ideals of those he is exposing (p.343). These ideas are not directly

related to EA. However, they can help conduct enterprise analysis, design, planning, and implementation to develop and execute value realisation strategy successfully. Verstegen highlights applicable lessons in applying a 'self-accepting fallacy' of taking a relativistic approach without understanding this in terms of value. Therefore, accounting for relativism can help EA practitioners understand better value rather than taking an absolutist approach.

According to the principle of eliminative realism, we cannot apply a single standard of either aesthetic excellence (or excellence in EA). Still, we can analyse the value of individual situations to remove absolute relativism while acknowledging the problem of perspectival changes in different contexts.

3.7 Open Systems and Ambiguity in The Context Action of EA implementation In Programmes

According to Pawson (2006, p.31) and Pawson et al. (2005, p.23), cultural aspects are implicit within the structures of social systems in realist enquiries that are attuned to the context mechanism outcome configuration. Nevertheless, there is a propensity to exclude the impact of culture on organisational structure (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63).

The morphogenic approach to social action gives equal prominence to culture and structure as they facilitate understanding the dynamics of social action. Hence such understanding is curtailed if creativity and facts of social contingencies are excluded (Archer, 1995).

It is within these structures that EA interventions occur; as such, the impact of culture on mechanisms in the context of action should be considered. "*Causal laws . . . must be analysed as tendencies*" (Bhaskar, 2009, p.40). Power relates to the hierarchical position of the individual employees and teams for which ideational and tangible resources are assigned. Relational elements are not limited to duties, rights, and responsibilities, as is the focus.

According to de Souza (2013, p.150), in the mode of inquiry of engineered systems such as EA interventions, it is helpful to investigate duties and responsibilities with the overarching assumption of the impact structure, culture and agency since roles (people), rather than hierarchies, operate within

them. Success in an EA implementation programme may be determined by the competency of Architects and related teams conducting their proposed roles and responsibilities.

de Souza (2013) argues that accepted rights exist in the action context of social engineering investigations but are not examined or challenged. These social mechanisms are often transcendental and hidden (Bhaskar, 1978).

The distribution of power to different roles and positional hierarchies within an action context of EA implementations need to be scrutinised; because of the relations within the structure of organisations, their culture, agency, and the impact of these mechanisms on program outcomes (Bhaskar, 1978, p.45). Such relational conceptions, Bhaskar argues, enable investigations to be focused on the distribution of conditions of structural power in the action context, such as resource allocation to individual groups to function effectively. Focusing on structural power enables the intervention to assess the possibility of conflict of interest and different viewpoints that may motivate the programme transformation, invariant transformation, or reproduction of the structure that the program intends to change.

The impact of relations in the outcome of programmes in a social action context is those aspects of relations associated with duties, responsibilities, rights and power of individuals and teams. Relations may cause the program outcomes to be transformative, invariant or reproduce the pre-existing state of structures (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012; de Souza, 2013, p. 149).

This section demonstrated how the Mechanism Context Outcome configuration might implement an EA programme in healthcare organisations. According to Archer (1995), the relations between the components of the configuration mechanisms in the context of action and their outcome need to be internal and necessary to have emergent properties. It shows that modifying one component tends to affect others.

3.8 Essential Building Blocks for The Abductive Theorising Approach Used to Formulate the Conceptual Framework.

The building blocks of the conceptual framework for this research are based on the fundamental principles of Pawson and Tilley's Scientific Realism and arguments from (Jagosh Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh, 2020b), an abductive approach. The research enquiry commenced with an incomplete set of observations of the mechanisms of EA that are critical to successful outcomes and the challenges that may contribute to the failure of the EA programme from the literature that formed the basis for the theoretical framework. It then proceeds to the most probable possible explanation from inferences to the best explanation from the data obtained from the participants and the secondary reports. *“Abductive reasoning is commonly applied when there is lack of completeness, either in the evidence that the data provides, or in the explanation, or both” (Mukumbang et al., 2020, p.491).*

According to Mukumbang et al. (2020), abductive reasoning is essential in establishing and evaluating explanatory hypotheses, crucial tasks in realist evaluation.

3.9 The Context Mechanism Outcome Configuration (CMOc) Heuristic Applied to the Research

The research examines the mechanisms triggered in context and their influence on the outcome of EA programmes. The context-mechanism-outcome configuration (CMOc) is a heuristic, an original contribution to realist theory by Pawson and Tilley (1997).

This section describes the various definitions of the concepts used in realist research. The research relies on some definitions within the critical realist theory of social systems. An organisation's enterprise architecture is moulded by various stakeholders, including programme implementers, architects, clinicians, and others. Value creation in EA is interactive and economic activity since its implementation is about the desired transformation of the organisation's vision requiring funding.

For instance, the business architecture domain in phase B is composed of *"the product and [or] service strategy and the organisational, functional, process, information, and geographic aspects of*

the business environment, based on the business principles, business goals, and strategic drivers"(The Open Group,2018, Phase B: Business Architecture).

The importance of funding for digital transformation in the NHS is evident; insufficient funding can lead to failure. *"Recent investment in digital transformation has not been sufficient to deliver the national ambitions"* (NOA, 2020a, p.7). Consequently, a proposed socio-technological Enterprise Architecture is conceived as the fundamental characteristics or attributes of a software-intensive social system within its environment, as embodied in its components, connections, and guiding principles for design and evolution. Socio-technological Architecture is an interplay of individuals and institutions, agency and structure, micro and macro-social processes (social system) (Pawson & Tilley, 1997), and software-intensive influences in the system's design, and construction, deployment, and evolution (ISO, 2011). The focal point of this thesis relies on the above description of a socio-technological approach to architecting.

3.9.1 Context

Context refers to salient circumstances that are likely to enable or prevent the activation of the programme from promoting or depriving the expected outcomes mechanisms (Mukumbang et al., 2016b).

However, it may also refer to programme situations or aspects beyond programme designers' control — for example, people's motives, the organisational context, or organisational structures (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016). As such, context is not the setting for a site/study/case, as some have suggested, but the situation that activates or triggers specific processes in the programmes (Timmins & Miller, 2007; Dixon-Woods, 2014; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016).

Context is unhidden features (space, place, people, things) that exist prior to the Programme (Jackson & Kolla, 2012) that *"triggered or blocked the [EA intervention]; assuming that context operates at one moment in time and sets in motion a chain reaction of programme events"* (Greenhalgh & Manzano, 2021, p.1).

Context is also the *"relational and dynamic features that shaped the mechanisms through which the programme works or [does not work]; assuming that context operates in dynamic, emergent way overtime at multiple different levels of the [organisation as a social system]"* (Greenhalgh and Ana, p.1).

Context is *"pre-existing conditions for an intervention, consisting of multiple layers and (3) multiple factors, (4) enabling or disabling of the mechanisms, and (5) through its interaction with mechanisms potentially constituting new contexts "* (Nielsen, Lemire, and Tangsig, 2022, p.95).

Context *"pertains to the backdrop of programs and research" ... , and a mechanism is "the intended or unintended resources created by an intervention and the response to those resources (cognitive, emotional, and motivational) by participants"* (Jagosh et al.,2015, p.3).

Context is the condition of the space or location that fires the programme's mechanisms (Tilley, 2000).

Context may also refer to the circumstances of programmes or elements outside the control of programme designers — for example, people's motives, the organisational context, or organisational structures (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016).

Context is also *"the relational and dynamic features that shaped the mechanisms through which the intervention works, assuming that context operates in a dynamic, emergent way"...* *"at multiple different levels of the social system. These two context narratives have different"* (Greenhalgh and Manzano,2021, p.1).

Context is the *"observable features (space, place, people, things) that triggered or blocked the intervention, assuming that context operates at one moment in time and sets in motion a chain reaction of events"* (Greenhalgh and Manzano,2021, p.1).

Context classifiers have been proposed to simplify how context can be represented since context means several things; In this research, the CRAFTS model is proposed, confining contextual variables to those relevant to this research; Culture, Relation, Agency, Funding, Technology, and Structure. IT alignment is about technology. (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993,1999).

Context is "conditions relevant to the operation of the program mechanism, i.e., facilitates or hinders the program. Contexts consist of the broader historical, cultural, economic, geographical, and structural factors that exist at the time of the initiative, which includes individuals (the characteristics and capacities of the stakeholders); interpersonal (relationships); institutional settings (rules, norms, and customs) and infrastructural system (the wider social, economic and cultural setting)." (Sorinola et al., 2017).

In this research, context is the irreducible circumstance of the programme prior to or during the programme's implementation. Because of the prevailing conditions of the programme elicited from the relevant literature, the context has been classified into culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure. Definitions from previous researchers support this consideration—for instance, the action context of the programme (Archer, 1995; Bhaskar, 2009).

Mechanisms are the programme's stakeholders (human and institutional agency – reasoning and emotions) and the broader IT resources of the EA intervention and its associated digital transformation programme.

3.9.2 Mechanisms

A mechanism is what individuals or stakeholders do in response (reasoning) to the resources (of any sort) that a programme offers (Westhorp, Prins, Kusters, Hultink, Guijt, & Brouwers, 2011).

Mechanisms create outcomes only when triggered under specific contexts or conditions (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Westhorp et al., 2011; Astbury & Leeuw, 2010).

*Mechanism = EA programme's mechanism embedded in ADM processes and strategies
+ agency of stakeholders + IT resources*

"Outcomes are explained by the action of particular mechanisms in particular contexts, and this explanatory structure is put in place over time by a combination of theory and experimental observation" (Pawson & Tilley, p. 59). This research considers the mechanisms embedded in the

TOGAF ADM processes and strategies (The Open Group, 2018). It is noteworthy that EA may use other frameworks, processes, and strategies and their mechanisms.

A mechanism is what individuals or stakeholders do in response (reasoning) to the resources (of any sort) that a programme offers (Westthorp et al., 2011). Understanding how a clock works lies hidden inside the clock and not the clock's face unhidden (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Mechanisms create outcomes only when triggered under specific contexts or conditions (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016; Pawson and Tilley, 1997; Westthorp et al., 2011; Astbury & Leeuw, 2010).

3.9.3 Outcome

An outcome is an effect (Jackson & Kolla, 2012; Jagosh et al., 2015) of the digital transformation programme's activity related to the EA intervention. Outcomes may be direct or indirect and may also have ripple effects on the digital Programme (Jagosh, 2018).

Outcomes or effects refer to the researcher's interest in the evaluation study of the CRS to assess the intended EA initiative outcomes in the digital transformation measured as alignment or misalignment with the organisation's objectives and goals. These outcomes may be direct, indirect, intermediate, unplanned, expected, or unexpected (Jagosh, 2018).

"Outcomes and effects: Our interest in evaluating ... outcomes are not only in assessing intended outcomes (did the project succeed the criteria it set itself at the outset) but also [in] all the intermediate outcomes as well as unplanned and [or] unexpected impacts, of which we have noted many" (Jagosh et al., 2015, p.3).

"a phrase coded as an outcome if it described a result of the [technology] program or intervention" (Jackson & Kolla, 2012, p.343).

EA create outcomes that are beneficial to organisations. For example, project outcomes include *"Improved decision-making, project management effectiveness, improved business capabilities and improved IT platform and systems "(p.144). Organisational outcomes include "improved agility, competitive advantage and value" (Shanks et al., 2018, p.144).*

In this research, outcomes constitute stakeholder concerns within the purview of Enterprise Architecture, guided by the TOGAF framework, about the organisation's strategic alignment and its stakeholder needs and IT.

“Outcomes and effects: Our interest in evaluating ... outcomes are not only in assessing intended outcomes (did the project succeed the criteria it set itself at the outset) but also [in] all the intermediate outcomes as well as unplanned and [or] unexpected impacts, of which we have noted many” (Jagosh et al., 2015, p.3)

Outcomes or effects, therefore, refer to the researcher's interest in the evaluation study of the CRS to assess the intended EA initiative outcomes in the digital transformation measured as alignment or misalignment with the organisation's objectives and goals. These outcomes may be direct, indirect, intermediate, unplanned, expected or unexpected.

3.9.4 CMO Configuration

The CMO configuring is “a heuristic used to generate causative explanations about outcomes in the observed data” (Jagosh et al., 2015, p.3).

The configuration of mechanisms in context helps analyse the generative causation of these programmes' outcomes (Bhaskar, 1978; Jagosh, 2018). Jagosh (2018) argues that these configurations are only useful heuristics and do not provide a definitive method for theorising, modelling, and capturing generative causal pathways in their attempt to understand and explain outcomes.

CMO configurations are midrange theories and can be *“generated directly from the narratives of the practitioners” (Jackson & Kolla, 2012, p.342) ... within “programmes or across sites of implementation” (Wong et al., 2016, p.2).*

CMO configurations enable *“a deeper and more detailed understanding of for whom, in what circumstances and why the programme works” (Wong et al., 2016, p.2).*

Data collected *"may be used to develop, support, refute or refine the assignment of the conceptual label of C, M or O within a CMO configuration – i.e., in this aspect of the analysis, this item of data is functioning as [the] context within this CMO configuration"* Wong et al. (2016, p.12).

CMO configurations enable "evaluators to make inferences about the relationship of contexts, mechanisms and outcomes within a particular CMO configuration (Wong et al. (2016, p.12).

CMO Configurations enable *"inferences to be made about (and later support, refute or refine) the relationships across CMO configurations – i.e., the location and interactions between CMO configurations within a programme theory"* (Wong et al. (2016, p.12).

Data sources may rely on recurrent patterns of CMO configurations for analysis (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010; Brown et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2016).

In this research, CMO configuration is *"a heuristic used to generate causative explanations about [EA] outcomes in the observed data"* (Jagosh et al., 2015. p.3) from participants. The configuration of mechanisms in context helps analyse the generative causation of the programmes' outcomes (Bhaskar, 1978; Jagosh, 2018). The CMO configuration may constitute a failure (misaligned) or successful (aligned) outcome. The Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) configuration may lead to either a successful (aligned) or unsuccessful (misaligned) result. The associated mechanisms and contexts can thus be critical indicators of success or failure, their significance varying in accordance with the nature of the outcome. Consequently, understanding these interactions is fundamental in determining a given situation's trajectory and eventual results.

3.9.5 The Scientific Realist Perspective on EA Programme Outcomes

Pawson (2013) cites all his influences in his book the science of Evaluation realist manifesto in the first chapter. Those influences are from critical and scientific realism, with specific contributions from the philosopher and critical rationalist Karl Popper. Pawson refers to Karl Popper's assertion that for a theory to qualify as scientific, it must be susceptible to testing and capable of being proven false. An example is the assertion 'All swans are white', which can be falsified by observing a single

black swan. In light of this perspective, participants'/stakeholders' theories about Enterprise Architecture (EA) outcomes must be considered contextually valid without being subject to falsification. This underlines the importance of the contextual validation of theories in the field of EA as applied in this research, a process which diverges from the classical model of scientific falsification.

According to Bhaskar (1978), Scientific realism is a research approach based on the empirical enquiry of observable and hidden forces on generative causal mechanisms. Mechanisms are generative and have causal powers. These hidden mechanisms are within the TOGAF ADM and contribute to determining the outcome of the EA program initiatives. The primary objective of this research is to discern and elucidate the critical success and failure factors associated with Enterprise Architecture (EA) programmes. This endeavour is undertaken within the frame of reference provided by the relevant mechanisms and the specific context which precipitates their activation. Through this exploration, the study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the determinants of success and failure in EA programmes.

3.9.6 The Implications of the Longitudinal critical realist EA Programme

Jagosh (2018) argue that the impact of social action, the human resource effort, may not manifest immediately, especially in programmes with longitudinal pathways, a characteristic of complex and lengthy programmes. Therefore, obtaining longitudinal outcomes or attributing the human effort to observed outcomes is an inherent difficulty. He further argues that, in such circumstances, a favourable mode of questioning is retroduction, a mode of inference in which the circumstances of the programme are explained by proposing and recognizing mechanisms that can generate outcomes.

3.9.7 Ontological Depth of the EA Research

According to Pawson and Tilley (1997), all objects of scientific investigation are ontologically deep and should be explored retroductively to avoid the skewed optics of a flat (empirical) ontology.

According to Pawson and Tilley, "that which we can observe, including the most manifest and routine regularities, is produced by the operation of underlying generative forces which may not be immediately observable" (p.216).

Figure 3.1. The volcanic eruption analogy illustrates how hidden and observable mechanisms of EA are triggered in context to create EA programme outcomes.

Stratified ontology (Empirical, Actual and Real) of Critical Realism (Bhaskar, 1978) depicted within a Volcanic Eruption Metaphor. EA Mechanism are triggered in context to produce EA Outcomes.

Figure 3.1 uses the volcanic eruption analogy to illustrate the generative mechanism inherent in ontological depths. The mechanisms of generative forces that cause the volcanic eruption to lie latent and may not be observable until the appropriate condition cause an activation. Bhaskar (1978) argues that reality is stratified into the empirical, the actual and the real. The researcher argues that EA mechanisms in implementation may be unobservable, but their effects manifest as causal outcomes. Thus, the research seeks to uncover the generative causal pathways that best explain strategic EA alignment or misalignment.

3.9.8 Inference Sufficiency of the Investigation of The EA Case Study

Induction and deduction as stand-alone modes of inference and, in the absence of retroduction, are insufficient for analysing the depth of a phenomenon. Doing so creates the risk of scientific outputs that are ontologically flat.

Inferring universality from single events is flawed logically. For example, as Popper (1959, p.27) suggests, observing many white swans is no justification for inferring universality that all swans are white.

Lewis-Beck, Bryman, and Liao (2004) argue that inductive and deductive arguments cannot explain social outcomes. Jagosh(2020b) proposes retroductive theorising as a solution inference insufficiency of inductive and deductive approaches to research.

"Induction is to generate theory from evidence (i.e., studying one or many cases to generate generalised theories). Deductive approaches test theory against evidence (i.e., testing generalised expectations against specific cases). Inherent to both are inference deficiencies to which retroduction has been advocated for resolution" (Jagosh, 2020b, p.124).

The research aims to understand the mechanisms in the context of EA implementations in technology programmes and the associated outcomes inherent in their configurations. Some of the mechanisms may be hidden, as already argued by Jagosh. Given the underlying hidden mechanisms, retroduction thus bridges the gap between induction and deduction. It facilitates testing the programme theory underpinning the research and further allows the theory to be tested against the evidence derived from the participants and secondary data. Consequently, retroduction is an invaluable methodological tool in navigating the interplay between theory and empirical evidence, thereby enhancing the validity and depth of the research outcomes (Bhaskar, Danermark & Price, 2017; Danermark, Ekström & Karlsson, 2019).

The retroductive approach in this study intends to overcome the deficiencies of the logic of induction and deduction by offering the best inference to a causal explanation for successful EA implementation outcomes.

3.9.9 Mechanisms Latency and Activation in The Context of Programme Action

Mechanisms lay dormant (non-manifested existence) until activated. In their latent state, the mechanisms of the EA programme exist as possibilities or potentiality. They possess a form that may or may not be available for empirical observation in their activated state (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010).

Mechanisms are often hidden in a so-called black box. Some visible mechanisms are referred to as 'white box'.

When researchers refer to the 'black box problem', they usually view social programmes primarily in terms of effects without paying close attention to how those effects are achieved. The contrast between the black box problem and 'the white box problem' is that 'the black box problem' implies that social programs can be improved only by changing their design.

Astbury and Leeuw further argue that evaluating a white box mechanism involves attempting to 'unpack' a black box to inspect the programme's inner workings.

Mechanisms are latent and may be activated under the appropriate context. Mechanisms lay dormant in a state of "*non-manifested existence*" (Jagosh, 2020a, p.124) in the domain of the 'real', as suggested by Bhaskar's stratified ontology. Latent mechanisms, those not manifested in existence, latent or universal, are distinguishable from activated mechanisms. Activated mechanisms are context-sensitive and have generative causal properties.

[EA] Mechanisms are the programme implementers' resources and cognitive and emotional reasoning. The mechanisms are linked to the programme strategies and are triggered by the environmental constraints of the programme (Pawson & Tilley, 2004; Jagosh, 2020a). The mechanisms of interest are embedded in the Architecture Development Method, the TOGAF Architecture framework adopted for this research. The reasons for selecting the TOGAF ADM have been explained in section 3.19 of this thesis.

EA activities tend to moderate variables that have a causal relationship between the intervention activities and the EA resulting outcomes (Niemi & Pekkola, 2020; Schmidt & Buxmann, 2011).

“Value creation based on EA is a complex process, and therefore EA activities should be decomposed into value-creation mechanisms. EA efforts ... are likely only to be moderating variables, affecting the relationship between the activities and the resulting outcomes” (Schmidt & Buxmann, 2011, p.5).

The formulated EA theory in this research aims to unearth these activated mechanisms in EA implementation by interrogating the interview data from the participants.

3.9.10 Context-Mechanism Interaction is Necessarily Present in EA Management Action

Mechanisms are activated in context to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

“Without some conception of a generative mechanism at work, no attribution is justified” (Bhaskar, 2009, p.45). Activated EA mechanisms never activate in a vacuum. Adequately conducive contexts always trigger them. The context-mechanism relationship helps the researcher understand why things are how they are.

According to Pawson and Tilley (2004), the Context-Mechanism-Outcome configuration (CMOc) is derived from an amalgamation of various research inputs. The focus of the research question is shown in the research question RQ1 and RQ2. High-level in Figure 3.2 is the social-technical context of the EA implementation. It comprises concepts showing how the programme "activates mechanisms amongst whom and in what conditions, to bring about alterations in behavioural or event or state regularities" (p.9).

Figure 3.2. High-Level Conceptual Framework of Context (CRAFTS, ADM), Mechanism and Outcome Configuration of EA development. Theoretically elicited from Archer (1995), Bhaskar (1978), Dalkin et al. (2015), de Souza (2013), Jagosh et al. (2015), Pawson and Tilley (1997) and The Open Group (2018).

Entanglement of context is necessarily present in the empirical manifestation of activated mechanisms. The organisation’s vision informs the business drivers, causal factors for the EA programme and its IT strategy (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999). The vision serves as the input to the EA intervention, defining the business or stakeholder concerns for which the implementation is intended to align. Context is applied in a limited form, selected based on the review of the relevant literature, the CRAFTS model—strategies, actions and implementation mechanisms within the TOGAF framework. Context-sensitive mechanisms may be triggered to create program outcomes or dem-regularities (Pawson & Tilley, 1993; Jagosh et al., 2015). Outcomes are the organisation’s capabilities and competencies created by the EA implementation or transformations (The Open Group, 2018)

3.9.11 Outcomes Dependency on the Approximation and Accumulation of Triggered

Mechanisms in EA Implementations.

Some definitions of enterprise architecture have been provided in the literature review section.

The Henderson and Venkatraman strategic alignment model is an approach for organisations to align their objectives and information technology.

The organisation's vision is the bedrock of its objectives and requirements for technology (The Open Group, 2018; Gartner, 2021; Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999). The purpose of EA is to achieve alignment between the objectives and goals of the organisation and its IT (Lange, Mendling, and Recker, 2016; Tamm et al., 2011; Niemi and Pekkola, 2020; The Open Group, 2001; Hope, Chew & Sharma, 2017). Accordingly, successful outcomes represent the effect of the EA programme where the objectives and requirements of the organisation's stakeholders' expectations have been met. Outcomes may not comply with programme processes or contractual agreements by technology systems providers. Conversely, failure outcomes represent unalignment between the organisation's objectives and EA outcomes. Therefore, the CMO configuration offers a path to stakeholder engagement and incorporates stakeholder feedback or concerns into implementing the programme's architecture.

“NHS-wide IT programs have generally failed to meet expectations, though evaluations have usually overlooked longer-term progress. Realizing a long-term health IT strategy may be impeded by [the] volatility of the implementation environment as organizational structures and relationships change” (Price, Green, & Suhomlinova, 2019, p.188). “Alignment between incremental health IT strategy and dynamic structure is an under-researched area” (p.188).

Accordingly, EA outcomes are the outputs of EA implementations that create successful or failed alignment between the organisation's vision, objectives, goals, and information technology. These propositional formulations of vision are the organisation's strategy, business strategies, IT strategies, and business requirements (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999) that create action-oriented

outcomes. In the programme, the organisation's vision is represented by the requirements and concerns of stakeholders and the Architecture views and viewpoints (ISO, 2011, [3.5,3.6.3.10]).

"Stakeholders of a system have concerns with respect to the system-of-interest considered in relation to its environment. A concern could be held by one or more stakeholders. Concerns arise throughout the life cycle from system needs and requirements, design choices and from implementation and operational considerations. A concern could be manifest in many forms, such as in relation to one or more stakeholder needs, goals, expectations, responsibilities, requirements, design constraints, assumptions, dependencies, quality attributes, architecture decisions, risks or other issues pertaining to the system" (ISO, 2011, 4.3.2).

Since human actors implement EA in organisations within a social system, the proposed socio-technological perspective provides an architecture framework more aligned with social and technology. The CMO configuration EA transformational and the CRAFTS models suggest a socio-technology approach to how triggered mechanisms in context create EA outcomes. Human interaction is a necessary component of the EA process.

The models also show the connection between programme activity and the ensuing transformations or outcomes. The models provide an approach to managing the TOGAF ADM, including the deliverables, mechanisms, context and where they are triggered in the TOGAF ADM.

From a socio-technological perspective, the research considers outcomes as a conflation and abstraction of the social and the technological phenomena in social systems, the *"effect of the program or intervention [on stakeholder concerns]" (Jackson & Kolla, 2012, p.343)* and the result of *"conceiving, defining, expressing, documenting, communicating, certifying proper implementation of, maintaining and improving an architecture throughout a [programme's] life cycle" (ISO, 2011, [3.1])*. Therefore, the success or failure of outcomes depends on stakeholder perceptions, individual agency, and the collective agency of the teams and organisations.

Mechanisms elude empirical detection. Scientific procedures may produce and test proximally similar mechanisms, which should be scrutinised continuously in an accumulative approach to knowledge advancement (Jagosh, 2020b). [EA] programme outcomes can be intermediate, final, or proximal process outcomes. As such, some outcomes may be precursors to the direct outcomes of the EA programmes.

Jagosh further argues that scientific realism is defined by the belief that our idea about reality is distinguishable from actual reality, and the two can never be aligned. Social and physical reality exists independent of our awareness of it. As such, scientific inquiries are not the same as the sum of what Bhaskar (1978) argues to be a stratified reality, the empirical, the actual and the reality.

According to Williams (2018), Programme outcomes of realist scientific enquiry do not seek absolute truth in the ontological sense but attempt to explain and commit to a plausible direction towards causal pathways, a process of accumulation, for theory development and testing that increases knowledge and intelligence on the phenomenon.

"Cumulation is not a matter of achieving a series of studies with reliable, replicable, and universal applicability. The social world will always conspire to throw up changes, differences, and apparent anomalies from trial to trial in any field of programming" (p.116). Because mechanisms evade empirical capture, measurements are merely approximations of actual mechanisms, hidden and only activated in context to produce outcomes.

3.10 Social-Technological Conflation of Software-Intensive and Social-Intensive

Systems in EA Management

Previous sections have demonstrated embedding social and technology in social programmes. Accordingly, in this section, a socio-technological architecture is proposed. The gap in existing research on understanding EA mechanisms has been stated. These mechanisms are agency initiated, individual and institutional, as their purpose is to address stakeholder concerns and occur in software-intensive systems.

A System *"is a group of interrelated and interacting elements that form a complex whole"* (Montuori, 2011, p.414).

According to the ISO standard, a system is *"man-made and may be configured with one or more of the following: hardware, software, data, humans, processes (e.g., processes for providing service to users), procedures (e.g., operator instructions), facilities, materials and naturally occurring entities"* (ISO, 2021, system).

A Software-intensive system is "any system where software contributes essential influences to the design, construction, deployment, and evolution of the system as a whole" to encompass "individual applications, systems in the traditional sense, subsystems, systems of systems, product lines, product families, whole enterprises, and other aggregations of interest" (ISO, 2019).

Therefore, the analysis of EA mechanisms elicits the elements of propositional formulations about social and technological or software-intensive systems, a socio-technological architectural perspective.

The philosophical foundations of the method can usually be found in the nineteenth century, most notably in English sociologist and philosopher Herbert Spencer and French social scientist Émile Durkheim. Spencer advocated for a unified social system in which society constantly evolved toward a more complex level of perfection.

On the other hand, alternative types of social systems theory argue for a fundamentally different view of social development. Society is diverging toward greater complexity and structural difference. Through structural changes marked by differentiation in internal complexity, society and its constituting institutional microcosms demonstrate adaptability to their external environment. This dynamic process highlights the inherent capability of societal structures to evolve and adjust in response to the changing nuances of their surroundings.

On the one hand, society may be seen as a whole organism via the prism of the many processes that contribute to its function and survival. According to an alternate viewpoint, social systems stabilise

not because of any rational design for global existence but simply because they operate. How adaptation occurs, or how changes in the system's structure link to the system's continuing operations, is an important aspect of social differentiation (Gibson, 2019).

Here, context becomes a significant determinant of socio-technology, software-intensive systems within a social environment. Technology depends on society, its generative mechanisms, and its structure. According to AlQudah, Salloum and Shaalan (2021), the purpose is to fulfil stakeholder (society) needs such as storing, managing, and exchanging the clinical data.

Society is "the totality of social forms or . . . or the totality of social structures or generative mechanisms. . . or the totality of human relations within which praxis occur" Bhaskar (2009, p.129).

Gibson argues that "Social systems are related to society as a complex arrangement of elements, including individuals and their beliefs, as they relate to a whole." Gibson, 2019, para.1).

In social realist theory, adopted for the research, a social system is *"the interplays of individual and institution, of agency and structure, and of micro and macro social processes"*. Pawson & Tilley, p.63). Supporting Giddens (1977), Archer defines a social system as the *"visible pattern generated from agents transforming the modalities of structural properties to produce this patterning"* Archer (1995, p.96). Archer argues that Giddens's definition characterises structural integration, 'relations between groups', at the systematic level, distinguishable from individual action or agency.

Archer further argues that individual action is a continuity of a social system since *"the integration of social systems is something which is constantly reproduced by the actions of agents"* (Archer, p.96).

Consequently, when individual actors mirror the behaviours of agents within a digital transformation programme, it signifies the active involvement of social systems. This reflects the complex interplay between individual actions and broader systemic processes, emphasising the role of social structures in influencing and shaping the dynamics of digital transformation initiatives. A social system may also be defined as a collection of individuals or an organisation, society, or community of practice

with the ability and capacity to produce, utilise, and exchange understanding and information (Wenger 1998). As defined by Kroeber and Parsons (1958), a social system is a relational and collaborative system characterised by the dynamic interplay between individuals and groups. This system embodies the multifaceted interactions and mutual dependencies within the social sphere, reinforcing the complexity of social relations and their impact on collective behaviour. A system has input, output (outcome), people, processes, constraints, and stakeholder concerns and viewpoints. A social system may emerge as a team or community, expanding or contracting over time to achieve the desired mutual purpose (Gill, Alam, & Eustace, 2014).

"The key difference between the traditional static system and social system is the "dynamic" nature of the social system structure and behaviours" (p.4). Social systems can be applied to a dynamic emergency Electronic Health Record system environment and define healthcare management as a social system.

Gill, Alam, and Eustace, 2014) reported that traditional mainstream architecture frameworks such as TOGAF 9.1 and Zachman lack social architecture support. They suggest that Social Architecture is an emerging paradigm.

Some frameworks have provided support for Social Architecture. For instance, the Gill Framework (Gill, 2013) provides the requisite support for social architecture. However, their scope is limited to social technologies like Twitter, Facebook, and Yammer involving a single case. Social architecture is the *"fundamental concepts or properties of a social system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and principles of its design and evolution. Social architecture refers to the social structure, behaviour, culture, knowledge, and opinions of communities of people" (p.3).*

Stakeholders in digital transformation initiatives have concerns about the system of interest compared to its surroundings. One or more stakeholders may share a concern. Concerns develop during the system's life cycle due to system requirements and demands, design decisions, and implementation and operation factors. Concerns can present themselves in various ways, including concerning one or

more stakeholder demands, objectives, expectations, responsibilities, requirements, design restrictions, assumptions, dependencies, quality attributes, architecture decisions, hazards, or other system-related difficulties (ISO, 2011).

Accordingly, a socio-technological approach acknowledges the centrality of technology and the contribution of traditional architectural models, hence their relevance to providing a software-intensive architecture perspective. A unified approach supports software and social intensity, given that technology and society co-exist in time and space as systems.

Accordingly, EA implementations in healthcare organisations are social programmes involving stakeholder collaboration. Stakeholders are individuals, Architects, decision-makers, Clinicians, Programme Managers, users, and other stakeholders who may contribute as agents of change.

"Social programs are undeniably, unequivocally, unexceptionally social systems. They comprise, as with any social system, the interplays of individual and institution, of agency and structure, and of micro and macro-social processes" (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63).

From the socio-technological perspective of software-intensive systems, individuals and their beliefs relate to the whole and embody the architected system. ISO defines a service as an *"activity or set of activities, provided for the benefit, or to meet the needs, of a consumer (ISO, 2008, p.3)* and a consumer as an *"individual member of the general public who is the end-user of services or service-related goods" (p.2).*

In the preceding discussion, the case has been made for implementing Enterprise Architecture (EA) as a service within a social system. As characterised here, this system is a composition of technological elements and human agency. This framework emphasises the confluence of human and technological factors, advocating for their integration in the successful management of EA.

3.11 Transformations in Social Systems and How They Are Situated in EA

Transformations

Enterprise Architecture is a socio-technological process. The patterned interrelationships between individuals, groups, and institutions in social systems form a coherent whole. (Giddens, 1987). The interactions that occur repeatedly are social processes (Giddens, 1987). EA involves social interactions; it aligns objectives and goals determined and architected by human agency (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999). It creates outcomes that address stakeholder concerns (ISO, 2011).

Bhaskar (1979) proposed a model of social activity based on the Aristotelian view that any productive activity requires both an efficient and a material cause. In this model, the material cause is pre-existing social action, and social action is how this pre-existing reality is either reproduced or transformed by structure and agency. Social action has the "*causal power of things*" (Bhaskar 1978, p.50).

According to Matt, Hess and Benlian (2015), organisations in almost every industry have undertaken several initiatives to investigate and invest in new digital technologies. It typically entails changing core company activities, influencing processes and technology, as well as organisational structures and management philosophies. To handle these complex shifts, organisations must create management practices. An important technique is to develop a digital transformation plan that acts as a primary idea for integrating the coordination, prioritisation, and execution of digital changes inside an organisation.

EA aims to achieve the strategic alignment between its objectives and goals and IT when conducting its digital transformation activities (The Open Group, 2018).

Digital transformation is a process in which digital technologies cause disruptions, eliciting strategic responses from organisations seeking to change their value-creation pathway while monitoring structural changes and organisational barriers that influence these processes' positive and negative outcomes (Vial, 2021).

Hence, within socio-technological systems, transformations are essentially an amalgamation and abstraction of an organisation's social and digital changes and their corresponding Enterprise Architectures. This convergence reflects the intricate interplay between social dynamics and technological advancements, encapsulated within the overarching framework of socio-technological Enterprise Architecture. This perspective underscores the integrated nature of social and digital transformations and their mutual influence on organisational systems and structures.

Enterprise Architecture is the *"fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and principles of its design and evolution"* (ISO, 2011, *Enterprise Architecture*). In social systems, elements and relationships include social action, structure, and agency, drawing on the Transformation model of social activity. Mechanisms are contextually triggered to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Therefore, mechanisms within this socio-technological space are triggered in the context of social and technological action to create outcomes.

The transformation model of socio-technological action is illustrated in **Figure 13.1**. Superimposing the Transformational Model of Social Action in EA programme action, the Morphogenetic/static cycle, the Context-Mechanism-Outcome Configuration, The TOGAF ADM and the Strategic Alignment Model., a superimposition of the TAMS model (Bhaskar, 1979) and the CMO configuration model (Pawson & Tilley, 1997), the morphogenetic/static cycle (Archer, 1995, 2005) and the TOGAF ADM (The Open Group, 2018).

Analytical dualism is morphogenetic/static dualism. Structure predates action(s) that modify it, and structural elaboration postdates such acts (Archer, 1995).

Realism accepts and incorporates pre-existing structures as generative mechanisms, interactions with other things in a stratified social world, and the unpredictable but explicable outcomes of these interactions in society's open system (Archer, 1995). In EA, 'other things' include technology itself.

Unintended consequences and structural conditioning exist within organisations (Bhaskar, 1979, Archer, 1995). Previous cycles of social structures feed into existing structures and contexts (Archer, 1995). For instance, legacy technologies within the organisation create pre-existing Architecture structures and previous outcomes, as in T1.

T2 is characterised by production because of social interaction and programme activities. Superimposing generative mechanisms triggered in context create regularities. Social action or praxes results in adaptive structural change (variant transformation, T3) (morphogenesis) or reproduction, maintaining a system that has a given form or state of the organisation (T4), morphostasis (Archer, 1995, 2005). Accordingly, the conflation and abstraction of architecture and social praxes result in socio-technological transformations (morphogenesis) or reproductions (morphostasis) within organisations (Archer, 1995). Disentangling Social systems from Enterprise Architecture is to ignore human agency as a driver of it, its praxes of stakeholder concerns management. Thus, digital transformation and its embedded EA are socio-technological. This argument forms the basis for arguments in the rest of the thesis. According to Essien (2013), to be systemic and pragmatic, a reference model should include a detailed explanation of the problem it is intended to solve and the concerns of the stakeholders who must see that problem resolved. TOGAF, FEAF, and DODAF are reference models.

Instead of encouraging the development of multiple perspectives on EA based on stakeholder concerns, the Zachman Framework believes that only six discrete perspectives are possible with six distinct roles: planner, owner, designer, architect, programmer, and stakeholder (Zachman, 1987).

3.12 The EA Context-Mechanism-Outcome Configuration Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework relies on arguments by Pawson and Tilley (1997) that mechanisms are triggered in context to create outcomes. **Figure 3.3** outline some examples of mechanisms, context, and outcomes. The subsections elaborate on these concepts.

Figure 3.3 The realist evaluation of the EA programme depicting the Mechanism-Context-outcome configuration of the EA programme theory, adapted from Pawson and Tilley (1997), Pawson (2006), Gilmore, McAuliffe, et al. (2019), and Jagosh (2020b).

“The theoretical/conceptual framework defines the key concepts in your research, proposes relations between them, and discusses relevant theories based on a literature review” (Scribbr,2020, [What is [a] theoretical framework and example?]).

A conceptual framework is a linked network of concepts. (Jabareen, 2009, p.50) The researcher uses concepts as the building blocks of the conceptual framework for this research study. According to Deleuze and Guattari (1991), *“Every concept has components and is defined by them” (p.51)*. These components of concepts or the consistency that define them are *“distinct, heterogeneous and, yet, not separable” (p. 19)*. Every concept has an irregular contour, and history contains originations from other concepts and is related to them.

Concepts are comprehended relative to their constituents’ components, adjacent concepts, and the problem they intend to resolve. Deleuze and Guattari further argue that concepts must be regarded as *“the point of coincidence, condensation, or accumulation of its own components” (p.20)*.

Social phenomena are linked to several bodies of multidisciplinary knowledge and are complex. According to Jabareen (2009), qualitative approaches to research are sufficient for investigating complex phenomena. Multidisciplinary phenomena are characterised by components identified from previous inquiries providing an internal structure beginning with observations and interview questions as a basis for analysis.

In this research, the proposed CMO configuration conceptual framework or initial, middle-range programme theory is built on contextual structures of social action, padding these with the ADM mechanisms and organising these structures to fit together to produce outcomes.

Realist assessments often begin with identifying initial programme theories (IPTs) that explain "how, why, or whom, and under what conditions the programme intervention may work." For example, it might be based on evaluations of literature and documents, as well as critical informant opinions of programme architects or facilitators (Gilmore et al., 2019; Van Belle, Marchal, & Van Wyk, 2016b; Pawson & Tilley, 1997, 2004; Mukumbang). According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), Conceptual frameworks have an ontological character and knowledge of how things are. Concepts also have epistemological character, the nature of reality. The methodological supposition is associated with constructing the conceptual framework and evaluating what it can tell us about reality.

The conceptual framework is developed through qualitative analysis of the extant literature (Jabareen, 2009, p.51). The process commences with the organisation's vision, which serves as the determining factor for the requirements of the Enterprise Architecture (EA) programme.

Organisation VISION determines the requirements to be fulfilled by the ADM MECHANISMS, which are triggered in SOCIAL-TECHNOLOGICAL ACTION (CRAFTS) to produce longitudinal OUTCOMES (ATUTIT). **Figure 3.4** Shows these concepts gleaned from the peer-reviewed academic literature and organisational reports to define the contextual boundaries using key attributes, the global standard (The Open Group, 2018) for EA used in Healthcare technology programme design, TOGAF and the Mechanism-context-outcome configuration (Archer, 1995; Bhaskar, 1978;

Dalkin, Greenhalgh et al., 2015; de Souza, 2013 Jagosh et al., 2015; Pawson and Tilley, 1997; The Open Group, 2018).

Figure 3.4. Generative Causal Pathways of EA Mechanisms in the Context of Social Action. Abstracted from Archer (1995), Bhaskar (1978), Dalkin et al. (2015), de Souza (2013); Jagosh et al. (2015), NHS Digital (2021a), NOA (2020a), Pawson and Tilley (1997) and The Open Group (2018).

The organisation's vision informs its requirements (objectives and goals) which determine the CMO configuration. Drawing on the extant literature, culture, relations, agency (Archer, 1995), funding (NOA, 2020a), technology (NOA, 2020), and structure are essential contexts (The CRAFTS Model) within which the mechanisms of EA are triggered. TOGAF classifies the domain within these mechanisms are triggered as business, information systems (data and applications) and technology architectures (The Open Group, 2018). The triggered EA mechanisms within the digital transformation programme (CRS) seek to reconfigure these domains to fulfil the organisation's vision

by Strategically aligning its objectives, goals, and IT (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999). mechanisms, triggered in context, may create outcomes or transformations in social systems (Archer, 1995; Pawson & Tilley, 1997). These transformations may align with the organisation's strategic intent, and the related mechanisms are characterised as success factors. Their triggered mechanisms lead to successfully aligning the organisation's objectives and goals and its IT.

Conversely, transformation may reproduce the action context resulting in misalignment. Therefore, the related triggered mechanisms constitute failure factors since the organisation's objectives and goals are unmet. **Figure 3.4.** depicts a vivid of the complexity that is inherent in social and technological interactions in programme activities.

3.12.1 Building the Conceptual Framework for the EA Programme Intervention

The conceptual framework for this research is constructed drawing upon an extensive body of multidisciplinary peer-reviewed literature. Enterprise Architecture (EA) theorisation, Business Management, and Sociology are the selected sources. By amalgamating insights from these diverse disciplines, the framework aims to offer a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the research subject, thereby reinforcing the validity and depth of the study. In addition, the TOGAF Architecture development methodology originates in collaborative work from industry practice (The Open Group, 2018).

The Context-Mechanism-Outcome configuration model emanates from research in critical realism (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The CRAFTS model (culture, relation, agency, funding, technology, and structure) is the social context of programme actions. Archer (1995) and de Souza (2013) argue that such contextual factors necessarily exist in the context of social action and profoundly impact how mechanisms are triggered to create programme outcomes.

The argument is already that social action in programme implementation leads to transformation. Transformation necessarily exists in social action through transformations or invariant transformations where the pre-existing action context is reproduced (Archer, 1995).

A conceptual model/framework outlines *"the key factors, constructs, or variables, and presumes relationships among them"* (Miles & Huberman (1994, p.440). The formed conceptual model is more than just a collection of ideas; it is a construct of three notions, CMOc, TOGAF ADM mechanisms and the CRAFTS context of social action, which play an integrated role Socio-Technological investigation of EA programme implementations.

The conceptual framework provides explanatory power through an interpretative perspective of the social reality of EA implementation. The framework also provides an explanatory causal pathway for EA outcomes. According to Jabareen (2009), a conceptual framework does not provide a causal or analytical setting but a perspective for interpreting and understanding the social reality of the action context.

Therefore, the trio of the conceptual framework proposed provides "soft interpretations of intentions" of participants in the EA programme implementation in this research (Levering, 2002). The conceptual framework explains but does not predict the outcomes of the EA programme implementation.

The *"concept of freedom"* (p.38) informs us that human behaviour can be anticipated and explained by the idea of external influences trapped in cohesion. Thus, human action can be appreciated but not anticipated.

The conceptual framework does not intend to be deterministic and does not enable the prediction of outcomes. Instead, the proposed conceptual framework provides explanatory power for generative causal pathways of the EA mechanisms in social action to produce transformation in EA outcomes. The proposed conceptual framework draws on sources of information from the various disciplines, technology, business management, sociology, and philosophy, to form empirical data for subsequent analysis of the conceptual framework in the later phase of this research.

The purpose of metasynthesis and systematic synthesis of qualitative research results is to construct and enhance theories from disparate bodies of knowledge. Furthermore, it aims to develop new

interpretations to reach a consensus within the EA area of research (Nelson, 2006; Sandelowski et al., 1997; Jensen & Allen, 1996).

According to Sandelowski (1993) and Paterson et al. (2009), metasynthesis has hermeneutic and comparative characteristics that enable the researcher to expand their interpretation beyond existing qualitative research. Metasynthesis also enables the researcher to generate ideas, metaphors, and concepts. These ideas and concepts may be relational (Noblit & Hare, 1988; Nelson, 2006; Campbell et al., 2003).

The advent of artificial intelligence could profoundly impact the configuration of context mechanisms outcomes of EA programmes using network theory approaches, which is out of the scope of this investigation for outcomes optimisation. **Figure 3.4** shows a configuration similar in structure to a neural network as applied to network theory.

Borgatti and Halgin (2011) define Network theory as *"the mechanisms and processes that interact with network structures to yield certain outcomes for individuals and groups"* (p.1168). Ultimately, qualitative *"research aims to describe and explain a pattern of relationships, which can only be done with a set of conceptually specified categories"* (Mishler, 1991, p. 431).

3.12.2 Hypothesis

The research hypothesis is to generate and explain the critical success and failure factors of EA interventions through the lens of context mechanisms and outcomes configurations of the programme. Specifically, the study limits context to culture, relations, agency, funding, technology and structure as theories in the conceptual model derived from the extant literature related to the programme under study. The test of the hypothesis is embedded in the generated CMO configurations or programme theories elicited from participant narratives (De Brún & McAuliffe, 2020; Wong et al., 2103; Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The reality of the reproduced mechanism is examined empirically, and the hypothesis's empirical adequacy is maintained compared to alternative explanations (Mader, 2018). This does not suggest that there are no alternative explanations. Such alternative explanations are

possible with variations in context or circumstances. The explanation is based on “*what works for whom and under what circumstances*” (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63).

According to Mader, “*If one hypothesis of a mechanism capable of explaining a given contrastive demi-reg of interest is produced, experience suggests that there will usually be many such hypotheses in contention*” (Mader, 2018, p.12).

“*A hypothesis that might be tested about realist review, therefore, is that reviews should align with specific intervention theories. Insofar as they concentrate on these very general levers, reviews can be ‘recycled’ to inform all manner of future programmes*” (Pawson et al., 2004, p36). Thus, realist evaluation is about generating hypotheses and evaluating such CMO configurations.

The synthesis includes evidence for outcomes, evidence to support the presence of hypothesised mechanisms, evidence that those mechanisms produce those outcomes, evidence that contextual factors exist, and evidence that contextual characteristics impact whether or not the mechanisms activate (Wong et al., 2013). CMO configurations are therefore generated from Participant theories of the programme's mechanisms.

3.12.3 Boundary Conditions: The TOGAF ADM, Mechanisms-Context-Outcome configuration (CMOc) and The Social Context of Culture, Relations, Agency, Funding, Technology and Structure (CRAFTS)

According to Makadok et al. (2018), although theory can be generalised under certain conditions, it is not universally applicable. A practical approach must have boundaries of applicability outside of which is less valuable. “*Boundary conditions are levers that define when theory works or does work*” (Makadok et al., 2018, p.1537).

The levers for this research are Socio-Technological and lie within the boundaries of The Open Group’s architecture development method (ADM) (The Open Group, 2018) as the technological framework on one side and the Mechanism-Context-Outcome configuration proposed by Pawson and

Tilley (1997). The realist approach to evaluation is underpinned by a social action context of culture, relations, agency, and structure, argued by Archer (1995) and elaborated by de Souza (2013).

The ontological foundation of the theory applied in this research framework is based on a critical realist perspective in Bhaskar's transformational model of social action Bhaskar (1978).

3.12.4 Retrodution in the development for development of EA vision

Retrodution is the process of uncovering causal forces. It is generally applied in realist theory testing in a context-mechanism-outcome configuration interaction to help construct predictive capacity (Jagosh, 2018).

Mechanisms are activated when the conditions for their observable outcomes are conducive. The process involves retrodution, unearthing causal forces for the outcome generation by these mechanisms. It is the fundamental basis for realist theory testing and accounts for developing foresight within an ecosystem of context-mechanism interactions (Bhaskar,1978; Pawson, 2013; Jagosh, 2018).

Solutions to Complex EA programmes in healthcare can be optimised to develop theory, model the virtual future state, and investigate outcomes related to longitudinal manifestation characteristic of complexity.

Applying a realist methodology is a significant potential contributor to foresight development. It provides a comprehensive lens through which to view and understand complex phenomena, thus optimising the leverage programmes have in addressing intricate, entrenched, and multifaceted emerging problems. This approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of the interplay between various elements, making it instrumental in tackling complex challenges effectively and efficiently (Jagosh, 2018).

As realist methodology is best suited to resolving strategic alignment, EA programmes aim to resolve complex and multifaceted problems.

An appropriate research paradigm must account for the unfolding complexities to gain adequate foresight (Pawson & Tilley, 2004). Accordingly, unfolding complexity may present a hostile dispensation on programme outcomes. It is, therefore, essential that such effects are acknowledged. Realist methodologies are particularly suited to developing such foresight to manage the associated complex and emerging problems (Jagosh, 2018).

3.12.5 Retrodiction develops foresight for the EA Programme outcomes.

Creative theorising becomes a requisite in developing the anticipated target outcomes of program interventions. Therefore, programmes' mechanisms can be modelled and realistically assessed through the associated generative causal pathways (Bhaskar, 1978).

3.12.6 The Hidden Reality of EA Outcomes in a Realist Ontology

Hidden reality accounts for observable manifestations. In realist ontology, reality may be hidden below the observable empirical threshold and subjective within a given configuration of context and mechanism interaction; These mechanisms may lay dormant until the necessary trigger conditions are activated. Consequently, longitudinal outcomes are not immediately discernable or predictable due to the extensive sequence of actions involved in the implementation process. The elongated timeframe and intricate nature of such processes inherently obscure the final outcomes, acknowledging they may be intermediate outcomes, making it challenging to forecast them accurately in advance. This emphasises the inherent complexity and uncertainty in predicting long-term outcomes in such contexts (Pawson, 2013; Jagosh, 2018).

Defining outcomes is complex due to the absence of a shared understanding of duties (Iyamu, 2019). How the organisation defines the concept of outcomes is based on the development and implementation domains of EA, which shape the overall EA programme. The interconnectedness and interdependencies between various agents or participants, bear considerable influence on the focus and deliverables of Enterprise Architecture (EA) development and implementation. These relationships, essentially, mould the direction and outcomes of the EA process. It underscores the

complex dynamics in such projects, highlighting the critical role of stakeholder interactions in shaping the trajectory and ultimate success of EA development and implementation.

“This is complex in that the relationships and connectivity have no guiding principles or formula. As a result, they are subjectively defined based on personal interests rather than organizational objectives. This situation is hugely influenced by lack of clear definition of roles and responsibilities”
(p.5)

3.12.7 Realist Causal Explanation for EA Programme Implementation

Context impacts the outcomes of programmes through the mechanisms; how agents respond and interact with resources available to the mechanisms of these programmes are riddled with intended and unintended observable consequences of their outcomes. These context-mechanisms interactions in each time horizon generate outcomes that can neither be predicted nor modelled with a reliable degree of certainty and are naturally emergent (Pawson, 2013; Jagosh, 2018).

3.12.8 The Impact of Context on EA Mechanisms and Outcomes

Figure 3.5 shows a high-level view of the underpinning theories of the conceptual framework used in the research—the Trio of CMO configuration Conceptual framework for The EA programme.

Figure 3.5. A high-Level view of the Components of the Conceptual Framework. Mechanisms are triggered in context to create programme outcomes.

ATUTIT : Aligned Transformations, Unaligned Transformations, Invariant Transformations

CRAFTS: Culture, Relations, Agency, Funding, Technology, Structure

TOGAF ADM: Preliminary, Vision, Business Architecture, Information Systems Architecture, Technology Architecture, Opportunities and Solutions.

- Aligned Transformations, Unaligned Transformations, Invariant Transformations.
- CRAFTS: Culture, Relations, Agency, Funding, Technology, Structure.
- TOGAF ADM: Preliminary, Vision, Business Architecture, Information Systems Architecture, Technology Architecture, Opportunities and Solutions.

3.13 The Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) Configuration Conceptual

Framework

The context-mechanism-outcome configuration (CMOc) is a 'trio of explanatory components' used as a critical realist evaluation approach proposal by Pawson and Tilley (1997, p77) and Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012). The approach focuses on the extant context of action and its related operational mechanisms, offering a broader scope of application beyond social programmes.

Figure 3.6. Conceptual Framework, abstracted from Archer (1995), de Souza (2013), Pawson and Tilley (1997), and The Open Group (2018).

Figure 3.6 is the backbone of the conceptual framework for this evaluative research. It is a propositional formulation of how [EA] Mechanisms (F4) are triggered in context to generate outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). It is an abstraction of the context-mechanism-outcome (Pawson & Tilley, 1997) conceptualisation of how the digital transformation programme that embeds EA initiatives might work.

Mechanisms of the [EA] programme are triggered in context (F3) to create demi-regularities (F5) and regularities which constitute outcomes(F6, F8) (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). EA implementation enables the alignment of the business/organisation’s vision (F1) and IT, embedded in its business strategy with IT (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 199; Saat et al., 2010; Alaeddini et al., 2017; Goepf & Petit, 2017; Zhang, Chen, & Luo, 2018; Malta & Sousa, 2016; Pasaribu, Hakiki et al., 2019). Outcomes (F6, F8) are the outputs or business capabilities enabled by the EA programme’s implementation. The organisational vision or strategy drives the EA programme’s action (The Open Group, 2018; Diefenthaler and Bauer, 2014; Tamm et al., 2011).

Archer (1995), collective, constrained decision-making is the underlying mechanism that creates all social outcomes. Archer (1995), the causal outcomes never conform to their intended purpose stating that society is patterned and re-patterned by deliberate action. Accordingly, while some EA action may achieve their intended purpose, create successful outcomes, and are aligned with the organisational vision and strategy, some may be misaligned, create failed outcomes, and relinquish the benefits of the digital transformation programme.

Mechanisms combine resources offered by the social programme understudy and stakeholders' reasoning in response (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Mechanisms will only trigger under certain conditions, providing a context + mechanism = outcome heuristic, shown in **Figure 3.6**, as a principle to realist evaluation.

Mechanisms *"intervene between the delivery of program service and the occurrence of outcomes of interest"* (Weiss 1997, p.46). *"Mechanisms are not the programme service but the"* (p.3) responses it activates from stakeholders and the resulting outcome (Dalkin et al., 2015).

Mechanisms are observable and unobservable but have enduring properties with generative causal powers (Bhaskar 2014, p.26).

The context mechanism outcome configurations (CMOc) are a methodological contribution from Bhaskar's ontology of the transformational model of social action with support from Archer's social theory of the morphogenic approach (1995). In realist social theory, *"meaning has to be understood, it cannot be measured or counted, and there is always an interpretive or hermeneutic element in social science"* (Sayer, 2000, p.17).

People's social environments give 'directed guidance' regarding good ideas and actions (Archer 1995, p.213). Upon understanding the temporal context and cultural significance of a given social practice, we can start to comprehend the alternative actions available to individuals and their motivations for acting in particular ways. This understanding provides valuable insights into the complex web of human behaviour and decision-making processes deeply embedded within their socio-cultural

context. This, in turn, aids in fostering a nuanced understanding of human actions and their underlying motivations within a specific social practice. This understanding forms the bedrock of the rationale for selecting the Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) configuration and theoretically leans towards viewing Enterprise Architecture (EA) as a catalyst for social change. This argument draws on the notion that social change and reproduction occur in society (de Souza, 2013). By situating EA within a socio-cultural framework, this perspective seeks to elucidate the complex interplay between EA and social transformations, thereby enhancing our comprehension of the dynamics and implications of EA interventions.

According to de Souza (2013), adopting a realist approach to evaluating interventional programmes in organisations concerned with healthcare delivery or other social domains is appropriate because such institutions are a micro-scaled version of the wider society. As such, organisational transformations because of program interventions can be understood and explained similarly to the connectivity between the societal and the individual influences of the context, mechanisms, and outcomes of these program interventions.

The CMOC emphasises a social context construct as an extension of social programmes. The social context is defined as *"are relatively enduring and are what social programmes aim to transform (rather than reproduce) by activating various structural, cultural, agential and relational mechanisms to produce various outcomes"* (de Souza, 2013, p.142).

This definition is more appropriate for EA interventions as they occur within a social context. However, not all mechanisms may appear within a social program. The causal explanation of program intervention within a social context has explanatory power in their embedded mechanisms before introducing such programmes. Bhaskar's transformational model of social action provides a framework for conducting a realist evaluation of programmes within a social context Bhaskar (1978). Outcomes are the organisational or business capabilities (F7) enabled by the EA implementation within digital transformation programmes. EA implementation action may produce or create

outcomes aligned (F6) or misaligned (F8) with the organisation's objectives and goals. In this research, unaligned and misaligned are used interchangeably to mean the organisation's expected objectives and goals are not achieved by the programme's action.

3.13.1 The Archery Analogy of EA Programme Implementation CMO configuration

The archery analogy serves as a fitting illustration for the configuration of an Enterprise Architecture (EA) programme's mechanisms. This analogy encapsulates several challenges the programme intervention faces, mainly dictated by a complex mix of socio-technological forces. These forces, comparable to an archer's pull on the bowstring, are determined by the agent's reasoning and material resources - such as technology services and funding (Jagosh et al., 2015; Jagosh, 2020b; Pawson and Tilley, 1997).

Upon release, akin to the execution of a programme effort, the arrow may hit the target (meeting organizational objectives and goals) or deviate off-course. The intended target signifies the expected outcomes the programme intervention strives to accomplish.

The central aim of this conceptual framework is to illuminate the underlying mechanisms of EA within digital transformation programmes, explore the routine influence of context on these mechanisms, and discern whether these impacts lead to successes or failures. Drawing on the archery analogy, this involves finding the optimal combination of a finely crafted bow and arrow (resources) and a skilled archer (reasoning and competencies).

Success factors encapsulate the circumstances that trigger mechanisms leading to successful outcomes, represented by hitting a bullseye. In contrast, under specific conditions, the activation of certain mechanisms can lead to failures, symbolized by an off-target shot. These scenarios may be deemed as failure factors.

This research aims to utilise the discerned Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) patterns as a resource to assist programme implementers in strategically planning and evaluating future programmes. Two key considerations are paramount. First, the conditions under which the arrow

(programme intervention) is launched can be variable and unpredictable due to the fluctuating nature of context, resources, and reasoning. Secondly, the precision and effectiveness of the aim (programme's implementation) are contingent upon the quality of the bow and arrow (resources) and the expertise of the archer (agency skills, interpretation, and competency).

3.13.2 The TOGAF ADM Mechanisms of EA In the Context-Mechanism-Outcome

Configuration

Various activities or processes occur within the TOGAF ADM, for which the research findings may need to be reconfigured. According to Pawson and Tilley, evaluation studies that state whether a change occurred due to the implementation of a programme should not be commissioned or accepted by policymakers. They are worthless, as they contain no information on what to do and what not to do in the future. Accordingly, the conceptual framework seeks to inform Architects of the phases of the TOGAF ADM where the elicited CMO configurations are likely to be delivered. It will enable Architects and other programme implementers to reconfigure these processes for better future outcomes.

The researcher has drawn on extant literature to support the need for Socio-Technological (technical) considerations of EA because of its role in determining the outcomes of EA programmes (Hope, 2015). The researcher has also discussed the TOGAF architecture development method as a widely used framework for EA implementations. In the literature review, the researcher discussed the lack of coverage of the mechanisms of the TOGAF ADM. In the Steps for developing architectures using the TOGAF ADM, the researcher has also discussed the absence of sociological considerations. Nevertheless, de Souza (2013) and Archer (1995) remind us of the preponderance of social action in programme execution.

Figure 3.7 is a high-level framework for how EA programmes might be reconfigured in triggered mechanisms under the antecedent condition of a social action context. The diagram depicts how the research question RQ1 and RQ2 may be answered involving enacting the TOGAF ADM, the

CRAFTS model of the social context of culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure mechanism-context-outcome configurations. These elements are discussed in much detail later in this thesis. Input to the programme for action processes is the business vision, business drivers, causal factors or stakeholder concerns and the organisation's strategy (The Open Group, 2018). Hidden and unhidden mechanisms in the current state architecture are triggered in the context following programme action (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The significant contextual factors surrounding the programme as culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure, as elicited from the extant literature. These contextual factors surround the triggered mechanism's regularities and demi-regularities that create outcomes. The outcomes represent the future state of the organisation's architecture, new capabilities and competence because of the programme implementation. When input strategic drivers (objectives and goals of the organisation, are aligned with the outcome throughout the programme's activities, the programme would have been deemed successful. When there is no alignment, then the programme is deemed a failure. These phenomena of triggered mechanisms in the context that create specific outcomes constitute a configuration.

Figure 3.7. shows a detailed programme theory or conceptual Framework of CMO configuration for Implementing EA based on the TOGAF ADM.

Figure 3.8 shows an expanded view of the TOGAF ADM within which mechanisms are triggered. Phases A to Phase H, discussed in the earlier chapters, outline the strategies for delivering the mechanisms.

Figure 3.8. The CMO configuration programme theory of EA Implementation

Figure 3.8 is a generated synthesis of the initial programme theory of how the TOGAF EA Framework mechanisms are embedded within the Organisation’s EA. It is within this framework that CMO configurations may be configured on the TOGAF ADM mechanisms, the generative causal pathways in the Context (CRAFTS) of EA Implementations using the realist paradigm Mechanism-Context-Outcome Configuration Pawson and Tilley, 1997; Archer, 1995; de Souza, 2013; Jagosh, 2020b; The Open Group, 2018).

3.13.3 Socio-Technological Conflation in EA: TOGAF ADM Mechanisms in Social Context of Action

Socio-technological conflation creates EA complexity. Organisational size significantly influences the adoption of EA by public sector organizations and EA complexity (Ahmad, Drus & Kasim, 2020). Organizations are inherently complex due to the interdependence of their constituent pieces, many

stakeholders, and the dynamic nature of internal and external events. Organizations face ever-increasing levels of complexity and uncertainty (Lapalme, 2012).

In this thesis, the Socio-Technical Systems (STS) concept plays a significant role. Originating in the post-World War II era, STS theory is an approach to complex organizational work design that recognizes the interaction between people and technology in workplaces (Trist & Bamforth, 1951). It was first developed by the Tavistock Institute in London in the 1940s and 1950s as they studied coal miners in the UK. Their seminal papers provide crucial insights into the intricate relationship between societal needs, technological advancements, and the corresponding changes in work structures.

One of the foundational ideas of STS is that organizations are not merely technical systems but complex interactions of technical and human elements, each with its unique characteristics and goals. The STS perspective emphasizes optimizing the joint performance of the social and technical system, aiming for increased productivity and human satisfaction (Emery & Trist, 1965).

In relation to developing the CRAFTS model presented in this thesis, STS theory offers a valuable lens. Figure 3.9 depicts how the EA programme's social and technical aspects are brought together and regarded as interdependent components of a complex system.

Organizational change programs often stumble due to a narrow focus on technology, neglecting the intricate interdependencies within the organization (Dery, Sebastian, & van der Meulen, 2017). Initiatives focused predominantly on technological changes often fall short, as they inadequately consider the interconnected nature of various organizational facets. A technology-centric approach frequently leads to failure, underscored by a lack of understanding and management of organizational complexity. Similarly, Raja et al. (2013) underscore the importance of an integrated approach in change programs to achieve customer satisfaction.

Figure 3.9. Socio-Technological Enactment of Complexity in EA Using the TOGAF ADM Mechanisms, inspired by de Souza (2013), Archer (1995), The Open Group (2018), and reports from NHS Digital.

Mechanisms are contextually triggered to create programme outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The research focuses on the mechanisms embedded in TOGAF ADM, a widely used standard framework for architecting (The Open Group, 2018). Various theories and a review of reports related to the CRS programme suggest that culture, relations, agency (de Souza, 2013, Archer, 1995), funding (NOA, 2020a), technology (NOA, 2020a; NHS Digital, 2021a) and structure (Archer, 1995) are importance contextual influences on the mechanisms that are triggered in the programme’s activities to create regularities or transformational outcomes. **Figure 3.9** depicts the components and interactive forces that may occur within the programme’s mechanisms and the surrounding circumstances. It seeks to

illustrate the complexity of interactions within socio-technological programmes. Some mechanisms may be hidden whilst others are unhidden with causal generative power (Pawson & Tilley, 1997) and, therefore, not captured by informants as reported. Similarly, context cannot be fully understood as they are transient and surrounded by events that are complex, emergent, and dynamic (Pawson & Tilley; Jagosh et al., 2015; Jagosh, 2020b).

3.13.4 Propositional Formulations of a Conceptual CMO configuration For the EA Programme

Drawing from existing literature and the NHS's Clinical Reporting System (CRS) reports on circumstances unique to the technology programme; notably, identifying pertinent contextual variables influencing a phenomenon is a complex task (Marchal et al., 2012). Figure 3.10 presents a proposed formulation of a possible Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) configuration. This figure highlights the significant and noteworthy contextual factors of interest derived from the current literature, their associated propositional mechanisms (including resources and agential reasoning), and the effects or outcomes. Reports from the National Audit Office (NOA, 2020), NHS Digital, and the King's Fund were especially pertinent in this context.

“There is no simple recipe for making these decisions—sound judgment is called for. However, more formalized guidance on how to select the most relevant contextual factors in a systematic and transparent manner would surely be of value” (Nielsen, Lemire, & Tangsig, 2022, p.95).

When it comes to identifying salient contextual conditions, Prashanth et al. (2014) observed that when viewing social reality as an open systems world with open boundaries of what is considered context, there is no end to the rival explanatory possibilities that could potentially be included as part of examining the contextual conditions of the intervention. Consequently, whatever contextual factors are judged to be the most relevant and important to provide must be prioritised. For example, the context of culture comprises the circumstances of the CRS programme's aspects of the NHS culture in the triggered mechanisms during the digital transformation. These mechanisms may be ideas or propositional formulations about culture. These propositional formulations form the bedrock of the

conceptual framework through the CMO configuration, and the participant data is analysed. The outcomes are transformations or reproductions of the organisation's cultural features related to the propositional formulations of culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012).

Figure 3.10. Shows the Propositional formulations ‘network of outcomes’ for CMO configurations of the case study, adapted from Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012, p.181).

Propositional formulations about context, which are found to be relevant, culture, relations and agency and structure are abstracted from Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012, p.181). For Funding, propositional formulations about context were extracted from the NHS organisational reports, especially from the UK NOA, and extant literature about the programme. For technology, propositional formulations (Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012) are about context extracted from relevant literature, such as the NOA (2020) and NHS Digital review reports about the programme and academic literature. For Example, on the propositional formulation of technology, theories have

been drawn from the following authors; Wimelius et al. (2021), Guo, Li, and Gao (2019) and Yeo (2002).

The concept of a propositional formulation of the ‘network of outcomes’ is adapted from Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, (2012, p.181), theoretical contributions from Archer (1995), de Souza (2013), and review reports about the case under study on culture, relations, agency, and structure from NOA (2020a, 2020) and NHS Digital (2021a, 2021b). On Funding, the researcher draws on the theoretical literature the review reports about the funding context of the programme, notably NOA (2020), NHS Digital (2021b), McKenna, Dunn, Northern, & Buckley (2017), Triggler (2022), NOA (2020a), Wimelius et al. (2021), and Archer (1995), leading to the programme’s transformation or reproduction of the action context (Organisational Culture, Relation, Agency, Funding, Technology and Structure). In technology, theories from Wimelius et al. (2021), Yeo (2002), and Guo, Li, and Gao (2019) regarding the renewal of technology are used in analysing the case studies.

For instance, in **Figure 3.10**, propositional formulations about technology are circumstances of triggered mechanisms – ‘established versus renewed usage, deliberate versus emergent renewal practices, inner versus outer renewal practices, comprises of aspects of technology’ (Wimelius et al., 2021). These mechanisms, triggered in the context [of technology], create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012) that are transformational features of the organisation’s vision. The strategic objectives, goals and stakeholder concerns, a reflection of the vision, are aligned with IT (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993, 1999; Bradley, Pratt, Byrd, Outlay & Wynn, Jr., 2012; The Open Group, 2018; Ross, Weill, & Robertson, 2006; Bhattacharya, 2018; Abunadi, 2019). For instance, these goals and stakeholder concerns may include adoption pace, fragmented systems, sharing, siloed systems, volatility, efficiency data deluge, value, benefits, reliability, efficiency, interoperability, integration, interoperability, and legacy IT (NHS Digital, 2021b).

3.13.5 Culture as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms

In conclusion, an organisational social action view emphasises social interdependence and interaction in controlling social intervention-endangering behaviour. It proposes mechanisms by which environmental structures influence cognitive action strategies, objectives, and cogent activities critical to sustaining the organisation's target outcomes (Archer, 1995). The mechanisms of EA implementation in healthcare are considered in the context of such social action.

3.13.5.1 External and Organisational Culture in the Context of EA Implementation

According to Hofstede et al. (1990), organisational culture is the symbols, Heroes, rituals, values, and practices embedded within the organisational analogous to structure, control, and strategy. They argue that culture is *"is (1) holistic, (2) historically determined, (3) related to anthropological concepts, (4) socially constructed, (5) soft, and (6) difficult to change"* (p.286).

Organisational culture is a crucial issue of collaboration in developing the EA. Banaeianjahromi and Smolander (2019) argue that organisational culture is essential in cooperation and collaboration in EA development. The proficiency of employees in initiating effective communication and collaboration, alongside their ability to stimulate and actively contribute, plays a significant role in shaping the organisational culture.

In their finding, they argue that *"lack of communication and collaboration in EA development, 'Organisational culture and 'clarity in EA development process' as causes and 'Personnel's trust' and 'organisation loses its competitive edge' like effects"* (p.886). The results are partly consistent with the existing literature and improve understanding of practitioners' obstacles in developing environmental agreements.

The social context of action and culture are interrelated. Willmott (2000) states that culture is related to theories, beliefs, values, and arguments. According to him, the structure, culture, agency, and relations impact an institution's agent's transaction and operations. These are communicated to all

collectively in the institution by organising various discursive strategies, documents, symbols, and characterizations, which may be initiated by informants internal to the context or external informants.

3.13.6 Relations as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms

According to Bhaskar (1978) and Collier (1994), society is relational. One is a teacher because of their relation to a learner. Learners' existence is a necessary precondition for the existence of teachers (Collier, 1994, p.140). The relationship between structure and agency argument is “*widely acknowledged to lie at the heart of sociological theorising*” (Archer, 2000, p.1). It occupies this prominent place due to the fundamental nature of the connection it tries to investigate, namely that between people, the origins of agency in the social environment, and the social relations or structures that emerge as a result of their interaction (agency and structure) (New and Carter, 2005). Structural and cultural factors ultimately emerge from people and are efficacious only through people, then social forms are reified (make something abstract more concrete or ‘real’) (Archer, 2000, 4).

The social contexts that stakeholders “*inhabit provide them with directional guidance in terms of ... reasonable .. “beliefs and courses of action”*” (Archer 1995, p.213). Stakeholders as agents and actors are shaped, though not confirmed, by their structural circumstances. Although the two may exist in ontological independence, social beings and actions are sustained by relations.

The independence of an individual sense of reality and agency can harmoniously sustain an intervening social fact (p.149). Archer (1995; p.143) argues that relations strive and may not necessarily be exercised by the related entities but by the potential that one entity can regulate and influence another entity's actions.

3.13.6.1 Relations in the Context of EA Implementation

Individuals in pre-existing social systems are assigned roles to perform specific duties and responsibilities with associated expectations. They get rights and authority along with their role and duties. Rights are linked to the position held by the individual, and powers come along with the "position" provided by the social system. The individuals have the ideations and materials as

resources at their command. Duties and responsibilities are assumed concerning structure, culture, and agency. The role rather than the position one occupies matters the most in the current social system. There is no singular linear relationship between the mechanism and the outcome. The notion of emergence in realist social theory addresses the interlink and the interaction.

3.13.7 Agency as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms

An individual's structural and cultural circumstances within a social system influence their actions or inertia. They do so to consider intent and self-monitoring of the interventions of their worldview (Bhaskar, 1978).

According to Giddens (1984), agency occurs when individuals can observe their experience and justify their actions. Individuals have agency when they can act freely and make their own decisions. People as agents and actors are influenced, though not determined, by their structural situations. People select what they do, but they do it from a set of structurally and culturally created options – which they do not choose. *'Causal power or social forms are mediated through social agency'* (Bhaskar 2014, p.26). *"Bodies have properties and powers of their own and are active in their environment, which is broader than "society's conversation"* (Archer, 2000, p.4).

According to social realism, social science research analyses social phenomena to find underlying causal processes. Good explanations explain patterns in occurrences by showing what causal mechanisms are at work at different levels of the social environment. Some of the distinguishing characteristics of humans that are essential to Agency include self-consciousness, reflexivity, intentionality, cognition, and emotionality. As reflexive creatures capable of sophisticated symbolic communication, humans may devise programmes, plan, set goals, and follow interests. This fundamental agency capability, the power to maintain or alter reality, relies not only on the attribute of self-consciousness. People may collectively exert influence solely by their numbers, a feature known as demographic agency.

Structure and agency are irreducible due to their different features and capacities. This doubts the mutually constitutive 'structuration' viewpoint of structure and agency. It also involves rejecting the structuralist position since we cannot get at a convincing explanation for structures without an active concept of agency, that is, without being able to ask who is doing or not doing what to whom and why. Recognizing persons as passive puppets, cultural dopes, or discursive effects is impossible (Carter & New, 2004).

For reasons to be admissible as having causal powers, the concept of the agency must be sacrosanct as an imperative for reasoning. The generative causal mechanisms Bhaskar proposes are fundamental reasons agents assign for action or inertia that tip the balance of events to create the known outcomes.

These reasons are the circumstance that prevailed to generate the outcomes (Bhaskar, 1978).

Agents, he argues, fall categorised into positions of practices that exist in social structures. These positions are designations of the social positions the agents hold. Positional behaviour patterns and their interrelationship with society are keys to social reproduction and transformation.

Social structures may be limited to individual action but do not determine how individuals act.

In explaining the actions of agents in realist enquiry, Sayer (1992, p.112) and Pawson and Tilley (1997, p.207) propose a sequence of social practices or actions agents engage in when programming within a social context as follows:

1. Observe the action.
2. Understand reasons individuals give for action or inertia.
3. The researcher should find the rules within the context of the social action and make sense of the reasons advanced by agents (Participants).
4. Identify the extant social structures that generate the formal and informal rules and how they influence agent actions and perceptions.

According to Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012), the client or agent is a factor in realism appraisal. Activating agency-related processes in the action context affects the beliefs and justifications people use to justify their actions or inactions in the action context.

Human agency is an essential and indispensable determinant of socio-technological enterprise architecture outcomes since human actors perform their activities to meet stakeholder needs.

“Structure and agency constitute different levels of stratified social reality; each possesses distinctive emergent properties which are real and causally efficacious but irreducible to one another” (Archer, 1995, p.1).

Accordingly, Enterprise Architecture exists as a social reality and is not transcendental. Humans architect software-intensive systems to meet human needs in social systems. Because of human agency, social reality is unlike any other. It contrasts with natural reality, which is defined by self-sufficiency. It is distinct from natural/transcendental reality, defined by self-sufficiency. Its existence is not contingent on humans, a truth unaffected by our human capacity to intervene and alter the natural world. Society is even more unlike transcendental reality, in which divinity is self-sustaining and unchanging at our command, traits unaffected by human intervention. The nascent is self-sustaining and unchanging at our command, neither of which is damaged by human intervention (Archer, 1995; Bhaskar, 2009).

The ADM process involves social change. Social systems are embedded in Enterprise Architecture and core to the TOGAF enterprise architecture description. For example, the business architecture domain operates to achieve business goals and respond to the strategic drivers in the Architecture vision of people (agency) (The Open Group, 2018). Drawing on the definition of service by the Cambridge Service Alliance, human agency in EA implementations may therefore be characterised as a service.

According to the social cognitive theory of causality, human agency is based on a triadic codetermination; personal, social, and environmental determinants. Because personal factors play a

role in the casual mix, individuals have a hand in moulding events and the paths their lives follow. Human functioning results from this three-way interaction between intrapersonal factors, individuals' activities, and the external forces impinge on them (Bandura, 2018).

"To be an agent is to intentionally produce certain effects by one's actions"(p.130).

Agentic qualities play a critical role in psychosocial functioning, with three primary features: foresight, self-reactivity, and self-reflection. Individuals drive and steer themselves via foresight by developing action plans, adopting objectives, and picturing the potential consequences of their activities. Because a future condition does not exist materially, it cannot cause current behaviour. Anticipatory self-guided behaviour is envisioned objectives and anticipated consequences rather than an unrealised future state. People may transcend the dictates of their current environment via forethought, shaping and regulating the present to actualise desired futures. When applied to critical issues over the long term, a forethoughtful perspective gives direction, coherence, and meaning to one's actions (Bandura, 2018).

In Self-reactivity, agents are not only planners and thinkers in advance; they are self-regulators. Individuals self-regulate their behaviour inside a self-governing system. They accomplish this by establishing behavioural criteria against which to measure their performance. They react positively or negatively to their evaluations, depending on how closely their behaviour conforms to their accepted criteria (Bandura, 1991).

Agents in Self-reflectiveness are not just individual self-regulators but also self-examiners of their functioning. They think about their capacity to overcome barriers, the legitimacy of their thoughts and actions, their ideals, and the importance and morality of their endeavours. At this greater degree of self-reflection, individuals face conflicts between multiple courses of action and opposing principles and pick one choice over another.

The capacity for meta-cognitive reflection on one's capacities, ideas, and acts is the most distinctively human essential feature of the agency that impacts how they conduct their lives. The form is

constrained to individually controllable fields of action. However, individuals lack direct influence over the social and institutional factors that shape their daily lives in many realms of functioning. They rely on socially mediated proxy agency in these instances. They employ this agency style by persuading those who possess the resources, expertise, and ability to act on their behalf to achieve the desired outcomes. Many of the things individuals desire are only possible via collaborative effort. Collectively, they combine their knowledge, abilities, and resources and act cooperatively to determine their destiny. Participants in this multi-agent paradigm of collective agency establish cohesion of effort toward a shared goal (Bandura, 2018).

3.13.8 Funding as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms

Funding refers to monetary resources given to an organisation for a particular purpose, event, or activity (Cambridge Dictionary, 1995). CMO configurations comprise context-related aspects of the programmes' triggered mechanisms to create outcomes. These outcomes are transformations or may be invariant or reproductive features of the programme (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012, p.181). Accordingly, the Funding context in CMO configurations comprises the funding aspects of the mechanisms related to established funding approaches in the EA programme. These include funding availability, funding deficits, and funding delay, as gleaned from the NHS technology funding patterns (see literature review on NHS funding in Chapter 2).

The funding context is a propositional formulation about budgeting, funding deficits, access to funding, funding allocations, spending efficiency, and value for money. According to McKenna, Dunn, Northern, & Buckley (2017), funding is a challenge in digital transformation programmes within the NHS. The NHS is experiencing the most protracted and severe slowdown in funding history, and it has raised concerns about the sustainability of its funding model (McKenna et al., 2017). The UK Parliament, which is responsible for approving and allocating funding for technology within the NHS, have observed that the NHS has overseen several years of deterioration in cancer care and non-emergency hospital services in England.

Enterprise Architecture (EA) mechanisms are activated within digital transformation or technology programmes operating in an environment with funding challenges. Consequently, the researcher posits that the funding context is crucial when analysing the mechanisms triggered, which subsequently lead to digital transformation and EA outcomes.

According to McKenna et al., accounting to the Public Accounts Committee of the House of Commons (PAC) reported that services had begun to deteriorate even before the epidemic. In the report, the PAC argued that the critical benchmarks for funding had not been fulfilled and that the epidemic had aggravated the situation. However, Ministers stated they were spending additional funds and expanding the capacity to treat patients to alleviate the backlog created (McKenna et al., 2017).

Over six million individuals – one in every nine– are presently on a hospital waiting list, the highest. It includes patients awaiting knee and hip replacements. Only around two-thirds of patients with urgent cancer begin therapy within the desired time frame of 62 days. Patients awaiting knee and hip replacements target have not been met. Meanwhile, only around two-thirds of urgent cancer patients begin therapy within 62 days. Cancer referrals have decreased by between 240,000 and 740,000 since the epidemic began. Cancer referrals have decreased between 240,000 and 740,000 since the epidemic began (Triggle, 2022).

According to NHS (2018), the UK parliament affirmed a 1.25 per cent ringfenced levy from April 2022 to fund £36 billion for health and social care across the UK. Over the expenditure review period, £8 billion was dedicated to the elective backlog. Taxes generated £5.4 billion for social care reform over three years, including £500 million for worker skills, credentials, and well-being. The more extensive social care system received £1.7 billion to increase quality and integration. NHS local organisations receive £3.6 billion. While this financing helps stabilise the NHS, fundamental problems remain. Whether it is adequate, what is allotted for medical education, and how much is required to meet the (unknown) COVID-19 expenditures. Whereas the NHS accounted for 27% of

daily government expenditure in 1999–2000, predictions suggest this will climb to 44% in only three years. According to Trigg, the extra cash was required to help the NHS reduce the large backlog of patients awaiting treatment caused by the epidemic. NHS Providers and the NHS Confederation have pointed out the funding gap and the 'impossible set of options' regarding patient care.

Anderson (2004) and Anderson and Shemilt (2010) argue that a realist evaluation approach is appropriate for determining 'what works, or does not work, for whom, under what circumstances and why' (Pawson & Tilley, 1997) regarding a programme's funding strategies, costs, and cost-effectiveness. Drawing on this argument, Anderson and Hardwick (2016) argue that since hidden and unhidden mechanisms (reasoning and resources) play a vital role in realist evaluation, it implies that economic aspects of context, mechanisms, and outcomes are consistent within the approach.

Economic evaluations are about the various evaluation approaches with cost-benefit and cost-effectiveness (Anderson & Hardwick, 2016; Drummond, Sculpher, Claxton, Stoddart, & Torrance, 2015; Layard & Glaister, 1994). Anderson and Harwick argue further that those economic evaluations compare the cost and value of programmes. It should involve a cost-effectiveness comparison between doing nothing and programme interventions. They further caution that economic and realist evaluations differ, arguing that realist methods try to create generalisable causal explanations of specific programmes, policies, or services. In contrast, economic assessments measure or estimate the cost-effectiveness of establishing a particular programme.

The funding context in this research seeks to provide a causal explanation of the cost and cost-effectiveness of the programme and not as an economic assessment. The funding context does not seek to estimate the programme's cost-effectiveness. It provides a generalisable causal explanation of the impact of funding on its mechanisms and outcomes.

3.13.9 Technology as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms

CMO configurations comprise context-related aspects of the programmes' triggered mechanisms to create outcomes. These outcomes are transformations or may be invariant or reproductive features of the programme (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012, p.181).

Wimelius et al. argues that technology renewal is vital on both a practical and theoretical level. According to Wimelius et al. (2021), Three contradictory pressures drive technology renewal initiatives. These are the settings of "established versus renewed technology usage," "deliberate versus emergent renewal practises," and "inner versus outer renewal".

As a result, in CMO setups, the technology context includes the technical features of the program's procedures. These features are connected to the program's results created by established vs renewed technology utilisation, intentional versus emergence renewal techniques, and inner versus outside renewal practices.

The way organisations work has been substantially altered by digital technology (Tilson, Lyytinen, & Sørensen, 2010; Galliers & Sutherland, 1991). To stay up with technological changes, organisations must constantly create and adopt new digital capabilities and applications in comparison to their current software-intensive systems, as well as regularly upgrade their underlying digital platforms and infrastructures (Nambisan, Lyytinen, Majchrzak, & Song, 2017; Hanseth & Lyytinen, 2010).

3.13.9.1 Established Versus Renewed Technology Usage

Wimelius et al. (2021) suggest that technology renewal research determines how to replace an organisation's technology backbone and issues that straddle many research streams. This regrettable dispersal adds to several difficulties; restrictive and incoherency in existing knowledge provide limited insights into the characteristics of technology renewal. The technology context seeks to resolve these issues by focusing on the paradoxical tensions within the programme.

These paradoxical technology tensions are applied contextual drivers in analysing the programme's triggered mechanisms that create its outcomes (Agarwal & Helfat, 2009).

Renewal technology usage is seen as a process of change that involves the *"replacement of attributes of an organisation that has the potential to substantially affect its long-term prospects"* (p. 282).

Accordingly, the researcher defines Socio-technology renewal as the process through which organisations attempt to replace their social structure and software-intensive systems to realise their vision.

3.13.9.2 Deliberate Versus Emergent Renewal Practices

Deploying digital platforms requires the organisation to change its technology, structures, processes, and people concurrently (Robey, Ross, & Boudreau, 2002). Because of this, these implementations are linked with lengthy commitments and significant funding; these components increase the likelihood of failure and make programme trajectories challenging to reverse once launched (Barker & Frolick, 2003).

Technologies are interpretively malleable. The necessary integration of technology with human agency and its use results in unanticipated differences between planned and actual practices (Orlikowski, 1992). Similarly, adopting new technologies is frequently lengthy and unpleasant (Wessel et al., 2020; Lyytinen and Damsgaard, 2001). Therefore, integrating complex digital technologies requires specific implementation approaches, top-level leadership assistance, and open communication lines (Nah & Delgado, 2006).

3.13.9.3 Inner vs outer renewal

External pressures may also impact the goals and motives for technological growth (Teo, Wei, and Benbasat, 2003; Liang et al., 2007). External effects include technology standards (Lyytinen & King, 2006), digital platform ecosystems (Rolland et al., 2018), legal needs, and managerial styles (Brown

et al., 2002). Accordingly, organisations that adopt industry-standard EA frameworks such as TOGAF demonstrate how external forces impact their implementation agenda.

Simultaneously, organisations are permeated by internal conflicts between organisational entities and levels (Gregory et al., 2015; Bacharach, Bamberger, & Sonnenstuhl, 1996), creating an environment conducive to the flourishing of situated agendas and cultures, creating rationales and practices that may impact technology renewal (Hoffman & Klepper, 2000). For instance, Internal cultures may conflict with external rationalisation and standardisation goals (Hanseth, Jacucci, Grisot, & Aanestad, 2006).

Wimelius, Mathiassen, Holmstrom, and Keil (2021) argue that the paradox of technological renewal produces conflicts between inner and exterior settings. The inner contexts of an organisational entity include its culture (including social norms, strategic aims, and management structures), while the exterior contexts include the environment in which it functions (including social, psychological, economic, and political elements) (Pettigrew, 1987).

CMO configurations comprise context-related aspects related to the programmes' triggered mechanisms to create outcomes. These outcomes are transformations or may be invariant or reproductive features of the programme (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012, p.181).

As a result, the technology context in CMO setups includes the technical features of the processes that generate the program's results, such as established vs renewed technology utilisation, intentional versus emergent renewal activities, and inner versus outward renewal practices.

3.13.10 Structure as Context in Triggered EA Mechanisms

According to Archer (1996), organisational structure relates to objects such as physical and material resources and their practices. Practices are human-centred activities. The relationship between the context of action and organisational structure may manifest in resistance relative to time. Such temporal resistance is a generic condition of the context of action (Archer, 2010a, p.239).

The structure is the recurrent patterned arrangements that influence or limit the choices and opportunities available (Archer, 2000).

"While the strategy proposed in realist evaluation has highlighted the structural dimensions of social systems" (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; p.63), there has been a propensity to leave the cultural dimension inferred within a structure (Pawson, 2006, p.31; Pawson et al., 2005; p.23).

There are various sociological theories about structure. Structure and agency lie at the heart of sociological theorising (Archer, 2000, p.1). In the 'structuralist' view, social structures, whether in cultural norms, production relations, discourses, or system demands and socialisation processes, play a causal role in understanding the social world (Carter & New, 2004).

According to (Giddens, 1984, p.292), social structures have a virtual life until people instantiate them, that is, until they are employed in social activity and hence replicated or transformed. Thus, social interactions are intrinsically related and cannot be isolated from human-knowing activities. Structure and agency are only actual in combination, and they cannot be studied or recognised individually since no analytic separation is possible. No side of the dyad is given explanatory precedence since they are mutually constitutive.

A 'voluntarist' view, which reverses the direction of the explanatory flow, explains social structures only via the actions of individuals and is opposed to structuralism. Humans are given causal precedence in understanding the social world, and social structures are assumed to be derived from people's beliefs (idealism, various varieties of interpretivism) or through their habits and dialogues (social constructionism, ethnomethodology) (Carter & New, 2004).

A realist perspective on the agency-structure relationship is also conceivable. Archer (1995), Layder (1994), Pawson (1989), and Sayer (1984) contend that structure and agency have distinct properties and powers in and of themselves. For example, one of the properties of social structures is their anteriority. Hence, social structures are inherent aspects of the environment we are born. Another

defining feature of social structures is their long-term viability. Among the powers wielded by social structures are enablement and limitation.

According to the realist viewpoint, pre-existing structures exist independently, with causal powers and properties of their own, and humans, with distinct causal powers and attributes of their own, result in contingent yet explicable outcomes. In a significant way, the world is mindless. Archer (1995), Pawson and Tilley (1997, 2008)

Individuals are confronted with a reality mainly due to previous interactions with others and their structural contexts rather than being directly formed or manufactured by them. Structures exist and have effects independently of their knowledge due to their temporal precedence, which makes them intransitive objects of knowledge. Thus, for realists, how things differ from how individuals perceive them (Carter & New, 2004).

3.13.10.1 Structure in the Context of EA Implementations

The expression ‘social structures’ and ‘structures’ is used by Bhaskar (1978), which Archer (1995, p.202) refers to as institutional structures. Sometimes it refers to institutional and cultural structures (refer to Archer, 1995, p.202), and sometimes to “social structures”. Other times, structure encompasses ‘agency’, ‘culture’, ‘structure’ and ‘relations’ (Archer, 1995, p.165–7).

Social structures circumscribe agency, culture, structure, funding, technology, and relations. In this thesis, ‘Structure’ will be used interchangeably also as organisational structures.

de Souza (2013) explains the mechanism with an example of pre-existing structures such as processes, roles/positions, resources, and practices about an organisation or a school. Citing the example of an input of a training program for the teachers to prepare them for "21st-century teaching" to change the existing structure by:

- Assess the mechanisms against the evolving role of the teacher in the new arrangement to guide. The changing role of the teachers may also need a synergistic alignment with the position of

the students as self-learners. This initiative activates the mechanism in the structural aspect of the action context related to "roles" (de Souza, 2013),

- The need to retrain the teacher in the new practices for the new role by adopting the indirect teaching methods activates the structural aspect of the action context related to “practices” (de Souza, 2013).

- The use of computers in schools instead of chalkboards as 21st-century resources trigger a mechanism in the structural component of the action context associated with resources,
- The processes between the structures are modified to activate the mechanism in the action context's structural component. One example is the alignment of the newly proposed teaching technique with the format of classroom assessment, which is a structured process, and performing national and state-level exams, as well as throughout the structured process. (2013) (de Souza).

Therefore, a change in structural mechanisms, even in one element, has a ripple effect on other aspects of the structure. These changes can occur within and between the structural mechanisms in EA implementations (Banaeianjahromi & Smolander, 2019).

The challenge of assessing the impact of structure and agency in EA implementation is how to link them. Conflation may be inward, where individual acts are aggregated or downward, where agent action is orchestrated. Archer (1995) argues that the common practice is to conflate these two attributes. *"Since structure and agency constitute different levels of stratified social reality, each possesses distinctive emergent properties which are real and causally efficacious but irreducible to one another"* (Archer, 1995, p.1).

3.13.10.2 Implications of Context for EA Program Theories

According to Archer (1996), culture encompasses consciousness and unconsciousness, exchanging thoughts and feelings among human subjects. It involves a great deal of empathy.

Such intersubjectivity pertains to how ideas and matters related to idea creation between human subjects.

Like organisational structure, the culture of the groups of individuals and ideas shape the action of individuals, the possibility of these actions and their related outcomes. Culture is related to the individual or group's logical relations with costs and benefits. Culture also determines individuals' or groups' choices about which ideas to adopt and abandon (Willmott, 2000; p.108).

3.13.11 Elaborating Context for EA Programme Theories

The context of action in this research proposes the EA program intervention's social action and behavioural intent. Certain conditions pre-exist in organisations and the broader ecosystem it operates (Bhaskar, 1978).

Pawson and Tilley (1997, p.70) argue that interventional programmes are always presented within a social context. As such, the prevailing conditions of such program social environments are crucial in explaining the success or failure of the programmes.

According to Sayer (1992, p.112), these conditions do not exist in isolation. However, they are in an action context of material resources and social structures such as standards, guidelines, policies, and systems. Such conditions are the basis for which ideas are formulated. The interaction of culture, agency, social structure, and relations promotes an in-depth understanding of the working of the programmes in social action.

However, such interactions of contextual factors can introduce complexity and create challenges and difficulties in achieving successful implementations (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.70). Iyamu (2019) suggested in their analysis of qualitative research using structuration theory that technology, social environment, organisational structure, and process-oriented elements are crucial and impact EA complexity. *"The key factors that influence EA complexity in organisations include organisational structure, technology, social context, and process-oriented"* (Iyamu, 2019, p.6).

Social context influences the application of guidelines, principles, and resources to advise communication and sensemaking toward EA program interventions; the social context of the EA program, therefore, has implications on how these guidelines are applied and how organisational resources are utilised for the benefit of strategic intent.

3.13.12 Mechanisms and Emergence in The Context of EA Management

According to Bhaskar (2009), mechanisms have generative causal powers. Mechanisms "*exists in the causal power of things*" (p.40). Supporting his view, Pawson and Tilley (1997) argue that mechanisms are theories that determine "*the potential of human resources and reasoning*" (p.68)

According to Collier (1994, p.62), a generative mechanism is a technical term that designates something 'real' and independent of patterns of events affecting it. For Instance, the generative mechanisms of an individual's brain structure are 'real', with the potential and capacity to enable that individual to learn a language. The individual's brain's structure has causal powers of language acquisition.

In the volcanic eruption analogy used in describing the generative causal pathways, what happens beneath the surface may be hidden. Still, under the proper context and conditions, there is an eruption. The mechanisms within the volcano lay dormant and have the capacity and potential to cause a volcanic eruption.

Collier (1994) distinguishes horizontal mechanisms with antecedents in other generative mechanisms and vertical mechanisms with explanatory power from one primary source. Vertical mechanisms exist because of stratified layers of reality (Bhaskar, 2009, p.47). Mechanisms, therefore, exist in multiple layers of reality, both observable and unobservable.

An event or change is generated when certain triggered conditions cause structures of objects, with some intervention, to cause potentials to be exercised. Collier (1994) argues that, for that matter, mechanisms are located within structures, social or material, with action potentials. He also claims that it is feasible to investigate, even predict, the structures that generate these potentials.

de Souza (2013) draws on Collier's explanation to suggest that generative mechanisms within an organisational context are in culture, relational, agency, and structural properties since domains are the locus for organisational context. Since social context pre-exists in social programmes, mechanisms exist and behave in the social context independent of the program interventions.

Accordingly, the question for EA implementers intends to unearth the nature of the generative mechanisms in operation within the social context that can transform or reproduce existing social structures, whether they contribute to desired outcomes of the social programmes or create problems. Accordingly, the intention should be to identify program input that can configure or trigger the generative mechanisms in context to transform it towards successful outcomes rather than reproduce the action context it aims to change.

3.13.12.1 Activating Mechanisms in The Context of Culture

Culture is a mechanism that refers to ideas in social action (Willmott, 2000, p.105). The formation of the suggested emergent properties of culture operates within organisations. They “are propositional formulations” (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012) of *"theories, beliefs, arguments"* (p.20) about culture, structure, agency, and relations.

These propositional formulations are usually communicated to organisations by employing meetings, conversations, documents, artefacts, guidelines, frameworks, and white papers; and instigated through internal or external sources the organisation (de Souza, 2013, p.150).

Therefore, sustaining the transformation of the action context from the pre-existing state necessitates an equivalent switch in structure and ideation of the action context (de Souza, 2013, p.150). For Instance, imagination and reasoning play a role in choosing an EA framework to adopt and why this is important for the action context of an EA programme.

Taking such an approach triggers the cultural aspects of the EA programme intervention and the action context related to propositions about the EA program practices, processes, roles, structure,

mechanisms and resources. Similarly, propositions entail ideas or culture of the EA programme intervention and propositions about relations with experts and agencies.

According to Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012), programmes within the context of social action are transformations, invariant or reproduced aspects of culture associated with the propositional formulations regarding culture itself, structure, agency, and relations that exist in them. Indeed, the role of culture in social programmes is implicitly crucial in determining outcomes. Culture shapes the attitudes, behaviours, and perceptions of individuals within a group or organisation and thus significantly influences the way social programmes are received and implemented and their ultimate effectiveness. Therefore, understanding the cultural context is integral to designing and implementing social programmes that can achieve their desired outcomes.

3.13.12.2 Activating Mechanisms in The Context of Relation

The circumstances or events surrounding roles and responsibilities influence triggered mechanisms in the socio-technological action of EA within digital transformation programmes.

Duties and responsibilities are related to roles assigned to individuals and teams in the context of social systems, such as EA interventions in healthcare organisations. These duties confer their rights and power to the various roles in EA implementation. The relational properties of rights, duties, responsibilities, and power are emergent (Bhaskar, 2014). The right of duty in social systems relates to entrenched laws and rules that protect individual action within the system's action context. It follows, therefore, that the impact of their decisions on the action context may be emergent, leading to unpredictable outcomes in the form of reproduction of the existing state, invariant transformation or variant transformation that may not necessarily be aligned with expected outcomes.

Löhe and Legner (2014) suggest that when existing IT roles and committees commit to understanding EA artefacts and assume responsibilities for EA management activities, it promotes EAM acceptance in the (IT) organization and resolves difficulties in enforcing EA policies and standards. *"Unclear enterprise architecture roles and responsibilities" (p.639) is a challenge that can impede the EA*

implementation process, " ... which could be caused by a lack of rules and policies" (p.641) (Olsen, 2017). NHS Digital (2018) says their stakeholders think they are distant from the front line. This is made worse by how they communicate with other organisations, which is seen as "transmitting" information instead of "engaging" with other organisations.

According to NHS Digital, stakeholders are concerned about the obscure roles of NHS national organisations that deal with data and technology, the system-level leadership and governance, authorizations, assurance, and governance processes, and the roles and functions of those organisations.

3.13.12.3 Activating Mechanisms in The Context of Agency

The circumstances or events surrounding skills and knowledge, such as availability, influence triggered mechanisms in the socio-technological action of EA within digital transformation programmes. Individually, agents have subjective ideas in social programmes are subjective, and these ideas may not be the ideations of a collective or group (de Souza, 2013).

According to Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012), clients' or agents' reasoning is perceived as defining the program context's social action. To activate the agency (individual and organisational) related mechanisms in the action context is to understand the reasoning behind these mechanisms in the context of action. Reason pertains to agential beliefs and justification for action or inaction in the context of the programme intervention.

Mechanism activation related to beliefs and reasons for an action context may lead to transformation, invariance, or reproduction of outcomes related to agency-related aspects of these beliefs and reasoning. For example, adopting a particular EA Framework over others in EA program interventions depends on the individual decision-makers beliefs and ideas to justify their choice.

The impact of agency on outcomes is embedded in the transformation, invariance, or reproduction of the action context of programmes in the form of agency-related aspects related to beliefs and reasons for decision-making that informs action (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012; de Souza, 2013).

"The lack of soft skills, such as people skills and leadership skills among practitioners, has been attributed to poor communication during EA adoption" (Jonnagaddala et al., 2020, p.7).

Application and technical architectures are used to build technology interaction and communication. Technology is the product of human recursive behaviours, frequently influenced by knowledge (skills) and interests (Iyamu, 2019). If an organisation has a broader range of professional skills (knowledge) to choose from because it has good relationships or because it can benefit more from such choices, this can make a difference in how well it performs (Madhok, 2002)

3.13.12.4 Activating Mechanisms in The Context of Funding

The circumstances or events surrounding funding approaches and constraints influence triggered mechanisms in the socio-technological action of EA within digital transformation programmes. That is the funding circumstances under which programmes are delivered. *"The NHS is experiencing the longest and most severe slowdown in funding in its history. This has raised questions about the sustainability of its funding model"* (McKenna et al., 2017).

Moreover, *"Organisations cite difficulties in justifying their EA investments, and anecdotal evidence suggests that the existence and funding of the EA function are often based more on the beliefs of the incumbent management team than on demonstrated value"* (Tamm et al. 2011).

Despite the magnitude of expansion in health and social care spending, periodic crises have occurred as budget increases have lagged, expanding demand, expectations, and technical requirements (Charlesworth et al., 2021). Establishing this infrastructure takes a significant effort from the organisation and funding (Lange et al., 2016). Insufficient funding has been identified as a challenge relevant to the usage behaviour of EA (Guo, Li & Gao, 2019; Mohamed, Galal-Edeen & Hassan, 2013). NHS Providers and the NHS Confederation quickly emphasised the funding gap and an 'impossible set of options' over how and when to prioritise patient care. The primary predictor of the quality of EA planning is the availability of sufficient high-quality resources throughout EA planning.

It includes adequate continuing funding to ensure the continued availability of these resources throughout EA planning (Bernard, 2005; Spewak & Hill, 1992).

Insufficient funding constitutes a major impediment to the successful implementation of strategic initiatives within the National Health Service (NHS). According to NOA (2020a), funding hinders NHS plans. This financial constraint can impede the implementation of strategic initiatives, technology advancements, or improvements to service delivery, thereby challenging the NHS's ability to optimise patient care and operational efficiency. It underscores the critical need for adequate funding to enable the effective execution of healthcare strategies and plans.

3.13.12.5 Activating Mechanisms in The Context of Technology

The circumstances or events surrounding the technology landscape influence triggered mechanisms in the socio-technological action of EA within digital transformation programmes. That is the funding circumstances under which programmes are delivered.

Technological forces exist in triggered mechanisms in socio-technological action of EA implementation within digital transformation programmes. That is the technology landscape under which EA programmes are implemented.

NHS Digital (2018) has pledged to 'fit for purpose' to deliver their commitments for Personalised Health and Care technology, but this is achievable through support from the appropriate technology landscape. According to the NOA (2020a), legacy IT hinders NHS plans.

Advancements in technology impact the Architectural Design of Healthcare systems (van Velthoven et al., 2019).

Artificial intelligence (AI) advancements have gone further and quicker than anybody could have predicted. AI can now do complex tasks, including image classification, speech recognition, translation, object identification, driving, gaming, finance, and decision-making. Such actions need extensive computation and decision-making; previous Scientists and academics have lately made significant efforts to utilise AI in diagnosis, therapy, and medical care. AI will drastically alter the

healthcare landscape in future. According to medical physics, AI will significantly enhance overall healthcare (Vatandsoost & Litkouhi, 2019).

AI can identify illnesses using complicated algorithms generated from millions of patients' imaging results, hundreds of biomarkers, electronic health records (EHRs) data, and clinical research findings published in PubMed (Krittanawong, 2018).

Some scientists think that artificial intelligence (AI) will influence medical physics research and practice, while others argue that such predictions are impractical due to AI's technical validation and practical constraints (Ibragimov & Xing, 2017; Patel et al., 2009; Bennett & Hauser, 2013).

AI can be used in radiology and radiation therapy for image categorization, object recognition, image reconstruction and analysis, image-guided, tumour detection and characterization, therapeutic response and toxicity prediction, treatment decision-making, and other tasks (Ibragimov & Xing, 2017; Wang, Kalra, & Orton, 2017).

3.13.12.6 Activating Mechanisms in the Context of Structure

The circumstances or events surrounding the organisation's structure and its processes influence triggered mechanisms in the socio-technological action of EA within digital transformation programmes.

Structural circumstances play a crucial role in EA outcomes. For instance, Liddell, Adshead and Burgess (2008) recommended that the NHS reviews national procurement processes to ensure they are structured to ease the uptake of innovation and suitable technology based on a 'best value' proposition. Portraying alternative futures for the use of technology by the health system over the next 10 to 20 years, the structure of the health care system, Liddell, Adshead and Burgess referred to the structure as a "*super force*" (p.5).

Structural forces exist in triggered mechanisms in the socio-technological action of EA Interventions. It is noteworthy that structure is not organisational hierarchies as defined in the English language but

processes, resources, roles, and responsibilities of the organisation in social action (Iyamu & Roode, 2010; Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012).

According to de Souza (2013), the aspects of structure in program action are composed of four fundamental and internally linked with emergent properties. Because of their distinct analytical power, these internally related structures are usually managed distinctly. Such distinctions offer explanatory power in the action context of programmes.

The four components of the structure or organisation are roles/positions, practices, processes, and resources (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012). First, structure redefines roles for the programme action context, activating mechanisms in the structural features of the action context associated with roles. Secondly, Structures retrain stakeholders relevant to the [EA] programme in the action context, equipping them with the requisite skills for their given roles. Thirdly, these skills are acted upon to activate those mechanisms in the structural features associated with praxes.

Finally, change processes may occur in structures or between structures. These changes activate mechanisms in the structural features of the action context within or between structural processes.

Structural changes occur in programmes, such as the digitisation of manual processes and the interaction between digitised and existing manual processes because action activates changes in structure.

[EA] programmes may then aim to transform existing EA by modifying organisational structures in the following ways drawing on the arguments by Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012).

Accordingly, realigning the organisational IT strategy with its key objective of providing safe and efficient health and social care to NHS patients (NHS Digital, 2021a) may require structural adjustments so mechanisms in the structural features of the action context of the [EA] programmes can be activated.

Structure plays a significant role in shaping programme outcomes by affecting the roles, positions, and practices of individuals and teams and the organisation's broader practices, resources, and

processes. Mechanisms are embedded in the structural aspects of transformation, whether they are variant or reproduce action context (Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012; de Souza, 2013). E.g., in Phase B of the ADM, the business architecture requires the organisation to describe its operational needs necessary for achieving alignment between its goals and architectural vision (The Open Group, 2018). However, the ADM does not provide a framework for required resources and social processes. It is understandable since resources and social processes have contextual dependencies that cannot be determined apriori.

3.13.13 Structuration Theory and Implications for the Implementation of EA Programmes

According to Hardcastle, Usher and Holmes (2005), structuration theory is a Socio-Technological constructivist conjuncture, mainly concerned with human-centred and institutional social constructs sustained by the reality of human action. Another argument by Puron-Cid (2013) suggests that saturation theory is a dual process between human action and structures as single rather than separate entities. Central to the theory is agents and structure. The structure constrains agency and enables them simultaneously (MacKay & Tambeau, 2013). These theories support the impact of structure as an influencing construct in determining programme outcomes where human action is involved.

Arguments within the theoretical framework of structuration perceive technologies as change agents of social structure. Structure shapes human development in technology usage (Nicholson et al., 2013). Agents refer to individuals or teams of individuals, but all such entities have the potential power of influence over other social actions in the context, such as an organisation (Giddens, 1984). The implication of such an argument suggests that agents have power over a social construct's structure, processes, roles, responsibilities, and resources (Iyamu & Roode, 2010). Suppliers of technology systems external to the organisation in this regard are agents and constitute the structural component of the social action of programmes.

Drawing on the above arguments, the power of EA programmes to redistribute structure is apparent.

Human agents can transform or reproduce social structure in the action context of programmes. The structure of a social system is both an outcome and a medium for reproducing practices (Archer, 2010a).

3.13.14 Emergence In the Context of EA Mechanisms

Emergence is characteristic of nature and humanity with implications for reconstructing historical processes from simpler things (Bhaskar, 2014; Archer, 1995).

Social structures and systems that exist because of positional practices are stable and may not be predetermined. Social interaction accounts for the emergence and their associated properties (Archer, 1995; p.11); social positions individuals take to occupy in their selected practices amend or ignore such rules, resulting in cost and benefits outcomes. Emergence, therefore, depends on social action (p.167)

"There are a variety of emergent properties – structural, cultural and agential, each of which is irreducible to the others, has relative autonomy, and is also relatively enduring" (p.175).

Emergence is located within the constituents of social structures. The relation between structure and emergence is society's structural components, with emergence derived from the relation. **Figure 3.11** below illustrates the emergent nature of the organisation's EA.

Figure 3.11. illustrates the emergent properties of EA for the context-sensitive mechanism of the Organisations.

A dynamic perspective on EA complexity allows for an account of the emergent character of the underlying complex sets of interactions.

Hjort-Madsen (2007) argued that EA is “an emergent, evolving, embedded, fragmented, and provisional social production that is shaped as much by cultural and structural forces in the organizational context” (p. 334).

A static approach confines EA to single cause-effect relationships, a snapshot of emergent phenomena of the organisation’s dynamic architecture, thus, omitting its underlying structure (Haki & Legner, 2013; Haki et al., 2016). In realist evaluation, these relationships exist within the CMO configurations.

A certain level of complexity is regarded as an essential property to enable an information architecture behaviour to be dynamic and emergent (Benbya & McKelvey 2006; Vessey & Ward 2013).

Complexity causes the integrant components of an information system architecture to “interact in unpredictable and non-linear ways” (Lyytinen & Newman 2008, p. 606).

(Karpovsky & Galliers, 2015) argue that the dynamic perspective of EA is relevant as organisational practices are emergent and are usually exposed to political and interpretative influences.

The generative causal processes produce results that vary throughout time (Cardinal et al., 2004). This is especially true for emergent information system activities like EA management (Cram et al., 2015).

The organisation's EA CMO configurations have emergent properties. For example, structure and agency create multiple levels of stratified social reality; each exhibits distinct emergent features that are real and causally effective but irreducible from the others (Archer, 1995). The underpinning ontological position of the context-mechanisms-outcome configuration is that mechanisms are context-sensitive (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Figure 3.11 shows a longitudinal and dynamic view of the organisation's architecture. Input from the organisation's vision and strategy define the requirements that the EA programme uses to form the basis for modifying the current state architecture. The programme of EA action results in a future or a target state which is expected to reflect action to fulfil the organisation's strategy and vision. EA CMOc-0 represent the organisation's snapshot architecture. At EA CMOc-1, a transitional state of the architecture, circumstances change, and the prevailing circumstances and triggered mechanisms and related are different and unpredictable.

Similarly, at EACMOc-2, a snapshot of the EA has different CMO configurations and interactions. The cycle of transitions of EA CMOs continues indefinitely in a continuum, even beyond the timeline of the target architecture, CMOc-n. This dynamic behaviour of the EA CMO configuration has several profound implications. First, EA is virtual and in a continuous state of change, even beyond the programme timeline. Secondly, contexts, mechanisms and outcome interactions are also dynamic. Thirdly, alignment could occur long after the EA programme has been completed. For example, at the time when the emergent conditions of context, mechanisms triggered create the desired outcomes. The notion of EA failure or success of an initiative is a snapshot perspective that changes over time.

Implementation is achieved through a tailored TOGAF ADM (The Open Group, 2018). The dynamicity and emergence of EA are thus explained. The organisation's architecture snapshot has circumstances peculiar to it over time.

Eliciting the programme theory implementation, the emerging CMO configuration of the context-mechanism-output link becomes the context for another configuration of the EA of the organisation over time (Jagosh et al., 2015). Therefore, this link is crucial in aligning the organisation's strategy, technology, and the value EA programmes deliver.

3.13.15 Outcomes of Generative Mechanisms of EA in Context

Otto (2012) further argues that such EA mechanisms deliver value only in the EA programme intervention context. *“Research has indicated that while EA is necessary, merely having EA is not sufficient for creating value in specific application contexts”* (Schmidt & Buxmann, 2011, p.5).

Social organisations, such as healthcare, are scaled-down versions of society. It is possible to observe societal changes in action context within specific social program interventions (Archer, 1995).

Archer (1995) proposes a morphogenetic approach to dealing with the dynamic of social reality within organisations. Therefore, social change of the kind that occurs in society is possible in organisations.

Byng et al. (2005; p.140) and (de Souza, 2013; p.147) argue that social systems operate in feedback loops with an input-output feedback configuration.

According to Sayer (1992, p.94), three potential patterns of outcomes characterise the feedback loop behaviour of social processes. The action context of the program may undergo a transformational change from its previous state; remain preserved and invariant; or experience a transformational change that may reproduce/reinforce organisational culture, relations, and organisational structure and longitudinally modify the social structures of the program.

In realist evaluation, outcomes are responses (reflections or representations) to different mechanisms in specific contexts (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016). According to Rycroft-

Malone et al., outcomes may include programme learning or impact, such as changes in behaviour or processes connected to whether an intervention was effective. Stakeholder (agency) concerns determine the alignment or misalignment of EA outputs, not how effectively architecting has been accomplished (process paradox). From systems thinking perspective, information systems exist to serve, facilitate, or support real-world activities. Stakeholder expectation is a key performance indicator of success (Yeo, 2002; Checkland & Scholes, 1990).

Rycroft-Malone et al. *“Captured a range of different types of impact [the] implementation activity might have, from those that are more direct to those that are more conceptual and processual”* (p.23).
Outcomes *“reflect, or represent, the responses to different mechanisms in particular Outcomes may include the learning from programmes or can be related to impact Contexts”* (Williams, 2013, p.77).

3.14 A Critical Realist Approach to Elaborating the CMOc Configuration in EA

Programme Implementations

The researcher suggests that the action context comprises contextual factors such as structure, culture, agency, and relation, drawing on arguments by Archer (1995) and later de Souza (2013). The researcher has also argued that hidden and observable generative mechanisms are contextually located. Inputs such as strategies and organisational vision in Socio-Technological program interventions may reconfigure or activate these contextual mechanisms in different ways and cited arguments from Bhaskar (2009), Pawson and Tilley (1997), and Archer (1995) to confirm these.

The researcher has argued that reconfiguring or activating Socio-Technological programmes changes the constituent elements the program seeks to change for outcomes. The researcher argued that these outcomes might transform, reproduce the existing state, or cause the action context invariant transformation drawing on the argument on the morphogenesis of transformations (Archer, 1995).

The researcher draws on the above argument to suggest that EA programme interventions fall under similar categories of outcomes.

The assessment of success driven by mechanisms presumes that the outcomes align with the expectations of the organization implementing the EA initiative. The mechanism's critical success factors within the action context enable the transformation to create successful outcomes. Configurations that transform the action context to create outcomes aligned with the organisation's intended purpose; alignment with its strategies and vision generally constitutes critical success factors since reconfiguration enables the organisation to achieve its objectives (Henderson and Venkataraman, 1993; Archer, 1995).

Reproduction or invariant transformation of the action context creates undesired outcomes. Generally, it constitutes a failure to align with the vision and strategic objective of the organisation implementing the EA program intervention. Therefore, the input mechanisms associated with such failure constitute critical failure factors (Archer, 1995). The assumption is that a mere reproduction or invariant transformation of the action context does not produce outcomes aligned with the organisation's objective. Such outcomes are either misaligned with their intended purpose (off-target) or do not affect the success of the action context of the EA programme.

3.15 Elaborating The CMO Configuration on Critical Success and Critical Failure

Factors of EA Management

The researcher proposes that the action context comprises contextual factors such as structure, culture, agency, and relation as significant influences on the EA outcomes in digital transformation programmes, drawing on arguments by Archer (1998a). The researcher seeks to support, refute, and refine these theories (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The researcher also suggested that hidden and observable generative mechanisms are contextually located. Inputs such as strategies and organisational vision in Socio-Technological program interventions may reconfigure or activate these contextual mechanisms in different ways and cited arguments from Bhaskar (1978), Pawson and Tilley (1997), Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012), Archer (1995) and de Souza (2013) to support these.

The researcher has argued that reconfiguring or activating Socio-Technological programmes changes the configuration of constituent elements the program seeks to produce outcomes. The researcher has argued that these outcomes may transform, reproduce the existing state, or cause the action context invariant transformation.

The researcher draws on the above argument to suggest that EA Programme interventions fall under similar categories of outcomes. The researcher suggests that those mechanisms that cause the transformation of the action context toward a successful outcome constitute critical success factors. On the contrary Contextual mechanisms that reproduce the pre-existing state or drive invariant transformation are critical failure factors.

3.15.1 Critical Success Factors of the CMOc of EA Programmes

Drawing on arguments by Archer (1995) regarding transformations of social action, Critical success factors influence the action context and the transformative mechanisms that tend to create successful outcomes. Successful outcomes must meet the expectations of the implementing organisation for successful alignment with its objectives. In TOGAF, the object of alignment of outcomes of the action context is the organisation's vision (The Open Group, 2018).

Reconfigurations transform the action context to create outcomes aligned with the organisation's intended purposes and alignment between IT and its strategic objectives and vision. It generally constitutes a critical success factor since reconfiguration, through programme action, enables the organisation to achieve alignment.

3.15.2 Critical Failure Factors of the CMOc of the EA Programme Intervention

Drawing on arguments by Archer (1995), I contend that reproduction or invariant transformation of the action context creates undesired outcomes. Generally, it constitutes a failure to align with the vision and strategic objective of the organisation implementing the EA program intervention. Therefore, the input mechanisms associated with such failure constitute critical failure factors.

The premise is that simply reproducing or invariantly transforming the action environment does not yield results consistent with the organization's goal. Such results are either mismatched with their intended aim (off-target) or have no impact on the success of the EA Programme's action context.

3.16 Summary

Figure 3.7 shows A summary of the programme theory. Hidden EA Mechanisms are triggered in context to produce outcomes.

Mechanisms of EA and Socio-Technological factors require further investigation to understand better their impact on EA outcomes (Hope, 2015). EA implementations are complex, and the underpinning mechanisms are often hidden and triggered in context to produce organisational outcomes. There are causal pathways of these mechanisms in context. Because of actors' social action, the outcomes can reproduce the action context leading to invariant transformation and aligned and unaligned transformation to the target or desired architecture.

In conclusion, practical and methodological difficulties may be tackled by embracing realist social theory in the organisational program as a steering principle by recognising structure, relation, agency, and culture pre-existing in program intervention. However, the Open Group Architecture framework does not prominence its Architecture development method to such aspects.

Program theories such as TOGAF merely describe the method an EA program intends to reconfigure the existing components of the ADM to produce target architectures but fall short of reactivating pre-existing contextual mechanisms of the social action.

Program theories are often silent on the action context such as culture, relation, agency, and structure, and are contingent *"on a hypothesis that postulates: if we deliver a program in this way or we manage services like so, then this will bring about some improved outcome"* (Pawson et al., 2005, p.22).

Introducing social programmes as inputs to an action context to transform an existing social system activates the pre-existing mechanisms, culture, agency, relation, and structure. Activating these

mechanisms is essential to the transformation of the action context of the program (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Social programmes are introduced into social systems as inputs into action contexts to affect change in an existing social network. A pre-existing plan's parts in an action context include features of structure, culture, agency, and relations that interact to produce the current social network with its difficulties. The transition may be accomplished by reorganising or activating the component pieces in a new manner.

According to de Souza (2013), a social programme input reconfigures or activates pre-existing contextual processes differently, resulting in a restricted number of alternative configurations. "networks of outcomes". These networks identify *"what works for whom in what circumstances"* (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63; Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012, p.177).

4 CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The study aims to explore how EA is implemented in healthcare organisations. This chapter discusses and justifies the realist methodology used in this study. The study addressed the following research questions:

1. **Main Research Question 1 (RQ1):** What are the Mechanisms for managing EA programmes in healthcare organisations?
2. **Research question 2 (RQ2):** What critical factors and challenges affect EA programmes in healthcare?

The methodology in this research is a realist evaluation. Realist evaluation is progressively "*applied in the evaluation of complex healthcare interventions as it seeks to provide a more explicit and in-depth understanding of what works, for whom and in what circumstances and has been recommended for the evaluation of integrated care interventions*" (Nurjono et al., p.3).

Realist evaluation is "*a theory-driven, interpretative approach to uncovering underlying middle-range theories (or logics) driving interventions and their multiple components, as well as illuminating the contextual factors that influence mechanisms of change to produce outcomes*" (Jagosh et al., 2015, p.3).

While critical realists do not entirely reject empiricist methodologies such as statistical analysis, they believe that underlying causal processes at work must be studied. Extracting and conceptualising the object's underlying causal capacities or processes is required. Qualitative techniques assist the researcher in this endeavour by constructing a model of a potential mechanism by comparisons to other well-known things, which is then used to explain a set of observed patterns. (Harré, 1984, pp.174-6; Bhaskar, 2009, p.68).

The chapter continues by describing the research design and approach. It justifies critical realism as the philosophical perspective underpinning the research. It represents the research site, the participant's profile, and how access to the research participants was negotiated and established. The

chapter subsequently discusses the technique (s) used in analysing and synthesising the data from different sources. It also explained how trustworthiness was maintained and highlighted the ethical considerations made throughout the study. **Figure 4.1** outlines the method used in this research.

Figure 4.1. The methodological approach to critical evaluation is used in the research.

4.2 The Environment Surrounding the Evaluation.

In December 2003, then-Health Secretary John Reid revealed intentions for every NHS patient in England to have an electronic NHS Care Record system. A national NHS Care Records Service (SCR) is managed on 10-year contracts. The SCR is derived from patients' GP-held computerised data, including allergies, medications, summary medical history, operations, and procedures. Initially intended for emergency and unplanned treatment, it was intended to integrate data from other care contexts eventually.

The Secondary Uses Service allows NHS personnel to access anonymized spine database data. Patients may examine their SCR and record and organise their health data using a different internet-based platform called HealthSpace. Advocates of the Summary Care Record (SCR) highlight the enhancement of patient safety, manifested in a decrease in medication errors and adverse reactions, improved efficiency and coordination of treatment, and more informed and engaged patients as the key benefits. However, the SCR roll-out has prompted questions regarding secrecy and whether the public has been fully informed. Concerns have been raised concerning patients' ability to “opt-out” and decline to have their data uploaded and its mechanism (Powell and Thompson, 2010).

In addition to providing complete electronic records in primary and secondary care, the SCR is part of a more extensive NHS National Programme for IT. The NHS Care Records Service also includes:

- A Personal Demographics Service encompasses essential individual details such as name, address, date of birth, NHS number, and current General Practitioner.
- A Secondary Uses service provides centralised access to aggregated data for management, commissioning, clinical audit, and research.
- Local record systems, including comprehensive patient records, have always existed on paper or electronically and are stored in hospitals, GP surgeries, and other organisations (Pettrakaki, Klecun and Cornford, 2016).

NHS Digital supports clinicians in designing, building, and administering national IT and data systems that improve health and care (NHS Digital, 2018).

Stakeholders of the programme include technology experts, clinicians, other NHS staff, Architects, senior leaders and senior clinicians in the NHS, and the UK Parliament, which is responsible for funding the programme. Stakeholders also include external suppliers of technology products and services.

4.3 The Realist Paradigm as a Programme Theory for EA Management

Generative causation is the realist evaluation process for explaining and analysing the causal pathways for the nature and behaviour of the mechanisms in program interventions. It is the underpinning assumption of the realist philosophy (Bhaskar,1978; Pawson, 2013; Jagosh, 2018). Mechanisms are hidden or may not be observed. In this thesis, evaluation and research are used interchangeably and synonymously. In realist philosophy, Programme theory is synonymous with a conceptual framework and is therefore used interchangeably (Wong et al., 2016).

According to Jagosh, generative causal pathways are constant conjunctions of observable outcomes for the activated mechanisms of the programme's activities.

These often-hidden mechanisms lie dormant until they are activated in context over a given time. The generative causal pathway may be trajectoryed by a series of mechanisms triggered in a mechanism-context interaction over time (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

According to Jagosh (2018), Pawson and Tilley (1997) and Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, and Vallières (2019), generative causal pathways are constant conjunctions of observable outcomes for the activated mechanisms of the programme's activities. These hidden mechanisms of the EA program lie dormant until they are activated in context over a given time. The generative causal pathway may be trajectoryed by a series of these TOGAF ADM mechanisms triggered in a mechanism-context interaction over time, drawing from studies conducted by Pawson and Tilley (1997).

The programme theory combines the Open Group Architecture Framework's ontological, evaluative, synthesis, and practical theory. **Figure 4.2** shows some critical contributors to the realist paradigm theory used to formulate the conceptual framework for the research. In the following discussion, arguments and theories from these researchers are applied.

Figure 4.2 shows the critical contributors to the conceptual framework development.

Drawing on Dalkin et al. (2015), I argue that the TOGAF ADM mechanisms are triggered slowly over time, a phenomenon analogous to *"the dimmer switch"* (p.5).

Mechanisms that may lay dormant under context sensitivity are only triggered at different time horizons under the appropriate context. The theoretical framework is limited to culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure as the essential factors for the program under study.

4.4 The Rationale for Using realist evaluation in the Research

A realism assessment technique was used in this investigation. A fundamental tenet of realist methodology is that programmes behave differently in various settings. As a result, digital transformation that works in one context may fail (or succeed just partly) in another. The success mechanisms are activated to variable degrees in different settings or situations in which the mechanisms are triggered. A second assumption is that mechanisms are participants' cognitive or emotive responses to resources given in social programmes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Wong et al., 2016; Jagosh et al., 2015). The realist methodology applies to the study of Enterprise Architecture implementation in digital transformation programmes within healthcare organisations, which can be understood as a collection of intervention strategies implemented in geographically and functionally

diverse communities of practice. An organisation as diverse as the NHS operates contingent on the interplay of relationships among all stakeholders.

The research aims to explain who, how and why some conditions came into being in the design implementation of EA programmes leading to the observed outcomes (Yin, 2018).

This research design adopts a qualitative retroduction approach (Gilmore et al., 2019). The idea is to “understand [the implementation of EA] situations in their uniqueness as part of a particular context” (Merriam, 2002, p.5). Qualitative researchers seek to examine the research problems in their natural settings (Creswell, 2013), allowing participants and researchers to co-construct the meaning and realities (Merriam, 2002). The study's meaning within the qualitative paradigm employed a case study approach (see 4.2.1).

4.4.1 Critical realist perspective of EA Programme Mechanisms

According to Bhaskar (2009), Critical Realism (CR) is a school of thought in philosophy that separates the 'real' world from the 'observable' world. Reality exists independent of observable events, despite variations in human belief. Reality exists independent of human beliefs, conjectures, and constructions. Therefore, approximating our observations to reality is an epistemic fallacy.

“Empirical realism is underpinned by a metaphysical dogma, which I call the epistemic fallacy, that statements about being can always be transposed about our knowledge of being” (p.16).

Drawing on Bhaskar’s argument, all there is to know about EA and the mechanisms that influence the outcomes of their intervention cannot, therefore, be known.

Research philosophy is an integral part of the research process that explains what knowledge researchers intend to generate and how they intend to create it (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It is a set of beliefs and assumptions that governs and justify how knowledge is developed (Saunders et al., 2019).

“A credible research philosophy underpins the methodological choice, research strategy, data collection techniques, and analysis procedures. [In other words, it] allows for a coherent research design in which all elements of research fit together”. (Saunders et al., 2019, p.125). As noted in

sections 4.1 and 4.2, the current study is qualitative research that employs an instrumental case study approach. This research was designed from a critical realism perspective.

Critical realism is “*an underlying structure of reality that shapes the observable events*” (Saunders et al., 2019, p.138). It uses the subjective-objective multidimensional continuum (see **Figure 4.3**) to describe knowledge and how learning can be constituted (Fletcher, 2017; Saunders et al., 2019). From the subjectivist perspective, social reality is constructed by both the researcher and the participants (Saunders et al., 2019). On the other hand, the objectivist perspective shows that reality exists independently of the researcher and is the same for all social actors. Roy Bhaskar developed critical realism to replace the positivist and constructivist paradigms (Saunders et al., 2019; Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). The positivist and constructivist paradigms of human knowledge as a lens or container for reality are limited to what can be observed (Fletcher, 2017). Fletcher further explains that reality does not reflect what we know as human knowledge. We can only capture “*a small part of a deeper and vaster reality*” (p. 182). The critical realist paradigm maintains that knowledge is layered and is “*external and independent, but not directly accessible through our observation and knowledge of it*” (Saunders et al., 2019, p. 139).

Figure 4.3. The objectivism-subjectivism multidimensional continuum. Source: (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2019, p. 129).

From the ongoing discussion, it is apparent that ontology is crucial to critical realism. Danermark et al. (2002) observed that critical realism involves switching from epistemology to ontology and, within ontology, switching from events to the mechanism (p.5). Like the positivist approach, critical realists believe in the existence of the “real social world” and causality (Saunders et al., 2019; Fletcher, 2017).

However, unlike the positivists, who measure and quantify the data without altering the elements of the data collected, critical realists approach the knowledge of reality in terms of theories that drive the phenomenon being researched (Fletcher, 2017; Danermark et al., 2019). Archer (1998) argues that gaining knowledge through theories helps critical realists to identify the casualties that drive the phenomena. Archer's argument has a significant impact, especially as "*the nature of the society as an open system makes it impracticable to make predictions as is the case in [of positivism]*" (Danermark et al., 2002, p.2). Although positivists seek causal effects, they "*remain neutral and detached from your research and data to avoid influencing your findings*" (Saunders et al., 2019, p. 137).

In contrast, the theories used to identify causal mechanisms in critical realism are justified using the researchers' rational judgment of the data (Fletcher 2017). It is where critical realism aligns with constructivism. A constructivist believes that knowledge is socially constructed; hence what is real is subject to the researcher's interpretation of the participants' views or the data collected (Saunders et al., 2019; Creswell, 2013). However, unlike the constructivists, critical realists believe that knowledge is stratified or arranged in levels, namely: the 'empirical', 'actual', and 'real' levels (see **Figure 4.4**). These three levels represent what is experienced (empirical), what happens in terms of events and experiences (actual) and the underlying mechanisms, events and experiences that create the events (the real) (Bhaskar, 1978). The stratified domains of reality and their tendencies are shown in

Table 4.1.

Figure 4.4. Stratified ontology (Empirical, Actual and Real) of Critical Realism (Bhaskar, 1978; Saunders, 2109, p.139) is depicted within a Volcanic Eruption Metaphor. Mechanisms are triggered in context to produce Outcomes.

Table 4.1. Tendencies of the stratified domains of reality. Source: (Bhaskar, 1978)

Domains	Tendencies
Real	Mechanisms, Events and Experiences
Actual	Events and experiences
Empirical	Experiences

“If experimental activity is to be rendered intelligible, that natural mechanisms endure and act outside the conditions that enable us to identify them that the applicability of known laws in open systems can be sustained” (Bhaskar, 1978, p.13).

The researcher argues that the systems under which EA programmes operate are open. If systems are closed, neither experimental nor practical use of our knowledge in open systems can be sustained. Bhaskar further argues that the notion of closed systems is a human weakness. Laws can only be universal if they operate as an open system through a non-empirical or transfactual lens. Generative mechanisms are independent of the patterns of events. According to Bhaskar, our experiences of things cannot be equated to our knowledge of them, as doing so commits an ‘epistemic fallacy’ (p.16).

Bhaskar argues that real structures exist as independent entities out of synchronicity, often with real patterns of actual events. Bhaskar argues that asynchronicity between our experiences of a phenomenon and related events is necessary for our perceptions of reality. Asynchronicity ensures intelligibility.

“Our experiences are usually out of phase with the events” (p.13).

He argues for three distinct domains of reality: the real, the actual and the empirical. Mechanisms, nothing other than the ways of acting, must be generative as a basis for causal laws, which are essentially tendencies. Tendencies may take the form of liabilities or powers, and these may manifest without affecting outcomes.

Table 4.1 represents the independent existence of reality's “real” in the structural domains (Bhaskar, 1978). Bhaskar argues that the domain is ‘real’ and has mechanisms, events, and experiential tendencies. The domain of the actual has events and experiential tendencies. The domain of the empirical has experiential tendencies only.

These hidden mechanisms are present in the EA programme in a social-technical context that this research aims to cover. Whether these tendencies are liabilities or powers, and whether they affect the outcomes of EA programmes. The researcher argues that tendencies that are liabilities to the outcome of the EA programme represent critical failure factors, whilst tendencies that confer causal powers and create desired EA programme outcomes constitute critical success factors (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012; Jagosh, 2018).

Each level of reality must be exercised as tendencies that may not be realised in programme outcomes.

The empirical is the level of reality at which the researcher ‘observed or experienced’ a phenomenon (Saunders et al. (2019). Fletcher (2017) described it as the level where a phenomenon is measured and interpreted through a mix of the researcher’s “common sense” and “experience”. Thus, in critical realism, it is believed that the researcher’s observation is only a tiny part of a phenomenon's “actual” occurrence, irrespective of the setting (Saunders et al., 2019). The researcher *describes “things as*

they see them” rather than as “*as they are*” (Saunders et al., 2019, p.139). This assumption implies that the “empirical” level alone cannot describe the true nature of reality or knowledge as it tends to overlook the causality of events. No wonder Danermark et al. (2002) argued that “*the explanation of social phenomena by revealing the causal mechanisms which produce them is the fundamental task of research*” (p.2). Hence, Fletcher (2017) noted that the practical level of reality is transitive, where social ideas, meanings, decisions, and actions occur (p.183). Danermark et al. (2002) explain that researchers collect data at the “empirical level”. They maintain that in critical realism, “*all data arises in connection with some theory that the researcher partly observed or experienced*” (p.21). Hence, critical realists investigate and identify relationships between our collected data, events, and causal explanations.

The actual level of reality is the realm in which events occur, whether experienced or not (Danermark et al., 2002; Fletcher, 2017). Fletcher (2017) maintains that reality at this level is ‘true’ occurrences that are often different from what is observed at the “*empirical level*” (p.183). The “**real**” level represents the social structures that bring about social events. Saunders et al. (2019) define the ‘*real*’ level as the realm of reality at which the researcher seeks to understand social structures that have given rise to the phenomena they are studying. Therefore, these social structures act as causal forces or generative mechanisms to produce the realities experienced at the ‘*empirical*’ level (Fletcher, 2017; Danermark et al., 2019). Although it is considered that “critical realism's major purpose is to explain social occurrences via reference to these causal processes and the consequences, they can have across the layers of realities,” no one level is preferable to the others (Fletcher, 2017, p.183). The relationship and interactions among the three layers of realities are rather “activity-dependent in that “*causal mechanisms ‘exist only in virtue of the activities they govern and cannot be empirically identified independently of them*” (Bhaskar, 1979, cited in Fletcher, 2017, p.183).

4.4.2 The rationale for adopting a critical realist perspective for the research design

The main strength of critical realism is its ability to engage in explanation and causal analysis through the researcher's common sense and experience (Danermark et al., 2002; Fletcher, 2017; Saunders et al., 2019). Danermark (2019) noted that although critical realism has been criticised for being generalist, it provides a practical explanation for observable events by looking for the underlying causal mechanisms through which deep social structures shape everyday organisational life (Saunders et al., 2019). It also helps "*researchers to explain social events and suggest practical policy recommendations to address social problems*" (Fletcher, 2017, p. 181). Therefore, researchers who employ critical realism focus on identifying the mechanisms of social structures that brought about the studied phenomena. These mechanisms cannot be reduced to statistical correlations and quantitative methods (Saunders et al., 2019, p. 140).

Pawson and Tilley (1997) proposed a realist evaluation for complex program interventions characterised by varying and abductive outcomes. In this study, Critical realism is considered appropriate for this study. EA is widely employed to manage complexity (Banaeianjahromi & Smolander, 2019).

4.5 THE CRITICAL REALIST INTERVIEW Approach in the EA Program

Intervention

The research study seeks to evaluate the causal mechanisms of EA using the TOGAF ADM framework, the context in which these mechanisms occur and the critical success and critical failure factors informing the outcome of the EA program. It seeks to identify the context-mechanism-outcome configuration for these outcomes.

The context-mechanism-outcome configuration approach to realist evaluation is method agnostic. It applies various tools and concepts to refine middle-range theories. It is commonly used in the mixed-method case study (Gilmore et al., 2019; Pawson and Tilley, 2004; Mukumbang et al., 2016b).

This research focuses on the impact of EA mechanisms in healthcare technology programme action to create outcomes. There is the widespread use of realist evaluation in understanding how context influences health interventions by academics, policymakers, and practitioners within healthcare (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016; Prashanth, Marchal, Devadasan, Kegels, & Criel, 2014; Goicolea, Coe, Hurtig, & San Sebastian, 2012; Ranmuthugala et al., 2011).

Why Mechanisms? Realist assessments strive to understand how a programme performs or is anticipated to function within settings, as well as what factors may hinder or encourage good results (Jagosh, 2020a; Pawson, 2006; Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, & Vallières, 2019).

Mechanisms are an essential part of achieving business-IT alignment and are an appreciation of how they impact implementation outcomes. However, the governance of these mechanisms has remained unexplored (Zhang, Chen, & Luo, 2018).

"In view of its multiple viewpoints and artefacts, the discipline of Enterprise Architecture is often regarded as an effective methodology to deal with business-IT alignment (BITA) issues and thus has attracted plenty of research" (p.18933).

"Moreover, the set of complete governance mechanisms of BITA has not been explored" (p.18941).

Moreover, the Extant research on EA management mainly focuses on traditional control mechanisms such as standards and principles, a means by which global businesses (controllers) adopt design constraints on their business strategies in a top-to-bottom manner. (Boh & Yellin, 2006; Richardson et al., 1990; Zachman, 1987). The qualitative interview approach aims to articulate what the study intends to uncover about the aspirations and viewpoints of those involved in the social interactions necessary for the mechanisms of the EA program intervention.

Organizations are "networked" by their socio-material construction. According to Sousa and Machado (2014), IT alignment to business needs is not a single dimension but an enactment of technology on one hand and information systems on the other. They describe information systems as an entanglement of the organization's structure, strategy, and culture at several levels to create a

holistic demand for the organization. Entanglement is consistent with the notion of Sociomateriality by Orlikowski and Scott (2008). Chan (2002) argues that socio-material entanglement is essential in transformations. It emphasises the importance of interdependence and coevolution of technology and information systems.

Boh and Yellin's control mechanisms for IT alignment have already been established. Given that Information Technology (IT) alignment is conceptualised as a sociomaterial entanglement, it stands to reason that a comprehensive understanding of control mechanisms is indispensable to achieving IT alignment. This understanding notably influences both the organisational structure and culture, as per the observations of Boh & Yellin (2006). It becomes a Sociomaterial construction defined by Orlikowski and Scott (2008). *"It emphasizes principles of interdependence and coevolution. Furthermore, decision-making and business processes are being overhauled to fit better with 'networked' organizations that defy old hierarchical models"* (p.570).

The use of EA for IT strategic alignment has already been stated in the extant literature review of this thesis. Realist evaluation enables us to understand the impact of the program's mechanisms being evaluated. Therefore, the notion of Sociomaterial enactment in strategic IT alignment is a significant consideration for using the realist evaluation to evaluate programmes and policies of human services for their effectiveness (Kazi, 2003).

According to Pawson and Tilley (1997), the realism evaluation methodology is method-neutral. Nonetheless, it implies that a formal interviewing approach alone is insufficient to understand how the EA programme works, for whom, and under what conditions for the Program's theory. They put forward a combination of theory-driven and 'realist interviews' to address this insufficiency. However, the variety of qualitative interviewing with a theory-driven data collection approach is uncommon (Manzano, 2016).

"Qualitative research questions, then, need to articulate what a researcher wants to know about the intentions and perspectives of those involved in social interactions" (Agee, 2009, p.2).

Building upon Bhaskar's underlying ontological proposition, the researcher posits that causal mechanisms within Enterprise Architecture (EA) are set into motion within a specific context over a period of time, leading to the creation of outcomes within that same context (Bhaskar, 1979). The research seeks to uncover these causal pathways, the Mechanisms and the context that determine the Outcomes of EA programmes. Based on a theory-led approach, the realist evaluation (Westhorp, 2014; Wong et al., 2016) seeks to draw on the contribution of Pawson and Tilley (1997) by combining the context, mechanism output configuration with the Architecture development TOGAF framework (The Open Group, 2018) in identifying the critical success factors and critical failure factors of the management of EA in Healthcare organizations.

Over the last 20 years, the realist evaluation has effectively featured in research, including healthcare management policies, programmes, and interventions (Wong et al., 2016).

(Kazi, 2003) argue the value-enhancing effect of realist evaluations in services to humans within an open system.

As part of helping to improve the refinement of theoretical models, the realist evaluation contributes to enhancing the theory content in the Practice of the programmes, interventions, and theories.

Kazi and Spurling (2000) argue that *"realist evaluation research is about improving the construction of [theories or] models, and therefore about improving the content of the practice itself"* (p.4).

As Pawson and Sridharan (2009) and (Sharpe (2011) argued, realist evaluation is an incarnation of the underpinning theoretical frameworks that inform them but, most importantly, evaluate the programmes or interventions themselves, the basis for its application in the research.

4.6 The Realist evaluation interviewing of EA Management

As adopted in this research, the qualitative realist evaluation approach to interviewing has been criticized by Bendassolli (2013) as being unwieldy because it lacks specificity. Realist research is, however, agnostic to the method and, as a result, amenable to qualitative interviewing for theory-led evaluations.

According to Pawson and Tilley (1997), traditional interviewing techniques of a qualitative nature might not be suitable as a means for preliminary theory in Chapter 3, verification. They argue that *"if one puts a straight question, then most of the time one gets a straight answer"*(p.165), a notion implicitly shared between the researcher and the interview respondent.

A data-driven approach, on the contrary, common in realist studies, is problematic in that they fail to offer an opportunity for respondents to scrutinize the underlying theoretical frameworks that underpin the research (Emmel, 2015; Manzano, 2016). Therefore, the realist interview technique focuses on *"a situation in which the theoretical postulates/conceptual structures under investigation are open for inspection in a way that allows the respondent to make an informed and critical account of them"* (Pawson, 1996, p.313).

Furthermore, according to Maxwell (2012a), qualitative interviews provide rich, detailed data that offer deep insights into participants' experiences and perspectives. Qualitative interviews' flexible and open-ended nature allows for exploring nuances and complexities, thereby contributing to a realist evaluation study's depth and breadth of understanding.

4.7 The realist interviewing approach in determining the critical Failure Factors and critical success factors in EA Management

The evaluation elicits the theoretical program framework (Westhorp, 2014), drawing on the TOGAF Architecture development framework and the context-mechanism-output configuration.

The next step involves hypothesis testing the cases under investigation to verify whether the TOGAF ADM and Mechanism-context-outcome configuration program theories are applicable (Manzano, 2016), drawing on the realist interview technique Pawson (1996, p.304) proposes. This technique is made up of teacher-learning and conceptual focusing functions.

The participants are presented with the teacher-leaning function with the TOGAF ADM and Mechanism-context-output configuration formal descriptions of the initial Program for scrutiny. The

participants are then offered a choice to elucidate their thoughts on the researcher's theory drawing on their ideas, events, and experiences, conceptually focusing on the EA function.

There are defined methods for deducing the initial program theory of EA program theory. Still, the exploratory interview method applied during theory-gleaning could clarify the content and context of the Management of an EA programme. Connelly (2001) backs up this theory-gleaning thesis. They contend that the realist interview, as a data-gathering tool, is the primary source for identifying and visualising the generative processes at work in the particular setting under consideration.

In this study, the specific mechanisms of EA are based on the TOGAF architecture development method (TOGAF, 2018). The context under examination is the conceptual framework of structure, culture, relations, and agency, as outlined in Chapter 3.

Manzano (2016) argues that applying theory-gleaning and theory-consolidation combined with other systematic literature reviews, observations, and relevant data collection approaches is central to acquiring a more relevant EA program theory desired outcomes. This approach is consistent with the teaching-learning function of realist interviewing and emphasizes the need for an expert position rather than naivety (Kvale, 1996, p.33). Pawson and Tilley (1997) use the phrase "*I will show you my theory if you show me yours*" (p.169) to capture the teacher-learning dialogue between researcher and interviewee. Therefore, the interviewee understands the EA program and can make sense of the interview questions during the interviewing process. The interviewer, in turn, can then make the connection between the interviewee's responses through the lens of the conceptual framework. Apart from being a source of information, the participant becomes a party to making meaning in the research process.

In the interview process, the conceptual focusing function, the TOGAF Architecture development method and the context-mechanism-output configuration of the EA program under evaluation are applied to solicit responses to the interview questions. The focus is on how the respondent's thoughts and decision-making are influenced by their theory of the EA program implementation.

According to Pawson (1996), the 'generative mechanisms' of the EA "program often lies with the informant as s/he describes the detailed way in which reasoning contributes to the observed outcomes" (p.303). Therefore, the critical success or failure factors lie in applying the generative mechanisms and the respondent's reasoning and ideas, the focal attributes of this research.

The "knowledgeability" of the interviewees in EA Management is an essential consideration in realist evaluation research (Pawson & Tilley, p.160-161); as such, participants are drawn from Architecture practitioners with significant knowledge and experience in the TOGAF Architecture development method mechanisms. "Practitioners" and "subjects" of EA program interventions, contexts, actors, and outcomes were essential in selecting interviewees critical to the exploration. The interview approach is illustrated in **Figure 4.5**.

Figure 4.5. The Realist Interview Approach to EA Program Intervention was abstracted from Pawson and Tilley (1997), Bhaskar (2009), TOGAF (2018), de Souza (2013), and Mukumbang et al. (2020).

This approach to realist research explores the assumptions and aspirations of EA program theories, in this case, the TOGAF ADM. It also explores the experiences and sensitivities of the various actors within the EA program under study and how they build, influence, and maintain everyday actions.

4.8 Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis

The interview data is collected and analysed through qualitative semi-structured interviews and document analysis. An online survey was used at the last stage of the data collection process to reconfirm the discoveries of the first and second phases.

The research aims to explain the mechanisms in social systems that contribute to EA failure or success (see research questions, aims, and objectives). The critical realist theory characterises mechanisms as often hidden with generative causal powers that produce outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh, 2018; Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012). Accordingly, data collection and analysis approaches must have the power to analyse and synthesize meaningfully to uncover these ‘often hidden mechanisms. *“Qualitative approaches are often used to explore the context features, the underlining mechanism, and the intervention modalities. In other words, the qualitative methods allow for the identification of the constraints and opportunities the program offers, the relevant context elements, the generative mechanisms (reasoning and the choices of the actors), and the behaviours of the actors’ emergent demi-regularities”* (Mukumbang et al., 2020, p.490).

Qualitative methods may be used to analyse complex social processes, capture critical features of phenomena from the study's and participants' perspectives, and discover participants' beliefs, values, and motivations (Curry, Nembhard & Bradley, 2009; Malterud, 2001).

In Aristotelian philosophy, causation is founded on structural-systemic reasoning (Aristotle, 1941). Toomela (2010) contends that structural-systemic research, which is based on Aristotelian reasoning, is aimed at understanding the structure that underlies the researched processes rather than determining cause-effect connections between events that have no possible connection to the understanding of the structures that underpin the processes. Toomela contends that the Aristotelian philosophy of knowing the reasons for an event is *"to explain, [and] to know why"* (p.6), implying that the quantitative approach is ineffective for answering inquiries about the structures and processes that underpin observed behaviours. Scientific understanding necessitates the delineation of individual components,

their exclusive interplays, the characteristics that embody the novel structure resulting from the amalgamation of these elements, and the intricate interactions associated with the emergence of this structure (Toomela, 2009, 2010). Critical realist methodology alters our perspective on the process of empirical data collection. For example, while conducting qualitative interviews, a realist approach averts the temptation to merely transform research technique questions into research interview questions. Realist research interview questions enable a researcher to obtain responses pertinent to research methodology queries (Maxwell, 2012, p.104)—inquiries in research methodology direct attention to the areas that require exploration and comprehension.

There must be some latitude in how interview questions are constructed to extract the specific interplay of causal mechanisms in a particular setting. On the one hand, methodological investigations seek to understand the causal processes of the action in each context to replicate specific results (Pawson, 2002a; Pawson & Tilley, 1997). On the other hand, research interview questions are tailored to the actual particularity of a particular environment.

Likewise, such knowledge enables us to understand better how a causal mechanism acts and under what conditions it is engaged (Sayer, 2000, p.14). It entails a thorough study approach “*mainly concerned with what causes things to happen in certain circumstances, or, in more anthropological terms, what type of meaning universe exists in a given scenario*” (Sayer, 2000, p.20). While variables may help to explain behavioural patterns, they are typically insufficient for characterising the social structures and their associated powers and capacities (causal processes) that support such patterns. According to Maxwell (2012, p.38-40), a realistic approach to qualitative research allows for the analysis of causal linkages within a single case study without variable control.

4.9 Validity and generalisation of research findings

The realist tendency is to return to the theoretical drawing board to deepen our knowledge of the risk enhancement process to separate and compare the various outcomes. However, the ultimate validity

challenge is not whether the elicited CMO configurations reflect a subject's attitudes or if a prolonged citation of their words accurately reflects their beliefs.

The experimental technique establishes the causal regularity with which programme A affects outcome B. This process is achieved by first addressing 'internal validity and excluding additional effects, C, which may have contributed to B by statistical or experimental control. Generalization is accomplished in realism research by extending this reasoning to concepts of 'external validity,' The programme is duplicated in various settings to ensure uniformity in the face of a more diverse collection of possible confounding factors (C). The paradox is that to generalise, one must identify and regulate every possible confounding factor, even infinite. The existential implication is widespread confidence in empirical generalisations, even though no one has claimed to have discovered a programme with such effects (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

It is not a matter of comprehending a program's usual generalisation in its regular activity. Rather than that, generalisation is fundamentally an abstraction process. *"External validity in a more modest way by showing that, with proper attention to the contextual features of every case, evaluation research can be more than the sum of the individual cases" (p.28).*

According to Yin (2018), generalisations of research finding in the physical and life sciences are usually based on multiple experiments replicated across different conditions with no guarantee of consistency, as results can fluctuate over time. As such, the overarching aim of the research is not generalised to the entire population of the universe but theoretical propositions.

"Neither the case, the [CMO configurations] nor the case study, like the experiments, represent samples. Rather, in doing case study research, [the] goal will be to expand and generalise theories (analytical generalisations) and not to extrapolate probabilities (statistical generalisations)" (p.21).

The research findings are generalisable but must be tested against contextual factors since these cannot be replicated in future programmes.

4.10 Recruitment Process and Sampling Strategy

This section explains “*how a participant in the research evaluation was recruited or engaged and how their interviews, experiences, and perceptions contributed to the development, support, refutation, or refinement of programme theory*” (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Wong et al., 2016).

This section describes how the researcher identified and negotiated access to participants. It explained the selection strategy employed in this study. Purposeful sampling was applied in this qualitative research. Purposeful sampling identifies data-rich instances that give the most insight into the research questions.

Emmel (2013) argues that purposeful sampling is critical in research because it identifies examples with a wealth of information that can be investigated in detail. According to Emmel, for realists, participant narratives, descriptions of experiences and events, do not provide the factual dimensions necessary for developing critical cases. Rather than that, they are chances to test and develop concepts, and initial programme theories, to verify and invalidate hypotheses. What matters is how insights into events and experiences are employed for interpretation, explanation, and research claims, rather than the number of instances obtained. Realist sampling methodologies seek detailed descriptions that widen the descriptive baseline for the selected examples, exposing how events are felt, perceived, understood, and accepted in specific situations and circumstances.

Realists will want to understand how each case contributes to the research's interpretation and explanation work and how ideas are tested and refined inside and between cases.

Purposefulness suggests finding information-rich cases that can be investigated in-depth (Strauss and Corbin, 1990; Morse, 2003). The research, explaining critical failure factors and critical success factors of EA implementations, seeks to uncover what [EA] mechanisms work or do not, for whom, under what circumstance and why’ (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

It focuses on uncovering mechanisms of EA, hidden and unhidden, the circumstance under which these mechanisms are triggered, and the nature of the resulting outcomes.

According to Emmel (2013), purposive sampling is the most pragmatic approach for qualitative research. “*The detail and richness of narrative we seek in qualitative research mean that it is inevitable that qualitative samples are small*” (p.4). Patton (2002a) invites researchers to consider what is believed is real, challenge what is known, and delve into how to believe what is known. Patton describes sampling as deliberate.

Patton (2002b) argues that purposeful sampling strategies are appropriate for critical cases, theory-based or operational constructs, or homogenous interviews based on assertions without evidence.

Saturation and information power were achieved after the 12 participants were interviewed and the data analysed. According to Mason (2010), Fusch and Ness (2015) and Sykes et al. (2018), theoretical saturation is the most common justification for stated sample size in qualitative research.

Mason argues for interpretation where, for practical reasons, the quota of context, situations, and social interactions starts with a number. Evidence is collected and interpreted to bring ideas into play as the research describes and re-describes cases. There is no prescribed sample size.

All participants were internal to the organisation within which this research was undertaken. One participant, however, is a technology supplier to the NHS Care Records Service programme. Participants are drawn from middle to senior clinical informatics experts, Clinician Consultants, Senior Nurses, Senior digital transformation leads, Enterprise Architects, Chief Clinical Information officers and Senior Directors. Participants were all actively engaged in the programme. Each had at least 12 years of experience across the implementing organisation and its technology solutions and suppliers in the digital transformation programmes. As such, the information provided was rich and detailed.

According to Marshall (1996), a qualitative study's sample size should “*adequately address the research question/s*” (p.522). As stated by Morse (2000), the scope, nature, design, and quality of the study's data are important factors in determining the most appropriate sample size for qualitative designs, while Sandelowski (1995) states that the research method and sampling technique used is a

matter of researcher judgement and experience. Malterud et al. (2015) advise using ‘information power’ to help choose sample size. It is founded on the premise that “*the more information the sample possesses relevant to the particular study, the [fewer] participants are needed*” (Malterud et al., 2015, p. 1754).

Emmel argues that rather than the sample size, judgement depends on “*a deep exploration of how processes work in particular contexts, under certain sets of circumstances, and in particular sets of social relations*” (p.9). it enables the researcher to construct a persuasive analytical narrative by exploring the process's richness, complexity, and depth.

A semi-structured interview instrument applied by Guest et al. (2006) reported that a significant outcome of their study was elicited after 12 interviews, 100 of the 107 codes (93.45 per cent) were identified, and 97 per cent of the adjustments to these codes were made. Some notable sample sizes and their usage are shown in **Table 4.2** (Cresswell, 2002, 2006; Guest et al., 2006; Kuzel, 1992; Morse, 2000; Stake & Schwandt, 2006).

Table 4.2. Some illustrative sample sizing for qualitative research

Author	Sample Size(<i>n</i>)	When the Sample Size is Used
Kuzel (1992)	6-8	Kuzel used a homogeneous sample with assertions from participants with no evidence.
Kuzel (1992)	12-20	Kuzel used a homogeneous sample of profiles based on participant assertions with no evidence. When looking for disconfirming evidence, Kuzel used a heterogeneous sample to achieve maximum variation through participant assertions with no evidence.

Guest et al. (2006, p.79)	12	Guest et al. argue that <i>“for most research enterprises ... in which the aim is to understand common perceptions and experiences among a group of relatively homogeneous individuals, twelve interviews should suffice”</i> (p.79).
Stake & Schwandt (2006)	4-10	Single case
Cresswell (2002)	5-25	Cresswell used an Open-ended, structured, or semi-structured interview in narrative research.
Cresswell (2006)	4-10	Cresswell used a single case
Morse (2000, p.225)	At least 6	Morse aimed to understand the essence of experiences.

4.10.1 Ethical Approval

With ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee, the letters, emails and phone call correspondents were sent to potential participants. Letters were sent to 13 suitable participants with a participant information sheet, shown in Appendix B, and the ethical approval form, shown in Appendix A. Whilst no responses were received from some, 30 respondents responded to the request for participation, with five declining. Out of the remainder, fifteen were deemed to be suitable participants because of their closeness, knowledge, and involvement in the digital transformation programmes of the NHS. Some were personally known to the researcher, having worked for the organisation where the research is located. Interviews were then scheduled for the participants. All interviews were conducted via Zoom. It was due to Covid-19 Pandemic restrictions and for the convenience of participants.

4.10.2 Sampling, Access, and Recruitment Strategy

The realist methodology relies on expert knowledge to synthesise realist evaluative research about programmes. Experts include researchers and practitioners working in the field under study. They ensure the review is targeted and the evidence is understood adequately to create results with broad validity (Killaspy, King, Holloway et al., 2017).

NHS Digital is an agency of the NHS responsible for digital technology. Others include the technology departments of healthcare provider organisations such as Ambulance services, clinics, and hospitals in England. The study population includes participants, practitioners, and policy-makers (Pawson & Tilley, 1997) implementing professionals and end-users of the integrated electronic health record system of the National Care record programme. These professionals and experts include Enterprise Architects, Technical Architects, Programme Directors, transformation leaders, Clinicians, Doctors and Nurses, Clinical Leads, Chief Information Officers, Health Informaticians, and key decision-makers across the NHS. These professionals' viewpoints enabled the researcher to explain and analyse how EA is implemented in healthcare. Data from these viewpoints were instrumental in identifying potential factors critical to the success or failure of EA implementation in healthcare organisations.

A participant is a person from whom case study data are collected (Yin, 2018, p.287).

According to Robson (2011), Gaining access to participants is critical to the research process. "Issues regarding access vary to a considerable extent with the kind of task you are carrying out and the nature of the organisation concerned" (p.400). Devers and Frankel (2000) observed that if the researcher cannot secure the subjects' participation, the research cannot occur (p.265). In qualitative research, enabling access to participants requires that the researcher build rapport and support a good relationship with the potential participants (Devers & Frankel, 2000; Emmel et al., 2007). Hence, identifying and gaining access to these professionals was essential in this study. Some potential participants are from existing social networks, i.e., colleagues who had worked on a similar project.

They were a good point of contact and acted partly as gatekeepers in participant recruitment. As Devers and Frankel (2000) argue, starting from my social network is beneficial in gaining access to other potential participants. It does not, in any way, relate to a snowball sampling strategy. Instead, the researcher could find decision-makers and other end users through networks (e.g., a friend of a colleague). The researcher looked through colleagues' profiles to find any contact whose profile fits the participants' criteria needed for this study.

The participant has been selected following discussions with them to seek their informed consent. The researcher discussed the issue of harm and deception with them and assured them that measures had been taken to protect their identity. No vulnerable persons were involved in this study, only professional adults who had reached the Participants' consent age. Participants were selected equitably across gender and ethnicity who have at least five years of experience situated in the case (Yin, 2018, p.88).

Language barriers were removed by mandating that participants communicate in English, the researcher's language, to avoid research purpose ambiguity and inadvertent participant deception (Yin, 2018). A summary of the selection criteria is shown in **Table 4.3**.

Table 4.3. Participants' selection criteria

Location	The participants must live in the UK and be employed by the NHS, where the case is located.
In-depth knowledge of the Programme	Must have worked on the Care Record System (CRS) Programme in the UK as a Clinician user, implementer, or decision-maker with extensive experience.
Relevant experience	Participants must have at least ten years of relevant experience either as a user or an implementer of aspects of the CRS.

4.10.3 Selection Of Participants

Participant selection is flexible in qualitative research (Crowe et al., 2011; Robson, 2011; Gall et al., 2007). Crowe et al. (2011) noted that the sample size needed for qualitative studies is smaller than that required for quantitative studies. Hence, care ensures that the recruited participants fit well for the research (Bryman & Cramer, 2012). A “purposive sampling strategy” was employed in finding potential participants. Purposive sampling is the best and most used sampling strategy in qualitative research (Devers and Frankel, 2000; Robson, 2011; Bryman & Cramer2012). Purposive sampling was mainly through social networks and LinkedIn. Employing the process helped find potential participants that could supply data “relevant to the research questions being posed’ (Bryman & Cramer, 2012).

In order words, purposive sampling enabled the selection of prospective participants that are “*information-rich concerning the purpose of the study*” (Gall et al., 2007, p.20). A total of 45 prospective participants were found. However, only 12 participants agreed and consented to participate in all the data collection stages. The reason for recruiting an extensive panel of experts is that it is difficult to predict the number of participants participating in all stages of the research. Nworie (2011) explained that participants’ attrition rate could be a significant issue. The demographics of the research participants are presented in **Table 4.4**. It is noteworthy that the participant names in **Table 4.4** are pseudonyms.

Table 4.4. Expert Participants' Profiles.

Participant	Relevant Years' Experience	Job Description	Role	Organisation/setting
Participant one	21	Global Health Policy Lead	Supplier/Vendor, Health Policy Lead	External
Participant Two	18	Regional Director of Digital Transformation	Decision-maker/Senior Leadership	Internal
Participant Three	20	Technical Architect	Design Architect on Programme	Internal

Participant Four	22	Clinical IT Systems Transformation Facilitator	Implementation and Assurance and health informatics	Internal
Participant Five	15	IT Strategy, Architecture and Product Design Lead	Designer, Architect, and IT strategist	Internal
Participant Six	27	Chief Clinical Information Officer (CCIO)	Clinician, Senior Leader, and User	Internal
Participant Seven	24	IT Assurance Lead - API Management	Designer and assurance lead	Internal
Participant Eight	15	Head Of Business Engagement	Engaging with the organisation to understand business objectives	Internal
Participant Nine	29	Consultant Clinical Psychiatrist	Senior Clinician User	Internal
Participant Ten	20	Lead Enterprise Architect/Chief Technology Officer (CTO)	Enterprise Architect and chief technology officer. Senior Technology leader	Internal
Participant Eleven	19	Clinical Transformation IT Lead and Staff Nurse	digital transformation Leader and staff nurse	Internal
Participant Twelve	20	Clinician Consultant Clinical Psychiatrist	Clinician (Doctor) and user	Internal

4.10.4 Internet-mediated Access

Although some were previous colleagues, their latest profiles and access were found on LinkedIn.com, a professional social networking site.

"Quantitative and Issues associated with Internet-mediated access qualitative data collection techniques are increasingly used via the Internet." (Saunders et al., 2016, p.220).

Stieger and Goritz (2006), Fenner et al. (2012), Arcia(2014) and Pedersen & Kurz (2016) used social networking to recruit participants and email and instant messaging to conduct interviews.

Their respective organisations obtained ethical considerations around participants' permission to share information openly. Information retrieved from participants was about technology resources,

and no personal- identifiable or personal information was obtained. Aliases were used to protect the identity and confidentiality of participants in the research.

4.11 Retroduction: A Conceptual Configuration Approach EA Research and Generative Mechanisms

A retroductive approach is required for realistic evaluative research in data analysis. Retroduction is the “*identification of hidden causal forces that lie behind identified patterns or changes in those patterns*” (Wong et al., 2016, p.1) of the reasoning and reactions of the technology programmes' development and implementation.

“In realist evaluation, the retroductive question is about the causal powers of the policy or programme” (p.2).

Its use in this research is underpinned by the argument that mechanisms are triggered in context to produce context-dependent programme outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh, 2020a). Therefore, retroduction enables the researcher to capture the causal powers of the mechanisms in the EA programmes. The research aims to determine what worked for whom, when, and under what circumstances of the technology implementation.

Various descriptions have been postulated to explain the retroduction, sometimes called retroductive or abductive reasoning (Jagosh, 2020b).

Lewis-Beck, Bryman, and Liao (2004) describe retroduction as an idea that involves going ‘back from, below, or behind’ observable patterns of regularities to unearth what causes them.

According to Saunders et al. (2016), retroduction is sometimes called abduction and abductive reasoning. Retroduction uses inductive and deductive approaches to data analysis (Gilmore et al., 2019).

“A requirement for realist evaluation research is that data analysis takes a “retroductive” approach (p.1). Untested conclusions are derived from known premises in induction. In deductive reasoning, the conclusion must be true if the premise is true.

An abductive approach is applied in this research where available premises are drawn from previous research in EA. Notably, from critical realism Bhaskar (1978), Pawson and Tilley (1997), context-dependent mechanisms in the context of social action Archer (1996), and context-mechanism-outcome configuration Pawson and Tilley (1997); de Souza (2013) and Jagosh (2018), to generate testable conclusions on critical success and critical failure factors in the management of EA.

In the retroductive approach, the generalizability of the findings is the interactions within the specific context of the research. Retroduction applies inductive and deductive reasoning of the researcher's intuition to establish generative causality by examining the underpinning psychosocial drivers determining programme outcomes (Gilmore et al., 2019).

The data collected from the participants form the basis for exploring critical success and failure factors for EA implementations. The data identify themes within the devised conceptual framework and test. The conceptual framework may be modified and added to existing theories applicable to construct other EA theories of amending existing theories (Saunders et al., 2016, p.145). Although retroduction is method agnostic, it is commonly applied in a mixed case study approach (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Westhorp, 2014).

Mingers argues that retroduction is the process of taking *"some unexplained phenomenon and [proposing]hypothetical mechanisms that, if they existed, would generate or cause that which is to be explained"* (Mingers,2004, p.94-95).

"Retroduction is a mode of inference in which events are explained by postulating mechanisms which are capable of producing them" (Wynn Jr & Williams, 2012, p.799).

Tsang (2014) argues that *"retroduction presents a logical argument explaining what properties must exist for the phenomenon of interest to exist and be what it is."* (p.181). According to Tsang (2014), retroduction may be categorised into four subcategories, confusing retroductive mechanisms.

Firstly, "Overcoded" retroduction occurs when explanations are apparent from existing knowledge.

In 'overcoded' retroduction, mechanisms that explain a situation are reasoned abductively automatic

or semi-automatic. Secondly, retrodution may be "Undercoded". Undercoded retrodution, the researcher's function is to select the most likely mechanism from several potential mechanisms in the context of the investigation.

Thirdly, retrodution can be creative, where the researcher brings to bear their creativity by formulating mechanisms without befitting mechanisms.

Mingers and Standing (2017) argue for two distinct forms of retrodution based on diachronic mechanisms as processes occurring over time and synchronic mechanisms that happen in each moment to create emergence phenomena. In Meta-retrodution, methodological or conceptual paradigm shifts may be invented to align with such conceptual frameworks and empirical observations. Finally, retrodution may be meta-reproductive.

4.12 The TOGAF ADM in EA Program Management and The Phases in the realist interview applied to the Research.

Pawson and Tilley (1997) propose the context-mechanism-outcome configuration for realist evaluation research. The context-mechanism-outcome 'configuration' combines with the TOGAF ADM to construct the EA program theoretical framework discussed in Chapter 3. The initial programme theory or the conceptual theory drives this research.

The realist interview is categorised into 4 phases, as shown in **Figure 4.6**. Phase 1 is the theory-gleaning phase, where the initial programme theory of the EA programme is formulated. Phase 2 is a theory-testing phase of the gleaned interview. Phase 3 consolidates the tested theory, and phase 4 refines the CMO configurations into critical failure and success factors. Mechanisms are activated in context to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Power et al., 2019; Jagosh, 2020b). The ranked consolidated outcome constitutes the expected transformation or invariance of the implementation in a mechanism's context and outcome configuration in each causal pathway.

Figure 4.6. The realist research interview phases of the EA Programmes Interview Process. Reference: (Mukumbang et al., 2020; Yin, 2018).

Manzano proposes three types of interviews for realistic evaluation; *"theory gleaning"*, *"theory refinement"*, and *"theory consolidation"* as a guide to obtaining participant responses to test the conceptual frameworks of the Program under evaluation Manzano (2016, p.343).

4.12.1 Phase 1 of the study interview: The EA programme theory gleaning.

In this phase, the study aims to solicit participants' input on the data sources from the extant literature under review that is used to formulate the theoretical framework in Chapter 3 to gain an understanding of how, why, to whom, and under what circumstances the technology programme worked or otherwise (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Mukumbang et al., 2020).

Figure 4.7. Phase 1: The Theory Gleaning Interview Process. Source: (Mukumbang et al., 2020).

Figure 4.7 depicts how the experiences and assumptions of the EA programme actors, designers, decision-makers, clinicians and implementors were elicited. The theory-gleaning phase provides the basis for grouping, framing, and arranging, explaining their rationale (Andersen & Kragh, 2010; Grisot, Hanseth & Thorseng, 2014; Agerfalk, Conboy & Myers, 2020; Dietz et al., 2013).

Pawson and Tilley (1997) propose these actors as credible sources of insight. They further argue that these actors are involved in the programme's implementation and, as such, serve as a valuable source of organisational memory. They are also aware of the environmental context of the technology programme within which the EA implementation is embedded and, therefore, are likely to contribute practical knowledge about the Program. EA Practitioners, Architects, Clinicians, and middle to Senior-level managers are well-placed to provide insight for the theory-gleaning phase (Mukumbang et al., 2016b). In this phase, questions about the Enterprise Architect within the programme are exploratory. The aim is to understand as such; a semi-structured in-depth interview technique is applied.

Questions are posed to solicit feedback from respondents about observed and emergent outcomes of the EA Program. How do the resources provide for the Program lead to change to glean the technology programme's relevant contexts and causal social and technical mechanisms?

Furthermore, to clarify the mechanism-context-configuration, a review of the extant literature on the value of EA implementation and how they explain the outcomes of EA programmes. A retroductive approach is implemented to produce the initial programme theories of programmes from the interview transcripts. The output of the retroductive theorizing techniques generates a logical roadmap of aligned attributes within a case, as experienced by respondents (Danermark, 2002; Jagosh et al., 2014; Byrne & Callaghan, 2013; Jagosh, 2019). These attributes constitute the elements of the realist heuristic instrument, the mechanism-context-outcome configuration of the EA program, drawn from Pawson and Tilley (1997, 2004).

Figure 4.8. Building Blocks of the Context-Mechanisms-Outcome Configuration Roadmap of The EA Program Theory, abstracted from Archer 1995; Pawson and Tilley (1997), de Souza (2013), The Open Group (2018), Bhaskar (2009), and Jagosh (2020a).

Figure 4.8 depicts the midrange theory or conceptual framework elicited from the theoretical literature and reports about the NHS CRS programme showing how participants' ideas and experiences are used as input to test it. Processes or programme activities are elicited from participants' ideas of the programme. Context broadly represents the circumstances under which the mechanisms are triggered, the “backdrop of programs and research” (Jagosh et al., 2015, p.3). The reviewed theoretical literature and reports about the programmes indicate that culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure were the most important contextual influences. These may be refined following data analysis to uncover other contextual influences (Archer, 1995; NOA, 2020a;

NOA, 2020; NHS Digital, 2021a; NHS Digital, 2021b; DHSC, 2018). The triggered mechanisms of the CRS programme may contribute to intended outcomes (M+) or may impact negatively on outcomes (M-) (Jagosh, 2020a). Outcomes (o) may be transformative or reproductive (the action context) of the organisation's current state where outcomes are misaligned with the organisation's objectives and goals (Archer, 1995). **Table 4.5** shows some definitions of terms used in the CMO configuration definitions.

Table 4.5 defines the EA programme theory's relevant CMO configuration terms and coding frames. Source: (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Mukumbang et al., 2020).

EA Configuration Element	Description of the configuration Element of the EA Program	Coding Rule of the EA Program Intervention	Abbreviation
EA Intervention	An intervention is a combination of EA program elements or strategies designed to produce behaviour changes or improve value of the expected outcomes of the program.	Modalities or program activities of the EA program to improve strategi alignment with the organisation objectives or vision.	E
Context	Context refers to primary circumstances that are likely to validate or drive the activation of EA program mechanisms.	Elements of both the physical and the social environment of the EA program that favour or disfavour the expected outcomes. These elements include Structure, culture, agency and relations.	C
Performer	These are the stakeholders, groups, and organisations who play a role in the EA program implementation and outcomes of an E EA intervention	This was coded as the stakeholders or actual practices of a stakeholder, group, or institution on the activities of the EA program intervention.	P
EA Mechanisms	This refers to any underlying program outcome determinants or social behaviours generated in certain contexts.	Any explanation or rationalisation why a service or a resource was used by a stakeholder to achieve an expected EA program outcome, or considered as a limitation.	M
Immediate EA Outcomes	Relates to the immediate ramification of the EA program activities.	Immediate the EA program outcome commonly refers to changes in knowledge, competencies, or realisation, as these types of changes normally precede changes in actions or operations.	ImO
Intermediate EA Outcomes	Intermediate outcomes refer to behavioural changes or ramification that follow the immediate knowledge and awareness changes leading to longitudinal outcomes of the EA program.	Codes here define a move from direct outcomes to intermediate outcomes, identified through the indirect impact of the activity and accountability of the program	InO
Longitudinal EA Outcomes	Touch on changes in the medium-term and long-term, such as a realised values, and impact on strategic alignment of organisational goals of the system that the EA program is intended to deliver value.	The codes constitute the supplemental indirect impact of the activity demonstrating the subsidiary accountability of the EA program intervention. These are longitudinal in nature and complex with emergent characteristics.	LnO

Firstly, the Logical configuration roadmap of the EA program links the triggered causal mechanisms with observed outcomes. These outcomes may be successful or deemed as a failure.

Secondly, the context-dependency is assessed for the EA program mechanisms for their action potential and the actors involved retroductively.

Finally, mechanism-centric counterfactual thinking and rational judgement assess the logical configuration map for clarity and validity. In applying abductive reasoning to the interview transcripts, a possible explanatory context-mechanism-outcome configuration for the program actors

is identified with the causal mechanisms that play a central role (Isaksen, 2016; Timmermans & Tavory, 2014; Wodak & Meyer, 2015). The Program's mechanism-context-outcome configurations are converted into a logical statement in the following phrasal forms (Mukumbang et al., 2018b).

4.12.2 Phase 2 of the study interview: The EA Program theory refinement

In phase 2 of this research, the initial EA program theory elicited from stakeholder interviews is rectified empirically using a semi-structured approach. A semi-structured interview ensures the case study design aligns with the realist evaluation principles. The interview is conducted with open-ended questions (Yin, 2018).

The focus of the conceptual refinement phase of the interview function is to avoid uncertainty and doubt in the eyes of the participants. Therefore, the refinement phase offers contextual help (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.168). It helps to manage contextual difficulties by contextualising the domain of EA in which participants on their reasoning. **Figure 4.9** depicts the theory refinement interview process in phase 2.

Figure 4.9. The EA program theoretical framework is the subject of the phase 2 interview, theory Gleaning. Mukumbang et al. (2020).

In phase 2, the researcher has classified the cases within the program theory into three main themes. The mechanisms of the Program that represents the phenomenon of steady improvement within the 'mechanisms' being explored as typical, the cases that define the successful outcome of the mechanisms critical to the understanding of the phenomenon under study as crucial and the possibilities that capture the negative aspects leading to failure of the EA program as deviating from the expected outcomes (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Gerring, 2009)

The aim of phase 2 of the interview is to refine the conceptual refining function of the EA program theory.

"The researcher's theory is the subject matter of the interview, and the subject is there to confirm or falsify and, above all, to refine that theory" (Pawson, 1996; p.299).

First, the researcher explains the theory to the respondents. Having understood the EA conceptual framework modalities of the interviewer, the participants provided their comments on the EA

program theory based on their ideas, experiences, why, how and under what circumstances they think the EA program worked or not. Semi-structured qualitative data on the first EA programme theory is gathered during the theory refining phase of the research investigation. The EA program's operation was primarily established during the interview-gleaning phase. In the refine phase, the researcher aims to refine the obtained hypothesis by eliciting further impact on the participant's thinking. The refined theory informs and shapes the subsequent phase, the consolidated phase 3, to collect data on the participant priorities of reasoning and ideas concerning the triggered mechanisms, the context of the programme activities, and the EA programme's anticipated outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Adu (2019) argues that interview prompts are a usual method for extracting relevant data from participants concerning the interview questions. The prompts help the researcher follow their line of enquiry, maintain consistency and verbalise the research question in a conversational and unbiased manner (Yin, 2018). **Table 4.6** outlines the interview prompts during the semi-structured interviewing process. The prompts enabled the stream of questions in the case study to be ‘fluid rather than rigid’ (Rubin & Rubin, 2011).

Table 4.6. Interview questions and prompts for participants.

Research Question 1 (RQ1):	What are the Mechanisms for managing EA programs in healthcare organisations?
Interview prompt 1:	<i>“I am interested in what was going on in the design of the technology programme and the driving forces for aligning objectives. What were the mechanisms that triggered the change? Furthermore, how did that work with existing social processes within the organisation?”</i>
Interview prompt 2:	<i>“So, the first thing that I would like to know is what factors you would consider as essential indicators in contributing to the success of the programme?”</i>

Research Question 2 (RQ2):	<i>What critical factors for success and challenges affect EA programs in healthcare?</i>
Interview Prompt 2:	<i>“What were the social and cultural conditions necessary for the mechanisms for change that programme intended to make?”</i>
Interview Prompt 3:	<i>“Have there been successes?”</i>
Interview Prompt 4:	<i>“Have there been challenges?”</i>
Interview Prompt 5:	<i>“And finally, can you tell me about your experiences with the Covid-19 Pandemic in relation to the programme?”</i>

4.12.3 Phase 3 of the study interview. The EA Program theory Consolidation interview

Phase 3, the EA program theory consolidation interview, aims to strengthen or weaken participant support for the refined program theory (Mukumbang et al., 2020). The Refined EA program theories from Phase 2. are consolidated and refined in Phase 3 of the interview. Consolidated and refined EA CMO configuration and the TOGAF ADM of the EA program theories ascertain how they explain, fail to explain, why, and in what circumstances the EA programmes work successfully or are deemed as having failed. **Figure 4.10** depicts the theory refinement interview process in phase 3.

Figure 4.10. The EA program theoretical framework is the subject of the phase 3 interview, theory Refinement and Consolidation. Mukumbang et al. (2020).

Two approaches capture the realistic evaluation interview format (Mukumbang et al., 2020).

First, a conceptual focusing part consolidates the theory via an open conversation with interviewees.

Secondly, the teacher-learner aspect of the interview is conducted through an online Zoom meeting with Enterprise Architects, managers, clinicians, and other key decision-makers.

In this conceptual focusing session, Manzano (2016) argues that theory consolidation " *should be guided with the help of specificities of the individual cases, from there, they can be directed in the general program*" (p.356).

At this stage of conceptual focusing, the interview aims to represent the primary participants' and researchers' interpretation of the mechanisms and how these, in turn, impact the program theory's social actions and context (Wynn Jr & Williams, 2012).

The interview seeks to present the participants' refined and consolidated programme theory for scrutiny in the teacher-learner aspect of this dual approach. This phase rationally reviews the EA program theory formulated in the interview process (Mukumbang et al., 2020).

The teacher-learner role of the researcher's interview, the devised EA program theory (the ADM and the Context-Mechanism-Outcome configuration process), is described to participants of the study to facilitate their understanding.

The researcher finds this to be appropriate, drawing on the argument by Mukumbang et al. (2020, p.504) that "*Judgemental rationality is applied to evaluate and compare the explanatory power of different theoretical explanations and to select theories which most accurately represent the domain of 'real' abductively*".

Following data collection from relevant stakeholders, counterfactual thinking is applied to refine the consolidated EA program theory to the ideas. This process is in keeping with the argument Bhaskar (2009) and Roese (1997) put forward that counterfactual conditions help provide a more significant judgement-based explanatory power of causality in the developing program theory.

Alternative thoughtfulness helps to build confidence in considering the explanatory power of the findings derived from the interviews (Yin, 2013).

The output of the consolidation interview phase, phase 3, is constructing a configurational model or model to portray a big picture of the refined and consolidated EA program theory (Byng et al., 2005). He suggests that providing different CMO configurations of the Program, policy, or intervention adds value to the explanation when they are treated.

This process is achieved retroductively by "*placing the different within-case theories or models in a juxtaposition allowing for the differences and similarities to become clear*" (McAvoy & Butler, 2018; Mukumbang et al., 2020, p.505).

Retroduction is vital in attaining similarities and differences between diverse EA programme scenarios by identifying the most effective processes (Hedstrom & Swedberg, 1998).

Hedstrom and Swedberg's approach is based on the idea that mechanisms determine programme results regarding effect and frequency.

Therefore, the retroductive process highlights the most prominent cases that form the basis of the EA program's critical failure and success factors. In his realist theory of science, Bhaskar (2013) argues that this retroductive process creates the phenomenon of partial and demi-regularities at the actual level of reality.

4.12.4 Conjecturing the CMO Configurations as programme theories and findings

The findings of the evaluative study are contained within the elicited CMO configurations, details of which are provided during the analysis and finding stages. The findings include the mechanism, context, outcomes and whether the CMO configuration represents a critical success or failure factor. The explanation of how these inferences are elicited is explained in the conceptual framework. **Figure 5.1** depicts the elements of a CMO configuration.

Subsequently, Context-Mechanism-Outcomes (CMOs) were evaluated through Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). The uniqueness of these interviews did not pertain to a specific case study but to participants who possessed a broad understanding of the intervention's general functioning. Consequently, it was paramount that the focus of their interviews was directed towards the operational level (Gilmore et al., 2019). This approach was intended not to discredit emerging hypotheses from the case studies but to fortify and substantiate existing ones. If there were differences between the case study results, data was also utilised to determine how the various intervention levels interacted. The KIIs might assist by providing a "systems thinking" perspective on the intervention. Because the KIIs had prior experience working in this socio-ecological sector, this procedure aided in developing theories at the "societal" level. These new MRTs or CMO settings were compared to existing formal theories. The purpose was to identify any ideas that reported on linked causal processes or other elements that may make them more or less plausible. This is known as a "plausibility check" (Marchal et al., 2012; Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, and Vallières, 2019).

4.13 Explanation of the Analysis

The research used a thematic analysis guided by CMO configurations of the interview scripts.

Qualitative methods have used thematic analysis (Tolson et al., 2007; Patton, 2002a). Braun and Clarke (2006) used thematic analysis to derive midrange hypotheses in realist research.

The sample size was at the low end of the choice of sample sizes used in the thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This allowed substantial reflection, dialogue, and time on each transcript. It was consistent with the more latent level of analysis used, which sought to identify underlying ideas about the CRS programme rather than a more superficial descriptive analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

According to Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas (2013), qualitative description methods such as content analysis and thematic are appropriate for use in a relatively low level of interpretation.

Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas argue that research findings are located along a description continuum to interpretation, indicating the degree of data change following the data analysis process.

The boundaries between content and thematic analysis are unclear and exist in a continuum (Sandelowski & Leeman, 2012). They are therefore used interchangeably in this research analysis.

Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas argue that a rebuke has been made *“in all qualitative approaches is that they lack the ‘scientific rigour and” (p.401) ... trustworthiness associated with conventional quantitative methods. “As a practical way to improve rigour in both approaches, researchers are encouraged to maintain a personal research diary” (p.401).* A personal research diary was maintained electronically during the research process.

The research aims to add to the body of knowledge by refining and consolidating the formulated programme theory or conceptual framework in Chapter 3.

“One of the best ways for judging the quality of findings is whether new insights into the studied phenomenon have been provided; if so, the study should have increased the understanding of particular phenomena or informed practical actions” (p.401).

The analysis, therefore, commenced with apriori ideas and concepts based on the extant literature and the conceptual framework. The programme theory, the mechanism-context-outcome configuration of the EA framework, is discussed in Chapter 3.

“When using content analysis, the primary aim is to describe the phenomenon in a conceptual form” (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008).

Content analysis interprets the data. The data represent texts and expressions created from the participant interviews to be perceived as viewed, read, interpreted, and actioned on for their meaning during analysis (Krippendorff, 2004; Graneheim & Lundman, 2017; Vaismoradi, Turunen & Bondas, 2013; Elo & Kyngäs, 2008)

4.14 Trustworthiness

Participants in the research were given written assurance of their confidentiality and their right to withdraw participation from the research at any given time. Their information is irrecoverably purged should they wish to discontinue the research.

“Combined with assurances about anonymity, this should increase the level of confidence in your trustworthiness and reduce the possibility of interviewee or response bias” (Saunders et al., 2016, p.406).

Anonymisation of data, however, had some challenges, finding the balance between compromising the integrity of the data and maximising anonymity to protect the identity of participants. The findings explain what worked in the programmes, for whom and under what circumstances (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Therefore, the job titles for participants have not been anonymised because of the significance in interpreting the findings, as they offer causal explanatory power of the programme's outcome. Therefore, anonymisation was done manually, not automatically, through multiple meetings with correspondence with participants. (Saunders, Kitzinger & Kitzinger, 2015).

“... at times, we have sacrificed some of the integrity of the data in order to maximise [the] anonymity, and at other times, we may have risked compromising anonymity to maintain the integrity of the data” (p.267).

4.15 Ethical Considerations

Ethical consideration is a critical part of this research. Business management research unequivocally involves human actors (Saunders et al., 2016). It is especially so given that this research draws participants who have practised EA in healthcare organisations. Even though no patients are involved, the participants may have interacted with patient data in their work. Participants selected must have good standing during their duty and should not have been dismissed for misconduct from the organisations from where they draw their relevant experiences as participants in this research.

4.16 Summary

Chapter 4 discusses the research design and methodology employed in this study. It justified critical realism as the philosophical stance that drives the study. The chapter argued that critical realism is instrumental in identifying the social structures or mechanisms that inform the success or failure of an EA project. The chapter also described the data collection and analysis methods and procedures. Semi-structured interviews and document analysis were the primary data collection instruments. However, a survey was used in the third stage of the data collection process to capture experts' opinions on the study's findings. The survey was also valuable for triangulation and member-checking purposes. The chapter also highlighted how ethical issues are considered at every study stage. It reflected on the processes and strategies used to ensure the trustworthiness of the research findings.

The realist interview has three phases, theory gleaning, theory refinement and consolidation, which generates the programme theory with a configuration map of the mechanism-context-outcome configuration of the cases.

5 CHAPTER FIVE: ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

The analysis aims to answer the following questions:

- Research question 1 (RQ1): What are the Mechanisms for managing EA programs in healthcare organisations?
- Research question 2 (RQ2): What critical factors and challenges (critical failure factors) impact EA programme delivery in healthcare organisations?

Contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes are generated to form CMO configurations based on the conceptual framework. The unit of analysis is the participants' interview scripts. Twelve interview scripts were transcribed, one for each participant (Wong et al., 2013).

The analysis uses a realist evaluation of EA implementation in a healthcare organisation.

Realist evaluation is progressively being used to evaluate complex healthcare interventions. It aims to give a more explicit and in-depth explanation of “*what works for whom and under what circumstances*” Pawson & Tilley (1997, p.63); Pawson and Manzano-Santaella (2012, p.177). It has been recommended to evaluate integrated care interventions (Nurjono et al., 2018; Salter and Kothari, 2014; Byng, Norman, & Redfern, 2005).

The analysis is utilised to build, support, refute or refine the conceptual label of the Context, Mechanism, or Outcome inside a CMO configuration. Second, it helps the evaluator or researcher conclude the relationship between contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes within a given CMO configuration.

Thirdly, it enables conclusions about (and subsequent confirmation, refutation, or refinement of) the links between CMO configurations – i.e., the position and interactions of CMO configurations inside a programme theory (Wong et al., 2016; Wong et al., 2014; Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012).

The analysis involves allocating themes from each participant's script into separate contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes elements (Jackson & Kolla, 2012; Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, &

Vallières, 2019). It also involves an ongoing analytical, interpretative, and deliberative approach to uncover linked CMO patterns: the vital explanatory components (Jagosh et al., 2015) that might explain how, why, for whom and with what impact(s) the CRS implementation. In this regard, research is the instrument of measurement (Mukumbang et al., 2020; Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

The critical realist evaluation of the technology programme aims to explain the critical success and failure factors of the programme's mechanisms in culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structural contexts. A case study approach collects participant data through a semi-structured interview (Yin, 2018). The data is then analysed using retroductive theorising, interlacing interpretation and the relevant theoretical literature (Jagosh, 2020a). The resulting findings are then consolidated and refined into CMO configurations (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2016; Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, & Vallières, 2019; Jackson & Kolla, 2012). These CMO configurations are the programme theories that answer the research questions, RQ1, the related mechanisms and RQ2, the critical success and failure factors of EA implementations.

5.2 Qualitative Research Design – Analysis Approach

This research analysis aims to explain, using the conceptual framework formulated, that Mechanisms of EA in the context of a healthcare technology programme are triggered to create outcomes.

Mechanisms are contextually triggered to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh, 2020a).

The analysis aims to extract what aspects of the programme worked or did not work for whom and under what circumstances (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

“Realist review cannot rely solely on quantitative analytic techniques to achieve its ends (although it can use them where the available data allows). Its purpose is explanatory, and it needs to be able to explain the conflicting patterns of outcomes that are almost invariably found in reviews of social programs” (Wong et al., p.43).

The research aims to uncover mechanisms with ‘explanatory’ power for generative outcomes in digital transformation programmes that may be aligned or misaligned with the organisation’s goals;

Wong et al. suggest a qualitative approach as appropriate.

The initial programme theory from the academic literature is tested against the participant data and refined (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh et al., 2015). The research findings are limited to the Socio-Technological perspective, a gap in EA research, and this research study's scope. The programme for digital transformation catalyses specific socio-technological Enterprise Architecture mechanisms within a contextual framework encompassing culture, relationships, agency, funding, technology, and structure. These mechanisms are pivotal to the programme's success or failure and thus instrumental in generating transformational outcomes.

Socio-Technological Mechanisms that are triggered have causal pathways; Mechanisms that pose challenges to the programme may lead to failure outcomes. Conversely, Socio-Technological EA mechanisms in the programme lead to successful transformational outcomes.

Therefore, the transcripts from the semi-structured interviews were examined for context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configuration or regularities.

What effect or outcome did the EA mechanisms triggered in the programmes align the organisational or business objectives and goals with the programme's outcome? What triggered these Socio-Technological EA mechanisms? Under what internal and external programme environments (context - culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure) did these occur?

Whether programme outcomes were perceived to be successful or failed was obtained from participant data and retroductively theorised with the extant peer-reviewed theoretical literature (Wong et al., 2016). Each participant's video recording was obtained through a semi-structured interview on Zoom. The audio recordings of the interviews were then extracted and transcribed using online transcription services from Rev.com.

The researcher proofread, identified, and corrected errors in the interview transcripts (Gilmore et al., 2019). The interviewer provided the proofread interview transcripts to each participant to validate, modify, or redact any information confirming whether they included them in their transcript.

There was no redaction request for the interview transcript content; however, some participants clarified or added additional information. The researcher added the requested amendments to the related interview transcript of the participant.

The researcher recorded interviews using Zoom and created video files of the interview. The researcher transcribed the anonymised audio recording using the Rev.com transcription service by uploading them onto the Rev.com online portal. The researcher downloaded and conducted data cleansing on the transcribed information, proofreading and correcting any errors in the transcription. The interview transcripts were sent verbatim to each participant in Microsoft Word for checks and approval. The participants returned the transcripts with minor amendments.

The researcher uploaded interview transcripts onto the NVIVO software as text files and then created cases for each interview participant file. In some cases, additional information was updated in the relevant interview files. The participant transcripts were securely uploaded in textual form to the University of the West of Scotland and secured on Microsoft Onedrive onto the NVIVO software for encoding.

The transcripts were coded using version 12 of the NVIVO software to understand the EA Socio-Technological contexts, mechanisms and outcomes in the technology programmes that informed the participants' experiences. The researcher created codes and themes using content and thematic analysis.

The coding template or model shown in Figure 5.1 for each participant interview transcript lists the configurations identified from the codes and themes during the analysis. Columns for the related themes; phases of the TOGAF ADM, participant comments about the mechanisms triggered in the programme, and the context under which the mechanism triggered (the manipulated variables in the context of culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure) the stated outcomes.

The researcher then compared the identified CMO configurations from the participant interviews in the codes and themes depicted in the table seeking evidence of Socio-Technological programme

mechanisms to corroborate and refine the EA Socio-Technological initial programme theory or conceptual framework. The researcher draws on the theoretical literature, where necessary, to support the researcher’s findings and conclusions. Where the participant data do not corroborate the programme theory, different mechanisms operating in different contexts can provide alternative explanations (Lefroy et al., 2015).

5.3 Generating the CMO Configurations

The analysis process generates CMO configurations through retroductive theorising (Jagosh, 2020b). It involves a backward and forward analysis of the conceptual framework, the literature, and the participant interviews.

5.3.1 Approach to Analysis Process

A realist data analysis attempts to analyse data using realism notions. Realism adheres to a generative explanation for causality. Relevant outcomes were generated by relevant mechanism(s), hidden and unhidden, which are triggered by or could only operate in the programme context (Wong et al., 2016). The analysis elicits CMO configuration within or across the data collected from participants, determining recurrent patterns of CMO configurations (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010; Brown et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2016) about what worked on did not work for whom under what circumstances (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Figure 5.1 shows a template used to extract the relevant attribute that forms the CMO configurations of the study.

Figure 5.1. Extracting the CMO Configuration from participant interviews. Source: Format adapted from (Gilmore et al., 2019, p.7).

Participant Programme theory code (coded in NVIVO) <i>[Keywords for identified Mechanisms]</i>	<i>[Relevant Extract from Participant interview transcript in chronological order]</i>
Source Participant:	<i>[Participant identification and role in the Programme]</i>

Code:	<i>[Code for the theory]</i>
Context (environment):	<i>[Context in the extracted interview script]</i>
Mechanisms (Resources and Reasoning - Cognitive and Emotional):	<i>[Description of the mechanism in the programme theory]</i>
Outcome (Effect):	<i>[Outcome of the Programme theory]</i>
CMO Configuration:	<i>[The CMO configuration is consolidated and refined from the participant programme theory]</i>
Support/Refute/Refine:	<i>[Whether the CMO configuration support, refutes or refines the conceptual framework]</i>
How/Decisions:	<i>[How the researcher made their decision through reasoning and interpretation]</i>
Success factor/ Failure factor:	<i>[Whether the CMO constitutes a failure or a success outcome interpreted from the participant's interview]</i>
TOGAF ADM Phase:	<i>[The ADM phase where the CMO might occur]</i>
Result Refine:	<i>[the CMO configurations that this CMO refines]</i>
Links/Ripple Effects:	<i>[The intermediate and indirect effects of the programme theory]</i>

In this section, the researcher detailed how data were analysed. This analysis includes information on the constructs identified in the EA programme theories (EA PTs), mechanisms within a healthcare technology programme triggered in the context of culture, agency, relations, funding, technology, and structure that healthcare organisations create programme outcomes.

Figure 5.1 outlines the components, consistent with the initial programme theory in Chapter 3, extracted from participant interview scripts. They are explained later in this section.

Pawson and Tilley (1997) argue that mechanisms have causal properties in social programs. This analysis seeks to “understand ‘why’ a program work [or does not work], through an understanding of the action of mechanism” (p.216).

The unit of analysis is the individual participant's interviews situated within the cases of designing a technology programme in a healthcare organisation. The researcher draws respondents from EA

Practitioners, technology managers, Clinician users, Chief Clinical Information Officers, Consultant Clinicians, Executive Leadership, Health Informaticians, Digital Transformation leaders and decision-makers of the organisation with experience in implementing the CRS digital transformation programme.

The qualitative interview transcripts for all participants were anonymised to keep “*participants’ identities secret*” ... “*while maintaining the value of and integrity of the data*” (p.617). *The researcher achieved* anonymisation by disguising the person-identifiable data of the participants (Saunders, Kitzinger & Kitzinger, 2015; BSA, 2002:). For instance, the researcher replaced Interviewee One’s name with Participant One.

The mechanisms in the analysed cases from the programs are the choices and capacities of the various actors of the programmes as observed by the participants, which lead to regular patterns of social behaviour in the context of culture, structure, agency, funding, technology, and relations, to create the outcomes. A phenomenon Pawson and Tilley (1997) described as “*folk theories*” (p.107).

The data analysis process explains how the [EA] programme theory was further developed, supported, refuted, and refined, and, where applicable, how the analysis changed as the data evaluation unfolded (Wong et al., 2013; Wong et al., 2016). The research analysis adopts a content and thematic analysis approach to codify transcribed interviews of participant data and identify patterns and interpret them.

“Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns or themes with data. It minimally organises and describes (participant) data in detail. However, frequently it goes further than this and interprets various aspects of the research topic” (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p.79).

Eliciting the CMO configurations involved several steps in maintaining data transparency and credibility of the coding process of the interview transcripts (Gilmore et al., 2019).

Figure 5.2 Outlines the analysis processes, a summary of which is provided in **Table 5.1**. The analysis and synthesis process of the cases was adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).

Figure 5.2. A summary of the analysis and synthesis process of the Case Study is adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).

Table 5.1. analysis and synthesis process for generating the CMO configuration of the study. Adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).

Analysis Method Step	Description
----------------------	-------------

<p>Step 1: Initial EA Programme Theory/Conceptual Framework)</p>	<p>Synthesis of Initial Programme Theories/ conceptual framework (see Chapter 3):</p> <p>Based on sources such as previous research findings, organisation reports, documentary analysis, document reviews and critical interviews from experts to understand critical concepts and broad candidate/participant theories (folk theories).</p>
<p>Step 2: Code interview scripts in NVIVO</p>	<p>Data collection from interview scripts, using semi-structured qualitative interviews, to test and refine the initial framework and identify and explain the critical failure and success factors of the programme under study.</p>
<p>Step 3: Case studies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All qualitative data from interview scripts are entered into NVivo version 12 as Data files, one script per participant for all 12 participants. • Each interview script is coded into the nodes. Each node becomes a PT for the case. For instance, if case study 1 has 3 PTs, case study 1 is coded a PT, and each PT1 node under PT1 is coded PT1.1, PT1.2 and PT1.3. • IPT nodes for each case, including the applicable portion of the interview data, are then extracted into a table in Microsoft Word. • Elicit relevant attributes to configure relevant CMOs (<i>stakeholder viewpoint, node code, context, Mechanism, outcome, CMO configuration for the related node, state whether the initial program theory (IPT)/ conceptual framework is supported, refuted or refined, and how the decision to elicit the CMO was made, identify the related TOGAF phase, identify the context refined, whether CMOc contributes to the success or failure of outcomes, elicit Link/ripple effects</i>). • Generate demi-regularities in CMO configurations across the case studies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing theories and demi-regularities effort to identify and refine middle-range theories Migrate data to Microsoft Excel, sort, and format CMO configurations into success and failure factors.
Step 4: Synthesis of the Case Studies	All elicited Programme theories (PTS) and their supported CMO configurations are collated, aggregated, consolidated, refined, and reviewed for demi-regularities.
Step 4: Elicit success and failure factor Mechanisms and related CMO configurations for all PTs from Step 3. (RQ1)	The CMO configurations and demi-regularities are synthesised into critical success and failure factors mechanisms for all PTs, CMOc and Key Informants Interviews (KIIs) in step 3. Step 5 focuses on answering research question RQ1.
Step 5: Refined EA Middle Range Programme Theory/ Conceptual Framework	Use the conceptual framework to refine the theories. The realist evaluation process is an iterative cycle (Gilmore et al., 2019). Review existing theoretical literature to understand further and refine the demi-regularities and the initial programme theory/conceptual framework.
Step 6: Elicit/synthesize The CMOc Critical Success Factors and Critical Failure Factors of EA Outcomes. From CMOc. (RQ2)	Aggregate, consolidate and refine key critical success and failure factors for EA outcomes for the programme from the output in step 5. Step 6 focuses on answering research question RQ2.

The analysis steps are further explained in the subsequent subsections below:

5.3.2 Step One of the Analysis

Eliciting the conceptual framework or initial programme theory involves moving backwards and forwards across the extant literature, previous research finding from the extant literature, the organisation's report, review reports, concepts and themes in the conceptual framework and the interview scripts, retroductively theorising the findings from the analysis (Jagosh, 2020b; Jackson and Kolla, 2012; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016).

Table 5.2 shows the distribution of extracted CMO configurations from the participant interview of the qualitative study. Two hundred and thirty-one (231) CMO configurations were elicited from analysing the participant interview transcripts. One-hundred and thirty-six (136) of the CMO configurations, representing 59% of CMO configurations, are related to critical failure factors, while ninety-five (95) CMO configurations, representing 41%, are critical success factors. Four of the twelve participants provided more evidence that elicited success-related CMO configurations than failure. It is noteworthy to state that their assertions vary and are unrelated due to the context-sensitivity of mechanisms of the programmes as experienced by each participant. It is because mechanisms are triggered in context to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh et al., 2015; Jagosh, 2020b). **Figure 5.3** shows the distribution of the CMO configuration into success and failure factors. Three out of the twelve participants provided more success than failure factors, Participants one, two and seven. Nine out of twelve participants provided evidence that elicited failure outcomes.

Table 5.2. shows the distribution of CMO configuration elicited from Participant Interview scripts into critical success and failure factors.

Participant	CMO configs	Programme theories code	CMO Configurations codes	Failure Factors	Success Factors
Participant One	26	PT1.1 to PT1.26	CMO1.1 to CMO1.26	7	19
Participant Two	25	PT2.1 to PT2.25	CMO2.1 to CMO2.25	11	14
Participant Three	13	PT3.1 to PT3.13	CMO3.1 to CMO3.13	8	5
Participant Four	13	PT4.1 to PT4.13	CMO4.1 to CMO4.13	11	2
Participant Five	22	PT5.1 to PT5.13	CMO5.1 to CMO5.22	18	4
Participant Six	21	PT6.1 to PT6.21	CMO6.1 to CMO6.21	16	5
Participant Seven	18	PT7.1 to PT7.18	CMO7.1 to CMO7.18	14	4
Participant Eight	16	PT8.1 to PT8.16	CMO8.1 to CMO8.16	6	10
Participant Nine	17	PT9.1 to PT9.16	CMO9.1 to CMO9.16	11	6
Participant Ten	21	PT10.1 to PT10.21	CMO10.1 to CMO10.21	11	10

Participant Eleven	28	PT11.1 to PT11.28	CMO11.1 to CMO11.28	20	8
Participant Twelve	11	PT12.1 to PT12.11	CMO12.1 to CMO12.11	3	8
	231		Totals	136	95
			Percentage	59%	41%

Figure 5.3. Distribution of Critical Failure Factors and Critical Success CMO Configurations from Participant Interviews.

The first phase of the analysis resulted in conjectured hypotheses or CMO configurations. The relevant section of the participant interview script for the related CMO configuration is extracted, outlining the participant positioning or viewpoint, context, mechanism, and outcome for the code. It follows similar approaches by Jackson and Kolla (2012) and Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, and Vallières (2019) with additional elements consistent with the CRAFTS conceptual model (the conceptual framework in chapter 3) of context-sensitive EA mechanisms theorised in this research. See CMO configuration tables, **Table 5.3** and **Table 5.4**.

Programme theories elicited from participant interviews are given unique codes. For instance, the programme theories for Participant One are prefixed with PT1 followed by a period, and the programme theories for Participant Two are prefixed with PT2 followed by a period. The related CMO configurations are prefixed as CMO1 and CMO2. Each programme theory is coded with the participant identifier followed by a period and the programme theory number. Each participant script generated multiple programme theories. For instance, the interview script for Participant Nine generated 16 programme theories. The related programme theories are coded PT9.1 to PT9.16, and the CMO configurations are coded as CMO9.1 and CMO9.16, respectively. The programmes theories and CMO configuration codes are shown in **Table 5.3** and **Table 5.4**

The criteria for identifying a phrase as a mechanism, context or outcome is described in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3.

The relevant part of the interview script elicited to form a CMO connection identifies context in italics, mechanisms in bold and outcomes underlined (Jackson & Kolla, 2012). Consistent with the initial programme theory/ conceptual framework in Chapter 3, whether the CMO configuration is supported, refuted, or refined, the initial programme theory is also elicited and coded.

The coupled triggered related mechanism and respective contexts create outcomes that contribute to the programme's success. Suppose the CMO configuration elicited is perceived by participants, as provided in the interview scripts, as contributing positively to the programme's outcome. In that case, it elicited critical success. Conversely, suppose the participants perceive the coupled triggered mechanism and context-generated outcomes unfavourable. The CMO configuration is elicited as a critical failure factor in that case.

The CMO configuration seeks to explain "what works for whom, under what circumstances" (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, p.63; Pawson and Manzano-Santaella, 2012, p.177) and why? (Lefroy et al., 2015).

THE TOGAF ADM phase code is consistent with the relevant deliverables for the TOGAF ADM phase (The Open Group, 2018). The related TOGAF ADM phase is also coded in which the related activity occurs. For instance, if the CMO configuration is related to triggered mechanisms related to the architecture vision, Phase A of TOGAF is coded against it. **Table 5.3** shows the CMO configuration formulation process for Participant Five programme theory 12.

If the elicited CMO configuration refines the initial programme's theory, it is identified, coded, and briefly described. Finally, suppose the CMO configuration elicits links to other CMO configurations or has ripple effects on the programme's outcomes. This is also coded (Gilmore et al., 2019).

Table 5.3. Formulating the Failure Factors CMO configuration process. Adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).

<p>PT5.12 <i>Poor Requirements Management</i> <i>Siloed programme leading to poor coordination</i> <i>Poor Communication</i> <i>Poor governance (lack of design authority)</i></p>	<p>“Yeah. They quite often guess requirements, which is a significant problem. I also find it quiet, I guess, within the programs that I've worked on, there is a, quite often, there's a lack of design authority. There doesn't seem to be a single person calling the shots or making the ultimate decision. <i>Quite often, there seems to be too much siloed working within programs. So, everybody's trying to achieve the same thing, but quite often, they are working in silos. Communication across those silos is very poor. And you end up either having massive gaps, where pieces of the program are not being tackled by anybody or the same piece of the program is being tackled by multiple silos.</i> And there seems to be very poor communication across the piece. I think the structure of the way in which program managers structure their programs <u>inherently leads to this kind of confusion and duplication. That is the program structure.</u>”</p>
<p>Source Participant/Viewpoint:</p>	<p>Participant Five: Technical Architect internal staff implementer on the IT programme.</p>
<p>Code:</p>	<p>Design authority</p>
<p>Context (environment):</p>	<p>Structure and Relations, Agency: The design authority</p>
<p>Mechanisms (Resources and Reasoning - Cognitive and Emotional):</p>	<p>The lack of design authority in the programme</p>
<p>Outcome (Effect):</p>	<p>Confusion and duplication across the programme, dissatisfaction, frustration</p>
<p>CMO5.12 Configuration:</p>	<p>The management of requirements presents a significant challenge. A conspicuous absence of design authority often results in a lack of transparent decision-making. Programmes</p>

	appear to be excessively compartmentalised, with individual teams operating in isolated silos towards a common goal, albeit with minimal inter-silo communication. This arrangement often leads to several teams redundantly addressing the same aspect of the programme, consequently leaving substantial gaps elsewhere. Compounding the issue, these programmes suffer from ineffective communication. How managers structure their programmes contributes inadvertently to a landscape of confusion and duplicative efforts.
Support/Refute/Refine:	Support – Structure, relations, and Agency
How/Decisions:	Emphasise collaborative team effort for effective implementation of EA programmes.
Success factor/ Failure factor:	Failure Factor
TOGAF ADM Phase:	ADM Requirement Management, Phase G – Implementation governance
Result Refine:	Structure
Links/Ripple Effects	Lack of alignment between programme outcomes and stakeholder expectations.

Table 5.4. Formulating the Success Factor CMO configuration process, adapted from Gilmore et al. (2019).

PT1.1 <i>Understanding Organisational Needs/Objectives Supplier Relationship</i>	<i>“I’m at [supplier company] now and have been for a few years. So, we are doing some work with the NHS, the National Health Service in the UK. A lot of the work we are doing is ensuring there is an understanding of the NHS’s needs, how we can play to our strengths in what we know and how to best support those needs. <u>As we know, there is so much scope for making an impact through</u></i>
--	---

	IT and transformation in the healthcare service. One of the key things is figuring out their needs and our strengths as providers. So that's a key factor in how we've approached the relationships with the healthcare service and how and where we can make an impact.”
Source Participant/Viewpoint:	Participant One: Clinician Global Health Policy Lead is a <i>supplier</i> of healthcare technology services to organisations engaged by the participant organisation of the case study. Role: Supplier implementer
Code:	Understanding an organisation’s needs
Context (environment):	Culture, relations, structure: understanding the organisation’s needs through stakeholder engagement
Mechanisms (Resources and Reasoning - Cognitive and Emotional):	Building relationships with the organisation, understanding its needs and making an impact.
Outcome (Effect):	Supplier empowerment, cordial supplier/customer relationship
CMO1.1 Configuration:	Ensure that the NHS's requirements are understood and suppliers can effectively assist in providing them. Finding the organisation’s needs and matching supplier strength is critical.
Support/Refute/Refine:	Support Relations and culture
How/Decisions:	Emphasises the role of relations in understanding the organisation's needs and how that empowers the suppliers to deliver value to the organisation.
Success factor/ Failure factor:	Success factor
TOGAF ADM Phase:	ADM Phase Requirements Management E-Opportunities and Solutions
Result Refine:	Relations
Links/Ripple Effects:	Friendly programme environment and cooperation

5.3.3 Step Two of the Analysis

The Context-Mechanism-Outcome configurations (CMOs) derived from participant interview data are used to test and refine the preliminary programme theory rigorously. The CMO configurations are elicited from each participant's "*Stakeholders' physical, cognitive and conceptual positioning at*

micro[-sociological], meso[-sociological] and macro[-sociological] levels" (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016, p.25) in the digital transformation in which the EA implementation is embedded. At the same time, some participants' viewpoints varied. Whilst some were frontline clinician users of the implemented system, others were decision-makers and designers.

For each CMO configuration elicited, attributes are also elicited (Jackson & Kolla, 2012):

- The related participant's viewpoint (extract from interview script),
- whether the initial program theory (IPT)/ conceptual framework is supported, refuted, or refined,
- how the decision to elicit the CMO is made,
- identifying the related TOGAF ADM phase,
- identify if CMO configuration refines the initial programme theory /conceptual framework
- whether CMO configuration elicited contributes to the success or failure of outcomes, and
- link/ripple effects of the CMO configuration on other CMO configurations elicited).

See Table 5.3 and Table 5.4's first columns for the attributes used to elicit the CMO configurations.

The output for step two is the elicited folk theories (Jagosh, 2020b) refined in later steps.

5.3.4 Step Three of the Analysis

In step 3, the programme theories or conjectured CMO configurations elicited are collated, aggregated, consolidated, refined, and reviewed for demi-regularities. In practice, step 3 involves eliciting and interpreting participants' ideas and reasoning about the programme mechanisms, the context in which these mechanisms are triggered, and the outcomes experienced or conjectured by the researcher (Gilmore et al., 2019).

The realist task was to extract inferences and identify contingencies and demi-regularities that provide insights into the mechanisms, context, and outcomes related to the critical success and failure factors of the CRS approach to implementation. It involved allocating themes into different contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes components and constructing them into CMO configurations. Microsoft Excel formats, sorts, and aggregates

the CMO configurations into failure and success factors. It enabled CMO configurations that may be related to being easily observed.

Bree and Gallagher (2016) migrated all the participant data to a Microsoft Excel worksheet, generating a single column containing all comments from research moderators. *"The data was then analysed with a view to assigning thematic areas"* (Bree and Gallagher, 2016, p.2815).

The retrieved interview transcripts for analysis were uploaded to Microsoft Word tables (La Pelle, 2004). Microsoft Excel was utilised for conditional formatting and categorising participant responses into themes, as is often done in qualitative analysis (Amozurrutia & Servós, 2011; Meyer & Avery, 2009).

A simple approach for systematically categorising and arranging interview data based on basic Word and Excel functionalities may benefit many academics and students (Ose, 2016). It was necessary to go from a description of the data to an explanation by identifying context (C), the mechanism (M), and outcome (O) regularities that connect the domains in the conceptual framework (basic programme theory from Chapter 3). (Gilmore, McAuliffe et al., 2019; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016). As a result, it was feasible to deduce the correlations between components that describe the CRS programme approach to implementation and the context in which they function or do not work from participant statements (Gilmore et al., 2019; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh et al., 2015; Jackson & Kolla, 2012).

5.3.5 Step Four of the Analysis

Successful or unsuccessful Implementations are depicted as a function of the type of evidence, characteristics of the environment in which the evidence is employed, and the participant's statement about whether the mechanisms were a success or a failure (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016). An additional description of what constitutes a critical success factor or a critical failure factor is explained in the conceptual framework. CMO configurations that contribute to unfavourable EA outcomes are critical failure factors. Those that contribute to successful EA outcomes are critical success factors.

The research aims to identify EA mechanisms and whether, when triggered, they constitute success or failure to achieve outcomes in programme implementation.

In steps, answers to the research question are unfolded. The mechanisms of EA are embedded in the CMO configurations. Some mechanisms create successful EA outcomes and other failure outcomes. The realist approach is based on the notion that these mechanisms are triggered in context to create EA outcomes. What (EA mechanisms) works (EA outcome) or do not work (EA outcome) for whom under what circumstances (context)? (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). The purpose of EA is to enable alignment between the organisation's goals and objectives; and its information technology (Guijarro, 2007; Guo, Li & Gao, 2019; ISO, 2019; Iyamu, 2019; Ross, Weill, and Robertson, 2006; Vallerand, Lapalme and Moïse, 2017; van de Wetering, Kurnia & Kotusev 2021). When alignment between outcomes and organisational objectives and goals is achieved, mechanisms triggered in context are critical success factors.

"Dynamic enterprise architecture capabilities positively enhance firms' process innovation and business-IT alignment ...The [organisation's] EA resources and EA deployment practices are essential in cultivating dynamic enterprise architecture capabilities" (van de Wetering, Kurnia & Kotusev, 2021, p.3).

Dynamic Capabilities, strategic agility or adaptability, refer to an organisation's capacity to integrate, develop, and reconfigure internal and external resources/competencies to respond to and influence rapidly evolving stakeholder expectations (Teece, 2010, 214; Ananthram, 2016).

Conversely, when there is no alignment between outcomes and objectives, mechanisms triggered in context constitute failure mechanisms. The interpretation of whether mechanisms are perceived as successful or failures is elicited from the resulting CMO configuration gleaned from the participant interviews and the relevant extant literature. It is a retroductive analytical approach to theorising (Jagosh, 2020b).

5.3.6 Step Five of the Analysis

In step five of the analysis, the reviewed and extant theoretical literature and relevant organisational reports are further elicited to understand emerging phenomena in the elicited CMO configurations from the participant interviews. The realist evaluation process is an iterative cycle (Gilmore et al., 2019). Further refinement and support for the conceptual framework (initial programme theory) and identified demi-regularities are elicited (Gilmore et al., 2019; Jagosh, 2020b; Jackson & Kolla, 2012).

5.3.7 Step Six of the Analysis

In step six, the critical success factors and critical failure factors (RQ2) of the programme are elicited, consolidated, and refined further. Form the socio-technological perspective and central to whether a CMO configuration constitutes a failure or a success factor is elicited from participant feedback stakeholder concerns, and architecture views are revisited.

An "Architecture description shall identify the system stakeholders, having concerns considered fundamental to the architecture of the system-of-interest; users, operators; acquirers; owners; suppliers, developers, builders and maintainers" (ISO, 2011, 3.1).

A view is "defined as a part of an Architecture Description that addresses a set of related concerns and is tailored for specific stakeholders... An architecture view (or simply "view") addresses one or more of the concerns held by a stakeholder of the system" (The Open Group, 2018, [14.3]).

Stakeholder concerns/feedback for a context, mechanism, and outcome heuristic are expressed in CMO configurations (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, Jagosh, 2020b; Jackson & Kolla, 2012; Gilmore, McAuliffe, Power, & Vallières, 2019; Rycroft-Malone, J. et al., 2016).

Critical success factors sustain the need not to ensure that the quality of EA meets stakeholder concerns/agency through their interpretation of the organisational vision, objectives, and goals.

"Critical Success Factor (CSF) stipulates the desired attributes that need to be ascertained in order to assure the quality of the EA model. It emphasises those considerations that must be addressed exceedingly well in order to attain EA maturation" (Essien, 2013, p.9).

Essien argues that Success factors in many Enterprise Architecture Frameworks adhere to some established principles; differential analysis indicates that many [of them] do not incorporate a validation strategy for created artefacts into their process. The socio-technological approach to eliciting critical success factors uses CMO configuration, those context-sensitive mechanisms that create aligned outcomes between IT and the Organisational vision and goals.

According to Ylimaki (2006), Numerous EA studies have been conducted to identify critical success factors for effective EA implementation. Notably, alignment could have been obtained simply by eliciting documented evidence of alignment, but they would not be situated in the circumstance within which the programme operated. It is also worth caution that stakeholder perspectives are subject to external influences extraneous to the programme, which could influence their subjective judgement about alignment. The framework, however, suggests that for a socio-technological approach, empirical user feedback presents a realistic perspective (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

In general, where a weakness has been elicited from participant interviews, the resulting CMO configuration constitutes a critical failure factor. The resulting CMO configuration constitutes a critical failure factor when a strength, a positive assertion, has been elicited.

According to Sidorova and Kappelman (2011, p.61), *EAMMF version 2.0, an enterprise architecture framework, "provides a simplified and structured way to answer a very complex question – Where does an organisation stand in its walk toward its enterprise architecture destination? ... It allows for the answer to be presented in terms of enterprise architecture management strengths [critical success factors] and weaknesses [critical failure factors] at both a single point in time and over a period of time, and for groups of enterprises to be assessed, represented, and compared ... it allows the user to apply their own set of criteria, or to use multiple sets of criteria"*.

EAMMF version 2.0 answers questions about alignment “*in three different ways: (1) requiring all core elements at a given stage to be met to achieve that stage of maturity; (2) requiring all core elements at a given stage to be at least partially met to achieve that stage of maturity; and (3) not*

using the maturity stages, and instead of describing what portion of the core elements was met or partially met across all stages or within one or more critical success attributes" (p6).

A logical fallacy implies that the inverse of critical failure factors is a critical success factor, thereby denying the antecedent. The inverse of a critical failure factor (a context-sensitive triggered EA mechanism or CMO configuration) is not necessarily elicited as a critical success factor. For example, suppose effective communication is a critical success factor, but it does not necessarily imply that a lack of effective communication is a failure factor.

Critical failures in information systems occur when the system does not work as intended. It is a critical failure if a software-intensive system does not perform as planned or becomes user-hostile, resulting in rejection and underutilisation. If the system's complexity or functioning is problematic, or if development is abandoned before or after completion (Beynon-Davies, 1998; Flowers, 1996; Yeo, 2002).

Confusion of the inverse, also known as the conditional probability fallacy or the inverse fallacy, is a logical fallacy in which a conditional probability is equated with its inverse. For example, given two events, A and B, the probability of A occurring, given that B occurs assumed to be approximately equal to the probability of B occurring given A, even though there is no evidence for this assumption (Villejoubert & Mandel, 2002; Plous, 1993). Accordingly, critical failure factors are elicited from the participants through interpretation and verbatim accounts of their experiences. Their inverse is not implied.

The Open Group (2018), Framework, TOGAF, recommend activities and iterative phases in the ADM with inputs and outputs. The phase/phases in which the triggered mechanisms might occur are also outlined against the CMO configuration. For example, where a CMO configuration is related to the Architecture vision of the programme, The TOGAF phase, 'A. Architecture Vision' is provided.

The outcome of the analysis processes and findings are discussed in the findings chapter. The analytical and synthesis are elicited from procedures in the RAMSES quality standards (Wong et al., 2016).

5.3.8 Reliability

A realist evaluation is a more organic, iterative, and non-prescriptive procedure. The evidence is searched for and evaluated to 'populate' the theoretical framework/initial programme theory in Chapter 3 with empirical data. The purposeful search for evidence is influenced by what is discovered. Attempting to compile a 'census' of all relevant evidence is neither desired nor practical. The study and synthesis findings combine theoretical reasoning and facts from participants to explain how EA mechanisms work in ways that policymakers may utilise and apply to their own circumstances (Pawson, Walshe, & Greenhalgh, 2004).

A realist review is a more varied and dynamic process that is less accessible to prescription and likely requires more methodological knowledge on the reviewer's side (Pawson et al., 2004). As realist evaluation relies on participant programme theories of mechanisms as generative causal explanations for outcomes, experts with extensive experience have been selected as respondents and participants in the research (Jagosh et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2013; Pawson et al., 2004). The profiles of the Participants are outlined in Table 4.4.

The researcher is an expert in the field of Enterprise Architecture and a certified TOGAF Practitioner with more than fifteen years of experience in Enterprise Architecture implementation within the study setting. The researcher has completed Realist Evaluation training and consulting from experts.

Formulating a conceptual framework/Initial Programme theory has been necessary because of the lack of suitable EA frameworks specific to healthcare for analysing socio-technological factors appropriate for the research evaluation. The initial programme theory/conceptual framework was drawn from inferences from the extant literature. The principle of providing reliability is to position the research to proactively reflect on reliability concerns and provide a procedure for later researchers

to follow (Yin, 2018). As such, the general approach has been to make the procedures in the research explicit. *“Opportunities for repeating case study rarely occur” (p.44).*

5.4 Summary

Chapter five is the analysis chapter. It describes the analysis process and how the CMO configurations were elicited from participant interviews. The CMO configurations are the empirical evidence that tests the initial framework and encapsulates the findings that answer the research questions.

6 CHAPTER SIX: RESULTS AND FINDINGS

6.1 Introduction

This section provides the findings of the research. Findings are expressed as Context-mechanism-outcome configurations (CMOc) consistent with the realist evaluative approach (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Jagosh et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2016). Critical success factors and critical failure factors of EA implementations focus on the role of mechanisms. The findings are presented in tabular form showing context, mechanisms, and outcome configurations and groups by context for critical success factors (alignment) and critical failure (misalignment) with the organisation's objectives and goals through the lens of 'stakeholder concerns' (Bolman & Deal, 2017; ISO, 2011; The Open Group, 2018; Hinkelmann et al., 2016; van der Raadt et al., 2010) or stakeholder expected value (Puspitasari, 2016, June).

6.2 Details of Participants

The study discusses who participated in the research assessment, as well as the features of the data and how the information was utilised to develop further, support, dispute, or enhance middle-range programme theory in this section (Wong et al., 2016; Pawson & Tilley, 1997). However, participants' anonymity is kept by simply addressing their function in the organisation (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2016). **Table 4.4** outlines the profile of the Participants.

All 12 participant interviews were conducted in the qualitative study:

- Eleven participants were implementing stakeholders, designers, and decision-makers, representing 92% of the participants.
- Three were frontline clinician users of the programme's technology systems, representing 25% of participants.
- Two females represented 17% of the participants, and ten were males, representing 83%.
- Seven were implementers of the technology programmes,

- Four Clinicians were involved with the design of the technology programme representing 33% of the participants.
- Two were vendors of the technology solution to the programmes, representing 17% of the participants.
- Ten worked for the organisation where the programme occurred, representing 83% of participants.

6.3 Results

The aim of this thesis is:

- To **evaluate** EA mechanisms in healthcare organisations.
- To **explain** the lack of perceived value in EA in healthcare.
- To **identify** the factors that facilitate the EA Management success or failure in healthcare organisations.

The result of interest, critical failure factors and critical success factors of EA were created by relevant aspects that were activated by or could only work in the context of themes related to culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure. The study discovered recurring patterns of CMO configuration inside or across data sources. As a result, the mechanisms are embedded in the CMO configurations (Mader, 2018; Wong et al., 2016; Astbury & Leeuw, 2010; Curry et al., 2009). *"Themes are recurrent unifying concepts or statements about the subject of inquiry" (Curry et al., 2009, p.1447).*

CMO configurations are also selected based on alignment or misalignment with the organisation's vision and care delivery through their 'ripple effects' (Gilmore et al., 2019; Jagosh, 2018). The NHS' vision is *"to provide care and services that we and our families would want to use" (DOH, 2018, para.3).*

The research results are presented as CMO configurations with supporting quotes as evidence from participants' interviews. In some cases, supporting evidence is drawn from the extant literature (De Brún and McAuliffe, 2020; Gilmore et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2016; Jagosh et al., 2015).

Realist evaluations inform policy and strategy and influence future programme action towards better outcomes. Policy recommendations are necessary for realist evaluations (Pawson et al., 2004).

The TOGAF ADM phases in the Architect may intervene in the development of EA have been included as a column in the findings table. Chapter Two Section 2.15 describes the TOGAF ADM. Their deliverables are provided in Appendix C. Letters represent the relevant TOGAF ADM phase in the CMOc configurations, shown in **Table 6.1**, so programme Architects may identify what stage of the EA implementation could be affected by the findings.

Table 6.1. TOGAF ADM Phases represented by letters

TOGAF ADM Phases
PP: Preliminary Phase
A: Architecture Vision
B: Business Architecture
C: Information Systems Architecture
D: Technology Architecture
E: Opportunities and Solutions
F: Migration Planning
G: Implementation Governance
H: Architecture Change Management
RM: Requirement Management

This goal is achieved if the study considers the practical demands of various stakeholders while developing an [EA] intervention (Pawson et al., 2004).

“The ‘hierarchy of evidence’ for systematic evaluation of biomedical therapies includes randomised controlled trials (RCTs), non-RCTs, before-and-after studies, descriptive case studies, and (lowest of all) ‘opinion pieces. Realist review adheres to this idea but differs [in] how research quality is assessed. Realist review rejects a hierarchical approach as an example of the law of the hammer (to a man with a hammer, everything is a nail)” (Pawson et al., 2004, p.21).

Table 6.2. Shows the Distribution of CMO configurations and Program theories elicited from Participant interview scripts

Participant	CMO Configs No.	PTs	CMO Configs	Failure Factors	Success Factors
Participant One	26	PT1.1 to PT1.26	CMO1.1 to CMO1.26	7	19
Participant Two	25	PT2.1 to PT2.24	CMO2.1 to CMO2.24	11	14
Participant Three	13	PT3.1 to PT3.13	CMO3.1 to CMO3.13	8	5
Participant Four	13	PT4.1 to PT4.13	CMO4.1 to CMO4.13	11	2
Participant Five	22	PT5.1 to PT5.13	CMO5.1 to CMO5.22	18	4
Participant Six	21	PT6.1 to PT6.21	CMO6.1 to CMO6.21	16	5
Participant Seven	18	PT7.1 to PT7.18	CMO7.1 to CMO7.18	14	4
Participant Eight	16	PT8.1 to PT8.16	CMO8.1 to CMO8.16	6	10
Participant Nine	17	PT9.1 to PT9.17	CMO9.1 to CMO9.17	10	7
Participant Ten	21	PT10.1 to PT10.21	CMO10.1 to CMO10.21	11	10
Participant Eleven	28	PT11.1 to PT11.28	CMO11.1 to CMO11.28	20	8
Participant Twelve	11	PT12.1 to PT12.11	CMO12.1 to CMO12.11	3	8
	231		Totals	135	96
			Percentage	58%	42%

6.4 Main Findings of the Research

The conceptual framework and CMO configuration approaches are a significant and original contribution to EA Architecture evaluations. The context-Mechanism-outcomes configurational approach to identifying critical failure factors is the first contribution to the field of EA. The expression of Critical success factors in context-mechanism-outcome configurations within an Architecture framework has previously not been researched.

Theories from Participants that inform the elicitation of the relevant CMO configurations (CMOCs) are supported by Participant quotes or from the extant literature as evidence (De Brún & McAuliffe, 2020; Nurjono et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2016; Wong et al., 2013).

A socio-technological approach to explaining the critical failure and success factors using context-mechanism-outcome configurations is also the first application in EA research. Two hundred and thirty-five CMO configurations have been condensed into five for each contextual factor as evidence for the recurring patterns. It is important to note that deprioritised CMO may be relevant but excluded because of the preponderance of evidence from the priority list. Sixty CMO configurations are provided as evidence with accompanying quotes from participant theories. Each CMO configuration is indexed for traceability; see **Evidence:** (first column) under CMO configuration **Table 6.3**.

CMOCs have been presented serially, but in reality, the relationship between CMO is complex because of their interactions and linkage. They are accompanying empirical evidence in the form of participant theories with the reference index of each CMO configuration. For example, participant quotes/empirical evidence related to CMO8.16 is referenced as [1], a format adapted from De Brún and McAuliffe (2020). Table 6.2 provides the participant identity, and Table 4.4 provides participant profiles for traceability.

6.5 Critical Failure Factors (Mechanisms) to EA Implementations

This section outlines the outcomes of the iterative approach used to construct and enhance the conceptual framework and generate essential failure factors, programme theories, and CMO

configurations for the programme. Each paragraph describes the CMO configuration for the linked cultural, agential, relational, financing, technical, and structural environment. Barriers are triggered processes that result in mismatched results. They impede synchronising the organization's objectives and goals with its IT.

6.5.1 Cultural Barriers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical failure factors related to the triggered mechanisms' cultural circumstances (norms, values, beliefs, symbols). The mechanisms are empirical theories or ideas about culture, relations, agency, technology and structure (see details of the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.3. CMO Configurations for Critical Failure Factors related to the cultural context and as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model)

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Culture)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
1	CMO8.16	Technology Resistance. Risk Aversion to Technology	Cultural barriers to adopting digital technology as a core part of Clinicians' ways of working.	There is a perceived dearth of intermediate value provided by digital technology to patient care.	All Phases of the ADM
2	CMO10.3	Risk-aversion to technology.	A risk-averse cultural outlook on technology innovation prevents the organisation from addressing complex issues affecting the organisation due to the changing environment in the healthcare sector.	Disempowerment, slow to innovate	All Phases of the ADM
3	CMO11.7	Top leadership Cultural	Cultural aversion to digital technology by the top	Perception of failure, apathy	G

		aversion to technology change.	leadership of the organisation.		
4	CMO5.1	Legacy technology	legacy IT systems and culture	Clinician disempowerment	G
5	CMO7.2	Technology risk-averse culture.	Low technology maturity levels because of a culture of risk-aversion to technology innovation	Stakeholder inertia and low patronage	All ADM Phases

Suppose there are culturally perceived barriers to digital technology by stakeholders. In that case, there will be a perceived lack of intermediate value to patient care because digital technology is not regarded as a core part of Clinicians' ways of working. The ripple effect is a slow pace of adoption that leads to misalignment with the programme schedule. CMO8.16 emphasises the value of embedding a digital culture in healthcare organisations.

“I’ll quote one of the things that they said to me in the past, ‘I’m here to see and treat patients, not really to mend IT systems or to feed IT systems.’ And when you understand that as a barrier, you demonstrate why then putting the information into the system, then you can see the benefits from that, the outcomes, the outcomes from the other end. And that’s probably true for all health IT programs that are Assessment, EPR-centric and not simply about an infrastructure project like putting in a network or wifi. They provide you with a platform to use those applications, but they’re not directly patient-facing type applications. Again, it’s an enabling tool.”[1].

A risk-averse culture to technology innovation disempowers Clinicians in their clinical effectiveness. It prevents the organisation and Clinicians from responding to the complex needs of patients because of the changing healthcare structure. CMO10.3 emphasises the role of empowerment of the organisation and its stakeholder in responding through EA. The ripple effect is misaligned organisational objectives, IT, changing healthcare structure, and patient needs.

“Well, you can agree on terms, and you can find a middle ground. You can get the win-win and all the rest of it when you're dealing with a multifaceted group of different stakeholders in large numbers of different degrees of interest, capability, passion, skill and all the rest of it. It is a very difficult cultural ask of an organisation that is very risk-averse by nature, very operationally contended; very cash poor; very technologically uneducated; very often uninterested in doing anything other than getting a lot more for less; keeping the outcome of the patient rightly sacrosanct and at the focus of everything that we do” [2].

Cultural resistance to digital technology within an organisation's top leadership can cultivate a perception of failure. This can subsequently engender a feeling of collective apathy amongst stakeholders, ultimately shaping the organisation's operational dynamics. Such cultural barriers at the leadership level can significantly impact the organisation's ability to effectively embrace and leverage digital transformations, underlining the pivotal role leadership attitudes play in shaping organisational culture and practices. CMO11.7 emphasises the negative impact of unfavourable leadership perception on the organisation on programme outcomes.

“The Culture eats strategy for breakfast. So, you can have all the strategic ideas in the world, but culture will come and defeat it all the time. ... And it's probably not that; it's probably the culture that was quite strong at the time. And the culture is what defines how things are going to work” [3].

Rationalising and modernising the existing legacy digital technology, and adopting new digital capabilities, empowers Clinicians and optimises the cost. CMO5.1 emphasises the positive impact of digital transformation through legacy modernisation on cost, Clinician empowerment and improved patient outcomes. The ripple effect is Improved patient outcomes and clinical effectiveness.

“It was about getting rid of an awful lot of legacy services and basically trying to reimagine those and deliver a brand-new consolidated service, which was, I guess, fit for today rather than something that was designed 10 or 15 years ago. So partly cost for

half of them, and the other half is actually digital transformation / trying to provide some significant new functionality"[4].

The CMO7.2 emphasises the importance of risk tolerance in technology adoption for improved EA outcomes. A culture of the organisation that is risk-averse to technology creates inertia and low patronage of digital transformations. The ripple effect is the misalignment of the organisation's intended objectives and goals and its IT.

“They are awaiting maturity. And there is a similar issue in ICS. Culturally, there is very little appetite for the more risky strategy of building a platform on just a data platform. ... And I think that kind of because the way culturally NHS has evolved, being very risk-averse, it is very difficult to have that kind of transformation. So, despite having a lot of opportunities to do that transformation, I think what we'll find in ICS or integrated care system is they will end up missing that opportunity and kind of getting the same old API vendors on the board.” [5].

6.5.2 Relations Barriers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical failure factors related to the triggered mechanisms' relational circumstances (duties and responsibilities, rights and power). The mechanisms are empirical theories about relations that create transformational outcomes of duties/responsibilities (skills and training), rights, and power (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.4. CMO configurations of critical failure factors in the Relations context as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model)

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Relations)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
6	CMO6.9	Clinician/IT engagement	Lack of collaboration between IT and Clinicians.	Dissatisfaction, disagreements	All ADM Phases
7	CMO12.7	Clinician engagement	Lack of Clinician engagement in change.	Fear, mistrust	All ADM Phased
8	CMO3.10	Stakeholder engagement and consultation	Key Clinicians, technical staff, and other programme stakeholders are not actively involved in the programme's	The frustration of stakeholders, Clinicians and technical experts, the	All ADM Phases

			decision-making processes.	unrealistic and unachievable timescale for deployment	
9	CMO9.13	Clinician engagement during negotiation with suppliers.	The procurement mechanisms are complicated and lack clinician involvement during negotiations and decision-making with suppliers regarding the functionality of technological solutions.	structural difficulties and Clinician frustration	B, C, D, RM
10	CMO7.6	Frontline Clinician engagement	Lack of User research and engagement to gain insight and understanding of issues through feedback about change implementation the frontline clinicians face in adopting digital technology.	User resistance to technology adoption, uncommitted	B, C, D, E, H, RM

Lack of collaboration between Clinicians and IT negatively impacts the adoption of the technology as Clinicians are dissatisfied and reluctant to use the IT systems. CMO6.9 emphasises the adverse impact on EA outcomes of the lack of relevant IT skills to support the programme, poor complaints management process, a lack of Clinician engagement with IT staff and a culture that does not encourage collaboration and adoption. The ripple effect is the misalignment of programme outcomes with user expectations.

"I got myself into the role of the CCIO because I became a strong advocate and a strong critic, be it in a good way to get a system functioning. So, the culture was that our IT colleagues were highly trained, [and] highly equipped with the skills to do the IT. Clinicians are trained in clinical matters, but I think the culture was that I think they hardly met together to be in a forum to agree that this is the system which would work for the IT colleagues felt that this is a good system. In contrast, the Clinician said it was a good system, and there was no meeting point. On the program board, there were many

times when the IT colleagues would say that the Clinicians are fixed in their way, and they don't want to use something new. So as far as they are concerned, the culture was [that] the Clinicians were not willing to use a system, even though the system was good. And I used to say to them that if the system is good, inclusive, and easy to use, why won't the Clinicians use it? Have you asked the Clinicians?" [6].

Lack of Clinician engagement in digital transformational change creates a misunderstanding of the implications of the change on their work and fear among Clinicians. CMO12.7 emphasises the adverse impact of not effectively engaging Clinicians in digital transformation change on their morale. The ripple effect is the misalignment between EA outcomes and Clinician expectation

“Change, and some will even retire because of change because there will not be able to cope. So when you bring change, you see, unlike you rightly mentioned in your first question, it is always good for management to discuss, ask for people's opinion, before you just bringing change and bring you so suddenly and say training here training there” [7].

CMO3.10 emphasises the adverse effect of not engaging Clinicians and Technical experts in decision-making on their morale. The lack of Clinicians and technical experts' decision-making engagement that affects the programmes leads to frustration and unachievable delivery time scales on programme deliverables. The ripple effect is apathy and misalignment of EA outcomes and stakeholder expectations.

“We will build the technology that you've asked us to build, and it's someone else's concern, responsibility to get the people actually to use what we built. ... If someone's made the political decision, the technical decision, [the] business decision to say more or less, ‘Build it then’, then everyone's got something to move to, then, “Why aren't you moving?” It's going to be like that, but the time scales on the program are not. I mean, they never really stick any of these time scales because the NHS is the NHS; it's not like Command and Control or having banks, where a single bank can move here, come Monday and make everything work” [8].

CMO9.13 emphasises the importance of Clinician involvement in negotiations and decision-making while engaging suppliers about technology solutions. Barriers to communication between Clinicians and suppliers during negotiations and decision-making on technology solutions options create Clinicians' frustration and mistrust. The ripple effect is the misalignment of supplier technology solutions and Clinician user expectations.

“So, they would have a different conversation with different suppliers of different things, different applications. So, as a Clinician, [I] do not have a preview to that. ... Certainly, because they're making decisions about something that is not for the use of the people who are deciding on the procurement of the system. They're not the end-users. The end users are the Clinicians. So whichever way, the chances are that you can end up with a fantastic system, but you can also end up with a system that has got all these structural difficulties with them. So one may just maybe argue or hope that that could have been discussed earlier, or if it was discussed, would we have resolved it. ... what has happened commonly is that there are usually problems with these systems at first used by the Clinician. I have worked mostly in the colossal NHS, where decision-making about the IT systems to procure can be complicated by the mechanisms used to procure” [9].

CMO7.6 emphasises soliciting feedback on user research and gaining insights into stakeholder issues to improve programme outcome acceptance. Lack of user research and engagement with frontline clinical users to gain insight and understand their issues through feedback about change implementation leads to change resistance. The ripple effect is adoption inertia and solutions that are not aligned with stakeholder expectations.

“I think that will resolve some of the business change and the cultural issue we got on the ground. Because historically, a lot of time, the resistance we have got on the ground is because that piece of user research and engagement wasn't done, and it landed on them. And then they felt that it wasn't the service they needed, it wasn't the product they needed, it was clunky, it was slow. So, I think it is more about understanding those issues with the clinicians on the ground to user research, then coming back to, before we start building anything, getting to include that in our work” [10].

6.5.3 Individual and Institutional Agency Barriers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical failure factors related to the individual and organisational agential circumstances (Beliefs and reasons for action or non-action) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about relations that create transformational outcomes of beliefs and reasons for action or non-action (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.5. CMO configurations of Critical failure factors in the individual and organisational agency context as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Agency: reasons for inaction)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
11	CMO7.18	Ownership and responsibility, skill gap	Ownership and responsibility are outsourced to third-party vendors because of a skills gap in platforms and structures and new technologies like artificial intelligence within the programme.	Mistrust	All phases ADM
12	CMO10.2	Technology Skills	The adverse effect of the technology skills gap on competence and understanding of programme processes	Misunderstanding and disempowerment	All ADM phases
13	CMO11.10	Lack of coordination and skills audit across multiple suppliers	Lack of coordination and skills audit across multiple suppliers	Confusion and frustration	All ADM Phases

14	CMO4.5	Training coordination Inefficient training schedules	Unfavourable timing for skills training and deployment schedules.	Fear, forgetfulness, and anxiety	All ADM Phases
15	CMO5.11	Digital Skills	The organisation is dealing with a technological skills gap and improper sequencing of tasks and activities within the programme.	Disempowerment, dissatisfaction, unmet programme outcomes	All ADM Phases

When capabilities are outsourced to third-party suppliers because of skill gaps in platform and structure and the deployment of new technologies, programme ownership and responsibility diminish, CMO7.18 emphasise the importance of ownership and responsibility for programme favourable EA outcomes. The ripple effect is skills attrition internal to the organisation, loss of organisational memory, and the lack of motivation of stakeholders leading to the inability to produce favourable outcomes to gain buy-in from users and stakeholders.

“There's a big skill gap within the NHS to have a strategic system; I'm thinking of platforms and ecosystems and deploying the new tech like artificial intelligence. There is not that level of expertise available for most Trusts, and they haven't had the habit. ... It fails because their strategy is to get a lot of small vendors together to own the platform, then there's a lot of ownership and responsibility, which I think people are very risk-averse to take it” [11].

CMO10.2 emphasises the need to enhance technical skills and competence to improve the understanding and adoption of technology that empowers Clinicians and technology staff to be more effective at their work. The ripple effect is the misalignment of technology with the organisation's objectives and goals.

A deficit in technical competence can adversely affect stakeholders' understanding and disempower users from effectively influencing programmes towards enhanced outcomes. Additionally, such a

skills gap can foster communication barriers within the organisation. These barriers may impede the effective exchange of information and ideas, thereby restricting the successful implementation and utilisation of technical programmes. Consequently, this highlights the critical need for adequate technical competence within the organisation for optimising operational outcomes and facilitating effective communication.

“And, of course, that requires an organisation that requires technical understanding. It requires technical foresight; it requires adjacent industry leverage and understanding. It requires a certain academic positioning. It requires all of the softer skills in influencing and understanding, and working together across different, very complicated in our spaces. ... And they want the technology to keep up; being able to have those conversations, understand, translate, adapt and implement requires a certain character. It requires a certain intellect because of a passion that is quite difficult to find in the market. These are the reasons why you people you are so valuable” [12].

CMO11.10 emphasises the importance of knowledge and experience in implementing technology programmes in Health on coordination and outcomes. Lack of coordination and skills audit to identify skills gaps amongst multiple suppliers creates confusion and frustration, adversely affecting the ability to execute the programme successfully. The inability to deliver the programme successfully is disempowering Clinicians and other users.

“Oh God, I don't know what was going on. But I think to me what seemed to be that we had three organisations working together. So, you had [organisation A]. Hang on. It was more than 3. We had [Organisation A]; we had [Organisation B]; we had [Organisation C]. So those three services we were working on. I'm not sure how together they were working, but they were working. And so, when they started, [Organisation B] would come in as the transformation specialist who hadn't seen the builds yet, but they were coming to work with us when they hadn't even seen the build. So, in the beginning, that transition phase was difficult because they were still working as three different entities. [Organisation B] had never done clinical projects, but they have never done a clinical project, never mind a project as large as this; this was the largest IT project in the world” [13].

CMO4.5 emphasises co-production and stakeholder collaboration as essential in controlling project duration and cost. When the timing of training delivery is far removed from the deployment schedule, users forget what they have been trained, leading to fear, anxiety and frustration and the need for retraining. The ripple effect is Stakeholders' disappointment and despair.

“And one thing I saw was they would train people, and it's good to train people, but if you set a deadline or a date to go live, then it should be very close to that date because people forget what they've used, and then when they start using, instead of using the system, instead of asking what they've forgotten or referring when they are referring to their notes or quick reference guides or whatever, asking somebody because they're under pressure because there's a queue of patients, they find the quickest way or a workaround and therefore not following the steps within the processes they're using” [14].

Suppose the technology programme resources are provided out of sequence and the wrong skills. In that case, it leads to the underutilisation of these resources because the programme objectives will not be analysed before development leading to stakeholder frustration and dissatisfaction. CMO5.11 emphasises the impact of human agency and structure of IT programmes for the availability sequencing of the right skills and the delivery of EA outcomes. The ripple effect is a Misalignment between programme outcomes and stakeholder expectations.

“There is a constant battle about getting the right skilled resource and the right number of resources for every program and sequencing them as well so that the right resources arrive on the program at the right time. And I've seen this in pretty much every program that I've been on, that effectively you get business analysis, user research, service design, developers, technicians, all landing at once. And that is highly inefficient and, in fact, quite disruptive. What I would like to see, and what I think will make for more successful projects, is to make sure that the right people arrive at the right time” [15].

6.5.4 Funding Barriers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical failure factors related to the funding circumstances (Funding availability and deficits, Funding delays, investment in digital

technology) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about relations that create outcomes that are transformational features of an organisation related to money, budgeting, investment, and cost (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.6. CMO configurations of critical failure factors in the funding context and as supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Funding)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
16	CMO1.21	Investing in Digital Technology	There has been a shortfall in investment in the necessary technical skills that foster the development of collaborative and stable teams.	The organisation is grappling with a loss of institutional knowledge and a technological skills gap, causing frustration.	All ADM Phases
17	CMO2.21	Funding constraints	The situation is aggravated by the stakeholders' uncooperative behaviour towards funding shortfalls, and the ill-timed cycles of budget allocation further complicate matters.	Frustration and missed programme schedules, and poor-quality outcomes	All ADM Phases
18	CMO6.16	Funding Decision-making	Decision-making is based on financial value for money over Clinician experience and quality.	There is a pervasive issue of clinician disempowerment, which correlates with the neglect of clinical outcomes.	All ADM Phases

19	CMO7.3	Funding constraints	Disparities amongst NHS Trusts in funding create varying digital maturities and their abilities to leverage technology innovation and integrate.	Poor integration disempowered Clinicians in their ability to share records across departments.	All ADM Phases
20	CMO10.9	Funding Constraints	Delivering complex longitudinal multiple IT projects programmes creates is costly.	Cost estimation difficulty	All ADM Phases

CMO1.21 emphasises the dynamic nature of organisational knowledge and collaborative teams as crucial to successful programme outcomes. If the organisation does not invest in talent and skills and promotes collaborative teamwork, EA programmes will likely fail despite the best architecture. When individuals depart from an organisation, there is a consequential loss of institutional knowledge. This departure can lead to a gap in technological skills within the organisation and engender frustration among stakeholders. This situation emphasises the significant value of institutional knowledge and the potential disruption its loss can cause, including compromised technological proficiency and increased stakeholder dissatisfaction. Thus, retaining and managing institutional knowledge becomes crucial for organisational continuity and success. The ripple effect is poor delivery of the organisation’s objectives and goals.

“And so, within an organisation, it will have to be, the people are a big thing. Getting the right people who are team players, collaborators who work with others and invest in people is something that sometimes organisations fail to do. And that can cause the failure of the best-intended programs and best-architected programs” [16].

CMO2.21 underscores the importance of having sufficient funding resources to realise programme outcomes efficiently. A deficiency in this aspect can have a ripple/cascading effect, potentially

leading to heightened frustration and dissatisfaction among clinicians. When there are funding deficits and inconvenient timing of budgetary allocation cycles, it leads to subversive behaviours to meet curtailed programme deadlines leading to poor quality EA outcomes.

“I think that a lot of the organisations that I sit at the moment focus 60% of their time chasing money from our national colleagues. So, I see that drives two behaviours. One behaviour is we can't do this until you give us the money. So then, things don't happen, which I classed as a failure” [17].

Focusing decision-making of technology procurement on financial value for money over Clinician experience and clinical quality disempowers Clinician users and adversely affects their effectiveness. CMO6.16 emphasises the need to prioritise finance in terms of the value realisation of technology solutions. The ripple effect is the misalignment of Clinician expectations and procured IT.

“Initially, I think the expectation was more about the structures we had, which didn't align Clinicians properly with the systems and the people building the system. I think finance was also one of the issues. At the time, I said on the board that if you have a finance director who is the senior responsible officer for IT projects in the trust, you could potentially have finance go ahead of quality. ... So that were some of the issues” [18].

CMO7.3 emphasises the adverse impact of digital inequality on technology programme outcomes. Disparities in funding, digital maturing, and the ability to leverage digital technology across various units of the NHS create digital inequality, resulting in tension between the centralised decision-making bodies and the decentralised operational services. The ripple effect is the Misalignment of the organisation's objectives, goals and IT.

“... there has been a lot of focus on global digital exemplars, local healthcare exemplars, and record exemplars. And those initiatives have helped some of the Trust to move forward. It has created a bit of disparity between the Trusts, which are lagging and more lagging. It has created more inequality. ... There's a tension between what should be done at the centre and what should be done locally” [19].

CMO10.9 emphasizes the adverse impact of the complex environment within healthcare organisations on EA outcomes. Dealing with organisational complexity, such as engaging with stakeholders and understanding the practical realities of delivering longitudinal programmes across multiple IT systems to enable EA change in an environment characterised by multiple programme challenges, creates implementation constraints. The ripple effect is a misalignment between organisational objectives and EA outcomes.

“...we're dealing with an onion here, many layers of delivering complexities. It is a 150-million-pound program over 15 years, effectively delivering all their IT services and enabling their change and transformation agenda. So, again, there's no singular. This is not a single project but a program of projects. These were multiple programs and IT service delivery efforts. There were many challenges brought along the way specific to each of the programs that we ran, I suppose, in general” [20].

6.5.5 Technology Barriers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the critical failure factors related to the technological circumstances (Established versus renewed technology Usage, Deliberate versus emergent renewal practices, Inner versus outer renewal practices) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about technology that create outcomes that are transformational features of the organisation’s vision, IT strategy, objectives and goals, and stakeholders' concerns. (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.7. CMO configuration of critical failure factors in the Technology context.

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Technology)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
21	CMO3.8	Usability of Applications and User interfaces	unreliable functional operation of technology systems for Clinicians	Frustration and disapproval	B, C, RM

22	CMO6.8	User-interface design and user experience.	The inability of Clinicians to record essential patient information in the EPR, such as auditing or capturing information for quality control.	Disempowered and frustrated Clinicians and administrative users	B, C, RM
23	CMO9.4	User-interface design and user experience.	Fragmented and incoherent records with no organic flow in the solutions by Clinicians create recording problems	Frustration, user attrition and slow adoption due to Clinician attrition in solution use.	B, C, RM
24	CMO12.4	User-interface design and user experience.	There are variable digital Applications and user interfaces across the organisations' departments and frequent retraining.	Clinicians face challenges when navigating diverse system interfaces, which hampers their professional mobility. This complexity necessitates supplementary training and often breeds distrust and frustration, impeding their work efficiency.	B, C, RM
25	CMO11.1 4	User-interface design and user experience.	Data quality errors due to poor vendor understanding of Clinical datasets.	Frustration and mistrust among users	B, C, RM

CMO3.8 emphasises the adverse impact of technology's unreliable and undependable functional operation on user confidence. The unreliable and undependable functional operation of technology

causes user frustration. The ripple effect is the misalignment between EA outcomes and user expectations.

“... in terms of patient transfers GP to GP, which is patient transfers from one GP [General Practitioner] Practice to another, that's ... I've been working on that. The idea is to make that a lot better, reduce the number of rejections, make it a lot smoother, provide a bit of reporting output, et cetera for the parties at each end” [21].

It is disempowering and frustrating for Clinicians and administrative users who cannot record patient information in the EPR, such as auditing or capturing information for quality control. CMO6.4 emphasises the absence of critical functional components in creating disempowerment and frustration amongst Clinicians and administrative users. The ripple effect is Misalignment between programme outcomes and user expectations.

“The other problem that we had with the system was also it had a front end that you could use to record patients' information, but behind it, it was difficult to do any auditing or capture information for audit for quality control. So, for instance, I see a different system where if I want to find out how many patients of mine are on a certain medication, you could somehow be able to extract that data. Whereas the electronic system we have, which we've been using for a lot, you cannot do that. You have to count the patients” [22].

CMO9.4 emphasise the adverse impact of a fragmented and incoherent clinical system that lacks organic flow on clinician perception and adoption. Fragmented and incoherent records with no organic flow in the clinical solutions cause Clinician frustration and user attrition. The ripple effect is the misalignment between strategic objectives and the organisation's IT.

“Maybe these trials happened wherever they were developing the software, but the reality is that when we started using these programs, there was a lot of attrition, if you like. It wasn't flowing organically. And different pieces of information were in different places and didn't seem to be related to the others. So it created problems and made recording problematic”[23].

Variations in technology and functional user interfaces across organisation departments negatively impact Clinician mobility and create the need for Clinician retraining, distrust and disempowerment. CMO12.4 emphasise the adverse impact of functionally inconsistent and incompatible user interfaces on Clinician productivity. The ripple effect of functionally inconsistent and incompatible user interfaces is the misalignment between EA outcomes and the organisation's objectives and goals.

“That's the way it works. I'm using this system to just buttress what I told you now. If I leave this hospital tomorrow [and] move to probably London to work, they might be using a different system. I have to receive another training to use their system. Whereas if we're all using the same system, it is not a problem if you move to another hospital. So that's another problem again” [24].

CMO11.14 underscores the negative impact of substandard engagement between suppliers and services on the quality of technology programme outcomes. The deficiency of meaningful engagement between technology vendors and services results in ambiguity and misunderstandings regarding the programme objectives. This is compounded by a prevailing mistrust of vendors and user frustration due to prior experiences with error-ridden deliveries. The ensuing domino effect

“And there were some major errors in there. So, they'd call them, and I challenged them, and there were some flaws, and they had to amend them, which was, um, you know, I felt quiet; that was the first time I did a really deep analysis of data and um, you know, I felt God, they spent 18 months doing this, you know? So, there wasn't enough interaction with the services when they were doing that because I was a national program. I've never been involved in this piece of work. So yeah, I think it was difficult; it was a difficult large project” [25].

6.5.6 Structural Barriers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical failure factors related to the structural circumstances (Roles And Positions, Rules and Resources, Processes, relationships) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about structure that create

transformational outcomes of the organisation related to roles/positions, practice, rules and resources, processes, and visible patterns. (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.8. CMO configuration of critical failure factors in the structural context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Structure)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
26	CMO11.11	Legacy IT and decision-making	Excessive Unrealistic expectations due to the large size of the programme. Preference for British vendors over international suppliers	resignation, dissatisfaction of stakeholders and disinterest in non-British capable vendors. Limited choice	All ADM Phases
27	CMO10.7	Legacy IT and decision-making	Despite their subpar services, reliance on legacy IT systems is a comfort blanket for the organisation. This reliance is further reinforced by consolidated, deeply ingrained, and trusting relationships with providers of these legacy systems.	Distrust of new technology providers and reluctance to migrate to new technologies.	All ADM Phases
28	CMO5.17	Legacy IT and decision-making	There is a culture of informal decision-making through relationships and networks, and teams have no confidence to challenge such decisions. Diktats from ministerial and external agencies are driving these decisions.	Distrust and frustration	All ADM Phases

29	CMO2.25	Legacy IT and decision-making	Challenge rigid programme mechanisms evaluated against an outdated business case because of pressures from leadership, workforce, and external influences.	High-risk of failure	All ADM Phases
30	CMO4.1	Legacy IT and decision-making	The scope of large and intricate implementation programmes is constrained by limited user choice, and the complex integration and exchange of information across systems present significant challenges.	The inadequate integration and connectivity of information amongst care providers have led to stakeholder dissatisfaction.	All ADM Phases

“*Too ambitious*” programmes are complex and challenging to manage, leading to stakeholder resignation and dissatisfaction. Preference for British suppliers leads to an inability to exploit international technology capabilities and limits organisational choices of emerging technology. The ripple effect is failure to deliver to schedule, technology that lags behind international quality standards, and Reluctance to exploit better technology internationally that might be available locally. CMO11.11 emphasises that competence and not nationality factors should drive the organisation's digital transformation agenda.

“But, you know, we picked organisation B maybe because they were British, but organisation A came and quite clearly said, this is a huge project. You need to focus on and only pick, you know, a small part that you're going to try and develop. They weren't interested in what the organisation was saying” [26].

CMO10.7 emphasises the difficulty of new entrants with innovative technology when dealing with organisations that have built an enduring and trusting relationship with legacy providers. When the

organisation builds trusting, close, and embedded relationships with legacy technology providers, there is distrust of new technology providers and inertia and reluctance to migrate to innovative technologies, especially in a competitive technology landscape. The ripple effect is Technology that lags behind changing organisational objectives and goals.

“Well, many, I mean, as I say, we walked into an environment where the organisation that got used to this comfort blanket of a legacy IT service provider, as much as the service is poor, people knew the people. They’ve been there a long time and done some good stuff on and off. It wasn’t all bad. And often that we, right? So our first biggest challenge to starting with was, gaining trust; they could not just do what they used to do, but we could do better, and we can make it better. And that’s difficult to do, especially in a competitive environment” [27].

CMO5.17 emphasises the need for formal governance processes as an effective means of decision-making, not informal relationships and networks. Lack of formal governance mechanisms, and stakeholders are unable to challenge decisions. Decision-making becomes irrational, opaque, and ineffective because organisational objectives are pursued as personal favourites instead of better patient outcomes, leading to distrust and frustration. The ripple effect is a misalignment between programme outcomes and patient outcomes.

“... a lot of decision-making is through informal channels. I think there is; you would expect large organisations to have strong governance and decision-making. Right the way from choosing which initiatives and programs to back through to technology choices will be based on a really strong governance framework. From my experience within the NHS, that is not the case. And it seems to be through informal relationships and who knows who, and who’s friends with who” [28].

When programme delivery is large, and durations are long, there is high exposure to the risk of not achieving programme outcomes due to scope creep and requirement volatility. Shorter, agile programme delivery reduces risk to the programme and improves outcomes. CMO2.25 emphasises

the adverse impact of unmanageable programme size and duration and the probability of risk and programme outcomes. The ripple effect is Misaligned EA outcomes with organisational objectives.

“And when I was doing my masters, the biggest failure for projects was the window of time. And there's a whole study around the window of time, done major transformation programs. The longer your period of the project, the more risk you're exposing to something happening. So shorter, sharp chunks, breaking things down can enable you to deliver something, iterate and build on, which in some parts is the philosophy behind agile and DSDM agile and those other kinds of methods” [29].

Policy directives that enable enormous implementation programme scope of multiple systems spread across the various care systems result in the difficulty of integrating and sharing information across the various health care organisations within the NHS. Breaking up systems across different health sectors was successful. CMO4.1 emphasises the adverse impact of the programme's large size on outcomes. The ripple effect is unmet opaque organisational objectives.

“It could have been a success, up to a point it was. But in the beginning, when they assigned everything they wanted to do to one organisation or company to handle the community mental health, private and secondary care, it didn't quite go well because it was just too big for them to handle. So, it didn't quite go well in that sense” [30].

6.6 Critical Success Factors to EA are expressed as Context-Mechanism-Configurations (CMOc).

This section describes the results following the iterative procedure to develop and refine the conceptual framework and elicit the programme's critical success factors, programme theories and CMO configurations. Each subsection provides the CMO configuration for the related context, cultural, agential, relational, funding, technological and structural (CRAFT Model. See conceptual framework in chapter 3). The CMO configurations enable successful EA outcomes. They enable alignment between the organisation's objectives and goals and its IT. Triggered mechanisms that create aligned outcomes are described as enablers.

6.6.1 Cultural Enablers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical success factors related to the triggered mechanisms' cultural circumstances (norms, values, beliefs, symbols). The mechanisms are empirical theories or ideas about culture, relations, agency, technology and structure (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.9. CMO configurations of Critical success factors in the cultural context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Culture)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
31	CMO1.6	Technology awareness	Awareness of the increasing importance of social and cultural impact on digital transformation and innovation as artificial intelligence capabilities are introduced into healthcare organisations.	Digital transformation and innovation that deliver socially and culturally sensitive technologies.	A, RM, E
32	CMO6.14	Clinician involvement	Improved culture of co-productive, bottom-up and consultative approach amongst multidisciplinary teams with clinician involvement and conducting regular update meetings, work plans, time scales and managing user feedback.	Improved Stakeholder empowerment, satisfaction, and confidence	All ADM phases
33	CMO8.5	Technology Awareness and adoption	The cultural change that embraces mobile technology infrastructure in emergency care serves supported by funding for mobile technology to improve access to	Improvement in technology-enabled patient care and timely clinical decision-making during emergencies	A, B, C, D, E

			information during emergency care intervention.		
34	CMO9.16	Technology Awareness and adoption	There exists an operational culture that encourages social and political acceptance of digital health among clinicians.	Improved adoption	All ADM Phases
35	CMO5.20	Technology awareness and adoption	The organisation has witnessed expedited technology adoption and growing interest in Telehealth solutions, including video conferencing and consultation technologies. Moreover, attitudes towards technology have become more favourable and associated risks have decreased.	Enthusiasm	H

Suppose suppliers are aware of the increasing importance of social and cultural implications of digital transformation and innovation. In that case, they become sensitive to stakeholder needs because healthcare is a people business, especially in applying artificial intelligence-driven technologies. CMO1.6 emphasises social and cultural sensitivity as important considerations for programme execution and accepting data-driven nascent technologies such as AI. The ripple effect is improved user decision-making and improved patient outcomes.

“Success in healthcare transformation, either with technology or without, cannot be achieved without both areas, social and cultural transformation. They must go alongside. We all know that healthcare is a people’s business at the end of the day, whether you have technology innovating there or not. And as we are innovating more and bringing more technical changes, I think going back and reminding ourselves of the cultural and

social factors has become increasingly important. Even things like AI, as that comes into the healthcare service” [31].

A culture of co-production, bottom-up and consultative approach amongst multidisciplinary teams through regular update meetings, agreeing on work plans and time scales, and managing user feedback improves stakeholder satisfaction and confidence in the technology and empowers them. CMO6.7 emphasizes stakeholder satisfaction and confidence in improving programme outcomes.

“And I’ve gone back the last two years again because of my position as a clinical director; somebody decided to attach a CCIO job prescription to it, which meant I couldn’t escape that. But I have a better relationship with the IT guys. And I have two weekly meetings, which are called the office of the CCIO meeting, and all the IT guys come, and there’s the head of the IT, the head of informatics and the head of IG, they all meet with me, and then all the project that we are talking about, we have a work plan and time scales. And I think we have somebody from finance on it, and then we kind of go through. And then, in meetings with clinicians, I give feedback to the clinicians; I meet all the CIOs from time to time to find out if things are going well, things like that. So the culture has changed, but initially, the culture was a top-down culture, take it or leave it type of approach” [32].

The cultural change that embraces mobile technology infrastructure in emergency care serves supported by funding for mobile technology to improve access to information during emergency care intervention and timely clinical decision-making that improves patient outcomes. CMO8.5 emphasises the positive impact of rapid access to patient history during emergency care on timely clinical decision-making and patient outcomes.

“So, one of the critical programs that I led as part of my portfolio was the instruction of iPads to 4,000 London ambulance crew members. Now, it isn’t simply just rolling out iPads; it’s also applications held on those iPads and the infrastructure needed to support them. A business and cultural change was required as a massive change; it wasn’t simply rolling out these iPads; it was also about the business and the clinical change that would have been required to make it a success” [33].

The pandemic has created a proliferation of different applications which allow us to access patients at a distance leading to advances in medical practice, but there are issues of safety, security, and the recording of patient information.

“So, there are other systems that we're finding now, especially; it has been crystallised during this COVID time, where we have seen a lot of applications—different applications which allow us to access patients at a distance. And a lot of them have got different advantages, and some of them have got different disadvantages. But I think that this is the advancement of IT in medical practice. ... The Covid-19 pandemic has exemplified the role of IT systems in enabling continuity of care even during the Lockdown” [34].

In organisations that are culturally risk-averse to digital technology, the Covid-19 pandemic has enabled increased technology adoption, reduced attitudes to risks, and increased the adoption rate of digital technology. CMO5.20 emphasises user risks appetite and embedded culture toward risk tolerance improves EA outcomes. The ripple effect of risk tolerance increased the appetite for technology modernisation and digital transformation, leading to better EA outcomes.

“The other interesting thing, of course, from an NHS healthcare perspective, is that it has definitely accelerated the adoption of technology across the NHS. People and organisations are more willing to accept new technology. Video conferencing and video consultations were something that had been trying to be pushed for a long time. And suddenly, that happened overnight because of the Pandemic. Attitude to risk has changed. As you know, the NHS is a very risk-averse organisation, NHS Digital is very risk-averse, and I think the Pandemic has forced them to be a bit more pragmatic about risk. That's been a significant change, I think, during the Pandemic” [35].

6.6.2 Relations Enablers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical success factors related to the triggered mechanisms' relational circumstances (duties and responsibilities, rights and power). The mechanisms are empirical theories about relations that create transformational outcomes of duties/responsibilities (skills and training), rights, and power (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.10. CMO configurations of Critical success factors in the Relations context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Relations)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
36	CMO1.10	Clinician Engagement	Accept change, digital maturity level and ensure clinical leadership for technology adoption through clinician engagement.	Stakeholder technology acceptance and buy-in	All ADM Phases
37	CMO2.8	Clinician Engagement	Co-production through collaborative design with Key stakeholders, including Clinicians, management, Patient groups and IT experts. Build stakeholder environments with the primary responsibility to work collaboratively in building the solutions designed involving local clinicians and admin staff with programme implementers to deliver the design specification.	Stakeholders' Buy-in and Trust	B, C, D, E, RM
38	CMO6.19	Clinician Engagement	engaging and listening to clinicians' opinions and co-producing technology solutions to address their concerns.	Commitment and buy-in among clinicians	B, C, D, RM
39	CMO9.1	Clinician Engagement	Co-production amongst a multidisciplinary team of top leadership, technical experts, and clinicians.	Meaningful operation of patient records and increased	All ADM Phases

				enthusiasm among Clinicians	
40	CMO12.11	Clinician Engagement	Collaboration and joint work increased with more focus on achieving programme outcomes and less on organisational politics.	Stakeholder satisfaction, commitment and buy-in	G, H, RM

Clinician engagement ensures clinical and operational voices are heard. Understanding the organisational affinity for change and its digital maturity leads to accepting the technology and aligning programmes to their needs.

“What is probably very important is listening to the business and the clinical voices. And we’ve seen that as we’ve tried to expand our customer base, we’ve realised that, while we might want to work with everybody, it’s not possible because of scale factors, but also because every organisation is different. And the factors that come to mind in alignment, which are important, are understanding how ready organisations are in terms of accepting change and accepting transformation” [36].

When a community user group of frontline local clinicians and administrative staff environment is set with the primary responsibility of working collaboratively to build the technology solutions designed and delivered by the programme implementers, the needs of frontline clinicians are met. CMO2.8 emphasises the importance of Clinician involvement in co-production to better solution design to achieve intended outcomes.

“So, we built those stakeholder environments with the frontline where their primary responsibility was to work collaboratively in designing and building the solutions. So, and you know the products that I’ll say, that we were building a national programme designed by local clinicians and designed by local admin staff. And our role then was to ensure we had worked with the supplier to deliver that to the spec for which the front

line designed it. And it took us a while to get to that point, but by the time the program was coming into its senior years, we were delivering releases of software that met the needs of the front line. So, for me, that's where we got the sweet spot of the stakeholder bit absolutely right” [37].

Listening to clinicians' opinions and co-producing technology solutions through design and testing drives up technology quality and acceptance and wins Clinicians' buy-in, appreciation, and trust. CMO6.12 emphasises the positive impact of co-creation amongst vendors, clinicians, and IT staff in winning clinician buy-in and confidence and improving the quality of technology solutions. The ripple effect is an Improved alignment of user expectations and IT.

“We found a few problems with it, so we couldn't measure diastolic, sitting and standing blood pressures were not quite clear in the system. And also, if the patient is not consenting, let's say. You need five of the data to be able to flag something. If somebody is consenting to, let's say, temperature but doesn't want his BP taken, then the system doesn't seem to capture it; you needed all the five things—that kind of a detailed conversation with him as a person who could build with us. Literally, within a couple of months, the system was functioning, and clinicians were very happy about it. So that kind of interaction helped shape the culture. And we, a lot of the staff, are saying, "Oh, actually, Tom is very helpful. If you need something or you find something which is not working, and you discuss it with him, he's able to..." So that was one of the things that shifted, so the change, the grammar to change the system if the system won't deliver, getting somebody who could help improve the system, who was willing to work with the clinicians, getting senior clinicians into CCO role” [38].

Soliciting Clinician stakeholder feedback through the co-creation and co-production of the programme deliverables' design increases clinicians' enthusiasm and makes the operation of the electronic patient records system meaningful to them. CMO9.1 emphasises the need for clinician engagement in co-creation and co-production for improved alignment of Business needs with IT. The ripple effect of Clinician engagement is aligning EA outcomes with organisational objectives and goals through stakeholder perspectives.

“So, I think that's one major one. Obviously, over time, that has developed through us giving feedback and the developers of the software themselves wanting to ask questions about how things are operating. And as it happens, some systems have done better than others; whether that is because they're much more compatible or much more user friendly, I cannot say because there's also competitiveness in the different systems that Trusts may use” [39].

There is improved stakeholder buy-in and satisfaction when planning is done collaboratively between top leadership and grassroots Clinicians. CMO12.11 emphasises the positive impact of collaborative planning between top leadership and grassroots stakeholders on satisfaction and buy-in in improving EA outcomes. The ripple effect is a better alignment of EA outcomes and stakeholder expectations.

“I always believe that you see that good planning is necessary for anything to work well, and planning should not always come from the top. It's always better when planning comes from the grassroots, the best ebb of the organisation. I will give you an example; when I was working in South Wales, the elderly unit used to be in [Britainox] hospital. [Britainox] hospital is now closed down. So, when I was working, they were trying to close down [Britainox] hospital. The old psychiatry in [Britainox] hospital is now matched with Prince [Twelvesteas] Hospital's main hospital” [40].

6.6.3 Individual and Organisational Agency Enablers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical success factors related to the individual and organisational agential circumstances (Beliefs and reasons for action or non-action) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about relations that create transformational outcomes of beliefs and reasons for action or non-action (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.11. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the individual and organisation agency context.

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Agency)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase

41	CMO10.11	Skills and training	The prevalence of skilled, technologically savvy, collaborative, co-productive multidisciplinary teams and consensus on delivery objectives is of significant importance.	Commitment and buy-in	All ADM Phases
42	CMO12.9	Skills and training	Train clinicians in digital skills, especially digital non-natives, to create and promote technology awareness before implementing the technology programme.	Acceptance, prevent adverse rumours, buy-in.	G, H, RM
43	CMO1.12	Skills and training	Introduce Clinician Change Champions.	Clinicians buy-in, drive change	All ADM Phases
44	CMO8.14	Skills and training	Adapting user training to different learning styles of stakeholder users.	Enthusiasm, engagement	G
45	CMO11.22	Skills and training	Actively soliciting feedback from non-native digital users enables the organisation to connect with them, capitalise on their strengths and interests, and leverage their related interests in technology solutions. This approach is instrumental in providing training, enhancing skill sets, and boosting user confidence.	Enthusiasm and buy-in, stakeholder confidence	RM, B, C, G

CMO10.11 emphasizes the impact of multidisciplinary team skills, consensus agreement, and the acceptability of programme outcomes. The preponderance of skilled, technologically literate,

collaborative, co-productive multidisciplinary teams who agree on clear delivery objectives improves tolerance and buy-in to the programme and creates better EA outcomes. The ripple effect is trust, confidence and buy-in from diverse stakeholders and delivery focused on delivering to fulfilling stakeholders' concerns.

“And I think that's the biggest reason you've got the upfront skill sets out; if you're clear on what you're delivering, you've agreed [on] what you are delivering. You're pretty sure everyone agrees what it is you're delivering, but enough mitigation and tolerance are in place to give you wriggle room. If you do not quite understand each other, then if you've got all of that in place, really, what are you going to watch out for?” [41].

The workforce is more likely to accept digital transformation when they are trained and aware of the value and use of technology. CMO12.9 emphasises the positive impact of stakeholder consultation and awareness of the scope and impact of digital transformation initiatives on workforce morale and buy-in. It also promotes confidence buy-in and unhelpful rumours about the programme and relieves the workforce's fear of losing jobs.

“Training is part of it, too, getting people involved before introducing the technology itself, letting people be aware of what you want, that particular technology, what should you be doing. And because if you bring in technology without that, there'll be a lot of rumours, a lot of things going on, or they want to sack people; they want to do this, which might not be true, totally unfounded” [42].

CMO1.12 emphasises the importance of promoting strategic objectives to stakeholders through direct engagement and obtaining buy-in as an essential influencer of programme outcomes. Stakeholder champions promote the strategic programme objectives and buy-in, making the programme's impact felt and improving stakeholder enthusiasm. The ripple effect is a clear understanding of their needs from their perspective and improved alignment between EA outcomes and stakeholder expectations.

“Having champions to then shout out from the rooftops that this is important to support that new strategy is equally important because otherwise, it'll fall flat, even if there was buy-in in the beginning, but there was not enough championship of that strategy down

the line. The effects will not be felt, and the outcomes won't be achieved. So, both the maturity of the organisation, the timing with which the change has been brought about, and the voice and the support, ongoing basis have been important” [43].

CMO8.14 places emphasis positive impact of training on technology adoption by users for successful outcomes of programmes. If digital technology training is adapted to different learning styles of users, then they will be enthusiastic and are likely to use the technology. The ripple effect is increased user confidence and digital technology adoption and usage rate.

“Well, basically, if people are not using it, then it's about additional training for them or buddying them up with somebody who is not afraid of using the technology and for them to learn. Because people have different learning styles, you have vital learning styles, which are visual, audible, kinaesthetic, and reading, there are different learning styles. Some people like to be shown, some people can read a novel and get it, and some need to listen and visualise it. So, there are different learning styles. And I think that when you do a program, that will have this massive change. The lessons I learned are to remember people have different learning styles” [44].

Listening to digital non-natives user stories to engage, tapping into their strengths, and exploiting their adjacent interests to increase their enthusiasm and confidence in using digital technology leads to improved user enthusiasm and use, providing support for digital immigrants. CMO11.22 emphasises the benefits of exploiting adjacent stakeholders' interests in digital technology adoption and improved EA outcomes.

“And some of them went on to teach other people in their wards. And one lady, the one I thought couldn't read. She went on to do a course. She signed up to do a course. So, you know, based on the challenges of the system and the cultural idiosyncrasies [peculiarities] around at the time, you know, we were able to break through those because we had to tap into other people's strengths” [45].

6.6.4 Funding Related Enablers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical success factors related to the funding circumstances (Funding availability and deficits, Funding delays, investment in digital

technology) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about relations that create outcomes that are transformational features of the organisation related to money, budgeting, investment, and cost (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.12. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the funding context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Funding)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
46	CMO1.23	Investing in emerging technology	Committing resources to cloud technology and harnessing the power of innovative technological advancements in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI).	Stakeholder enthusiasm and buy-in, confidence	E, RM
47	CMO5.21	Funding availability (investing in technology)	The Covid-19 pandemic has motivated the organisation to make funding for IT projects and clinician acceptance.	Clinicians' buy-in and enthusiasm	A, B, C
48	CMO8.10	Funding for core services	Allocating technological resources and financing IT programmes bolsters support in meeting the high service demand.	Trust and confidence	B, G
49	CMO8.12	Funding reviews	Review the benefits realisation plan and funding resources regularly to ensure the programme achieves set targets.	It enhanced reaction time for the ambulance team—treatment for more patients.	A, RM
50	CMO11.23	Value for money appraisal	Increase value appreciation of digital technology and access to funding.	Commitment and increased funding, enthusiasm	RM

Investing in cloud technology and leveraging cutting-edge technology in Artificial intelligence machine learning (AI) enabled the organisation to make better clinical decision-making to improve patient care. CMO1.23 emphasises the positive effect of cloud-based innovations such as artificial intelligence and machine learning on clinician effectiveness.

“And again, using the right technologies like leveraging the cloud is an important one, especially now with the machine learning world; instead of investing heavily into your own, increasing your GPU or whatever, how can we use the cloud models?” [46].

The Covid Pandemic 19 has promoted clinician acceptance and risk tolerance of digitisation, leading to increased investment in IT projects and improved speed and adoption. Although calamitous, CMO5.17 emphasises the positive impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on Clinician risk tolerance and enthusiasm towards digital transformation and enables increased investment in IT.

“Investment in IT has been flowing an awful lot better. We've seen more money being available for IT projects across the NHS. That's been another interesting dynamic that's come into play. ... And it's surprising how once they've adopted this technology, how they can't live without it once it's been adopted. I think, yeah, a massive sea change in terms of how quickly technologies are adopted, and there's almost a hunger for good technology now across the NHS” [47].

Technology resourcing and IT programme funding to support the high demand and pressure services create confidence and trust in technology programmes. CMO8.10 emphasises the positive impact of technology resourcing and funding on patient outcomes. The ripple effect of funding availability is better alignment between EA outcomes and organisational objectives and goals.

“As London expands, and as a nation, people are waiting longer, and obviously, there are other sorts of chronic conditions that are on the increase. The calls and requirements for emergency services are going up, and it's about balancing the funds and the resources. So that's the mechanism, and from a social perspective, people rely on the ambulance service as the first point of call. They say, "This is an emergency service." So culturally, if you call an ambulance, you want an ambulance to come to your house or to your place that you're injured quickly, and if they're stuck somewhere, they're not

going to be able to do that. So culturally, the people of London expect that we've got a world-class ambulance service, and we want to be able to see and respond” [48].

Regular review of the benefits realisation plan and funding resources will enable the programme to deliver benefits in the form of improved response time for ambulance crew and treatment of more patients at the scene of incidents. CMO8.12 emphasises the positive impact of a clear business case; and clinical and financial benefits statement on programme outcomes. The ripple effect is Improved delivery of programme schedules.

“I think when you set up a program, you've got to have your deliverables of what you want to achieve from it, and you look at business change and the benefits that you're looking to realise. So you look at your benefits from the onset as a part of the project's initiation, you'd have the business case, and you'd have your benefits realisation plan around what you want to deliver. And then, you work through your benefits to make sure that you're achieving them and that the whole program is achieving those benefits. So, its success criteria would be that you were able to improve the response times for your ambulances and improve the outcomes of the patients you have transferred, or you've seen treated” [49].

The Covid-19 pandemic created incentives for engagement with technology and access to funding. Increased appreciation for technology leads to improved organisational commitment and user enthusiasm. CMO11.23 emphasises the importance of IT programmes to organisations during the Covid-19 pandemic and the place of funding as an enabler. The ripple effect is improved programme delivery, capability and clinician empowerment.

“Oh gosh. Well, for IT, I shouldn't say this, but for IT, the pandemic was great. Because suddenly we became the most important department organisation. Usually, we can't get a word in; we can't get any funding. Suddenly, Information Technology was important [during the Covid-19 pandemic]. All the funding was for it because we needed to deliver, deliver, and deliver everybody within a few weeks was working from home, and we had to make it work so everybody could work from home. Even our switchboard was working from home. So, we were able to take non-facing staff away from the building and that ready, you know, cut the numbers by half” [50].

6.6.5 Technology Enablers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical success factors related to the technological circumstances (Established versus renewed technology Usage, Deliberate versus emergent renewal practices, Inner versus outer renewal practices) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about technology that create outcomes that are transformational features of the organisation's vision, IT strategy, objectives and goals, and stakeholders' concerns. (see details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.13. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the technology context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence :	CMOc	Context (Technology)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase
51	CMO1.2	Mobile technology	Mobile is currently one of the areas where health care appears to be making headway, and this strategy should be heavily focused on mobile. Board and national decision-making can be accelerated and concentrated on NHS mobile technology.	Quicker and better clinician decision-making.	E, RM
52	CMO1.11	Digital Maturity	Understand the organisation's digital maturity level by engaging Clinicians to assess and deliver the appropriate architecture.	Organisational readiness for digital transformation	PP, A, B, C, D, E
53	CMO3.9	A structure that encourages open relations with suppliers	User experience through Open relations with suppliers about the strength and weaknesses of existing legacy systems when	Increased supplier confidence and trust	All ADM Phases

			integration with new systems is required.		
54	CMO8.1	Structure of Clinical Systems that Prioritise Clinical Pathways	Digitising and loading clinical pathways paper-based records to mobile computers, e.g., iPods, for quicker user reaction to clinical events.	Clinician Buy-in and satisfaction	All ADM Phases
55	CMO9.14	Structurally secure systems	Accessible, affordable, secure, functionally consistent, and durable clinical solutions enable clinicians to manage patient information and conduct audits about what they do.	Buy-in, acceptance	B, C, D

Organisations that Put up a strategic plan for how suppliers might collaborate with the organisation in the short and long term find alignment in both needs and strengths and value offerings and build a strategy. Since mobile is currently one of the areas where health care appears to be making headway, this strategy should be heavily focused on mobile. Board and national decision-making can be accelerated and concentrated on NHS mobile technology. For the NHS to make quicker decisions in all sectors, concentrate on offering data analytics skills and capacities. CMO1.2 emphasise the need to understand the organisation to meet its needs.

“What are the wins along the way that can be achieved? And that's how we've architected our entire approach. The approach has largely included focusing on mobile because, at the moment, that's one of the areas where the health service seems that they can make the most progress. They can sort of making quicker decision-making both at the Board level and National level” [51].

CMO1.11 Emphasises technology acceptance and adaption as key to the success of EA programme outcomes success. Clinician engagement ensures clinical and operational voices are heard, and an

understanding of the organisational affinity for change and its digital maturity leads to acceptance of the technology and aligning programmes to their needs. The ripple effect is a Positive alignment between EA outcomes and programme objectives.

“The maturity level, I think, is a key one, and you can't just throw technology at an organisation and hope it'll stick. They must be ready; they have to be willing to accept it and adapt it. So those organisations that have had good leadership, in terms of clinical and operational, and their voices have been heard at the right levels. I think those have been key in aligning both the need to do the right thing and the ability to go ahead then do it” [52].

Open communication of the organisation in their relationship with suppliers about the strength and weaknesses of existing legacy technology where integration with the new system provided by the supplier-built supplier confidence and a trusting relationship with the stakeholder organisation. CMO3.9 emphasises the positive impact of open communication on building a trusting relationship between suppliers and implementing organisations to drive positive programme outcomes. The ripple effect is an Improvement in alignment between EA outcomes and organisational objectives.

“There are other areas as well, like pathology; again, there's an interface there which is simpler, there are some benefits around that, et cetera. I think it's just selling them the benefits and pointing out the drawbacks for any suppliers and existing suppliers that aren't willing to move to it” [53].

CMO8.1 Places emphasis on clinician engagement to identify their needs to improve outcome alignment. If clinicians and ambulance stakeholders are engaged in designing and testing the digitisation of paper-based clinical pathways, their needs are identified, leading to buy-in and satisfaction. The ripple effect is improved user effectiveness and patient outcomes due to improved response to treatment times.

“Whereas now, all that information is recorded on an iPad, [and] then downloaded onto a server. The other benefit of this particular program was that if an ambulance crew comes to your house and says you have got chest pains, okay, they will have all the

clinical pathways loaded onto the iPad. So, when they see you, they can react quickly to your needs. So, if you come in and say you've got a wound in your leg, they will then have the wound care pathway to act and react for you” [54].

Accessible, affordable, secure, functionally consistent and durable clinical systems enable clinicians to manage patient information and conducting clinical audits will improve their ease of use and satisfaction. CMO9.14 emphasise the importance of accessibility, affordability, security, functional consistency and durable clinical records in enabling effective management of patient information and clinical audits, which are crucial to improving patient care and clinician user experience. The ripple effect is the alignment between technology architecture and clinician-user expectations.

“So, in summary, the success of a program, first of all, acceptability. Even if a system is acceptable and affordable, it is durable, it is secure, and all the maintenance issues and functionality are consistent; those would be the general aspects of it. In terms of the detail of the clinical work that we do, a system that makes it easy for us to enter records and those records to be easily accessible to all those who need access to them is a good system. A secure system is a good system. Secure in the sense of access to it and protecting patient information; basically, that would be a good system. A system that will allow us to interrogate allow us to manage patient information, and manage the clinical system to conduct audits about what we do would be a good system” [55].

6.6.6 Structural Enablers

The CMO configurations in this section constitute the findings of the critical success factors related to the structural circumstances (Roles And Positions, Rules and Resources, Processes, relationships) of the triggered mechanisms. The mechanisms are empirical theories about structure that create transformational outcomes of an organisation related to roles/positions, practice, rules and resources, processes, and visible patterns. (See details in the conceptual framework in Chapter 3).

Table 6.14. CMO configurations of critical success factors in the structural context and supporting evidence of the Initial programme theory (CRAFTS Model).

Evidence:	CMOc	Context (Structure)	Mechanism	Outcome	ADM Phase

56	CMO1.13	Governance structure	A proficient organisational and governance framework fostering relationships with suppliers becomes crucial when the organisation internally determines a new strategy involving clinicians at all echelons.	Quicker times to achieve programme outcomes, buy-in.	G
57	CMO2.9	Clinicians engaging governance structure	Establish governance programme boards co-chaired by local clinicians, such as the Medical Director as Chief Clinical Information Officer, with programme implementers as servants.	Servant Leadership and ownership structure promote cooperation and favourable outcomes.	G
58	CMO5.6	Implementation Governance	Clear objectives and well-defined requirements are updated to reflect technological and healthcare changes.	Easier to demonstrate achievement, improve the visibility of objectives	G
59	CMO10.17	A structure that removes process paradox	Increased process efficiency and governance change were expedited due to diminished process paradox and improved governance processes.	Confidence, improved patient outcomes	RM, H
60	CMO11.18	Governance structures that ensure	Organisational readiness to adopt digital technology when structures such as	Enthusiasm, confidence, and commitment	G

		organisational readiness	governance documentation.	and		
--	--	-----------------------------	------------------------------	-----	--	--

CMO1.13 emphasises the positive impact of effective communication in decision-making and collaborative stakeholder engagement between the supplier and the implementing organisation. Building relationships, not in a one-time process and ensuring suitable governance structures that include clinicians' voices at various layers can lead to effective communication and create enthusiasm. In a deficient governance structure, the attainment of programme outcomes is subject to considerable delays. The ripple effect is the alignment between EA outcomes and Expectations.

“I think good governance structures were quite key and have been quite key. And, I think once we go into a relationship with customers or the organisation decides on a new strategy internally, it is not a one-time process; that is done. The right organisational framework and the right governance framework are critical; having the right voices around the table and having the right people has been critical, but implementing that right governance structure at various levels and layers [have] allowed the success of these programs to happen. Where that has been weak, there have been issues or programs that have taken longer to achieve their outcomes” [56].

When governance programme boards are established and co-chaired by implementers and local medical directors serving as Chief Clinical information officers and implementers serving as servant leads, clinician needs are met. CMO2.9 emphasises the importance of Clinician engagement and leadership in producing programme outcomes that meet clinician needs. The ripple effect is improved governance, timely implementation

“So, I am taking some of that learning that we had around stakeholder engagement and applying that today. So in some parts of England, we have a regional digital transformation board; and that is chaired by my medical director as the chief clinical information officer in the region. And it is co-chaired by an accountable officer from one of the ICSs, and what that meeting is doing is putting together all of the national teams and Organisation One, organisation two, our regional teams and our local ICSs, but the

ownership of that is owned at the chief exec and medical director level. And we are almost their servants to make sure we are delivering against what they need” [57].

Clear objectives and updated requirements to reflect changes in the technology and healthcare landscape promote ease of evaluation against the programmes, demonstrate achievement, and improve stakeholders' visibility of objectives. CMO5.6 emphasise the dynamic nature of organisational needs requiring regular review of objectives and requirements of the EA programmes for alignment with technology. The ripple effect is the alignment between EA outcomes and Stakeholder expectations.

“What worked? What worked, I think, is broadly speaking, where there are very, very clear objectives. And everybody is aligned [with] those objectives. I've got to submit that moving things in-house works very well, I thought. Because the requirements were very well-defined because we were just replicating what had already been proven for the last ten years, that seems to work well; transferring it works well if you're not changing the requirements. From a certain lens, you could say that [it] works extremely well” [58].

CMO10.17 emphasises the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic crisis on process efficiency and improved stakeholder confidence in achieving programme outcomes. The crisis brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated procedural efficiency, reduced process paradoxes and enhanced governance procedures, thereby promoting heightened confidence among stakeholders. The ripple effect is Improved alignment between organisational objectives and programme outcomes.

“People realised that you don't need all those processes or governance, all of that stuff that used to get in the way of delivery. It would be more outcome-focused, and I think that's the biggest win from a program delivery standpoint if he can distil any good from what's happened over this Pandemic” [59].

Stakeholders are enthusiastic and committed when organisational readiness for digital adoption, governance structures and documentation of policy guidelines, and a prepared infrastructure environment. CMO11.18 emphasises organisational readiness for technology adoption as an indicator

of success. The ripple effect is Reduced risks of errors in programme outcomes and technology-induced patient harm.

“So we had our own program board; we had services lined up. I had written a document, which was, you know, where Organisation A had given us a document where we had to prepare it. It was a readiness document. So, we had to prepare our organisation. And if you were ready and you had done, you know, certain things, they may have given you five tasks to do; if you were ready, then you would go through that gateway. And not until you already can you go through that gateway. I then created a document similar to that for services. So, they will say, oh, can we be first? Can we be first? Well, yes, you can be first if you have done these five things” [60].

6.6.7 Summary of Findings

The results confirm the hypothesis explained in Chapter 3. In the context of CRAFTS, EA mechanisms trigger outcomes in digital transformations. Some outcomes, through their related mechanisms, align with the organisation's objectives and goals, constituting critical success factors. Other triggered mechanisms create misaligned outcomes with the organisation's objectives and goals, constituting critical failure factors. CMO configurations that create alignment are enablers, and those that create misalignment are barriers.

6.7 Discussion

This study describes the findings of a rigorous and iterative method for developing an initial programme theory to assess the key success and critical failure elements for EA interventions in healthcare organisations. The study was retrieved and developed by a realist synthesis of the existing literature on EA interventions inside digital transformation programmes in healthcare, interviews with individual experts, programme implementers, and users on collectively led teams, and feedback. Two hundred and thirty-one (231) CMOCs present a basic programme theory of how critical success factor and critical failure factor mechanisms in various settings lead to EA outcomes that are either aligned or misaligned with the organisation's objectives, goals and expectations via the lens of stakeholder viewpoints.

The result of the study confirms the hypothesis. CMO configurations refined are consistent with the initial programme theory in the following ways and support the initial programme theory:

- CMO configurations constituting critical failure factors and critical success factors have been elicited from participant theories.
- The result confirms that the circumstances of the programme generally fall within culture, relations, agency, funding, technology and structure. Mechanisms of EA in the digital transformation are triggered in context to create outcomes that are either aligned or misaligned with the organisation’s goals and objectives through the lens of stakeholder theories.

6.7.1 CMO Configurations preponderance and distributions in CMO configuration in Mechanisms contributing to Alignment of Outcomes.

Table 6.15. Distribution of Critical Success Factors in the CRAFTS Model

Context	Critical Success Factors CMOc	Percentage
Culture	6	6%
Relations	34	35%
Agency	14	15%
Funding	5	5%
Technology	21	22%
Structure	16	17%
Total CMOc	96	

Figure 6.1. A bubble chart view of the Distribution of Critical Success Factors CMO configurations in the CRAFTS Model.

The findings show that the mechanisms regarding relations, duties and responsibilities, rights and power are the most critical determinant of successful EA outcomes, with funding being the least, as shown in **Figure 6.1**. Relations about collaboration and consultation with Clinician stakeholders are a recurrent pattern. Clinician involvement in decision-making and co-productions seems to be a desired feature by participants [36, 37, 38, 39, 40]. Whilst Funding scored 5%, the funding context success criteria mainly focus on investment in emerging technologies and regularly reviewing spending for value assessment [46, 49, 50]. Prioritising funding for technology that supports core services, especially during the Pandemic, with the most significant benefit to the patient is also a critical factor [47].

6.7.2 CMO Configurations preponderance and distributions in CMO configuration in Mechanisms contributing to Misalignment of outcomes.

Table 6.16. Distribution of Critical Failure Factors in the CRAFTS Model

Context	Critical Failure Factors CMOc	Percentage
---------	-------------------------------	------------

Culture	11	8%
Relations	26	19%
Agency	42	31%
Funding	10	7%
Technology	20	15%
Structure	26	19%
Total CMOc	135	

Table 6.17. A bubble chart view of the Distribution of Critical Failure Factors CMO configurations in the CRAFTS Model.

The findings from the CMO configurations from empirical theories from participants shows that individual and institutional agency has the most impact on determining failures in EA outcomes in digital transformation programme within the organisation. Institutional and individual agency barriers are mainly centred around training and skill development in digital technology skills and awareness,

especially for clinicians and the digital-non-native workforce. The increasing importance and demand for technology-enabled care intervention have been critical, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. Users embraced technology despite their cultural aversion [11, 12, 13, 14].

The most negligible contextual impact on the programme causes failure in funding, as depicted in the bubble chart in **Figure 6.5**, which is perhaps understandable since the programme never starts without funding.

6.7.3 Comparing CMO configurations for failure outcomes and Success outcomes

Table 6.18. Distribution of CMO configurations in the context of The CRAFTS model.

Context	Critical Success Factors CMOC	Critical Failure Factors CMOC
Culture	6	11
Relations	34	26
Agency	14	42
Funding	5	10
Technology	21	20
Structure	16	26
	96	135

Figure 6.2. Distribution of CMO configurations related to Critical success factors and Critical failure factors in Radar view in the context of the CRAFTS Model.

More CMO configurations elicited identified contexts more unfordable to programme outcomes except for relations.

6.7.4 Critical Success Factors of EA

Awareness of the increasing importance of social and cultural impact on digital transformation and innovation as artificial intelligence capabilities are introduced into healthcare organisations [31].

The cultural change that embraces mobile technology infrastructure in emergency care serves supported by funding for mobile technology to improve access to information during emergency care intervention.

Co-production through collaborative design with Key stakeholders, including Clinicians, management, Patient groups and IT experts. Build stakeholder environments with the primary responsibility to work collaboratively in building the solutions designed involving local clinicians and admin staff with programme implementers to deliver the design specification [37].

Engaging and listening to clinicians' opinions and co-producing technology solutions to address their concerns [38].

Improved culture of co-productive, bottom-up and consultative approach amongst multidisciplinary teams with clinician³³) involvement and conducting regular update meetings, work plans, time scales and managing user feedback [32].

The preponderance of skilled, technologically literate, Collaborative, co-productive multidisciplinary teams and agreement on delivery objectives improve stakeholder commitment and buy-in [41].

Training clinicians in digital skills, especially digital non-natives, creates and promotes technology awareness before implementing the technology programme. By introducing clinician champions, barriers to communication with clinicians can be improved, leading to better relationships with implementers and gaining Clinician buy-in [43]. Negative rumours can be detrimental to the reputation of the technology. Digital technology will likely be accepted when such rumours are curtailed through awareness sessions [42].

Listening to digital non-native user stories to engage, tapping into their strength and interest, and exploiting their adjacent interests in technology solutions to train, skill and increase user confidence peaks their enthusiasm. It leads to better confidence in using the technology solutions.

Investing in cloud technology and leveraging innovative technology in Artificial intelligence machine learning (AI) enable better insights into patient care and piques the enthusiasm of clinicians as they are empowered to drive up the quality of care through data-driven decision-making [46]. Regular review of the benefits realisation plan and funding resources to ensure the programme achieves set targets, especially in emergency services, improves response time to treatment since such reviews can reveal gaps vital to operations [49]. Increased value appreciation of digital technology and access to funding improves commitment and enthusiasm. This was witnessed during the Covid-19 pandemic when additional funding resources were provided to support digital transformation initiatives [50]. Mobile technology is currently one of the areas where health care appears to be making headway, and this strategy should be heavily focused on mobile. Board and national decision-making can be accelerated and concentrated on NHS mobile technology. It leads to quicker and better decision-making for clinicians [51]. It enables readiness for the digital transformation of the various organisations within the NHS [52]. However, there is a need to understand the organisation's digital maturity level by engaging with clinicians and other stakeholders to assess and deliver the appropriate architecture.

Implementing structures that encourage open relations with suppliers increases supplier confidence and trust. User experience through Open relations with suppliers about the strength and weaknesses of existing legacy systems when integration with new systems is required builds confidence and trust between stakeholders and suppliers [54].

Systems that are structurally secure, Accessible, affordable, secure, functionally consistent, and durable clinical solutions enable clinicians to manage patient information and conduct audits about what they do are acceptable to stakeholders and are likely to wind their buy-in [51].

An efficient organisational and governance structure that builds a relationship with suppliers, especially when the organisation decides on a new strategy internally, Engagement Clinicians at all levels create a quicker turnaround for achieving programme outcomes and stakeholder buy-in [56].

Establishing governance programme boards co-chaired by local clinicians, such as the Medical Director as Chief Clinical Information Officer, with programme implementers playing the role of servants promote cooperation and ultimately favourable EA outcomes [57].

Increased process efficiency and governance change were expedited due to diminished process paradox and improved governance processes. A structure that focuses on patient outcomes aligned to the vision of the NHS and not how efficiently the mechanisms within the programme are delivered removes the paradox of process and creates enthusiasm, confidence and commitment among essential technology solutions users such as Clinicians [59].

Organisational readiness to adopt digital technology improved when structures such as governance and documentation peak enthusiasm and confidence among stakeholders [60].

6.7.5 Critical Failure Factors Of EA

The research findings suggest that Clinicians feel disempowered and disapprove of the digital transformation outcomes. The NHS is culturally averse to technology. Users might feel threatened by digital transformations that are essentially cultural aversion to technology [1, 2, 3]. Culture can become an opposing force (Bolman & Deal, 2017), as it did in the CRS programme.

'Legacy IT' slows down technology adoption and disempowers Clinicians in their work effectiveness. The research findings suggest that a risk-averse cultural outlook on technology innovation is prevalent in the organisation, preventing it from addressing complex issues brought on by changing environment in the healthcare sector. The preponderance of a comfort blanket of legacy IT systems with poor services and close, embedded, and trusting relationships with legacy systems providers are prevalent [4].

Legacy IT limits organisational performance by rendering technology ineffective (Hafsi & Assar, 2016; Fitzgerald, Kruschwitz, Bonnet, & Welch, 2013; Westerman, Calmejane, Bonnet, Ferraris, & McAfee, 2011; Prahalad & Krishnan, 2002).

Architects and other programme implementers who understand cultural symbolism and accompany that by applying its 'spirit and soul' may help form more cohesive and productive organisations—if the cultural patterns reflect stakeholder concerns (Bolman & Deal, 2017).

Understanding and applying culture in EA is the TOGAF ADM is relevant in all phases where stakeholder concerns are relevant, especially in the requirement management and the Architecture change management phase (H).

The Architecture Requirement Management phase aims to manage architectural needs identified throughout any execution of the ADM cycle or phase. It also guarantees that relevant architecture requirements are accessible for usage by each phase when the phase is conducted.

The Phase H goals are to manage the architectural lifecycle, implement the Architecture Governance Framework, and guarantee that the Enterprise Architecture Capability fulfils current requirements (The Open Group, 2018).

Programme circumstances of the CRS, such as duties and responsibilities, rights, and power, triggered generative mechanisms within the CRS programme to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Pawson & Manzano-Santaella, 2012).

Yeo (2002) identified ineffective communication amongst stakeholders as a critical failure factor for technology programmes. The findings show that despite a high level of relevant IT skills to support the programme concerning the Electronic Health Record System (HER). There is a poor complaint management process, a lack of Clinician engagement with IT staff and a culture that does not encourage collaboration and adoption, resulting in Clinician dissatisfaction, disapproval of the solution and misalignment with stakeholder concerns.

De Brún and McAuliffe (2020) argue that motivation, empowerment, role clarity, feeling supported and valued, and psychological safety result in quality and safety improvements, staff and patient satisfaction, improved teamwork, and a greater willingness to share and adopt leadership roles and responsibilities.

The findings also show a lack of Clinician engagement and collaboration at the informatics board level, the highest level of decision-making about digital transformations within the programme. Unlike previous literature, the findings situate engagement and collaboration within Clinician behaviour as cultural attributes [6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

While Clinicians and non-clinicians share the view that Clinicians were generally not engaged in the digital transformation programme, non-clinicians gave varying opinions about why there was a lack of Clinician engagement.

Poor engagement of frontline Clinician users is due to inadequate training and a legacy culture, and a mindset of job security because of technology unemployment digital technology might create. Formal arrangements on how Clinicians and IT experts can engage for mutual understanding of the programme activities can enable better outcomes and alignment [4, 6, 7].

When things begin to move, individuals become unclear of their new responsibilities, how to interact with others, and who has the right to determine what. Confusion, loss of control, and a perception that politics trumps policy replace clarity, predictability, and rationale. To reduce such challenges, innovators must foresee structural obstacles and attempt to restructure the current architecture of roles and interactions. In other cases, altering the Framework might be done haphazardly. Structural arrangements need formal renegotiations (Bolman & Deal, 2017). "*Conflict and confusion are inevitable without a clear definition of roles and relationships*" (p.309).

As many staff as possible must be engaged to learn how various groups are impacted. Engagement, for example, could assess if expanding digital access to care would disproportionately affect specific stakeholder groups and how to manage this risk (Wenzel & Evans, 2019).

Architects should create a communication plan that involves Clinician engagement.

Enterprise architectures include massive amounts of complex and interconnected data. A Critical Success Factor (CSF) for Enterprise Architecture is promptly communicating future information to the relevant stakeholders. Creating an architectural communications strategy enables this

communication within a planned and regulated procedure (The Open Group, 2018). Participant Six characterised the inertia to migrate from legacy IT to renewed technology as one brought on by 'job formation'. The findings suggest that rationalising and modernising the existing legacy digital technology and adopting new digital capabilities is a challenge that adversely affects Clinician empowerment and cost optimisation.

The finding suggests a critical failure factor is poor Clinician User experience. Inconsistency in the user interfaces that lack mirroring with existing clinical processes in the design of the Electronic Patient Record system because of the lack of co-creation with Clinicians creates difficulty in usability and causes frustration among them [23].

Participant Seven describes the implementing organisation as cultural technology risk-averse with some tension between local and National provision of technology.

Renewal of technology is seen as a process of transformation that includes the *"replacement of attributes of an organization that has the potential to affect its long-term prospects substantially"* (Agarwal & Helfat, 2009, p. 282).

As a result, organisations must not only continuously develop and implement new digital capabilities and applications in comparison to their existing technology stacks, but they must also periodically renew their underlying digital platforms and infrastructures based on technological advances in order to remain competitive (Nambisan et al., 2017; Yoo, Henfridsson, & Lyytinen, 2010).

Technology renewal refers to the process through which organisations aim to replace their core digital platforms and infrastructures to achieve their strategic objectives (Wimelius et al., 2021).

Legacy IT culture. Changes to deeply embedded organisational structures, procedures, and cultures (Hanseth & Lyytinen, 2010; Liang, Saraf, Hu, & Xue, 2007; Wand & Weber, 1995) always render renewal projects vulnerable to failure.

As a result, there is a need for a precise understanding of the mechanisms driving risks and their resolution throughout technology renewal activities. Conclusion: there can be no development of a

cumulative tradition (Walsham, 1995) in which researchers and practitioners may integrate fresh empirical discoveries and advance theory without ideas and frameworks devoted to socio-technology renewal (Wimelius et al., 2021).

6.7.5.1 Challenges of technology renewal

Changes to organisational technology usage might be challenging due to the inertia caused by a culture of legacy IT (Hanseth & Lyytinen, 2010). Without explicit goals and anticipated results, integrating new digital platforms into organisational processes may take time (Liang et al., 2007; Öbrand, Augustsson, Mathiassen, & Holmström, 2019; Rolland, Mathiassen, & Rai, 2018).

6.7.5.2 The tension between strategic and tactical solutions

Technology renewal entails complicated changes with opposing paths that cause several strategic and operational difficulties during digital transformation initiatives. As a result, we define technology renewal as a paradoxical digital transformation process in which organisations must simultaneously eliminate their existing technologies while still building on the behaviours that rely on them to adopt a new technological foundation. Technology renewal is a paradox; established (legacy IT) versus renewed technology use, purposeful vs emergent renewal techniques, and inner vs exterior renewal settings. Given the state of technology, renewal is a paradoxical and more crucial digital transformation process, compelling Architects and other stakeholders to judge the numerous complicated and confusing choice circumstances that develop throughout these efforts (Wimelius et al., 2021).

Given the importance of technology renewal programmes in influencing how an organisation digitises its process and its broader strategic orientations, it is not unexpected that such initiatives are driven by conflicts (Wimelius et al., 2021).

Lack of collaboration between IT and Clinicians [6], Non-engagement of Clinicians, technical staff, and other programme stakeholders in the programme's decision-making. Complicated procurement

mechanisms that lack Clinician engagement during negotiations and decision-making with suppliers about the functionality of technology solutions mean a poor understanding of stakeholder concerns [9]. Lack of User research and engagement to gain insight and understand issues through feedback about change implementation the frontline clinicians face in adopting digital technology [10]. These have created structural difficulties and Clinician frustration and led to User resistance to technology adoption, lack of commitments and unachieved delivery targets [8, 9, 10].

Technology barriers mainly involve the usability of Applications and User interfaces. Unreliable functional operation of technology and variable digital Applications and user interfaces across the organisations' departments, and frequent retraining systems for Clinicians create frustration, user attrition and slow adoption due to Clinician attrition in solution use [21, 22, 23, 24]. Due to poor vendor understanding of Clinical data sets, data quality has resulted in mistrust and frustration among Clinicians and other programme stakeholders [25].

Underinvestment in the requisite technology skills that enable has led to technology skills attrition and a loss in organisational memory and the ability to support the services with cutting-edge technology [16].

The uncooperative behaviour of stakeholders towards funding deficits and inconvenient timing of budgetary allocation cycles has also been reported. This has led to frustration, missed programme schedules, and poor-quality outcomes [17]. There is a perception that NHS organisations prioritise decision-making based on financial value for money over Clinician experience and quality, which disempowers frontline clinicians in their ability to drive up standards using data-driven decision-making technology tools [18].

Disparities amongst NHS Trusts in funding create varying digital maturities and their abilities to leverage technology innovation and integrate to share information because the varying maturities create digital compatibility issues [19]. Cost estimation for complex longitudinal multiple IT projects

or programmes, which seems to be the characteristics of the NHS's digital transformation initiatives, becomes difficult [20].

Excessive Unrealistic expectations due to the programme's large size with a preference for British vendors over international suppliers seem to be holding down efforts to exploit open innovation globally. Preference for the locally developed system creates distrust of new technology from internal providers and a reluctance to migrate to these new technologies [26].

There is a culture of informal decision-making through relationships and networks, and teams have no confidence to challenge such decisions. Diktats from ministerial and external agencies allegedly drive these decisions, creating distrust and frustration among stakeholders because of the decision-making structures[29].

The lack of agility and rigid programme mechanisms evaluated against an outdated business case because of pressures from leadership, workforce, and external influences create a high-riks of digital transformation failure outcomes [29].

Large and complex implementation programmes scope with limited user choice and complex integration and transfer of information across systems means poor integration and connectivity of information across care providers leading to stakeholder dissatisfaction [30].

6.7.6 How an EA Program Might be Reconfigured in the Context of Triggering Mechanisms

Antecedent Conditions In an action context

Figure 6.3. shows how the EA CMO configurations for successful outcomes might be reconfigured to align with the organisation's objectives and goals, with agility with ongoing stakeholders' concerns as input.

The findings show that stakeholder concerns are frequently evolving, and there is a need for continuous and active engagement to understand their needs and win their trust in the programme. The initial programme theory might be reconfigured, as shown in **Figure 6.3**. The refined conceptual framework proposes a feedback loop mechanism for misaligned or aligned outcomes fed into the programme for reconfiguration for successful outcomes. Contextual changes and their impact on trigger mechanisms in the programme where requirements are frequently changing means the drive for agility and responsiveness to these changes in programme activities becomes all too clear. Stakeholder concerns are unfavourable to aligned EA outcomes and must be reconfigured by the programme's mechanisms towards successful outcomes.

6.7.7 EA Mechanisms and Emergence in the Context of Programme Action

According to Bhaskar (2009), Mechanisms have generative causal powers. Mechanisms "*exist in the causal power of things*" (p.40). Supporting his view, Pawson and Tilley (1997) argue that mechanisms are theories that determine "*the potential of human resources and reasoning*" (p.68).

According to Collier (1994, p.62), a generative mechanism is a technical term that designates something real and independent of patterns of events affecting it. For Instance, the generative mechanisms of an individual's brain structure are real, with the potential and capacity to enable that individual to learn a language. The individual's brain's structure has causal powers of language acquisition.

In the volcanic eruption analogy used in describing the generative causal pathways, what happens beneath the surface may be hidden. Still, under the proper context and conditions, there is an eruption. The mechanisms within the volcano lay dormant and have the capacity and potential to cause a volcanic eruption.

"Realist evaluations, therefore, seek to explain generative causation within the social world by identifying particular patterns of interactions" (Gilmore et al., 2019, p.1).

Collier distinguishes horizontal mechanisms with their antecedents in other generative mechanisms and vertical mechanisms with explanatory power from one based on another mechanism. Vertical mechanisms exist because of a stratified layer of reality (Bhaskar, 2009; p.47). Mechanisms, therefore, exist in multiple layers of reality, both observable and unobservable.

An event or change is generated when certain triggered conditions in structures of objects, with some intervention, cause action potentials to be triggered. Collier (1994) argues that objects and mechanisms are located within structures, social or material, with action potentials. He further contends that examining, even predicting, the structures that generate these potentials is possible.

de Souza (2013) draws on Collier's explanation to suggest that generative mechanisms within an organisational context are in structure, culture, agency, and relational properties since domains are the locus for organisational context. Given that the social context is an inherent aspect of social programmes, it can be logically inferred that the mechanisms within these programmes operate and behave autonomously within these social contexts, irrespective of any other program interventions.

EA Mechanisms, therefore, in the context of the programmes, are the cognitive processes, the minds or reasoning of participants/stakeholders, turned on or not when they engage in the intervention to align the organisation's objectives and its IT.

Therefore, the question for researchers intends to unearth the nature of the generative mechanisms in operation within the social context that can transform or reproduce existing social structures, whether they contribute to desired outcomes of the social programmes or create problems (Jagosh, 2020b).

The research aims were to identify program input that can configure or trigger the generative mechanisms in context to transform it towards successful outcomes rather than reproduce the action context it aims to change.

6.7.8 *Constructive Ambiguity of EA Frameworks*

The research findings show that mechanisms and outcomes applied in EA implementations are context-sensitive; what EA outcomes work [or do not work] for whom and under what circumstances

(Pawson & Tilley, 1997). According to Kotusev (2016), research evidence shows that many suggestions are deemed inapplicable and not implemented, even in organisations on The Open Group's list of TOGAF users.

The findings reported by Kotusev in the above research evidence are to be expected since mechanisms are context-sensitive and cannot be predicted because of changing circumstances and complexity under which EA is implemented. Accordingly, EA frameworks are applicable when adjustments are made for contextual variations in the mechanisms of EA. Indeed, The Open Group clearly states that the TOGAF framework requires tailoring. This research suggests obtaining stakeholder feedback and concerns can help tailor EA frameworks for better outcomes.

The TOGAF framework is ambiguous without context. For example, while some respondents reported the need for deep governance in large projects, others suggested that light governance during the pandemic yields successful outcomes. It is, therefore, understandable that EA frameworks are constructively ambiguous.

The TOGAF Framework is a valuable and powerful propositional formulation for architecting. Meaning can be made when the context in its implemented mechanisms is analysed. The Open Group recommends a tailored approach to TOGAF, and as context cannot be predetermined, the absence of social context consideration in traditional frameworks is perhaps constructive ambiguity.

Frameworks are only useful when their mechanisms within programmes are tailored to suit the programme context for outcomes. Frameworks cannot be specific because of variations in context. It is because the "triggered mechanisms that create the outcomes are context-sensitive. (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). EA Frameworks must necessarily be equivocal and not specific because of the impact of variation in the context of EA mechanisms.

6.7.9 Recurrent Patterns in CMO Configurations and Demi-regularities in EA Mechanisms

In one breadth, researchers argue that the generation of CMO configurations should be based on recurrent patterns across data sources to explain causation (Wong et al., 2016; Astbury & Leeuw,

2010; Curry et al., 2009). However, Lawson (1997) argues that patterns are semi-predictable and contingent on human agency. Patterns are semi-predictable as human agency appears semi-predictable since variances in behaviour patterns may be traced partly to contextual changes across settings. (Wong et al., 2013; Jagosh et al., 2010). Therefore, the notion of demi-regularity conflicts with the reliance on recurrent patterns for confirmation of causal explanation since Participant theories will vary because of variations in human agency and their demi-regularities as put forward by Lawson. Although some CMO configurations may be significant, they were not recurring in narratives from other participants. Mechanisms may also be hidden or positioned at a different 'layer' of social reality than the explanatory power of the regularity (Wong et al., 2013). Policymakers need to exercise expert and discretionary judgement on such matters.

6.7.10 Strengths

Realist review has an open-door attitude when it comes to evidence. It may include and rely on studies conducted utilising various EA research and assessment methods. It also extensively uses more conceptual and critical literature, which are excellent sources for EA programme theory. Legislative and general grey literature may all contribute to the synthesis since they may give contextual information that academic publications often lack. Review reports from the study organisations and other organisations interested in the CRS programme were helpful.

The realist evaluation enables direct and intermediate feedback from programme stakeholders in designing EA programmes that meet their expectations.

The evaluation method efficiently addresses the complexity of digital transformation interventions addressed in the health care policy and decision-making processes from the perspective of EA, specifically aligning stakeholder expectations with IT. It provides a direct path and view from stakeholder concerns to Architecture design in a responsive and agile manner.

A socio-technological perspective of EA provides a broader lens through which stakeholders' concerns are perceived to include social contingencies. Indeed, the findings have shown that most

issues may not be directly related to the technology itself. Critical success mechanisms and critical failure mechanisms are distributed in their context across culture, relations, agency (individual and organisational, funding, technology, and structure.

6.7.11 Limitations

Due to the closeness of this researcher to the case being researched, personal and professional training and experience of EA, bias may be present. A multimethod is used to code the data to minimise the impact of biases and maintain the objectivity of the research finding. Participants are asked to review the results. Results are verified with additional data sources, alternative explanations are considered, and a peer review of the findings of this research is considered (Merriam, 2009; Yin, 2018).

Another limitation is that no guarantee was that all contexts and mechanisms significant to the programme outcome were captured. Nevertheless, all Knowledge cumulates over time and is fallible (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Realist evaluation requires prolonged thinking and imagination to monitor and trace the original blueprint of programme ideas. In refining, judgement, expertise, and the ability to communicate with policymakers are required (Pawson et al., 2004). As the application of realist evaluation in EA in this research is the first of its kind, having reviewed the relevant research literature, participants in the field were unfamiliar with the realist evaluation approach used for the research. Researchers would therefore require mentoring or consulting with experts in realist evaluation.

The realist evaluation process is time-sensitive. For example, an extension of time was required to complete this thesis. This thesis presents a limitation in that it is an individual piece of work that is time and resource-limited; as such, the scope was pragmatic in the given time and resources. Future researchers would benefit from a team effort and an extension of the participant pool to include patient groups and other service users.

Data for the study were collected during the Covid-19 Pandemic outbreak. The impact of structural changes and their impact on the findings, participants' reasoning and choices have not been

specifically researched. Further research is therefore required to ascertain the impact of the pandemic on EA outcomes, although some mechanisms have been associated with the impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic. For instance, the increased funding for digital transformation programmes during the pandemic may have skewed the funding-related context's real impact on the research results.

7 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The thesis began by identifying the high failure rate for EA initiatives and interventions and identifying gaps in EA research on mechanisms. The absence of research in applying CMO configuration and realist evaluation approaches to EA has also been high. Even though some researchers have identified the need for socio-technical approaches to EA implementations (Hope, 2017), the impact of context or triggered EA mechanisms has not been previously researched. Also, the specific instance of a socioecology approach of EA in healthcare intervention has not been previously researched. In the later section, a socio-technological approach to EA implementations has been argued, emphasising the culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure derived from the extant literature related to the organisation under study.

Using retroductive theorising and based on the initial programme theory, the critical success and failure factors of EA implementations in the digital transformation programme are explained.

The findings explained the mechanisms of EA implementation embedded in the TOGAF framework and supported the initial programme theory. This EA mechanism is triggered in the context of culture, relations, agency, funding, technology and structure to create EA outcomes. These outcomes may be aligned transformation of programme actions that enable the organisation to achieve its objectives and goals. Conversely, the outcome may be misaligned with the organisation's objectives and goals. The hypothesis is thus sustained.

This thesis thus proposes a new framework, a socio-technological framework for enabling EA alignment in organisations.

7.1 Contribution of This research to Enterprise Architecture

Unlike the previous literature and research on EA, this thesis applies a realist approach to EA evaluation, delving into context mechanisms and outcome configurations. This research has also investigated the notion of hidden mechanisms of EA. The context-sensitivity of EA mechanisms has

also been investigated, taking a bottom-up approach by feeding stakeholders' concerns into architecting.

The CRAFTS model provides a framework for evaluating EA implementations in healthcare, although reconfigurations, tailoring and testing to context variations in the future programme are required. Applicability in other industry verticals beyond healthcare is also possible, but reconfiguring the framework and testing against a specific programme context is required.

The research also significantly contributes to identifying critical success and failure factors of EA management in healthcare with stakeholders, programme implementers and users as a core part of providing insights.

7.2 Recommendations

7.2.1 Future Directions

Mechanisms of EA are context-sensitive. Context includes the impact of environmental triggers on the mechanisms that determine EA outcomes. Contexts that trigger the mechanisms are subject to changes by other contextual influences over time. Further research is required to identify the changing landscape of contextual impacts on mechanisms triggered to create EA outcomes.

The contextual triggers discussed in this research do not limit the other confounding variables that might have impacted the mechanisms triggered in this study to create programme outcomes. Still, they are only focused on supporting evidence from the extant literature from arguments by Archer (1995) in support of transformations in an organisation. Further research is necessary to understand the nature and impact of the prevailing context on mechanisms in future programmes.

Therefore, the generalisability of the findings concerning mechanisms and their influence on EA outcomes can only be considered in context and must be tested against future context. The thesis contribution is an abstraction of the context-mechanism-outcome configuration in the realist evaluation of EA as an alignment between the organisation's objectives, goals, and digital

transformation. Mechanisms are contextually triggered to create outcomes (Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Greenhalgh & Manzano, 2021).

7.2.2 Using Artificial Intelligence to Configure Context-Mechanisms-Outcomes in EA Programmes

Previous sections have explained the fluidity of context and its impact on CMO configurations and outcomes alignment. This recommendation enables algorithms that can interrogate stakeholder feedback and assess changes in context and their impact on programme outcomes so that the CMO reconfigurations can be implemented to create favourable EA outcomes, i.e., favourable alignment between the organisation's objectives and goals and IT.

In the CMO configurations, mechanisms are context-sensitive. A supervised learning AI algorithm could achieve continuous and dynamic alignment with changing objectives/goals with IT or EA outcomes.

Raw data is injected into the CRAFTS model-based AI algorithm, examining outcomes for alignment or unalignment. Alignment is elicited from stakeholder (agency) sentiments. A combination of mechanism/s and context can be a simulator to analyse effects on outcomes. This will enable EA teams to update their design to fit the desired outcome using the mechanisms and context that generate the desired outcomes or mitigating actions if these variables cannot be controlled. The impact of context on the triggered mechanism and desired output can be modelled. Figure 7.1 shows a design diagram of how an artificial intelligence-driven design might elicit mechanism-context-outcome configurations to improve EA outcomes through design review recommendations.

As the research uses the TOGAF framework for EA implementations in Healthcare organisations, applicability in other domains and EA frameworks must be assessed for portability.

Figure 7.1. shows an illustrative Framework for uncovering contexts, Mechanisms and likely outcomes from Stakeholder perspectives.

Figure 7.1 illustrates an artificial intelligence/machine learning-driven model of how the CRAFTS model/framework may guide Enterprise Architecture implementations, ensuring ongoing stakeholder feedback is reflected in EA design decisions.

This research has shown the following finding for EA implementations:

- The mechanisms that direct the implementation of Enterprise Architecture (EA) are sensitive to context. In the context of this research, elements such as culture, relationships, agency,

funding, technology, and structural factors are essential in determining the effect of triggered EA mechanisms on outcomes in digital transformation programmes.

- Some mechanisms that influence the outcome of the digital transformation programme may be hidden or unhidden.
- The outcomes, their respective contexts, and triggered mechanisms evolve temporally. Consequently, architectural states are transient, offering value only within the specific context in which they were established.
- A combination of activated mechanisms (M) within particular contexts (C) may generate outcomes (O) that are either desirable or undesirable from the stakeholder perspective, which is presumed to embody the organisation's interests, objectives, and vision.
- Programmatic activities incite transformations that may or may not align with the objectives of the EA programme.
- In this study, Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) configurations can be deemed critical failure factors if they yield outcomes misaligned with the organisation's vision or objectives, as perceived from the stakeholder perspective. On the other hand, alignment with these elements comprises a critical success factor within the CMO configurations.

7.2.2.1 Design Option to Configure Context-Mechanisms-Outcomes in EA

This section presents a detailed design, as shown in Figure 7.1, for an AI system that utilizes artificial intelligence techniques to configure context-mechanisms-outcomes (CMO) in the domain of Enterprise Architecture (EA). The system aims to facilitate successful digital transformation programs by capturing stakeholder feedback, applying supervised or unsupervised learning algorithms, semantic analysis, text classification and text categorization.

The AI system processes stakeholder feedback and extracts meaningful insights to configure CMO relationships within the EA framework.

The design encompasses the following key components: algorithm selection, semantic analysis, sentiment analysis, text categorization, chatbot/Virtual Assistant interface, context modelling, pre-trained data integration, continuous monitoring, and recommendation report generation.

Algorithm Selection:

The system should employ supervised or unsupervised learning algorithms to analyze stakeholder feedback for CMO configurations about the digital transformation programme for EA implementation. Supervised learning algorithms are utilized when labelled training data is available, while unsupervised learning algorithms enable pattern recognition and structure identification in unlabeled data (Chaudhuri, Dayal & Narasayya, 2017; Sivarajah et al., 2017; Davenport & Ronanki, 2018).

Semantic Analysis of Stakeholder Feedback:

The system incorporates semantic analysis techniques to perceive the contextual meaning of stakeholder feedback. The analysis aims to extract pertinent information regarding context, mechanisms, and outcomes as indicated by the stakeholders of the digital transformation programme's Architecture (Liu & Zhang, 2012; Cambria & White, 2014; Jurafsky & Martin, 2019).

Sentiment Analysis to Determine Success or Failure EA Outcomes:

In this research, analysis was conducted by the research as an instrument of measure. This is subject to researcher interpretation and, therefore, agential bias (Dalkin et al., 2015; Emmel et al., 2018). Artificial intelligence-driven machine learning sentiment analysis is applied to assess the sentiment expressed in stakeholder feedback helps to limit these biases (Gilpin et al., 2018; Holstein et al., 2019). Positive sentiments indicate satisfaction or agreement, whereas negative sentiments signify dissatisfaction or disagreement (Medhat, Hassan & Korashy, 2014; Hutto & Gilbert, 2014; Pang & Lee, 2016).

Text Categorization of The CMO Configurations:

The system should utilize text categorization methods to classify stakeholder feedback into predefined categories such as context, mechanisms, and outcomes. This categorization enables a structured representation of the feedback data, facilitating subsequent analysis for context-mechanism outcome configurations (Le & Mikolov, 2014; Ravi & Ravi, 2015; Kowsari et al., 2017).

Text Classification to Elicit EA CMO Configurations:

Text classification models need to be trained on labelled data of the CMO configurations – the context, their triggered mechanisms and their success or failure EA outcomes. In the context of stakeholder feedback, this might involve manually categorizing some feedback samples to create a training dataset (Howard & Ruder, 2018).

Chatbot Interface To capture Ongoing Stakeholder feedback:

The system can employ a chatbot or virtual Assistant interface to interact with stakeholders and elicit their feedback. The chatbot should be equipped with prompt templates that guide users in providing feedback and facilitating the extraction of CMO configurations in relation to the digital transformation initiatives under which the EA effort is applied (Følstad & Brandtzaeg, 2017; Vaidyam et al., 2019; Abd-Alrazaq et al., 2020).

Context Modeling of Digital Transformation Programmes:

Context plays a crucial role in configuring CMO relationships. The system should consider various contextual factors, including culture, relations, agency, funding, technology, and structure. Culture represents stakeholders' beliefs, norms, and values, while relations encompass their duties, responsibilities, roles, and power. Agency pertains to the reasons driving stakeholders' actions or inactions, and funding relates to the availability or deficit of financial resources. Technology and structure encompass the program's technical infrastructure and organizational framework (Damschroder et al., 2009; Walshe, Rundall & Shortell, 2011; May, Johnson & Finch, 2016).

Pretrained Data Integration:

The system may incorporate a pre-trained data repository to enhance the modelling of mechanisms, contexts, and outcomes of the digital transformation programme for which EA seeks to align with the organisation's vision through the lens of stakeholder feedback. This data provides additional knowledge and patterns that augment the algorithm's predictive capabilities (Pan & Yang, 2010; Schmidhuber, 2015; Hinton, Vinyals & Dean, 2015).

Continuous Monitoring Of CMO Configurations of Digital Transformation Implementations:

The system operates continuously to adapt to evolving contexts. It monitors and analyzes contextual changes, allowing for the identification of trigger mechanisms that may yield different outcomes over time. This dynamic approach ensures up-to-date and relevant CMO predictions that accommodate context fluidity (He et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018; Sutton & Barto, 2018).

Recommendation Report Generation:

Based on the predicted CMO configurations, the system generates a recommendation report for program implementation. The report could highlight CMO configurations associated with successful outcomes and identifies those leading to failure. These recommendations empower can stakeholders and decision-makers to align outcomes with organizational objectives by making informed adjustments and reconfigurations (Pan & Yang, 2010; Davenport & Ronanki, 2018; Bresnick, 2019).

7.2.2.2 Improvement Strategies for the Application of Artificial Intelligence To CMO Configurations Elicitation

This section details key strategies to enhance machine learning algorithms, including Data Augmentation, Feature Engineering, Ensemble Methods, Hyperparameter Optimization, Model Regularization, Transfer Learning, Active Learning, Continuous Learning, Performance Evaluation, and Ethical Considerations. These strategies aim to foster a more robust, efficient, and ethically sound system. They are designed to interpret and learn from feedback, adapt to new scenarios, and provide accurate predictions. It aims to offer insights into how these strategies can be applied to better design,

implement, and refine machine learning algorithms for eliciting CMO configurations in an EA implementation.

Stakeholder Feedback Data Augmentation: Increase the size and diversity of the training data by incorporating data augmentation techniques. This can involve generating synthetic data or applying transformations to existing data collected through stakeholder feedback, resulting in a more robust and varied dataset for algorithm training (Perez & Wang, 2017; Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019).

Feature Engineering: Explore additional features or representations of the stakeholder feedback that could enhance the CMO configuration algorithm's understanding and prediction capabilities. This could involve extracting domain-specific features of the digital transformation programme's EA or leveraging external resources, such as domain ontologies or knowledge graphs (Rokach & Maimon, 2015; Goodfellow, Bengio & Courville, 2016).

Ensemble Methods: Employ ensemble methods, such as combining multiple models or algorithms, to leverage the strengths of different approaches. This can help mitigate the limitations of individual algorithms and improve overall prediction outcome predictions for CMO configurations' accuracy and robustness (Dietterich, 2000; Rokach, 2010).

Hyperparameter Optimization for CMO Configurations: Perform systematic hyperparameter tuning to find optimal CMO configurations for the learning algorithms. This can involve techniques like grid search, random search, or Bayesian optimization, which systematically explore the hyperparameter space to find the best parameter settings for the algorithm (Bergstra & Bengio, 2012; Snoek, Larochelle & Adams, 2012). By applying hyperparameter optimization techniques, the algorithm can find the optimal configurations that lead to accurate and reliable predictions of CMO relationships. This process involves iteratively adjusting hyperparameters, such as learning rates, regularization strengths, or model architecture choices, to optimize the algorithm's performance and improve the quality of CMO configurations obtained from stakeholder feedback.

The algorithm can significantly improve the precision, accuracy, and interpretability of Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) predictions by identifying optimal parameter settings. Hyperparameter optimization ensures that the algorithm is explicitly fine-tuned for CMO configurations, maximizing its ability to extract meaningful relationships between context, mechanisms, and outcomes. This optimisation process, in turn, facilitates more successful enterprise architecture outcomes in digital transformation programmes.

Model Regularization: One can apply regularisation techniques to address overfitting and improve generalization in the specific context of CMO configuration. Regularization methods, such as L1 or L2 regularization, help control the complexity of the CMO configuration model and mitigate the risk of relying excessively on specific features or patterns in the data.

Regularization introduces a penalty term to the model's loss function, discouraging the model from assigning excessively large weights to certain features. This regularization term helps prevent overfitting, where the model becomes too specialized to the training data and fails to generalize efficiently to new, unseen stakeholder feedback data.

By incorporating L1 regularization (Lasso) or L2 regularization (Ridge), the algorithm can effectively reduce the impact of irrelevant or noisy features in the CMO configuration model. L1 regularization encourages sparsity in feature selection by driving some feature weights to zero, whereas L2 regularization encourages smaller weights for all features. Both methods contribute to a more balanced and robust model that can generalize better to unseen stakeholder feedback, resulting in more accurate and reliable CMO configurations.

Applying regularization techniques helps ensure that the CMO configuration model focuses on the most informative and relevant features, avoiding overreliance on idiosyncratic patterns in the training data. This improves the algorithm's ability to capture the underlying relationships between context, mechanisms, and outcomes and enhances its predictive performance in real-world enterprise architecture scenarios. (Tibshirani, 1996; Ng, 2004).

Transfer Learning: Explore transfer learning by leveraging pre-trained models on related tasks or domains. By fine-tuning or adapting these models to the specific problem of CMO configuration, the algorithm can benefit from the knowledge and representations learned from larger and more diverse datasets, especially where stakeholder feedback is collected on an ongoing basis (Pan & Yang, 2010; Yosinski, Clune, Bengio & Lipson, 2014).

Active Learning: To enhance the specific task of eliciting CMO configuration, active learning strategies can be incorporated to intelligently select the most informative samples from stakeholder feedback for manual annotation or validation into context, mechanism and outcome. By iteratively choosing data points that pose the highest uncertainty or challenge to the algorithm, the model can be progressively enhanced with a reduced amount of labelled data, thereby minimizing the annotation effort and improving efficiency.

Active learning involves an iterative process where the algorithm actively selects samples from the unlabeled data pool for human experts to annotate or validate. Instead of relying solely on randomly selected data, active learning focuses on identifying instances that are expected to provide the most valuable information for improving the CMO configuration model.

By strategically selecting uncertain or difficult samples for the algorithm to classify accurately or predict, active learning enables it to refine its understanding of CMO relationships. The model can learn from challenging examples and adjust its predictions accordingly through expert annotation and validation of these selected samples. As more informative samples are incorporated, the model's performance and accuracy in CMO configuration can be incrementally improved.

By leveraging active learning, the algorithm can achieve more efficient and effective learning, reducing the burden of manual annotation efforts while maximizing the utilization of labelled data. This iterative process enhances the algorithm's ability to generalize and accurately predict CMO configurations, ultimately leading to more successful enterprise architecture outcomes in digital transformation programs. (Settles, 2012; Yang, Loog & Xu, 2018).

Continuous Learning: Implement mechanisms for continuous learning to elicit CMO configurations for stakeholder feedback, allowing the algorithm to adapt and update its knowledge as new feedback and data become available. This can involve online learning techniques, incremental training, or adaptive models that dynamically incorporate new information without requiring retraining from scratch (Chen, He, Garcia, & Li, 2017; Mitchell, 2018).

Performance Evaluation and Feedback Loop: Establish a comprehensive evaluation framework to continuously assess the algorithm's performance in eliciting CMO configurations and gather stakeholder feedback. By actively seeking input from users and monitoring the system's performance, areas of improvement can be identified, and the algorithm can be refined iteratively based on real-world feedback (Provost & Fawcett, 2013; Cui, Wang, Pei & Zhu, 2020).

Ethical Considerations: Incorporate ethical considerations into the algorithm design to address potential biases or discriminatory outcomes. Ensure fairness, transparency, and accountability by conducting fairness audits, employing explainable AI techniques, and addressing potential biases in the data or model predictions (Barocas, Hardt & Narayanan, 2019; Hagendorff, 2020).

- **Bias and Discrimination:** Incorporate ethical considerations to identify and address potential biases or discriminatory outcomes in the algorithm's predictions of CMO configurations. Ensure fairness across diverse stakeholder groups, considering patient demographics, medical history, and healthcare disparities (Obermeyer et al., 2019).
- **Fairness Audits:** Conduct regular fairness audits to evaluate the algorithm's impact on different stakeholder groups within the Healthcare organization. Assess whether the algorithm produces balanced and equitable CMO configurations that align with organizational objectives and do not disproportionately disadvantage any specific group (Zliobaite, 2015).
- **Explainability and Transparency:** Employ explainable AI techniques to provide clear and interpretable explanations for the algorithm's decisions in eliciting CMO configurations.

Transparency is essential in the Healthcare context to build trust among stakeholders and ensure they understand the rationale behind the algorithms (Caruana et al., 2015).

- **Privacy and Data Protection:** When handling stakeholder feedback data, adhere to strict privacy and data protection protocols. As such, EA Practitioners should implement robust security measures to safeguard sensitive information and comply with relevant healthcare privacy regulations, such as HIPAA or GDPR, to protect patient confidentiality and privacy (Jiang et al., 2017).
- **Informed Consent and Autonomy:** Honour the autonomy of stakeholders by offering comprehensive information regarding the objective and potential ramifications of utilising AI algorithms to elicit Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) configurations. Ensure stakeholders can give informed consent and give them a choice to withdraw if they harbour reservations about participating in the digital transformation programme (Char, Shah & Magnus, 2018).
- **Algorithmic Accountability:** Establish mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the algorithm's performance in eliciting CMO configurations. Hold accountable those responsible for the algorithm's development and implementation, ensuring they address any unintended consequences, errors, or biases that may arise during the digital transformation program (Zliobaite & Custers, 2016).
- **Human Oversight and Decision-making:** Recognize the importance of human expertise and judgment in eliciting CMO configurations. Healthcare professionals should maintain ultimate responsibility for decision-making, incorporating the algorithm's insights as one of several factors in their decision-making process (Price, 2020).

By explicitly considering these ethical considerations within the context of eliciting CMO configurations from stakeholder feedback in a digital transformation program within a Healthcare

organization, the algorithm can operate in a responsible and ethically sound manner, promoting fairness, transparency, privacy, and stakeholder autonomy.

The designed AI system leverages supervised or unsupervised learning algorithms, semantic analysis, sentiment analysis, and text categorization to configure context-mechanisms-outcomes in EA. The approach provides a comprehensive framework for capturing stakeholder feedback, predicting CMO configurations, and generating recommendation reports for successful digital transformation programs.

7.2.2.3 Using Large Language Models (LLMs) to Elicit CMO Configurations for EA Outcomes in A Digital Transformation programme implementation.

The application of large Language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, Bing or HuggingFace in various aspects of data analysis and interpretation of EA CMO configurations spans several domains:

Algorithm Selection: LLMs leverages transformer-based deep learning, a form of supervised learning. The model is trained on vast text corpora, enabling it to understand and generate context-mechanism-outcome configurations of human-like text (Vaswani et al., 2017). Therefore LLMs can be used to analyse stakeholder feedback to generate human-like text of semantic similarity where there is fuzziness or a lack of clarity in meaning.

Semantic Analysis: LLMs are equipped to perform semantic analysis. It comprehends the context of words and sentences within stakeholder feedback, which allows it to capture the underlying intended meaning (Pennington, Socher, & Manning, 2014).

Sentiment Analysis: Although sentiment analysis is not a primary function of LLMs, they can contribute to the process. By generating embeddings that encapsulate the semantic meaning of the text, LLMs can be coupled with other techniques to analyze stakeholder sentiment within the feedback (Bojanowski et al., 2017) and enable elicitation of CMO configurations on the EA implementation.

Text Categorization: LLMs can be fine-tuned to classify stakeholder feedback text into context mechanism outcome configurations and whether such configuration represents the success or failure factors of the EA implementation. In this capacity, they can categorize stakeholder feedback into predefined categories such as contexts, mechanisms and outcomes, making it more manageable and actionable (Howard & Ruder, 2018).

Chatbot/Virtual Assistant Interface: LLMs' capacity to construct conversational agents makes them ideal for interacting with stakeholders and eliciting CMO configurations. These agents can engage stakeholders to elicit and collect feedback (Radford et al., 2019). Audio or video data from stakeholder feedback can be transcribed into text using other machine learning models (e.g., automatic speech recognition for audio), and the resulting text data can then be fed into a language model for analysis (Carreira & Zisserman, 2017; Zeghidour et al., 2020).

Context Modeling: LLMs can grasp contexts like culture, relations, agency, funding, Technology and structure from the training text, although implicitly. Its interpretation and application of these contextual factors are, however, limited and required interpretation (Devlin et al., 2019).

Pretrained Data Integration: LLMs use pretraining on extensive text data and then fine-tune the model for specific tasks. This approach ensures that the model can handle various tasks after fine-tuning (Ruder et al., 2019). A possible approach is to elicit CMO configurations of the EA programme through a peer review mechanism to limit researcher bias which is then used to fine-tune the model (Smith, R. (2006).

Continuous Monitoring of stakeholder feedback on the EA implementation: LLMs do not natively support continuous learning. Once trained, the model remains static and does not update or learn from new data unless it undergoes a retraining process using stakeholder feedback (Crammer et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2013).

Recommendation Report Generation to Rectify Failure CMO Configurations: LLMs can generate human-readable reports on how CMO configurations of EA implementations may be

reconfigured to generate the desired outcome. However, the quality and precision of the recommendations in these reports are contingent on the specific task and the implementation approach adopted by the EA programme (Radford et al., 2019; Brown et al., 2020).

While LLMs are powerful and flexible, their use should be tailored to the specific requirements of the EA deliverables within the digital transformation programme's task, and care should be taken to manage their limitations and potential biases (Radford et al., 2019). The organisation's data protection regulations and guidelines must be complied with, especially regarding patient-identifiable data.

7.2.2.4 Relating CMO Configurations to TOGAF ADM Phases

Relating the context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configurations to specific phases of The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) Architecture Development Method (ADM) can provide insightful information about where to focus redesign or reconfiguration efforts when undesirable outcomes arise. This process might involve the following suggested steps, consistent with the CRAFTS model proposed in this research:

1. **Mapping CMO Configurations to TOGAF ADM Phases:** Each CMO configuration elicited from stakeholder feedback can be mapped to the relevant phase or phases of the TOGAF ADM.

For instance, each of the TOGAF ADM phases might relate to specific context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configurations in the following ways:

- **Preliminary Phase:** CMO configurations related to this phase could involve discussions around defining the enterprise architecture framework and its principles. For instance, an outcome could be the successful (or unsuccessful) establishment of architecture principles.
- **Phase A: Architecture Vision:** This phase is about creating the vision of the enterprise architecture. CMO configurations might be related to stakeholder engagement, communication of the architecture vision, or establishing a business case.

- Phase B: Business Architecture: CMO configurations here could revolve around business strategy, processes, organization structure, or business capabilities.
- Phase C: Information Systems Architectures:
 - Data Architecture: CMO configurations might relate to data management and structuring, data quality, or data governance practices.
 - Application Architecture: CMO configurations could involve application interoperability, functionality, or software design and structure.
- Phase D: Technology Architecture: CMO configurations here could pertain to decisions around the technological infrastructure or platforms, software and hardware choices, or scalability and performance considerations
- Phase E: Opportunities and Solutions: CMO configurations could relate to the development of the architecture roadmap, including decisions about project prioritization or solution identification.
- Phase E: Opportunities and Solutions: CMO configurations could relate to the development of the architecture roadmap, including decisions about project prioritization or solution identification.
- Phase E: Opportunities and Solutions: CMO configurations could relate to the development of the architecture roadmap, including decisions about project prioritization or solution identification.
- Phase E: Opportunities and Solutions: CMO configurations could relate to the development of the architecture roadmap, including decisions about project prioritization or solution identification.

This mapping simplifies, and the CMO configurations will depend heavily on the enterprise architecture's specific circumstances and nature. For instance, certain decisions or actions might span multiple phases, while some CMO configurations might recur throughout all the phases.

2. **Identifying adverse or failure outcomes:** Monitor the outcomes of each CMO configuration. If an outcome is negative or undesirable, flag it for further analysis.
3. **Analyzing the context and related EA mechanisms:** Review the context and mechanism that led to the negative/failure outcome. The goal here is to understand what conditions and actions (respectively) contributed to the undesired result.
4. **Targeting relevant ADM phases:** Once the problematic CMO configuration has been identified, focus on the corresponding ADM phase. The issues identified in the CMO analysis can guide changes in this phase.
5. **Redesign and reconfiguration of the EA components:** Based on the insights gathered, redesign or reconfigure the relevant parts of the enterprise architecture as described in the respective ADM phase. Depending on the identified issue, this might involve changing the business processes, technology choices, or governance mechanisms.
6. **Continuous monitoring and adjustment:** Continue to monitor outcomes after changes have been made. Adjustments might be required over time to maintain alignment between the CMO configurations and the enterprise architecture.

The process requires a detailed understanding of the CMO configurations and the TOGAF ADM phases and a close collaboration with stakeholders to ensure the changes meet the business needs and accurately address the problems. This highly iterative process will likely involve revisiting and refining the architecture multiple times (Foorthuis, Brinkkemper & Bos, 2016; The Open Group, 2018; Saha, 2018).

7.2.2.5 Using Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to Map CMO Configurtrions to TOGAF ADM Phases.

For more specific applications or contexts, more pertinent literature may be explicitly related to the specific industry or domain. It is also essential to note that, despite the capabilities of AI, human

expertise and knowledge of both the domain and the data are necessary to effectively apply these technologies, especially where patient confidentiality must be respected, such as in Healthcare.

AI and Machine Learning might be used in the following ways:

Text Analysis and Categorization: AI can help analyze the textual content of CMO configurations and categorize them according to their relevance to various TOGAF ADM phases. Techniques such as natural language processing and machine learning, as outlined by Jurafsky and Martin (2019), can be instrumental in accomplishing this task.

Pattern Recognition: AI can identify recurring patterns and trends in how certain CMO configurations relate to specific ADM phases. Goodfellow, Bengio, and Courville (2016) discuss deep learning for pattern recognition, a technique that can be used in this context.

Sentiment Analysis: AI can analyze stakeholder feedback and comments to infer sentiments that may hint at the success or challenges of a given ADM phase. Sentiment Analysis techniques discussed by Pang and Lee (2008) could be relevant.

Anomaly Detection: In mapping CMO configurations to ADM phases, AI can help detect outliers or anomalies that might signal potential issues or unique situations. The survey by Chandola, Banerjee, and Kumar (2009) offers a range of techniques for anomaly detection.

Recommendation Systems: Based on historical data and outcomes, AI can recommend adjustments to specific ADM phases based on CMO configurations. Koren, Bell, and Volinsky (2009) discuss matrix factorization techniques, a critical methodology in recommendation systems, that can be applied here.

Visualization: AI can assist in creating dynamic visualizations that present the relation between CMO configurations and ADM phases in an intuitive and easy-to-understand manner. Visualization techniques discussed by Heer, Bostock, and Ogievetsky (2010) could prove helpful.

7.3 Funding and Conflict of Interest

The researcher provided funding for this research as part of a research thesis submitted for a Doctor of Business Administration at the School of Business and Creative Industry, The University of the West of Scotland. No payment in cash or in-kind was made to participants in the research, and their participation was entirely voluntary. The views expressed are the authors' responsibility and do not necessarily reflect the view of the University of the West of Scotland.

8 REFERENCES

- Abd-Alrazaq, A., Alajlani, M., Alalwan, A. A., Bewick, B. M., Gardner, P., & Househ, M. (2020). An overview of the features influencing the usability of four leading mobile health apps for self-monitoring of blood pressure. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 136, 104074. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Abunadi, I. (2019). 'Enterprise Architecture Best Practices in Large Corporations', *Information. MDPI AG*, 10(10), p. 293. DOI: 10.3390/info10100293.
- Adu, P. (2019). *A Step-by-Step Guide to Qualitative Data Coding*. Routledge. New York.
- Agarwal, R., & Helfat, C. E. (2009). Strategic renewal of organizations. *Organization Science*, 20(2), 281–293.
- Alter, S. (2014). Theory of workarounds. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 34(55), 1041–1066.
- Agee, J. (2009). Developing qualitative research questions: a reflective process. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education* Vol. 22, No. 4, July–August 2009, 431–447, DOI: 10.1080/09518390902736512.
- Agerfalk, P. J. (2014). "Insufficient theoretical contribution: A conclusive rationale for rejection?" *European Journal of Information Systems*, 23(6), 593-599.
- Ågerfalk, P. J., Conboy, K., & Myers, M. D. (2020). Information systems in the age of pandemics: COVID-19 and beyond. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 29(3), 203-207.
- Ahlemann, F., Legner, C., & Lux, J. (2020). A resource-based perspective of value generation through Enterprise Architecture Management. *Information and Management*. DOI: 10.1016/j.im.2020.103266.
- Ahmad, N. A., Drus, S. M., & Kasim, H. (2020). 'Factors That Influence the Adoption of Enterprise Architecture by Public Sector Organizations: An Empirical Study', *IEEE Access*, 8, pp. 98847–98873. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2996584.

- Aier, S. (2014). The role of organisational culture for grounding, management, guidance, and effectiveness of Enterprise Architecture principles. *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, 12(1), pp.43-70.
- Aier, S., Gleichauf, B., & Winter, R. (2011). Understanding enterprise architecture management design—An empirical analysis.
- Al-Emran, M., Mezhuyev, V., & Kamaludin, A. (2018). Technology Acceptance Model in M-learning context: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 125, 389-412.
- Alaeddini, M., Asgari, H., Gharibi, A., & Rashidi Rad, M. (2017). Leveraging business-IT alignment through enterprise architecture—an empirical study to estimate the extents. *Information Technology and Management*, 18(1), 55-82. doi:10.1007/s10799-016-0256-6.
- Alfoudari, A. M., Durugbo, C. M., & Aldhmour, F. M. (2021). Understanding socio-technological challenges of smart classrooms using a systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 173, 104282. DOI: 10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104282.
- Alm, R., & Wißotzki, M. (2013). Togaf adaption for small and medium enterprises. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Business Information Systems Workshops*.
- AlQudah, A. A., Salloum, S. A., & Shaalan, K. (2021). The Role of Technology Acceptance in Healthcare to Mitigate COVID-19 Outbreak. In: Arpaci, I., Al-Emran, M., A. Al-Sharafi, M., Marques, G. (eds) *Emerging Technologies During the Era of COVID-19 Pandemic. Studies in Systems, Decision & Control*, vol 348. Springer, Cham. DOI.org/10.1007/978-3-030-67716-9_14.
- Alvesson, M. (2002). *Postmodernism and Social Research*, Buckingham: Open University.
- Amozurrutia, J. A., & Servós, C. M. (2011). Excel spreadsheet as a tool for social narrative analysis. *Qual Quant* 45, 953–967. DOI.org/10.1007/s11135-010-9406-9.
- Ananthram, S. (2016). *Asia Pacific Human Resource Management and Organisational Effectiveness*.

- Andersen, P. H., & Kragh, H. (2010). Sense and sensibility: two approaches for using existing theory in theory-building qualitative research. *Industrial Marketing Management* 39(1): 49–55. DOI: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2009.02.008.
- Anderson, P., & Backhouse, G. (2009). *Unleashing EA: Institutional architectures and the value of joined-up thinking*. UK: JISC: Bristol.
- Anderson, R. (2004). Realistic evaluation. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy* 2(1): 84–86.
- Anderson, R. A., Crabtree, B. F., Steele, D. J., & McDaniel, R. R., Jr. (2005). Case study research: the view from complexity science. *Qual Health Res.* May;15(5):669-85. DOI: 10.1177/1049732305275208. PMID: 15802542; PMCID: PMC1822534.
- Anderson, R., & Hardwick, R. (2016). Realism and resources: Towards more explanatory economic evaluation. *Evaluation (Lond)*. 2016 Jul;22(3):323-341. DOI: 10.1177/1356389016652742.
- Anderson, R., & Shemilt, I. (2010). “The role of economic perspectives and evidence in systematic review”. In: Shemilt I, Mugford M, Vale L, et al. (eds) *Evidence-based Decisions and Economics: Health Care, Social Welfare, Education and Criminal Justice*. 2nd ed. Oxford, UK: Wiley-Blackwell, pp.23–42.
- Anfara, Jr. V. A., & Mertz, N.T. (eds). (2006). *Theoretical frameworks in qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Ansola, P. G., Higuera, A. M., Morenas, J. D., & García-Escribano, J. (2011). Decision-Making Platform Supported on ICTs: Application to the Management of Ground Handling Operations at an Airport. *Proceedings of the 18th World Congress. The International Federation of Automatic Control Milano (Italy) August 28 - September 2, 2011*. Pp. 13074 – 13079.
- Ansyori, R., Qodarsih, N., & Soewito, B. (2018). A systematic literature review: Critical Success Factors to Implement Enterprise Architecture. *Procedia Computer Science*, 135, pp.43-51.

- Appleby, J., Galea, A., & Murray, R. (2014). The NHS productivity challenge: experience from the front line. The King's Fund.
- Archer, M. S. (2007b). *Making Our Way through the World: Human Reflexivity and Social Mobility*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Archer, M. S. (1985). The myth of cultural integration. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 36(3), 333. doi:10.2307/590456.
- Archer, M. S. (1995). *Realist Social Theory: The Morphogenetic Approach*. Cambridge University Press. DOI: 10.1017/CBO9780511557675.
- Archer, M. S. (1996). *Culture and Agency: The Place of Culture in Social Theory (Revised Edition)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Archer, M. S. (1998). Addressing the cultural system. In: Archer M, Bhaskar R, Collier A, Lawson T and Norrie A (eds), *Critical Realism: Essential Readings*. London: Routledge, 503–43.
- Archer, M. S. (1998a). Realism and morphogenesis. In: Archer M, Bhaskar R, Collier A, Lawson T and Norrie A (eds), *Critical Realism: Essential Readings*. London: Routledge, 356–81.
- Archer, M. S. (2000). *Being Human: The Problem of Agency*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Archer, M. S. (2003). *Structure, Agency, and the Internal Conversation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Archer, M. S. (2005). Structure, culture, and agency. In: Jacobs MD and Hanrahan NW (eds), *The Blackwell Companion to the Sociology of Culture*. Oxford: Blackwell, 17–34.
- Archer, M. S. (2007a). The trajectory of the morphogenetic approach: an account in the first-person. *Sociologia: Problemas e Práticas* 54: 35–47.
- Archer, M. S. (2010a). Morphogenesis versus structuration: on combining structure and action. *The British Journal of Sociology* 61(S1): 225–52.
- Archer, M. S. (2010b). *Conversations about Reflexivity*. London: Routledge.

- Archer, M. (2013a). "Critical Realism and the Conceptual Framework for Potential Explanations of IS Phenomena." *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 32, Article 7.
- Archer, M. S. (2013b). "Social Morphogenesis and the Prospects of Morphogenic Society." In *Social Morphogenesis*. Springer.
- Archer, M. S. (Ed.). (2015). *Generative mechanisms transforming the social order*. Springer.
- Archer, M. S., & Elder-Vass, D. (2012). Cultural system or norm circles? An exchange. *European Journal of Social Theory* 15: 93–115.
- Archer, M. S., & Morgan, J. (2020). Contributions to realist social theory: an interview with Margaret S. Archer. *Journal of Critical Realism*, 19(2), 179-200.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14767430.2020.1732760>.
- Archer, M., Decoteau, C., Gorski, P., Little, D., & Porpora, D. (2016). What is Critical Realism? Available at: <http://www.asatheory.org/current-newsletter-online/what-is-critical-realism> (accessed 10 October 2019).
- Arcia, A. (2014). Facebook advertisements for inexpensive participant recruitment among women in early pregnancy. *Health Education & Behavior*, 41(3), 237-241.
- Aristotle. (1941). *Metaphysics*, (Metaphysica.). in *The Basic Works of Aristotle*, ed. R. McKeon. New York.
- Astbury, B., & Leeuw, F. L. (2010). 'Unpacking Black Boxes: Mechanisms and Theory Building in Evaluation', *American Journal of Evaluation*, 31(3), pp. 363–381. DOI: 10.1177/1098214010371972.
- Attewell, P. (1992). Technology diffusion and organisational learning: The case of business computing. *Organization Science*, 3,1–19.
- Avison, D., & Malaurent, J. (2014). Is theory king? Questioning the theory fetish in information systems. *Journal of Information Technology*, 29(4), 327-336.

- Aziz, S., & Obitz, T. (2007). "Enterprise Architecture Is Maturing. Infosys Enterprise Architecture Survey 2007", Survey, Infosys. Available at <http://www.infosys.com/offerings/IT-services/architecture-services/ea-survey/Documents/ea-maturing.pdf> [Accessed: 20 June 2021].
- Bacharach, S. B., Bamberger, P., & Sonnenstuhl, W. J. (1996). The organizational transformation process: The micropolitics of dissonance reduction and the alignment of logics of action. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 41(3), 477–506.
- Bak, N. (2004). *Completing your thesis: A practical guide*. Pretoria: Van Schaik Sage.
- Bakar, N., Harihodin, S., & Kama, N. (2016). Assessment of Enterprise Architecture Implementation Capability and Priority in Public Sector Agency. *Procedia Comput Sci* [Internet]; 100:198–206. Available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.09.141>.
- Bakhtin, M. M., & Medvedev, P. N. (1978). *The Formal Method in Literary Scholarship*. Translated by A.J. Wehrle, Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press.
- Banaeianjahromi, N. (2018). 'Where Enterprise Architecture development fails a multiple case study of governmental organizations', in 2018 12th International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS). IEEE, pp. 1–9. DOI: 10.1109/RCIS.2018.8406644.
- Banaeianjahromi, N., & Smolander, K. (2019). 'Lack of Communication and Collaboration in ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE Development', *Information Systems Frontiers*. Springer New York LLC, 21(4), pp. 877–908. DOI: 10.1007/s10796-017-9779-6.
- Bandura, A. (1991). Social cognitive theory of self-regulation. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), 248-287.
- Bandura, A. (2018). Toward a psychology of human agency: Pathways and reflections. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 13(2), 130-136.
- Barker, T., & Frolick, M. N. (2003). ERP implementation failure: A case study. *Information Systems Management*, 20(4), 43–49.

- Barocas, S., Hardt, M., & Narayanan, A. (2019). *Fairness and machine learning*. fairmlbook.org. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Befani, B., Ledermann, S., & Sager, F. (2007). Realistic Evaluation and QCA. Conceptual parallels and an empirical application. *Evaluation*, 13, 171-192.
- Benbya, H., & McKelvey, B. (2006). "Using Coevolutionary and Complexity Theories to Improve IS Alignment: A Multi-Level Approach," *Journal of Information Technology* (21:4), pp. 284-298.
- Bendassolli, P. F. (2013). Theory building in qualitative research: reconsidering the problem of induction. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 14(1). DOI: 10.17169/fqs-14.1.1851.
- Bennett, C. C., & Hauser, K. (2013). Artificial intelligence framework for simulating clinical decision-making: a Markov decision process approach. *Artif Intell Med*. 57(1):9-19. doi:10.1016/j.artmed.2012.12.003.
- Benton, T., & Craib, I. (2001). *Philosophy of Social Science*, London: Palgrave.
- Berger, R. M., & Patchener, M. A. (1988). *Implementing the research plan*. London.
- Bergstra, J., & Bengio, Y. (2012). Random search for hyper-parameter optimization. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 13(Feb), 281-305.
- Bernard, S. A. (2005). *An Introduction to Enterprise Architecture*, 2nd edition, Bloomington, IN: AuthorHouse.
- Bernard, S. A. (2012). *An Introduction to Enterprise Architecture*. AuthorHouse.
- Bērziša, S., Bravos, G., Gonzalez, T. C., Czubayko, U., España, S., Grabis, J., Henkel, M., Jokste, L., Kampars, J., Koç, H., Kuhr, J. C., Llorca, C., Loucopoulos, P., Pascual, R. J., Pastor, O., Sandkuhl, K., Simic, H., Stirna, J., Valverde, F. G., & Zdravkovic, J. (2015). *Capability Driven Development: An Approach to Designing Digital Enterprises*. *Bus Inf Syst Eng* 57, 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-014-0362-0>.

Bernus, P., Noran, O., & Molina, A. (2015). Enterprise architecture: Twenty years of the GERAM framework. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 39, 83-93.

Beynon-Davies, P. (1998). *Information Systems Failure*. Information Systems Development. Macmillan Computer Science Series. Palgrave, London. DOI.org/10.1007/978-1-349-14931-5_37.

Bhaskar, R. (1975). Forms of realism. *Philosophica* 15(1): 99–127.

Bhaskar, R. (1978). On the possibility of social scientific knowledge and the limits of naturalism. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour* 8 (1), 1-28.

Bhaskar, R. (1979). *Reclaiming reality* Verso.

Bhaskar, R. (1993). *Dialectic: The Pulse of Freedom*, London: Verso

Bhaskar, R. (1994). *Plato, etc.*, London: Verso.

Bhaskar, R. (2009). *Scientific Realism and human emancipation*. London: Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9780203879849.

Bhaskar, R. (2013). *A realist theory of science*. Routledge.

Bhaskar, R. (2014). *The Possibility of Naturalism*. 4th ed. London: Routledge.

Bhaskar, R. (2015). *The Possibility of Naturalism: A Philosophical Critique of the Contemporary Human Sciences*. Oxon: Routledge.

Bhaskar, R. (2016). *Enlightened common sense: The philosophy of critical realism*. Routledge.

Bhaskar, R., Danermark, B., & Price, L. (2017). *Interdisciplinarity and wellbeing: A critical realist general theory of interdisciplinarity*. Taylor & Francis.

Bhattacharya, P. (2018). ‘Aligning Enterprise Systems Capabilities with Business Strategy: An extension of the Strategic Alignment Model (SAM) using Enterprise Architecture’, *Procedia Computer Science*. Elsevier B.V., 138, pp. 655–662. DOI: 10.1016/j.procs.2018.10.087.

Bhattarai, D. (2020). “A Detailed Summary of Digital Transformation from McKinsey” Available at <https://www.lftechnology.com/blog/digital-transformation/digital-transformation-mckinsey/> [Accessed: 1st January 2022].

- Billig, M., Condor, S., Edwards, D., Gane, M., Middleton, R., & Radley, A. (1988). *Ideological Dilemmas*, London: Sage.
- Bødker, S., & Kyng, M. (2018). Participatory design that matters—Facing the big issues. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 25(1), 1-31.
- Boh, W. F., & Yellin, D. (2006). Using Enterprise Architecture Standards in Managing Information Technology. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 23(3), 163–207.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/40398859>.
- Bojanowski, P., Grave, E., Joulin, A., & Mikolov, T. (2017). Enriching word vectors with subword information. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 5, 135-146. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00051.
- Bolman, L. G., & Deal, T. E. (2017). *Reframing Organizations, Reframing Organizations*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. DOI: 10.1002/9781119281856.
- Borgatti, S. P., & Halgin, D. S. (2011). 'On network theory', *Organization Science*, 22(5), pp. 1168–1181. DOI: 10.1287/orsc.1100.0641.
- Boucharas, V., van Steenberghe, M., Jansen, S., & Brinkkempe, S. (2010). The contribution of Enterprise Architecture to the achievement of organisational goals: a review of the evidence, *Trends in Enterprise Architecture Research, Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing* 70, pp. 1–15.
- Bourdieu, P. (2005). *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. *Journal of Economic Sociology*, 6(3), 25-48. doi:10.17323/1726-3247-2005-3-25-48.
- Bowden, T., & Coiera, E. (2013). Comparing New Zealand's 'Middle Out' health information technology strategy with other OECD nations. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 82(5), e87-e95. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2012.12.002.

- Bradley, R. V., Pratt, R. M. E., Byrd, T. A., Outlay, C. N., & Wynn, D. E. (2012). 'Enterprise architecture, IT effectiveness and the mediating role of IT alignment in US hospitals', *Information Systems Journal*, 22(2), pp. 97–127. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2575.2011.00379.x.
- Braun, C., Wortmann, F., Hafner, M., & Winter, R. (2005, March). Method construction-a core approach to organizational engineering. In *Proceedings of the 2005 ACM symposium on Applied computing* (pp. 1295-1299).
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3:2, 77-101, DOI: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.
- Bree, R. T., & Gallagher, G. (2016). Using Microsoft Excel to code and thematically analyse qualitative data: a simple, cost-effective approach. *All Ireland Journal of Higher Education*, 8(2).
- Bresnick, J. (2019). Explaining the basics of the Internet of Things for healthcare. *Health IT Analytics*. Retrieved from: <https://healthitanalytics.com/news/explaining-the-basics-of-the-internet-of-things-for-healthcare>. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- British Sociological Association (BSA). (2002). Statement of ethical practice. Available at [HTTP://www.britsoc.co.uk/about/equality/statement-of-ethical-practice.aspx](http://www.britsoc.co.uk/about/equality/statement-of-ethical-practice.aspx) [Accessed 30 August 2021].
- Brown, S. A., Massey, A. P., Montoya-Weiss, M. M., & Burkman, J. R. (2002). Do I really have to? User acceptance of mandated technology. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 11(4), 283–295.
- Brown, S., Lhussier, M., Dalkin, S. M., & Eaton, S. (2018). Care Planning: What Works, for Whom, and in What Circumstances? A Rapid Realist Review. *Qualitative Health Research*, 28(14), pp. 2250–2266. DOI: 10.1177/1049732318768807.
- Brown, T. B., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Agarwal, S., Herbert-Voss, A., Krueger, G., Henighan, T., Child, R., Ramesh, A., Ziegler, D. M., Wu, J., Winter, C., ... Amodei, D. (2020). Language models are few-shot learners. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Vol. 33). Retrieved from

<https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2020/hash/1457c0d6bfc4967418bfb8ac14280f9-Abstract.html>.

Bryman, A., & Cramer, D. (2012). *Quantitative data analysis with IBM SPSS 17, 18 & 19: A guide for social scientists*. Routledge.

Buckl, S., Matthes, F., & Schweda, C. M. (2010). Future research topics in enterprise architecture management—a knowledge management perspective. In *Service-Oriented Computing. ICSOC/ServiceWave 2009 Workshops: International Workshops, ICSOC/ServiceWave 2009, Stockholm, Sweden, November 23-27, 2009, Revised Selected Papers 2* (pp. 1-11). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Buckle, S., Ernst, A. M., Matthes, F., Ramacher, R., & Schweda, C. M. (2009). 'Using Enterprise Architecture management patterns to complement TOGAF'. In *Proceedings of the 13th IEEE International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Conference*.

Bui, Q. N., Markus, M. L., & Newell, S. (2015). Alternative designs in widespread innovation adoption: Empirical evidence from enterprise architecture implementation in US state governments.

Burn, J. M., & Szeto, C. (2000). “A comparison of the views of business and IT management on success factors for strategic alignment”. *Information and Management*, 37(4), pp. 197–216. DOI: 10.1016/S0378-7206(99)00048-8.

Buschle, M., Ekstedt, M., Grunow, S., Hauder, M., Matthes, F., & Roth, S. (2012). Automating enterprise architecture documentation using an enterprise service bus.

Byng, R., Norman, I., & Redfern, S. (2005). ‘Using realistic evaluation to evaluate a practice-level intervention to improve primary healthcare for patients with long-term mental illness’, *Evaluation* 11(1): 69–93. DOI: 10.1177/1356389005053198.

Byrne, D., & Callaghan, G. (2013). *Complexity theory and the social sciences: The state of the art*.

Calvo, P. (2021). Why Information Grows? The evolution of order, from atoms to economies. *Sociology International Journal*, 5(1), 19-21.

Cambria, E., & White, B. (2014). Jumping NLP curves: A review of natural language processing research.

Cambridge Dictionary. (1995). Funding. In dictionary.cambridge.org dictionary. Available at <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/Funding?q=Funding> [Accessed 21 January 2022].

Cambridge Dictionary. (n.d.). Organisation. In dictionary.cambridge.org dictionary. Available at <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/organization?q=organisation> [Access Date 1 January 2022].

Cameron, B. H., & Mcmillan, E. (2013). "Analyzing the Current Trends in Enterprise Architecture Frameworks," *Journal of Enterprise Architecture*. 60-71 February. [Online] Available: http://ea.ist.psu.edu/documents/journal_feb2013_cameron_2.pdf [Accessed: 22nd November, 2018].

Campbell, R., Pound, P., Pope, C., Britten, N., Pill, R., Morgan, M., & Donovan, J. (2003). Evaluating meta-ethnography: A synthesis of qualitative research on lay experiences of diabetes and diabetes care. *Social Science and Medicine*, 56(4) 671–684.

Camponovo, G., Pigneur, Y., & Lausanne, S. (2004). Information Systems alignment in uncertain environments. *Proceedings of Decision Support Systems (DSS)*.

Caprario, J., & Finotti, A. R. (2019). Socio-technological tool for mapping susceptibility to urban flooding. *Journal of Hydrology*, 574, 1152-1163. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhydrol.2019.05.005.

Carchedi, G. (2005). On the production of knowledge. In *The Capitalist State and Its Economy: Democracy in Socialism*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

Cardinal, L. B., Sitkin, S. B., & Long, C. P. (2004). "Balancing and Rebalancing in the Creation and Evolution of Organizational Control," *Organization Science* (15:4), pp. 411-431.

Carding, N. (2019). 'Revealed: the winners and losers of government's £2.9bn capital pot'. HSJ website. Available at: www.hsj.co.uk/finance-and-efficiency/revealed-the-winners-and-losers-of-governments-29bn-capital-pot/7024398.article HM02229.article [Accessed on 19th March 2021].

Carley, K. (1993). Coding choices for textual analysis: A comparison of content analysis and map analysis. In P. Marsden (Ed.). *Sociological methodology* (pp. 75–126). Oxford, UK: Blackwell.

Carreira, J., & Zisserman, A. (2017). Quo Vadis, action recognition? A new model and the kinetics dataset. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 6299-6308). Retrieved from https://www.cv-foundation.org/openaccess/content_cvpr_2017/html/Carreira_Quo_Vadis_Action_CVPR_2017_paper.html.

Carter, B., & New, C. (2004). "Paper to be presented at ESA Social Theory Conference", pp. 1–40.

Carter, B., & New, C. (2005). "Making realism work: Realist social theory and empirical research". Routledge.

Caruana, R., Lou, Y., Gehrke, J., Koch, P., Sturm, M., & Elhadad, N. (2015). Intelligible models for healthcare: Predicting pneumonia risk and hospital 30-day readmission. *Proceedings of the 21st ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*.

Chan, Y.E., and Reich, B.H. (2007). "IT alignment: what have we learned?." *Journal of Information Technology*, 22(4), pp.297-315.

Chan, Y. (2002). "Why haven't we mastered alignment? The importance of the informal organization structure". *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 1(2), June.

Chandola, V., Banerjee, A., & Kumar, V. (2009). Anomaly detection: A survey. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, 41(3), 1-58.

Char, D. S., Shah, N. H., & Magnus, D. (2018). Implementing machine learning in health care—addressing ethical challenges. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 378(11), 981-983.

Charlesworth, A., Anderson, M., Donaldson, C., Johnson, P., Knapp, J., & McGuire, A., & ... (2021). 'What is the right level of spending needed for health and care in the UK?', *The Lancet*. Elsevier Ltd, 397(10288), pp. 2012–2022. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00230-0.

Chatterjee, A., & Bhanja, N. (2020). "The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on socio-economic inequalities in India." *Journal of Social and Economic Development*, 22(2), 285-303.

Chaudhuri, S., Dayal, U., & Narasayya, V. (2017). An overview of business intelligence technology. *Communications of the ACM*, 54(8), 88-98. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].

Checkland, P., & Scholes, J. (1990). *Soft systems methodology in action*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley.

Chen, H. T., & Chen, H. T. (2005). *Practical program evaluation: Assessing and improving planning, implementation, and effectiveness*. Sage.

Chen, H. T., & Rossi, P. H. (1989). Issues in the theory-driven perspective. *Evaluation and program planning*, 12(4), 299-306. DOI:10.1016/0149-7189(89)90046-3.

Chen, S., He, H., Garcia, E., & Li, K. (2017). Incremental learning for v-Support Vector Regression. *Neural Networks*, 91, 61-74. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].

Chuang, C. H., & van Loggerenberg, J. (2010). Challenge facing Enterprise architects: A South African perspective. *Proceedings of the 43rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences – 2010*, pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=andarnumber=5428576> [Accessed 10 June 2020].

Coiera, E., Aarts, J., & Kulikowski, C. (2012). The dangerous decade. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*; 19 (1): 2–5.

Collier, A. (1994). *Critical Realism: An Introduction to Roy Bhaskar's Philosophy*. London: Verso.

Collins English dictionary. (2022a). Technological. Available from: <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/technology> [Accessed 20 January 2022].

Collins English dictionary. (2022b). Technical. Available from:
<https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/technology> [Accessed 20 January 2022].

Collins, J. C. (2001). *Good to Great: Why Some Companies Make the Leap and Others Don't*. New York: HarperCollins.

Collins, J. C., & Porras, J. I. (1994). *Built to Last: Successful Habits of Visionary Companies*. New York: Harper Business.

Coltman, T., Tallon, P., Sharma, R., & Queiroz, M. (2015). Strategic IT alignment: Twenty-five years on. *Journal of Information Technology*, 30(2), 91-100.

Connelly, J. (2001). Critical realism and health promotion: effective Practice needs an effective theory. *Health Education Research*, 16(2), 115-120. doi:10.1093/her/16.2.115.

Cook, T. H., Cordray, D., Hartman, H., Hedges, L., Light, R., Louis, T., & Mosteller, F. (1993). *Meta-Analysis for Explanation*. New York: Russell Sage Foundation.

Corbin, J. M., & Strauss, A. (1990). Grounded theory research: Procedures, canons, and evaluative criteria. *Qualitative Sociology*, 13(1), 3-21. DOI:10.1007/bf00988593.

Cowling, B. J., Ali, S. T., Ng, T. W. Y., Tsang, T. K., Li, J. C. M., Fong, M. W., ... & Leung, G. M. (2020). "Impact assessment of non-pharmaceutical interventions against coronavirus disease 2019 and influenza in Hong Kong: an observational study." *The Lancet Public Health*, 5(5), e279-e288.

Cram, W. A., Brohman, M. K., & Gallupe, B. R. (2015). "Addressing the Control Challenges of the Enterprise Architecture Process," *Journal of Information Systems* (29:2), pp. 161-182.

Crammer, K., Dekel, O., Keshet, J., Shalev-Shwartz, S., & Singer, Y. (2006). Online passive-aggressive algorithms. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 7(Mar), 551-585. Retrieved from <https://www.jmlr.org/papers/volume7/crammer06a/crammer06a.pdf>.

Cresswell, K., & Sheikh, A. (2009). The NHS Care Record Service (NHS CRS): recommendations from the literature on successful implementation and adoption. *Inform Prim Care*. 17(3):153-60. DOI: 10.14236/jhi.v17i3.730. PMID: 20074427.

- Cresswell, T. (2002). Introduction: theorizing place. In *Mobilizing place, placing mobility* (pp. 11-31). Brill.
- Cresswell, T. (2006). *On the move: Mobility in the modern Western world*. Taylor & Francis.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design. Choosing among five approaches*, Thousand Oaks, California: Sage.
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2011). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications. Available at: <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/aftr/designing-and-conducting-mixed-methods-research/book233508>.
- Creswell, J. W., Vicki, L., & Clark, P. (2007). "Choosing a mixed-methods design". Creswell, J. W., Vicki, L., & Clark, P. (Eds.), "In *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*". Sage Publications. Pp. 58-88.
- Crowe, S., Creswell, K., Robertson, A., Hubby, A., & Sheikh, A. (2011). The case study approach. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 11(100), pp. 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-11-100>.
- Cruikshank, J., & Sassower, R. (Eds.). (2017). *Neoliberalism and technoscience: Critical assessments*. Routledge.
- Cui, P., Wang, X., Pei, J., & Zhu, W. (2020). A survey on network embedding. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 33(8), 2916-2942. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Curry, L. A., Nembhard, I. M., & Bradley, E. H. (2009). 'Qualitative and mixed methods provide unique contributions to outcomes research.', *Circulation*, 119(10), pp. 1442–52. DOI: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.107.742775.
- Dalkin, S., Forster, N., Hodgson, P., Lhussier, M., & Carr, S. M. (2019). Using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS; NVivo) to assist in the complex process of realist theory generation, refinement and testing. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 24(1), 123-134.

- Dalkin, S. M., Greenhalgh, J., Jones, D., Cunningham, B., & Lhussier, M. (2015). What is in a mechanism? Development of a key concept in realist evaluation. *Implementation Sci* 10, 49. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-015-0237-x> [Accessed 21 March 2021].
- Damschroder, L. J., Aron, D. C., Keith, R. E., Kirsh, S. R., Alexander, J. A., & Lowery, J. C. (2009). Fostering implementation of health services research findings into practice: a consolidated framework for advancing implementation science. *Implementation Science*, 4(1), 1-15. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Danermark, B. (2002). Interdisciplinary research and critical realism the example of disability research. *Alethia*, 5(1), 56-64.
- Danermark, B. (2019). Applied interdisciplinary research: a critical realist perspective. *Journal of Critical Realism*, 18(4), 368-382.
- Danermark, B., Ekström, M., Jakobsen, L., & Karlsson, J. C. (2019). *Explaining society: An introduction to critical realism in the social sciences*. London: Routledge.
- Danermark, B., Ekström, M., & Karlsson, J. C. (2019). *Explaining society: Critical realism in the social sciences*. Routledge.
- Dang, D. D., & Pekkola, S. (2017). Systematic Literature Review on Enterprise Architecture in the Public Sector. *Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 15(2).
- Davenport, T. H., & Ronanki, R. (2018). Artificial intelligence for the real world. *Harvard Business Review*, 96(1), 108-116.
- Davenport, T. H., & Ronanki, R. (2018). Artificial intelligence for the real world. *Harvard Business Review*, 96(1), 108-116. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- De Brún, A., & McAuliffe, E. (2020). 'Identifying the context, mechanisms and outcomes underlying collective leadership in teams: building a realist programme theory', *BMC Health Services Research*. *BMC Health Services Research*, 20(1), p. 261. DOI: 10.1186/s12913-020-05129-1.

- de Souza, D. E. (2013). 'Elaborating the Context-Mechanism-Outcome configuration (CMOc) in realist evaluation: A critical realist perspective', *evaluation*, 19(2), pp. 141–154. DOI: 10.1177/1356389013485194.
- De Vries, M., & van Rensburg, A. C. J. (2009). 'Evaluating and refining the “enterprise architecture as strategy” approach and artefacts', *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 20(1), pp. 31–43. DOI: 10.7166/20-1-81.
- Deal, T. E., & Kennedy, A. A. (1982). *Corporate Cultures*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Deleuze, G., & Guattari, F. (1991). *What is philosophy?* New York: Columbia University Press.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2011). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research*, Thousand Oaks, California: Sage.
- Department of Health (DOH). (2015). *Culture change in the NHS. Applying the Lessons of the Francis Inquiries*. Available at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/403010/culture-change-nhs.pdf [Accessed on 19th March 2021].
- Department of Health (DOH). (2018). *Policy paper: The future of healthcare: our vision for digital, data and technology in health and care*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-future-of-healthcare-our-vision-for-digital-data-and-technology-in-health-and-care/the-future-of-healthcare-our-vision-for-digital-data-and-technology-in-health-and-care>. [Accessed 12 December 2021].
- Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC). (2018). *The future of healthcare: our vision for digital, data and technology in health and care* [online]. GOV.UK website. Available at: www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-future-of-healthcare-our-vision-for-digital-data-and-technology-in-health-and-care [accessed on 19th March 2021].

Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC). (2021). The NHS Constitution for England. Updated 1 January 2021. Available online at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-nhs-constitution-for-england/the-nhs-constitution-for-england> [Accessed on 26 May 2021].

Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC). (2019). The Government's revised 2019-20 Accountability Framework with NHS England and NHS Improvement. March 2020. Accessed online at https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/875716/The_government_s_revised_2019-20_Accountability_Framework_with_NHS_England_and_NHS_Improvement.pdf.

Dery, Kristine, Ina M. Sebastian, and Nick van der Meulen. "The digital workplace is key to digital innovation." *MIS Quarterly Executive* 16, no. 2 (2017).

Devers, K. J., & Frankel, R. M. (2000). Study design in qualitative research – 2: Sampling and data collection strategies. *Education for Health*, 13(2), pp. 263 -271.

Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019). BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)* (pp. 4171-4186). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/N19-1423>.

Diefenthaler, P., & Bauer, B. (2014). From Gaps to Transformation Paths in Enterprise Architecture Planning, in *Institute for Software and Systems Engineering, University of Augsburg, Germany*, pp. 474–489. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-09492-2_28.

Dietterich, T. G. (2000). Ensemble methods in machine learning. In *International workshop on multiple classifier systems* (pp. 1-15). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].

Dietz, J. L., Hoogervorst, J. A., Albani, A., Aveiro, D., Babkin, E., Barjis, J., ... & Winter, R. (2013). The discipline of enterprise engineering. *International Journal of Organisational Design and Engineering*, 3(1), 86-114.

Dietz, J. L. G., & Hoogervorst, J. A. P. (2011). 'A critical investigation of TOGAF - based on the enterprise engineering theory and practice', In Albani A., Dietz J.L.G., Verelst J. (eds) *Advances in Enterprise Engineering*, V. EEWC 2011. *Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing*, vol 79. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-21058-7_6.

Digitalhealth. (2020). NHS digital transformation remains tough. Available at <https://www.digitalhealth.net/2020/06/nhs-digital-transformation-remains-tough/> [Accessed 12th October 2021].

Dixon, J., & Mays, N. (2018). Is the British National Health Service equitable? The evidence on socioeconomic differences in utilization. *Journal of Health Services Research & Policy*, 23(2), 104-117.

Dixon-Woods, M. (2014). The Problem of Context in Quality Improvement Work. In The Health Foundation, editor. *Perspectives on Context: A Series of Short Essays Considering the Role of Context in Successful Quality Improvement*. London: The Health Foundation. pp. 89–101.

Drummond, M. F., Sculpher, M. J., Claxton, K., Stoddart, G. L., & Torrance, G. W. (2015). *Methods for the economic evaluation of health care programmes*. Oxford university press.

Easton, G. (2010). "Critical realism in case study research." *Industrial Marketing Management*, 39(1), 118-128.

Eccles, D. W., & Groth, P. T. (2006). Problem-solving systems theory: implications for the design of socio-technological systems. *TECHNOLOGY INSTRUCTION COGNITION AND LEARNING*, 3(3/4), 323.

Eisenhart, M. A. (1991). Conceptual Frameworks for Research Circa 1991: Ideas from a Cultural Anthropologist; Implications for Mathematics Education Researchers. *Proceedings of the 13th*

- Annual Meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education, Blacksburg, Vol. 1, 202-219.
- Elder-Vass, D. (2010). "The causal power of social structures: Emergence, structure and agency." Cambridge University Press.
- Elder-Vass, D. (2012). "The Reality of Social Construction." Cambridge University Press.
- Elder-Vass, D. (2016). Profit and gift in the digital economy. Cambridge University Press.
- Elo, S., & Kyngäs, H. (2008). The qualitative content analysis process. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 62: 107–115.
- Emery, F.E., & Trist, EL (1965). The causal texture of organizational environments. *Human Relations*, 18(1), 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872676501800103>.
- Emmel, N. (2013). Sample size. Sampling and choosing cases in qualitative research: A realist approach, 137-156.
- Emmel, N. (2015). Themes, variables, and the limits to calculating sample size in qualitative research: A response to Fugard and Potts. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 18(6), 685-686.
- Emmel, N., Greenhalgh, J., Manzano, A., Monaghan, M., & Dalkin, S. (2018). *Doing Realist Research*. SAGE Publications Ltd. ISBN: 9781473977896. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Emmel, N., Hughes, K., Greenhalgh, J., & Sales, A. (2007). Accessing Socially Excluded People — Trust and the Gatekeeper in the Researcher-Participant Relationship. *Sociological Research Online*.12(2):43-55. DOI:10.5153/sro.1512.
- England, N. H. S., & Improvement, N. H. S. (2019a). The NHS's recommendations to Government and Parliament for an NHS Bill.
- England, N. H. S., & Improvement, N. H. S. (2019b). The NHS patient safety strategy. Safer culture, safer systems, safer patients.
- Essien, J. (2013). 'Enterprise Architecture Models - Description of Integrated Components for Validation - A Case Study of Student Internship Programme', in Proceedings of the 15th

- International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems. SciTePress - Science and Technology Publications, pp. 302–309. DOI: 10.5220/0004443103020309.
- Faraj, S., Pachidi, S., & Sayegh, K. (2018). Working and organizing in the age of the learning algorithm. *Information and Organization*, 28(1), 62-70.
- Fenner, Y., Garland, S. M., Moore, E. E., Jayasinghe, Y., Fletcher, A., Tabrizi, S. N., ... & Wark, J. D. (2012). Web-based recruiting for health research using a social networking site: an exploratory study. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 14(1), e20.
- Fichman, R. G., Santos, B. L. D., & Zheng, Z. (2014). Digital innovation as a fundamental and powerful concept in the information systems curriculum. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(2), 329-353.
- Finney, S., & Corbett, M. (2007). "ERP implementation: a compilation and analysis of critical success factors". *Business Process Management Journal*, 13(3), 329–347.
- Fitzgerald, M., Kruschwitz, N., Bonnet, D., & Welch, M. (2013). "Embracing digital technology: A new strategic imperative," MIT Sloan Management Review, Research report.
- Fleetwood, S. (2014). "Bhaskar and critical realism." In Adler, P., du Gay, P., Morgan, G., & Reed, M. (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Sociology, Social Theory, and Organization Studies: Contemporary Currents*. Oxford University Press.
- Fletcher, A. J. (2017). Applying critical realism in qualitative research: methodology meets method. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 20(2), pp.181–194.
- Flowers, S. (1996). *Software failure: management failure*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley.
- Flick, U. (2018). *"An Introduction to Qualitative Research."* Sage Publications.
- Følstad, A., & Brandtzaeg, P. B. (2017). Chatbots and the new world of HCI. *Interactions*, 24(4), 38-42. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Foorthuis, R., & Brinkkemper, S. (2007). A FRAMEWORK FOR LOCAL PROJECT ARCHITECTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE. *a|EA Journal*.

Foorthuis, R., Hofman, F., Brinkkemper, S., & Bos, R. (2012). Compliance Assessments of Projects Adhering to Enterprise Architecture. *Journal of Database Management*, 23(2), pp. 44 – 71.

Foorthuis, R., Brinkkemper, S., & Bos, R. (2016). A framework for project architecture in the domain of product software: Combining the rational unified process software architecture and TOGAF's enterprise architecture. *International Journal of Information System Modeling and Design (IJISMD)*, 7(1), 75-105. doi:10.4018/IJISMD.2016010104.

Foster, D., & Harker, R. (2022). “Coronavirus: health and social care key issues and sources”. Available online at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-8887> [Date Accessed 26 March 2022].

Fusch, P. I., & Ness, L. R. (2015). Are We There Yet? Data Saturation in Qualitative Research. *The Qualitative Report*, 20(9), 1408-1416. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2015.2281>.

Gall, M., Gall, J., & Borg, R. (2007). *Educational research: An introduction* (8th ed.). New York, NY: Pearson Education.

Galliers, R. D., & Sutherland, A. (1991). “Information systems management and strategy formulation: The ‘stages of growth’ model revisited”. *Information Systems Journal*, 1(2), 89–114.

Gartner. (2009). 'Gartner Predicts That by 2012 40% of Today's Enterprise Architecture Programs Will Be Stopped (0.8 Probability)', Gartner Enterprise Architecture Summit: 2009.

Gartner. (2021). Enterprise Architecture (EA). Gartner Glossary, Information Technology Glossary. Retrieved May 15, 2021, from <https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/enterprise-architecture-ea> [Accessed 12 November 2021].

Geertz, C. (1993). “The Interpretation of Cultures, London”. Fontana Press.

Gellweiler, C. (2020). Connecting enterprise architecture and project portfolio management: a review and a model for IT project alignment. *International Journal of Information Technology Project Management*, 11(1), 99-114. DOI:10.4018/ijitpm.2020010106.

- Gerow, J. E., Grover, V., Thatcher, J. B., & Roth, P. L. (2014). Looking Toward the Future of IT-Business Strategic Alignment through the Past: A Meta-Analysis. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(4), 1059–1085.
- Gerring, J. (2009). *Case Selection for Case-Study Analysis: Qualitative and Quantitative Techniques*. (vol. 1). Oxford: Oxford University Press. DOI: 9780199286546.003.0028.
- Gibson, B. (2019). Systems theory. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at <https://www.britannica.com/topic/systems-theory> [Accessed 12 Oct. 2021].
- Genus, A., & Jha, P. (2012). The role of inertia in explanations of project performance: A framework and evidence from project-based organizations. *International Journal of Project Management*, 30(1), 117-126.
- Giddens, A. (1977). *Studies in Social and Political Theory (RLE Social Theory)* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315763224>.
- Giddens, A. (1984). *The constitution of society: Outline of the theory of structuration*. Cambridge, UK: John Polity Press.
- Giddens, A. (1987). *Social theory and modern sociology*. Stanford University Press.
- Gill, A. (2015). “Adaptive Enterprise Architecture-driven agile development”. In *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Information Systems Development*.
- Gill, A. Q. (2013). "Defining a Social Architecture within the Enterprise Architecture Context", Orbus Software, UK.
- Gill, A. Q., Alam, S. L., & Eustace, J. (2014). “Using social architecture to analyzing online social network use in emergency management”, In *20th Americas Conference on Information Systems, AMCIS*.
- Gilmore, B., McAuliffe, E., Power, J., & Vallières, F. (2019). Data analysis and synthesis within a realist evaluation: toward more transparent methodological approaches. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18, 1609406919859754.

- Gilpin, L. H., Bau, D., Yuan, B. Z., Bajwa, A., Specter, M., & Kagal, L. (2018). Explaining explanations: An approach to evaluating interpretability of machine learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.00069. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Girsang, A. S., & Abimanyu, A. (2021). “Development of an enterprise architecture for healthcare using togaf adm”, *Emerging Science Journal*, 5(3), pp. 305–321. DOI: 10.28991/esj-2021-01278.
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (2017). *The Discovery of Grounded Theory. The Discovery of Grounded Theory*, 1-18. doi:10.4324/9780203793206-1.
- Goepp, V., & Petit, M. (2017). 'Insight from a comparison of TOGAF ADM and SAM alignment processes', *IFAC-papers online. Elsevier BV*, 50(1), pp. 11707–11712. DOI: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.1693.
- Goethals, F. (2005). An overview of Enterprise Architecture frameworks. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=870207> [Accessed August 30, 2020].
- Goicolea, I., Coe, A. B., Hurtig, A. K., & San Sebastian, M. (2012). Mechanisms for achieving adolescent-friendly services in Ecuador: A realist evaluation approach. *Global Health Action*, 5. DOI: 10.3402/gha.v5i0.18748.
- Golinelli, D., Boetto, E., Carullo, G., Nuzzolese, A. G., Landini, M. P., & Fantini, M. P. (2020). How the COVID-19 pandemic is favoring the adoption of digital technologies in healthcare: a literature review. *MedRxiv*.
- Gong, Y., & Janssen, M. (2019). “The value of and myths about Enterprise Architecture”. *International Journal of Information Management. Elsevier Ltd*, 46, pp. 1–9.
- Gonzalez, E. B., Easdale, M. H., & Sacchero, D. M. (2021).” Socio-technical networks modulate on-farm technological innovations in wool production of North Patagonia”. *Journal of Rural Studies Argentina*.
- Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., & Courville, A. (2016). *Deep learning*. MIT Press.

Graneheim, U. H., & Lundman, B. (2017). Qualitative content analysis in nursing research: concepts, procedures and measures to achieve trustworthiness. *Nurse Education Today*, 24(2), 105-112.

Granovetter, M. (1983). "The Strength of Weak Ties: A Network Theory Revisited". *Sociological Theory*, Vol. 1, pp. 201-233 (33 pages). Wiley.

Greefhorst, D., & Proper, H. A. (2011). *Architecture Principles. The Cornerstones of Enterprise Architecture*. Springer.

Greenhalgh, J., & Manzano, A. (2021). Understanding 'context' in realist evaluation and synthesis. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 1-13. Taylor Francis Online.

Gregory, R. W., Keil, M., Muntermann, J., & Mähring, M. (2015). Paradoxes and the nature of ambidexterity in IT transformation programs. *Information Systems Research*, 26(1), 57–80.

Grisot, M., Hanseth, O., & Thorseng, A. A. (2014). Innovation of, in, on infrastructures: Articulating the role of architecture in information infrastructure evolution. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 15(4), 197-219.

Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1994). "Competing paradigms in qualitative research". In Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y. S. *Handbook of qualitative research*, 3rd Edition. (pp. 105 – 117). Sage Publications.

Guest, G., Bunce, A., & Johnson, L. (2006). How many interviews are enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field Methods*, 18(1), 59-82.

Guijarro, L. (2007). "Interoperability Frameworks and Enterprise Architectures in e-government Initiatives in Europe and the United States". *Government Information Quarterly*, 24(1), pp. 89–101. Doi: 10.1016/j.giq.2006.05.003.

Guo, H., Li, J., & Gao, S. (2019). Understanding challenges of applying enterprise architecture in public sectors: A technology acceptance perspective. In 2019 IEEE 23rd International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Workshop (EDOCW) (pp. 38-43). IEEE.

- Hackett, I., & Sibley, F. (1958). 'Aesthetic concepts'. *Philosophical Review* (1959). reprinted in *Approach to Aesthetics*, Clarendon: Oxford, 2001.
- Hafsi, M., & Assar, S. (2016). 'What enterprise architecture can bring for digital transformation: An exploratory study', in *Proceedings - CBI 2016: 18th IEEE Conference on Business Informatics*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., pp. 83–89. DOI: 10.1109/CBI.2016.55.
- Hagendorff, T. (2020). The ethics of AI ethics: An evaluation of guidelines. *Minds and Machines*, 30(1), 99-120. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Haki, K., & Legner, C. (2013). "The Dynamics of IS Adaptation in Multinational Corporations: A New Theoretical Lens," in *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2013)*, Milano, Italy.
- Haki, M. K., Aier, S., & Winter, R. (2016). "A Stakeholder Perspective to Study Enterprise-wide IS Initiatives," in *Proceedings of the 24th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2016)*, Istanbul, Turkey.
- Haki, K., & Legner, C. (2021). The mechanics of enterprise architecture principles. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 22(5), 1334-1375.
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., & Vaishya, R. (2020). "Effects of COVID-19 pandemic in daily life." *Current Medicine Research and Practice*, 10(3), 78-79.
- Hambrick, D. C. (2007). "The field of management's devotion to theory: Too much of a good thing?," *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(6), 1346-1352.
- Hanelt, A., Leonhardt, D., Hildebrandt, B., Piccinini, E., & Kolbe, L. M. (2019). Pushing and pulling—digital business model innovation and dynamic capabilities. *Journal of competences, strategy & management*, 10, 55-78.
- Hanschke, I. (2010). *Strategic IT Management. A Toolkit for Enterprise Architecture Management*. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-05034-3. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.

- Hanseth, O., & Lyytinen, K. (2010). Design theory for dynamic complexity in information infrastructures: The case of building internet. *Journal of Information Technology*, 25(1), 1–19.
- Hanseth, O., Jacucci, E., Grisot, M., & Aanestad, M. (2006). “Reflexive standardization: Side effects and complexity in standard making”. *MIS Quarterly*, 30, 563–581.
- Hardcastle, M. A. R., Usher, K. J., & Holmes, C. A. (2005). An overview of structuration theory and its usefulness for nursing research. *Nurs Philos*. 6(4):223–234. 10.1111/j.1466-769X.2005.00230.x.
- Harré, R. (1984). Some Reflections on the Concept of "Social Representation". *Social research*, 927-938.
- Harris, I. (2003). "What does The Discovery of Grounded Theory have to say to medical education?", *Advances in Health Sciences Education*, 8, 49–61.
- Hauder, M., Matthes, F., Roth, S., & Schulz, C. (2012). Generating Dynamic Cross-Organizational Process Visualizations through Abstract View Model Pattern Matching. *Enterprise Interoperability: I-ESA'12 Proceedings*, 95-101.
- Hauder, M., Roth, S., Schulz, C., & Matthes, F. (2013). An examination of organisational factors influencing Enterprise Architecture management challenges. *ECIS 2013 Proceedings*, Utrecht, Netherlands.
- Hawe, P., Shiell, A., Riley, T. (2009). Theorising interventions as events in systems. *Am J Community Psychol*. 43(3-4):267–76.
- He, H., Bai, Y., Garcia, E. A., & Li, S. (2008). ADASYN: Adaptive synthetic sampling approach for imbalanced learning. In *2008 IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IEEE World Congress on Computational Intelligence)* (pp. 1322-1328). IEEE. [Accessed: 20th May 2023].
- Health and Social Care Act (HSCA). (2012). Health and Social Care Act 2012. Available online at <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2012/7/contents/enacted> [Accessed date 20 October 2021].

Health Education England. (2020). Our Work. Accessed online at: <https://www.hee.nhs.uk/> [Access date: 6th March 2021].

Heather, B. (2018). 'Exclusive: Quarter of a billion marked for NHS tech goes unspent'. HSJ, 23rd January. Available at: www.hsj.co.uk/technology-and-innovation/exclusive-quarter-of-a-billion-marked-for-nhs-tech-goes-unspent/7021476.article [accessed on 19th March 2021].

Hedstrom, P., & Swedberg, R. (1998). *Social Mechanisms*. Melbourne: Cambridge University Press. Available at: <http://people.soc.cornell.edu/swedberg/1998SocialMechanisms.pdf> [Access date: 6th October 2020].

Heer, J., Bostock, M., & Ogievetsky, V. (2010). A tour through the visualization zoo. *Communications of the ACM*, 53(6), 59-67.

Heinrich, C. J. (2007). Evidence-based policy and performance management: Challenges and prospects in two parallel movements. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 37, 255-277.

Henderson, J. C., & Venkatraman, H. (1993). "Strategic alignment: Leveraging information technology for transforming organisations," in *IBM Systems Journal*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 472-484, 1993, DOI: 10.1147/sj.382.0472.

Henderson, J. C., & Venkatraman, H. (1999). Strategic alignment: Leveraging information technology for transforming organizations. *IBM systems journal*, 38(2.3), 472-484.

Hendy, J., Fulop, N., Reeves, B. C., Hutchings, A., & Collin, S. (2007). Implementing the NHS information technology programme: a qualitative study of progress in acute trusts. *Br Med J*; 334 (7608): 1360–4.

Herepath, A. (2014). In the Loop: A Realist Approach to Structure and Agency in the Practice of Strategy. *Organization Studies*, 35(6), pp. 857–879. DOI: 10.1177/0170840613509918.

Hiekkanen, K., Helenius, M., Korhonen, J. J., & Patricio, E. (2013). *Aligning Alignment with Strategic Context: A Literature Review*.

Hinkelmann, K., Gerber, A., Karagiannis, D., Thoenssen, B., Van der Merwe, A., & Woitsch, R. (2016). A new paradigm for the continuous alignment of business and IT: Combining enterprise architecture modelling and enterprise ontology. *Computers in Industry*, 79, 77-86.

Hinton, G., Vinyals, O., & Dean, J. (2015). Distilling the knowledge in a neural network. arXiv preprint arXiv:1503.02531. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Hjort-Madsen, K. (2007). "Institutional patterns of ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE adoption in government. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*". ISSN: 1750-6166. emerald insight.

Hoffman, N., & Klepper, R. (2000). Assimilating new technologies: The role of organizational culture. *Information Systems Management*, 17(3), 36–42.

Hofstede, G., Neuijen, B., Ohayv, D. D., & Sanders, G. (1990). "Measuring organizational cultures: A qualitative and quantitative study across twenty cases". *Administrative science quarterly*, 286-316. (1990). *Measuring Organisational Cultures; A Qualitative and Quantitative Study across Twenty Cases*.

Holstein, K., Wortman Vaughan, J., Daumé III, H., Dudík, M., & Wallach, H. (2019, January). Improving fairness in machine learning systems: What do industry practitioners need?. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-16). ACM. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Honeyman, M., Dunn, P., & McKenna, H. (2016). *A digital NHS? An introduction to the digital agenda and plans for implementation*. London: The King's Fund. Available at: www.kingsfund.org.uk/publications/digital-nhs [Accessed on 19th March 2021].

Hope, T. (2015). *The Critical Success Factors of Enterprise Architecture*. University of Technology, Sydney. Available at: <https://opus.lib.uts.edu.au/bitstream/10453/38961/2/02whole.pdf> [Accessed 26 December 2020].

- Hope, T., Chew, E., & Sharma, R. (2017). The Failure of Success Factors: Lessons from Success and Failure Cases of Enterprise Architecture Implementation. SIGMIS-CPR'17. p. 27.
- House of Commons Library. (2020). The Care Quality Commission. April 2020. Accessed online at: <<https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-8754/>> [Access date: 26 May 2021].
- Howard, J., & Ruder, S. (2018). Universal language model fine-tuning for text classification. In Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers) (pp. 328-339). <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/P18-1030>. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Howard, J., & Ruder, S. (2018). Universal language model fine-tuning for text classification. In Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers) (pp. 328-339). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/P18-1030>.
- Hu, X. (2018). Methodological implications of critical realism for entrepreneurship research. *Journal of Critical Realism* 17(2): 118–139. DOI: 10.1080/14767430.2018.1454705.
- Hutto, C.J., & Gilbert, E. (2014). VADER: A parsimonious rule-based model for sentiment analysis of social media text. Eighth International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media (ICWSM-14). AAAI. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Iacob, M. E., Meertens, L. O., Jonkers, H., Quartel, D. A., Nieuwenhuis, L. J., & Van Sinderen, M. J. (2014). From enterprise architecture to business models and back. *Software & Systems Modeling*, 13, 1059-1083.
- Ibragimov, B., & Xing, L. (2017). Segmentation of organs-at-risks in head and neck CT images using convolutional neural networks. *Med Phys.* 44(2):547-557. doi:10.1002/mp.12045.
- Illman, J. (2016). ‘*Hunt says £1.8bn will be spent on “paper-free NHS”*’. *HSJ*, 7 February. Available at: www.hsj.co.uk/technology-and-innovation/hunt-says-18bn-will-be-spent-on-paper-free-nhs/7002229.article [accessed on 19th March 2021].

Institute of Electrical & Electronics Engineers [IEEE]. (2000). Recommended Practice for Architectural Description for Software-Intensive Systems," in IEEE Std 1471-2000, vol., no., pp.1-30, 9 Oct. 2000, DOI: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2000.91944 [Accessed 12 Oct. 2021].

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2007). Systems and Software Engineering Recommended Practice for Architectural Description of Software-Intensive Systems," in ISO/IEC 42010 IEEE Std 1471-2000 First edition 2007-07-15, vol., no., pp.1-24, 15 Jul. 2007, DOI: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2007.386501.

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2008). Development of service standards — Recommendations for addressing consumer issues, 2020, pp. 1–32.

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2011). Systems and software engineering, vol., no., pp.1-46, DOI: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2011.6129467. [Accessed: 12 December 2021].

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2019). Software, systems and enterprise -- Architecture processes," in ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020:2019(E), vol., no., pp.1-126. DOI: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2019.8767004. [Accessed: 12 December 2021].

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2021). Draft Standard - Systems and Software engineering -- System Life Cycle Processes," in ISO/IEC/IEEE P15288/ CD, vol., no., pp.1-129, 19th April 2021.

Introna, L. D. (2016). Algorithms, governance, and governmentality: On governing academic writing. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 41(1), 17-49.

Isaksen, K. R. (2016). A critique of methodological applications of critical realism. *Journal of Critical Realism* 15(3): 245–262. DOI: 10.1080/14767430.2016.1169369.

Iyamu, T. (2019). 'Understanding the Complexities of ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE through Structuration Theory', *Journal of Computer Information Systems*. Taylor and Francis Inc., 59(3), pp. 287–295. DOI: 10.1080/08874417.2017.1354341.

- Iyamu, T., & Roode, D. (2010). The use of structuration and actor-network theory for analysis: a case study of a financial institution in South Africa. *Int J Actor-Network Theory Technol Innovation*. 2(1):1–26. 10.4018/jantti.2010071601.
- Jabareen, Y. (2009). Building a conceptual framework: Philosophy, definitions, and procedure. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 8, 49-62.
- Jackson, M. C., P. Keys, and S. A. Cropper (2016). "Operational Research and the Problem of Implementation." *European Journal of Operational Research*, 253(3), 603-611.
- Jackson, S. F., & Kolla, G. (2012). A New Realistic Evaluation Analysis Method: Linked Coding of Context, Mechanism, and Outcome Relationships. *Vol 33, 3: 339-349*
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214012440030>.
- Jagosh, J., Pluye, P., Wong, G., Cargo, M., Salsberg, J., Bush, P. L., ... & Macaulay, A. C. (2014). Critical reflections on realist review: insights from customizing the methodology to the needs of participatory research assessment. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 5(2), 131-141.
- Jagosh, J. (2018). Delivered for Realist Approaches Workshop: Founding Principles and Contemporary Development (Newcastle 14.11.18).
- Jagosh, J. (2019). "Realist Synthesis for Public Health: Building an Ontologically-Deep Understanding of How Programs Work, for Whom, and in Which Circumstances." *Annual Review of Public Health* 40: 361–372.
- Jagosh, J. (2020a). Lecture. Delivered for Solent University Realist Research Group (SURRG) on July 23rd, 2020.
- Jagosh, J. (2020b). Retroductive Theorising in Pawson and Tilley's Applied Scientific Realism. *Journal of Critical Realism*, 19:2 (p.121-130). DOI/abs/10.1080/14767430.2020.1723301.
- Jagosh, J., Bush, P. L., Salsberg, J., Macaulay, A. C., Greenhalgh, T., Wong, G., Cargo, M., Green, L. W., Herbert, C. P., & Pluye, P. (2015). 'A realist evaluation of community-based participatory

research: partnership synergy, trust-building and related ripple effects', *BMC Public Health*. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1) p. 725. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-015-1949-1.

Jagosh, J., Macaulay, A. C., Pluye, P., Salsberg, J. O. N., Bush, P. L., Henderson, J. I. M., ... & Greenhalgh, T. (2012). Uncovering the benefits of participatory research: implications of a realist review for health research and practice. *The Milbank Quarterly*, 90(2), 311-346.

Jensen, L. A., & Allen, M. N. (1996). Meta-synthesis of qualitative findings. *Qualitative Health Research*, 6(4), 553–560.

Jha, A. K., Doolan, D., & Grandt, D. (2008). The use of health information technology in seven nations. *Int J Med Inform*; 77 (12): 848–54.

Jiang, F., Jiang, Y., Zhi, H., Dong, Y., Li, H., Ma, S., ... & Wang, Y. (2017). Artificial intelligence in healthcare: past, present and future. *Stroke and vascular neurology*, 2(4), 230-243.

Jin, M., Kung, D., & Peng, W. (2010). Research of Information System Technology Architecture. 2010 2nd International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems, Dalian, 2010, pp. 293-296. DOI: 10.1109/INDUSIS.2010.5565708.

Johnson, P., Lagerström, R., Närman, P., & Simonsson, M. (2007). Enterprise Architecture analysis with extended influence diagrams. *Journal Information Systems Frontiers* 9 (July (2–3)), 163–180.

Jonnagaddala, J., Guo, G. N., Batongbacal, S., Marcelo, A., & Liaw, S. (2020). “Adoption of enterprise architecture for healthcare in AeHIN member countries”, *BMJ Health and Care Informatics*, 27(1), p. e100136. DOI: 10.1136/bmjhci-2020-100136.

Josey, A. (2017). GLOBAL TOGAF® 9 CERTIFICATION EXCEEDS 70,000 IN 134 COUNTRIES. The Open Group Blog. Available online at <https://blog.opengroup.org/2017/07/24/global-togaf-9-certification-exceeds-70000-in-134-countries/> [Data Accessed 1 January 2022].

Jurafsky, D., & Martin, J. H. (2019). *Speech and language processing* (3rd ed.). Prentice Hall. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

- Kadushin, C. (2012). *Understanding Social Networks: Theories, Concepts and Findings*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Kaivo-oja, J. R. L., & Lauraeus, I. T. (2018). 'The VUCA approach as a solution concept to corporate foresight challenges and global technological disruption', *Foresight*, 20(1), pp. 27–49. DOI: 10.1108/FS-06-2017-0022.
- Kane, M., & Trochim, W. M. K. (2007). *Concept mapping for planning and evaluation*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Kane, G. C., Alavi, M., Labianca, G., & Borgatti, S. P. (2014). What's different about social media networks? A framework and research agenda. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(1), 275-304.
- Kane, G. C., Palmer, D., & Phillips, A. N. (2019). *Accelerating digital innovation inside and out*. MIT Sloan Management Review.
- Karpovsky, A., & Galliers, R. D. (2015). "Aligning in Practice: From Current Cases to a New Agenda," *Journal of Information Technology* (30:2), pp. 136- 160.
- Kazi, M. A. F. (2003). The contribution of realist evaluation for Practice. In: Kazi MAF (ed) *Realist Evaluation in Practice*. DOI: 10.4135/9781849209762.
- Kazi, M. A. F., & Spurling, L. J. (2000). "Realist evaluation for evidence-based Practice". Paper Presented at the European Evaluation Society's Fourth Conference, Lausanne, Switzerland, October 2000. Available at: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.533.8182andrep> [Accessed 15 September 2021].
- Kemp, S., & Holmwood, J. (2003). 'Realism, Regularity and Social Explanation', *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour* 33(2): 165-187.
- Killaspy, H., King, M., Holloway, F., Craig, T. K., Cook, S., Mundy, T., Leavey, G., McCrone, P., Koeser, L., Omar, R. Z., Marston, L., Arbuthnott, M., Green, N., Harrison, I., Lean, M., Gee, M., & Bhanbhro, S. (2017). *The Rehabilitation Effectiveness for Activities for Life (REAL) study: a*

national programme of research into NHS inpatient mental health rehabilitation services across England.

King's Fund. (2019). *The NHS Long-term Plan Explained*.

Kohansal, M. A., Rolland, K. H. R., & Khodambashi, S. (2022). Towards an Explanation for Why Enterprise Architecture Management Fails: A Legitimacy Lens. In *Exploring Digital Resilience: Challenges for People and Organizations* (pp. 217-231). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Koren, Y., Bell, R., & Volinsky, C. (2009). Matrix factorization techniques for recommender systems. *Computer*, (8), 30-37.

Korhonen, J. J., & Poutanen, J. (2013). "Tripartite approach to EA," *Journal of ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 28– 38.

Kotter, J. P., & Heskett, J. L. (1992). *Corporate Culture and Performance*. New York: Free Press.

Kotusev, S. (2016). Enterprise architecture is not TOGAF | BCS. *Enterprise Architecture Is Not TOGAF | BCS*; www.bcs.org. <https://www.bcs.org/articles-opinion-and-research/enterprise-architecture-is-not-togaf/>, Available at <https://www.bcs.org/articles-opinion-and-research/enterprise-architecture-is-not-togaf/> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

Kotusev, S. (2017). "Enterprise architecture: What did we study?" *International Journal of Cooperative Information Systems*, 26(4), 1-84.

Kotusev, S. (2018). "TOGAF-based Enterprise Architecture Practice: An Exploratory Case Study". *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 43(1), pp. 321–359. DOI: 10.17705/1CAIS

Kotusev, S. (2018a). *Enterprise Architecture on a page, v1.2*. Available at [HTTP://eaonapage.com/Enterprise%20Architecture%20on%20a%20Page%20\(v1.2\).pdf](http://eaonapage.com/Enterprise%20Architecture%20on%20a%20Page%20(v1.2).pdf), [Accessed Date August 7, 2020].

Kowsari, K., Brown, D. E., Heidarysafa, M., Jafari Meimandi, K., Gerber, M. S., & Barnes, L. E. (2017). HDLTex: Hierarchical Deep Learning for Text Classification. In *2017 16th IEEE*

International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA) (pp. 364-371). IEEE. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Kraindler, J., Gershlick, B., & Charlesworth, A. (2018). Failing to capitalise capital spending in the NHS. London: The Health Foundation. Available at: www.health.org.uk/publications/reports/failing-to-capitalise [accessed on 19th March 2021].

Kreizman, G., & Bittler, R. S. (2005). Gartner Enterprise Architecture Process: Evolution 2005. ID: G00130849. Gartner Enterprise Architecture Process [Internet]. (October):21. Available from: <https://www.gartner.com/doc/486246/gartner-enterprise-architecture-process-evolution>. [Access 25 January 2021]

Krippendorff, K. (2004). Content Analysis: An Introduction to Its Methodology (2nd edn). London: Sage Publications. Lincoln.

Krittanawong, C. (2018). The rise of artificial intelligence and the uncertain future for physicians. *Eur J Intern Med*. 48:e13-e14. doi:10.1016/j.ejim.2017.06.017.

Kroeber, A. L., & Parsons, T. (1958). "The concepts of culture and of social systems", *The American Sociological Review*, Vol.23 (1), p.582.

Küppers, R. O. (1992). Emergence or Reduction? Chapter: Understanding Complexity. Publisher: Walter de Gruyter. Editors: Ansgar Beckermann, Hans Flohr, Jaegwon Kim.

Kuhn, T. S. (2012). *The structure of scientific revolutions*. University of Chicago Press.

Kuzel, A. J. (1992). Sampling in qualitative inquiry. In B. F. Crabtree and W. L. Miller (Eds.), *Doing qualitative research* (pp. 31–44). Sage Publications, Inc.

Kyngäs, H., Kääriäinen, M., & Elo, S. (2020). The trustworthiness of content analysis. *The application of content analysis in nursing science research*, 41-48.

Kvale, S. (1996). *Interviews: An Introduction to Qualitative Research Interviewing*. Thousand.

La Pelle, N. (2004). "Simplifying Qualitative Data Analysis Using General Purpose Software Tools." *Field Methods* 16(1):85–108.

- Lacouture, A., Breton, E., Guichard, A., & Ridde, V. (2015). The concept of mechanism from a realist.
- Lagerstro, R., Sommestad, T., Buschle, M., & Ekstedt, M. (2011). Enterprise Architecture management's impact on information technology Success, 44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences p.1–10.
- Lange, M., Mendling, J., & Recker, J. (2016). An empirical analysis of the factors and measures of Enterprise Architecture Management success. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 25(5), p.411-431.
- Langley, A. (2018). "Microfoundations of Strategy: A Matter of Substance." *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(12), 3234-3244.
- Lankhorst, M. (2005). *Enterprise Architecture at Work: Modelling, communication and analysis*. Springer.
- Lankhorst, M., & Lankhorst, M. (2013). Beyond enterprise architecture. *Enterprise Architecture at Work: Modelling, Communication and Analysis*, 303-308.
- Lapalme, J. (2012). "Three schools of thought on Enterprise Architecture". *IT Prof* (2012); 14(6): p.37–43.
- Layard, R., & Glaister, S. (1994). *Cost-Benefit Analysis*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Layder, D. (1994). *Understanding Social Theory*, London: Sage.
- Le, Q., & Mikolov, T. (2014). Distributed representations of sentences and documents. In *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML-14)* (pp. 1188-1196). [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Lawson, T. (2012). "Mathematical modelling and ideology in the economics academy: competing explanations of the failings of the modern discipline?" *Economic Thought*, 1(1), 3-22.

- LeanIX. (2019). " Enterprise Architecture Insights Report". 2019 LEANIX STUDY CONTENT. Available at: <https://www.leanix.net/en/download/enterprise-architecture-insights-report-2019>.
- Lee, C. J., Sugimoto, C. R., Zhang, G., & Cronin, B. (2013). Bias in peer review. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64(1), 2-17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.22784>.
- Lee, S., Oh, S., & Nam, K. (2016). 'Transformational and Transactional Factors for the Successful Implementation of Enterprise Architecture in Public Sector', *Sustainability*, 8(5), p. 456. DOI: 10.3390/su8050456.
- Lefroy, J., Hawarden, A., Gay, S. P., McKinley, R. K., & Cleland, J. (2015). Grades in formative workplace-based assessment: a study of what works for whom and why. *Med Educ.* Mar;49(3):307-20. DOI: 10.1111/medu.12659. PMID: 25693990.
- Lemire, S. T., Nielsen, S. B., & Dybdal, L. (2012). Making contribution analysis work: A practical framework for handling influencing factors and alternative explanations. *Evaluation* 18(3): 294–309.
- Lemire, S., Kwako, A., Nielsen, S. B., Christie, C. A., Stewart, I., Donaldson, S. I., & Leeuw, F. L. (2020). 'What Is This Thing Called a Mechanism? Findings From a Review of Realist Evaluations', *New Directions for Evaluation*, 2020(167), pp. 73–86. DOI: 10.1002/ev.20428.
- Lemmetti, J., & Pekkola, S (2014). 'Enterprise Architecture in public ICT procurement in Finland', *Innovation and the Public Sector*, 21, 227–236. Doi: 10.3233/978-1-61499-429-9-227.
- Leonardi, P. M., & Vaast, E. (2017). Social media and their affordances for organizing: A review and agenda for research. *Academy of Management Annals*, 11(1), 150-188.
- Levering, B. (2002). "Concept analysis as empirical method". *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 1(1), 35–48.
- Levy, M. (2019). How field-level institutions become a part of organisations: A study of Enterprise Architecture as a tool for institutional change—information and Organisation, 29(4), p.100272.

- Lewis-Beck, M., Bryman, A., & Liao, T. (Eds.). (2004). *Encyclopedia of Social Science Research Methods: Encyclopedia of Social Science Research Methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Liamputtong, P. (2016). "Qualitative Research Methods." Oxford University Press.
- Liang, H., Saraf, N., Hu, Q., & Xue, Y. (2007). Assimilation of enterprise systems: The effect of institutional pressures and the mediating role of top management. *MIS Quarterly*, 31(1), 59–87.
- Liddell, A., Adshead, S., & Burgess, E. (2008). *Technology in the NHS. Transforming the patient's experience of care*. The King's Fund 2008.
- Likourezos, A., Chalfin, D. B., Murphy, D. G., Sommer, B., Darcy, K., & Davidson, S. J. (2004). Physician and nurse satisfaction with an Electronic Medical Record system. *The Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 27(4), pp. 419–424. DOI: 10.1016/j.jemermed.2004.03.019.
- LinkedIn.com. (2018). *LinkedIn.com: The Enterprise Architecture Network: Why is EA such a hard sell despite the potential rewards it can bring to organisations? There must be solutions to the very high failure rate of EA initiatives*. Submitted on the 1st of June 2018. Available at <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/36781/36781-6407610716999737346> [Accessed 25 June 2019].
- Liu, B., & Zhang, L. (2012). A survey of opinion mining and sentiment analysis. In *Mining text data* (pp. 415-463). Springer, Boston, MA. *Computational Intelligence Magazine*, 9(2), 48-57. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Löhe, J., & Legner, C. (2014). 'Overcoming implementation challenges in ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE management: a design theory for architecture-driven IT Management (ADRIMA)', *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, 12(1), pp. 101–137. DOI: 10.1007/s10257-012-0211-y.
- Luftman, J. (2003). *Assessing It/Business Alignment*. *Inf Syst Manag* [Internet]. Sep 1;20(4):9–15. Available from: doi.org/10.1201/1078/43647.20.4.20030901/77287.2.

- Lyytinen, K., & Damsgaard, J. (2001). "What's wrong with the diffusion of innovation theory?", Paper presented at the Working Conference on Diffusing Software Product and Process Innovations.
- Lyytinen, K., & King, J. L. (2006). Standard making: A critical research frontier for information systems research. *MIS Quarterly*, 30, 405–411.
- Lyytinen, K., & Newman, M. (2008). "Explaining Information Systems Change: A Punctuated Socio-Technical Change Model," *European Journal of Information Systems* (17:6), pp. 589-613.
- MacKay, B., & Tambeau, P. (2013). A structuration approach to scenario praxis. *Technol Forecast Soc Change*. 80(4):673–686. 10.1016/j.techfore.2012.06.003.
- MacLennan, G. (1998). 'Aesthetics and the dialectic of desire', *Alethia* 1, 1998, pp. 19-22; 'Towards an ontological aesthetics', *Alethia* 1, 1998.
- MacLennan, G., & Thomas, P. (2003). 'Cultural studies: towards a realist intervention', in Justin Cruickshank, ed., *Critical Realism: The Difference it Makes*, London: Routledge.
- Mader, D. (2018). *Critical Realism*. Edited by M. A. B. A. C. L., Alan Norrie. New York: transcript Verlag. Available at: <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.14361/9783839440735-006/html>.
- Madhok, A. (2002). "Reassessing the fundamentals and beyond: Ronald Coase, the transaction cost and resource-based theories of the firm and the institutional structure of production", *Strategic Management Journal*, 23(6), pp. 535–550. DOI: 10.1002/smj.247.
- Makadok, R., Burton, R., & Barney, J. (2018). 'A practical guide for making theory contributions in strategic management', *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(6), pp. 1530–1545. DOI: 10.1002/smj.2789.
- Makiya, G. K., & Lyytinen, K. (2011). The antecedents of Enterprise Architecture assimilation in organizations. Unpublished Quantitative Research Report, Weatherhead School of Management, Case Western Reserve University.

- Malta, P., & Sousa, R. D. (2016). 'Process-Oriented Approaches in Enterprise Architecture for Business-IT Alignment', *Procedia Computer Science*. Elsevier B.V., 100, pp. 888–893. DOI: 10.1016/j.procs.2016.09.239.
- Malterud, K. (2001). The art and science of clinical knowledge: evidence beyond measures and numbers. *Lancet*. 358:397–400.
- Malterud, K., Siersma, V. D., & Guassora, A. D. (2015). Sample Size in Qualitative Interview Studies: Guided by Information Power. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1753–1760. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315617444>.
- Manson, S. M. (2001). Simplifying complexity: a review of complexity theory. *Geoforum*, 32(3), 405-414.
- Manzano, A. (2016). The craft of interviewing in realist evaluation. *Evaluation* 22(3): 342–360.
- Marchal, B., Kegels, G., & Van Belle, S. (2018). Theory and realist methods. In N. Emmel, J. Greenhalgh, A. Manzano, M. Monaghan, & S. Dalkin (Eds.), *Doing realist research* (pp. 79-90). SAGE Publications.
- Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., & Westhorp, G. (2018). Realist evaluation. Available at https://www.betterevaluation.org/en/approach/realist_evaluation [Date Accessed 12 January 2022].
- Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., van Olmen, J., Hoeree, T., & Kegels, G. (2012). Is realist evaluation keeping its promise? A review of published empirical studies in the field of health systems research. *Evaluation*, 18, 192–212. doi:10.1177/1356389012442444.
- Marnewick, C., & Labuschagne, L. (2011). An investigation into the governance of information technology projects in South Africa. *International Journal of Project Management*, 29(6), 661-670.
- Marshall, M. N. (1996). Sampling for qualitative research. *Family Practice*, 13(6), 522–526. <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/13.6.522>.

- Mason, M. (2010). Sample Size and Saturation in PhD Studies Using Qualitative Interviews. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 11(3).
<https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-11.3.1428>.
- Masuda, Y., & Viswanathan, M. (2019). Evaluation for EA Framework Implementation Method. In *Enterprise Architecture for Global Companies in a Digital IT Era* (pp. 89-98). Springer, Singapore.
- Matt, C., Hess, T., & Benlian, A. (2015). Digital transformation strategies. *Business and information systems engineering* 57 (5), 339-343.
- Maxcy, S. J. (2003). Pragmatic threads in mixed methods research in the social sciences. The search for multiple modes of Inquiry and the end of the philosophy of formalism. In Tashakkori and Teddie (Eds.), *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research*. Sage Publications. pp. 51–89.
- Maxwell, J. (2012). *A Realist Approach for Qualitative Research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012a). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*. Sage publications.
- May, C. R., Johnson, M., & Finch, T. (2016). Implementation, context and complexity, *Implementation Science*. *Implementation Science*, 11(1), p. 141. DOI: 10.1186/s13012-016-0506-3.
- May, C. R., Johnson, M., & Finch, T. (2016). Implementation, context and complexity. *Implementation Science*, 11(1), 1-12. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Mayer, N., Grandry, E., Feltus, C., Goettelmann, E., & Wieringa, R. (2019). “An integrated conceptual model for information system security risk management supported by Enterprise Architecture management”. *Software and Systems Modeling*, Springer Verlag, 18(3), pp. 2285–2312.
- Mayntz, R. (2004). 'Mechanisms in the Analysis of Social Macro-Phenomena', *Philosophy of the Social Sciences* 34(2): 237-259.
- McAvoy, J., & Butler, T. (2018). A critical realist method for applied business research. *Journal of Critical Realism* 17(2): 160–175. DOI: 10.1080/14767430.2018.1455477.

- McDermott, I., Warwick-Giles, L., Gore, O., Moran, V., Bramwell, D., Coleman, A., & PI, K. C. (2018). Understanding primary care co-commissioning: uptake, development, and impacts.
- McEvoy, P., & Richards, D. (2003). Critical realism: a way forward for evaluation research in nursing? *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 43(4): 411–420.
- McKee, M., Stuckler, D. (2018). Revisiting the Corporate and Commercial Determinants of Health. *American Journal of Public Health*, 108(9), 1167–1170.
- McKenna, H., Dunn, P., Northern, E., & Buckley, T. (2017). How health care is funded. Publisher: The King'sFund. Available at <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/publications/how-health-care-is-funded> [Accessed 20 March 2020].
- Medhat, W., Hassan, A., & Korashy, H. (2014). Sentiment analysis algorithms and applications: A survey. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 5(4), 1093-1113. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Melville, N., Kraemer, K., & Gurbaxani, V. (2004). Information technology and organisational performance: an integrative model of IT business value, *Mis Q.* 28 (2004) 283–322.
- Merriam, S. B. (2002). "Introduction to qualitative research". In Merriam, S. B. (Ed.). *Qualitative Research in Practice*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass. Pp. 3 – 17.
- Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*.
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Context. In the Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved May 15, 2021, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/context>.
- Meyer, D. Z., & Avery, L. M. (2009). Excel as a qualitative data analysis tool. *Field methods*, 21(1), 91-112.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook* (2nd ed.). Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Mingers, J. (2004). "Realising information systems: critical realism as an underpinning philosophy for information systems", *Information and Organization*, 14(2), pp. 87-103.

- Mingers, J. (2014). *Systems thinking, critical realism and philosophy: A confluence of ideas*. Oxon, UK: Routledge.
- Mingers, J., & Standing, C. (2017). "Why things happen: Developing the critical realist view of causal mechanisms". *Information and Organization*, 27(3), pp. 171-189.
- Minniti, M., & Van Audenhove, L. (2017). "Exploring the Dynamics of Institutional Complexity in Multi-Stakeholder Partnerships: A Process Approach." *Journal of Business Ethics*, 145(4), 787-803.
- Mishler, E. G. (1991). *Research interviewing: Context and narrative*. Harvard university press.
- Mitchell, T. M. (2018). *Machine learning: A guide to current research*. The Springer International Series in Engineering and Computer Science. Springer. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Mitchell, M. (2009). *Complexity: A guided tour*. Oxford university press.
- Mohamed, M. A., Galal-Edeen, G. H., & Hassan, H. A. (2013). "Towards Adoption of Government Enterprise Architecture: The Cases of Egypt and Syria," *Proc. 13th European Conference on eGovernment (ECEG 2013)*, Academic Conferences Limited, Jun, p. 345.
- Montuori, A. (2011). 'Systems Approach', in *Encyclopedia of Creativity*. 2nd edn. Elsevier, pp. 414–421. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-12-375038-9.00212-0.
- Morais, R. (2011). "Critical Realism and Case Studies in International Business Research".
- Morgan, D. L. (2013). Pragmatism as a paradigm for social research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 20(10), pp.1-9.
- Morganwalp, J. M., & Sage, A. P. (2004). "Enterprise Architecture measures of effectiveness". *Int J Technol Policy Manage* 4(1):81–94.
- Morse, J. M. (2000). Determining sample size. *Qualitative health research*, 10(1), 3-5.
- Morse, J. M. (2003). *A Review Committee's Guide for Evaluating Qualitative Proposals*. *Qualitative Health Research*, 13(6), 833–851. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732303013006005>.

- Morse, J. M., & Mitcham, C. (2002). Exploring qualitatively derived concepts: Inductive- deductive pitfalls. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 1(4), 28–35. Retrieved December 31st, 2009, from <http://ejournals.library.ualberta.ca/index.php/IJQM/index>.
- Morse, J. M., & Richards, L. (2002). *Readme first for a user's guide to qualitative methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Morse, J. M., Hupcey, J. E., Penrod, J., Spiers, J. A., Pooler, C., & Mitcham, C. (2002). "Symposium Conclusion: Issues of validity—Behavioral concepts, their derivation and interpretation". *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 1(4), 68–73.
- Morse, J. M. (2015). Critical analysis of strategies for determining rigor in qualitative inquiry. *Qualitative health research*, 25(9), 1212-1222.
- Mueller, T., Schuldt, D., Sewald, B., Morisse, M., & Petrikina, J. (2013). "Towards inter-organisational ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE management—applicability of TOGAF 9.1 for network organisations." *Proceedings of the 19th Americas Conference on Information Systems*.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., & Van Wyk, B. (2018b). A realist approach to eliciting the initial programme theory of the antiretroviral treatment adherence club intervention in the Western Cape province, South Africa. *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 18(47). DOI: 10.1186/s12874-018-0503-0.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., & Van Wyk, B. (2017b). "Exploring 'generative mechanisms' of the antiretroviral adherence club intervention using the realist approach: a scoping review of research-based antiretroviral treatment adherence theories", *BMC Public Health* 17(1): 385. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-017-4322-8.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., & van Wyk, B. (2018a). Unearthing how, why, for whom, and under what health system conditions the antiretroviral treatment adherence club intervention in South Africa works: a realist theory refining approach. *BMC Health Services Research* 18(1): 343. DOI: 10.1186/s12913-018-3150-6.

- Mukumbang, F. C., Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., & Van Wyk, B. (2018c). 'Patients are not following the [Adherence] club rules anymore': a realist case study of the antiretroviral treatment adherence club, South Africa. *Qualitative Health Research* 18(12): 1839–1857. DOI: 10.1177/1049732318784883.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Marchal, B., Van Belle, S., & van Wyk, B. (2020). 'Using the realist interview approach to maintain theoretical awareness in realist studies', *Qualitative Research*, 20(4), pp. 485–515. DOI: 10.1177/1468794119881985.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Orth, Z., & Van Wyk, B. (2019). What do the implementation outcome variables tell us about the scaling-up of the antiretroviral treatment adherence clubs in South Africa? *Health Research Policy and Systems* 17(1): 28. DOI: 10.1186/s12961-019-0428-z.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Van Belle, S., Marchal, B., & Van Wyk, B. (2016a). A realist evaluation of the antiretroviral treatment adherence club programme in selected primary healthcare facilities in the metropolitan area of Western Cape Province, South Africa: a study protocol. *BMJ Open* 6(4): e009977. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2015-009977.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Van Belle, S., Marchal, B., & Van Wyk, B. (2016b). Towards developing an initial programme theory: programme designers and managers' assumptions on the antiretroviral treatment adherence club programme in primary health care facilities in the metropolitan area of western Cape province, South Africa. *PLoS One* 11(8): e0161790. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0161790.
- Mukumbang, F. C., Van Belle, S., Marchal, B., & Van Wyk, B. (2017a). An exploration of group-based HIV/AIDS treatment and care models in Sub-Saharan Africa using a realist evaluation (Intervention- Context-Actor-Mechanism-Outcome) heuristic tool: a systematic review. *Implementation Sciences* 12: 107. DOI: 10.1186/s13012-017-0638-0.

Mukumbang, F. C., van Wyk, B., Van Belle, S., & Marchal, B. (2019a). Unravelling how and why the Antiretroviral Adherence Club Intervention works (or not) in a public health facility: a realist explanatory theory-building case study. *Plos One*: 1–26. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0210565.

Mukumbang, F. C., van Wyk, B., Van Belle, S., & Marchal, B. (2019b). 'At this [adherence] club, we are a family now': a realist theory-testing case study of the antiretroviral treatment adherence club, South Africa. *Southern African Journal of HIV Medicine* 20(1): 14. DOI: 10.4102/sajhivmed.v20i1.922.

Myers, M. D. (2009). *Qualitative research in business and management*. London: Sage.

Nah, F. F.-H., & Delgado, S. (2006). Critical success factors for enterprise resource planning implementation and upgrade. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 46(5), 99–113.

Nambisan, S., Lyytinen, K., Majchrzak, A., & Song, M. (2017). Digital innovation management: Reinventing innovation management research in a digital world. *MIS Quarterly*, 41(1), 223–238.

National Audit Office (NOA). (2020). The NHS nursing workforce. Accessed online at <<https://www.nao.org.uk/report/nhs-nursing-workforce/>> [Accessed on 26 May 2021].

National Audit Office (NOA). (2020a). Digital transformation in the NHS - Summary, National Audit Office. Available at: <https://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Digital-transformation-in-the-NHS.pdf> [Accessed 10th November 2021].

NHS England. (2023, February 1). NHS Digital and NHS England complete merger. <https://www.england.nhs.uk/2023/02/nhs-digital-and-nhs-england-complete-merger>. (Accessed 30th May 2023).

National Health Service, UK (NHS). (2018). The future of healthcare: our vision for digital, data and technology in health and care. October 2020. Department of Health, UK. Accessed online <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-future-of-healthcare-our-vision-for-digital-data-and-technology-in-health-and-care/the-future-of-healthcare-our-vision-for-digital-data-and-technology-in-health-and-care> [Accessed 24 May 2021].

- Naylor, R. (2017). NHS property and estates: why the estate matters for patients [online]. Available at: www.gov.uk/government/publications/nhs-property-and-estates-Naylor-review [accessed on 19th March 2021].
- Nelson, A. M. (2006). "A meta-synthesis of qualitative breastfeeding studies". *Journal of Midwifery and Women's Health*, 51(2), e13–e20.
- Nesari, M., Naghizadeh, M., Ghazinoori, S., & Manteghi, M. (2022). The evolution of socio-technical transition studies: A scientometric analysis, *Technology in Society*, Volume 68, 2022, 101834, ISSN 0160-791X. doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101834.
- Ng, A. Y. (2004). Feature selection, L1 vs. L2 regularization, and rotational invariance. In *Proceedings of the twenty-first international conference on Machine Learning* (p. 78). [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Ngulube, P., Mathipa, E. R., & Gumbo, M. T. (2015). 'Theoretical and conceptual frameworks in the social and management sciences', *Addressing research challenges: Making headway in developing researchers*, (June), pp. 43–66. DOI 10.13140/RG.2.1.3210.7680.
- NHS Commissioning. (2021). The library note, NHS Commissioning, contains information on how commissioning within the health service in England had been organised prior to the Health and Social Care Act 2012 reforms. Available online at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/commissioning> [20 October 2021].
- NHS Digital. (2017). Fit for 2020. Report from the NHS Digital Capability Review. July 2017 [online]. Available at: <https://apo.org.au/node/196221> [Access Date 06 October 2021]
- NHS Digital. (2021a). Our Organisation Structure: Strategy, policy and Governance. Available at: <https://digital.nhs.uk/about-nhs-digital/our-organisation/our-organisation-structure/strategy-policy-and-governance> [Accessed 10th January 2022].
- NHS Digital. (2021b). Accountability report. <https://digital.nhs.uk/about-nhs-digital/corporate-information-and-documents/nhs-digital-s-annual-reports-and-accounts/nhs-digital-annual-report->

- Nicolini, D., Mengis, J., & Swan, J. (2012). "Understanding the Role of Objects in Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration." *Organization Science*, 23(3), 612-629.
- Nielsen, S. B., Lemire, S., & Tangsig, S. (2022). 'Unpacking context in realist evaluations: Findings from a comprehensive review', *Evaluation*, 28(1), pp. 91–112. DOI: 10.1177/13563890211053032.
- Niemi, E., & Pekkola, S. (2017). The Benefits of Enterprise Architecture in Organizational Transformation. *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, 62(6), 585–597. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-019-00605-3>.
- Nikpay, F., Ahmad, R. B., Rouhani, B. D., Mahrin, M. N. R., & Shamshirband, S. (2017). An effective enterprise architecture implementation methodology. *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, 15(4), 927-962.
- Nikpay, F., Selamat, H., Rouhani, B. D., & Nikfard, P. (2013). "A Review of Critical Success Factors of Enterprise Architecture Implementation". In *Proceedings of the 2013 International Conference of Informatics and Creative Multimedia*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 4–6 September; pp. 38–42.
- Noblit, G. W., & Hare, R. W. (1988). *Meta-ethnography: Synthesising qualitative studies*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Norman, D. A., & Stappers, P. J. (2015). DesignX: complex sociotechnical systems. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 1(2), 83-106.
- Nurjono, M., Shrestha, R., Lee, A., Lim, X. Y., Shiraz, F., & Tan, S., & ... (2018). A realist evaluation of a complex integrated care programme: protocol for a mixed-methods study *BMJ Open*;8:e017111. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-017111.
- Nworie, J. (2011). Using the Delphi technique in educational technology research. *TechTrends*, 55(5), 24-30.

- Obermeyer, Z., Powers, B., Vogeli, C., & Mullainathan, S. (2019). Dissecting racial bias in an algorithm used to manage the health of populations. *Science*, 366(6464), 447-453.
- Obitz, T., & Babu, K. M. (2009). "Enterprise Architecture Expands its Role in Strategic Business Transformation: Infosys Enterprise Architecture Survey 2008/2009", Survey, Infosys, <http://www.infosys.com/offerings/IT-services/architecture-services/ea-survey/Pages/index.aspx> (Accessed 20 June 2021).
- Öbrand, L., Augustsson, N., Mathiassen, L., & Holmström, J. (2019). The interstitiality of IT risk: An inquiry into information systems development practices. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(1), 97–118.
- Olsen, D. H. (2017). 'Enterprise Architecture management challenges in the Norwegian health sector', *Procedia Computer Science*. Elsevier B.V., 121, pp. 637–645. DOI: 10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.084.
- Olsen, W. (2010). Editor's Introduction: Realist Methodology - A Review. Edited by W. Olsen. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Oppenheim, A. N. (1992). *Questionnaire Design, Interviewing and Attitude Measurement*, London: Printer Publishers.
- Orbus Software. (n.d.). Preliminary phase: Defining how we do architecture in your enterprise. Available at: <https://www.orbussoftware.com/enterprise-architecture/togaf/what-is-the-adm/preliminary-phase/> [Accessed 18 June 2019].
- Orlikowski, W. J. (1992). The duality of technology: Rethinking the concept of technology in organizations. *Organization Science*, 3(3), 398–427.
- Orlikowski, W. J. (1993). CASE tools as organisational change: Investigating incremental and radical changes in systems development. *MIS Quarterly*, 17, 309–340.

- Orlikowski, W. J., & Scott, S. V. (2008). "Sociomateriality: Challenging the Separation of Technology, Work and Organization". *The Academy of Management Annals*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 433–474, Jan.
- Orlikowski, W. J., & Scott, S. V. (2015). The Algorithm and the Crowd: Considering the Materiality of Service Innovation. *MIS Quarterly*, 39(1), 201-216.
- Ose, S. O. (2016). Using Excel and Word to structure qualitative data. *Journal of Applied Social Science*, 10(2), 147-162.
- Ostrom, A. L., Parasuraman, A., Bowen, D. E., Patricio, L., & Voss, C. A. (2015). Service research priorities in a rapidly changing context. *Journal of Service Research*, 18(2), 127-159.
- Otto, B. (2012). How to design the master data architecture: Findings from a case study at Bosch. *International Journal of Information Management*, 32(4), 337–346.
- Palmquist, M. E., Carley, K. M., & Dale, T. A. (1997). "Two applications of automated text analysis". *Analysing literary and non-literary texts*. In C. W. Roberts (Ed.), *Text analysis for the social sciences: Methods for drawing statistical inferences from texts and transcripts* (pp. 171–190). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Pan, S., & Yang, Q. (2010). A survey on transfer learning. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 22(10), 1345-1359. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Pang, B., & Lee, L. (2008). Opinion mining and sentiment analysis. *Foundations and Trends® in Information Retrieval*, 2(1-2), 1-135.
- Pang, B., & Lee, L. (2016). Opinion mining and sentiment analysis. *Foundations and Trends® in Information Retrieval*, 2(1-2), 1-135. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Pang, Z., Yang, G., Khedri, R. R., & Zhang, Y. T. (2018). "Introduction to the Special Section: Convergence of Automation Technology, Biomedical Engineering, and Health Informatics Toward the Healthcare 4.0," in *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 11, pp. 249-259, DOI: 10.1109/RBME.2018.2848518.

- Parviainen, P., Tihinen, M., Kääriäinen, J., & Teppola, S. (2017). Tackling the digitalization challenge: How to benefit from digitalization in practice. *International Journal of Information Systems and Project Management*, 5(1), 63-77.
- Pasaribu, F. A., Hakiki, J. S., Situmorang, B. P., Sfenrianto, S., & Kaburuan, E. R. (2019). 'Designing Enterprise Architecture in Hospitals Group', in 2019 International Conference on Information and Communications Technology (ICOIACT)', IEEE, pp. 862–867. DOI: 10.1109/ICOIACT46704.2019.8938526.
- Pascot, D., Bouslama, F., & Mellouli, S. (2011). Architecturing large integrated complex information systems: an application to healthcare. *Knowl Inf Syst* 27, 115–140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-010-0292-1>.
- Patel, V. L., Shortliffe, E. H., Stefanelli, M., Szolovits, P., Berthold, M. R., Bellazzi, R., & Abu-Hanna, A. (2009). The coming of age of artificial intelligence in medicine. *Artif Intell Med*. 46(1):5-17. doi:10.1016/j.artmed.2008.07.017.
- Paterson, B., Dubouloz, C. J., Chevrier, J., Ashe, B., King, J., & Moldoveanu, M. (2009). "Conducting qualitative metasynthesis research: Insights from a metasynthesis project".
- Patton, M. Q. (2002a). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002b). Two Decades of Developments in Qualitative Inquiry: A Personal, Experiential Perspective. *Qualitative Social Work*, 1(3), 261–283. doi.org/10.1177/1473325002001003636.
- Patton, M. Q. (2023). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. Sage publications.
- Pawson, R. (1989). *A Measure for Measures: A Manifesto for Empirical Sociology*, London: Routledge.

- Pawson, R. (1996). Theorizing the interview. *The British Journal of Sociology* 47(2): 295–314.
Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/591728>. [Date Accessed: 12 June 2020].
- Pawson, R. (2002a). Evidence-based policy: In search of a method. *Evaluation*, 8, 157-181.
- Pawson, R. (2002b). Evidence-based policy: The Promise of 'Realist Synthesis'. *Evaluation*, 8(3), 340-358. doi:10.1177/135638902401462448.
- Pawson, R. (2006). *Evidence-Based Policy: A Realist Perspective*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publication.
- Pawson, R. (2013). *The Science of Evaluation: A Realist Manifesto*. London: Sage Publications.
- Pawson, R., & Manzano-Santaella, A. (2012). A realist diagnostic workshop. *Evaluation*.18:176–91.
- Pawson, R., & Sridharan, S. (2009). Theory-driven evaluation of public health programmes. In Killoran A and Kelly MP (eds) *evidence-Based Public health*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 43–62. Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199563623.003.04>.
- Pawson, R., & Tilley, N. (1997). *Realistic Evaluation*. London, Thousand Oaks, CA, and New Delhi. Sage.
- Pawson, R., & Tilley, N. (2004). Realist evaluation. Available at: http://www.communitymatters.com.au/RE_chapter.pdf.
- Pawson, R., & Tilley, N. (2008). *Realistic evaluation*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Pawson, R., Greenhalgh, T., Harvey, G., & Walshe, K. (2005). Realist review – a new method of systematic review designed for complex policy interventions. *Journal of Health Services Research and Policy* 10(S1): 21–34.
- Pawson, R., Walshe, K., & Greenhalgh, T. (2004). Realist synthesis: an introduction.
- Pedersen, E. R., & Kurz, J. (2016). Using Facebook for health-related research study recruitment and program delivery. *Current opinion in psychology*, 9, 38-43.

- Pennington, J., Socher, R., & Manning, C. D. (2014). Glove: Global vectors for word representation. In Proceedings of the 2014 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing (EMNLP) (pp. 1532-1543). Retrieved from <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/D14-1162/>.
- Perez, L., & Wang, J. (2017). The effectiveness of data augmentation in image classification using deep learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.04621. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Peristeras, V., & Tarabanis, K. (2000). Towards an Enterprise Architecture for public administration using a top-down approach. *Eur J Inf Syst* 9, 252–260. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.ejis.3000378>.
- Perks, C., & Beveridge, T. (2003). Guide to enterprise IT architecture. New York, NY: Springer.
- Peterson, R. (2004). Crafting information technology governance. *Information Systems Management* 21 (4), 7–22.
- Petrakaki, D., Klecun, E., & Cornford, T. (2016). ‘Changes in healthcare professional work afforded by technology: The introduction of a national electronic patient record in an English hospital’, *Organization*, 23(2), pp. 206–226. DOI: 10.1177/1350508414545907.
- Pettigrew, A. M. (1987). Context and action in the transformation of the firm. *Journal of Management Studies*, 24(6), 649–670.
- Plous, S. (1993). The psychology of judgment and decision making. McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Popper, K. R. (1959). The propensity interpretation of probability. *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 10(37), 25-42.
- Porpora, D. V. (1998). Four concepts of social structure. In M. S. Archer, R. Bhaskar, A. Collier, T. Lawson, & A. Norrie (Eds.), *Critical realism: Essential readings*. London: Routledge.
- Pouloudi, N., Currie, W., & Whitley, E. A. (2016). "Entangled Stakeholder Roles and Perceptions in Health Information Systems: A Longitudinal Study of the UK NHS N3 Network." *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 17: Iss. 2, Article 1. DOI: 10.17705/1jais.00421.

Powell, T. (2020). The structure of the NHS in England (CBP07206). House Briefing Paper. of Commons Library, UK. June 2020.

Powell, T., & Thompson, G. (2010). 'Electronic Patient Records: the roll-out of the Summary Care Record'. House of Commons Library.

Power, J., Gilmore, B., Vallières, F., Toomey, E., Mannan, H., & McAuliffe, E. (2019). Adapting health interventions for local fit when scaling-up: A realist review protocol. *BMJ Open*, 9, e022084.

Prahalad, C. K., & Krishnan, M. S. (2002). "The dynamic synchronisation of strategy and information technology," *MIT Sloan Management Review*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 24–33.

Prashanth, N. S., Marchal, B., Devadasan, N., Kegels, G., & Criel, B. (2014). Advancing the application of systems thinking in health: A realist evaluation of a capacity-building programme for district managers in Tumkur, India. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 12, 42.

Price, C., Green, W., & Suhomlinova, O. (2019). Twenty-five years of national health IT: exploring strategy, structure, and systems in the English NHS. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association. JAMIA*. 26 (3), pp. 188–197.

Price, W. N. (2020). Artificial intelligence in health care: Anticipating challenges and opportunities. *California Law Review*, 108(3), 615-665.

Provost, F., & Fawcett, T. (2013). *Data Science for Business: What you need to know about data mining and data-analytic thinking*. O'Reilly Media, Inc. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Public Accounts Committee. (2013). The dismantled National Programme for IT in the NHS. Nineteenth Report of the Session. 2013–14. London: The Stationery Office.

Puron-Cid, G. (2013). Interdisciplinary application of structuration theory for e-government: a case study of IT-enabled budget reform. *Gov Inf Q*. 30: S46–S58. 10.1016/j.giq.2012.07.010

Puspitasari, I. (2016, June). Stakeholder's expected value of Enterprise Architecture: An Enterprise Architecture solution based on stakeholder perspective. In 2016 IEEE 14th International Conference on Software Engineering Research, Management and Applications (SERA) (pp. 243-248). IEEE.

Quaadgras, A., Weill, P., & Ross, J. W. (2014). 'Management Commitments that Maximize Business Impact from IT', *Journal of Information Technology*, 29(2), pp. 114–127. Doi: 10.1057/jit.2014.7.

Radford, A., Wu, J., Child, R., Luan, D., Amodei, D., & Sutskever, I. (2019). Language Models are Unsupervised Multitask Learners. OpenAI Blog. . [Accessed: 20th May 2023].https://d4mucfpksywv.cloudfront.net/better-language-models/language_models_are_unsupervised_multitask_learners.pdf. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Raja, J. Z., Bourne, D., Goffin, K., Çakkol, M., & Martinez, V. (2013). Achieving customer satisfaction through integrated products and services: An exploratory study. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 30(6), 1128-1144.

Ranmuthugala, G., Cunningham, F. C., Plumb, J. J., Long, J., Georgiou, A., Westbrook, J. I., & Braithwaite, J. (2011). A realist evaluation of the role of communities of practice in changing healthcare practice. *Implementation Science*, 6, 49. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-6-49.

Ravi, K., & Ravi, V. (2015). A survey on opinion mining and sentiment analysis: Tasks, approaches and applications. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 89, 14-46. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Richardson, G. L., Jackson, B. M., & Dickson, G. W. (1990). "A Principle-Based Enterprise Architecture: Lessons from Texaco and Star Enterprise," *MIS Quarterly* (14:4), pp. 385-403.

Repko, A. F., Szostak, R., & Buchberger, M. P. (2019). *Introduction to Interdisciplinary Studies*. Sage Publications.

Roberts, J. M. (2014). Critical realism, dialectics, and qualitative research methods. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 44(1), pp.1-23.

Robey, D., Ross, J. W., & Boudreau, M.-C. (2002). Learning to implement enterprise systems: An exploratory study of the dialectics of change. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 19(1), 17–46.

- Robson, C. (2011). *Real-world research: A resource for social scientists and practitioner-researchers*.
- Roelens, B., & Poels, G. (2014). The creation of business architecture heat maps to support strategy-aligned organizational decisions. In: 8th European Conference on IS Management and Evaluation (ECIME). Academic Conferences and Publishing International Limited, pp. 388–392.
- Roese, N. J. (1997). Counterfactual thinking. *Psychology Bulletin* 121(1): 133–148.
- Röglinger, M., Bolsinger, M., Haeckel, B., & Walter, M. (2016). How to structure business transformation projects: the case of Infineon's finance IT roadmap, *J. Inf. Technol. Theory Appl. (JITTA)* 17 (2).
- Rokach, L. (2010). Ensemble-based classifiers. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 33(1-2), 1-39.
- Rokach, L., & Maimon, O. (2015). *Data mining with decision trees: theory and applications*. World Scientific. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Rolland, K., Mathiassen, L., & Rai, A. (2018). Managing digital platforms in user organizations: The interactions between digital options and digital debt. *Information Systems Research*, 29(2), 419–443.
- Rood, M. A. (1994). Enterprise Architecture: Definitions, Tools, and Models. *Information Systems Management*, 11(2), 50-56.
- Ross, J. W., Weill, P., & Robertson, D. C. (2006). *Enterprise Architecture as Strategy*. Creating a Foundation for Business Execution, Harvard Business School Press, 411–431.
- Rubin, H. J., & Rubin, I. S. (2011). *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data*. Sage.
- Ruder, S., Peters, M. E., Swayamdipta, S., & Wolf, T. (2019). Transfer Learning in Natural Language Processing. In *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Tutorials* (pp. 15-18). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/n19-5004>.

- Ryan, G. W. (2004). Using a Word Processor to Tag and Retrieve Blocks of Text. *Field Methods*, 16(1):109-130. doi:10.1177/1525822X03261269.
- Rycroft-Malone, J., Burton, C. R., Wilkinson, J., Harvey, G., McCormack, B., Baker, R., & Thompson, C. (2016). Collective action for implementation: A realist evaluation of organisational collaboration in healthcare. *Implementation Science*, 11, 17.
- Saat, J., Franke, U., Lagerström, R., & Ekstedt, M. (2010). "Enterprise Architecture Meta Models for IT/Business Alignment Situations," 2010 14th IEEE International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Conference, pp. 14-23, DOI: 10.1109/EDOC.2010.17.
- Sager, F. (2007). Making transport policy work: Polity, policy, politics, and systematic review: *Policy and Politics*, 35, 269-288.
- Sager, F. (2008). Planning, power, and policy change in the networked city: The politics of a new tramway in the city of Bern. In G. Pflieger, L. Pattaroni, C. Jemelin, and V. Kaufmann (Eds.), *The social fabric of the networked city* (p.169-187). Lausanne and Oxford. EPFL Press/Routledge.
- Sager, F., & Andereggen, C. (2012). Dealing with Complex Causality in Realist Synthesis: The Promise of Qualitative Comparative Analysis, *American Journal of Evaluation*, 33 (1), 60-78.
- Saha, P. (2018). *Enterprise Architecture for Connected E-Government: Practices and Innovations*. IGI Global.
- Saint-Louis, P., & Lapalme, J. (2018). 'An exploration of the many ways to approach the discipline of Enterprise Architecture'. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*. SAGE Publications Inc., 10, p. 184797901880738. DOI: 10.1177/1847979018807383.
- Salter, K. L., & Kothari, A. (2014). Using realist evaluation to open the black box of knowledge translation: a state-of-the-art review. *Implementation Science* 9(1): 1–14. DOI: 10.1186/s13012-014-0115-y.

- Sandelowski, M. (1993). "Rigor or rigor mortis: the problem of rigor in qualitative research revisited". *ANS. Advances in Nursing Science*. Dec;16(2):1-8. DOI: 10.1097/00012272-199312000-00002. PMID: 8311428.
- Sandelowski, M. (1995). Sample size in qualitative research. *Research in Nursing and Health*, 18(1), 179–183. doi.org/10.1002/nur.4770180211.
- Sandelowski, M., & Leeman, J. (2012). "Writing usable qualitative health research findings". *Qualitative Health Research*, 22(10), 1404-1413.
- Sandelowski, M., Docherty, S., & Emden, C. (1997). Qualitative metasynthesis: Issues and techniques. *Research in Nursing and Health*, 20, 365– 371.
- Saunders, B., Kitzinger, J., & Kitzinger, C. (2015). 'Anonymising interview data: challenges and compromise in practice', *Qualitative Research*, 15(5), pp. 616–632. DOI: 10.1177/1468794114550439.
- Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2016). *Research methods for business students*. Seventh edn. Harlow: Pearson. Available at: www.pearson.com/uk.
- Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students*. 8th Edition. London: Pearson.
- Savedoff, W. D. (2004). Is there a case for social insurance? *Health Policy and Planning*, 19(3), 183-184.
- Sayer, A. (1984). "Method in Social Science: A Realist Approach", London: Routledge.
- Sayer, A. (1992). *Methods in Social Science a Realist approach* (2nd ed.).
- Sayer, A. (2000). *Realism and Social Science*. London: Sage.
- Sayer, A. (2011). *Why things matter to people: Social science, values and ethical life*. Cambridge University Press.
- Schein, E. H. 1992). *Organizational Culture and Leadership*. 2nd ed. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Schiffers, M. (2003). Quality of context: What it is and why we need it. Proceedings of the Workshop of the HP OpenView University Association. Available at https://www.academia.edu/24757454/Quality_of_context_What_it_is_and_why_we_need_it?auto=citationsandfrom=cover_page [Accessed on: 12 December 2021].

Schilling, R. (2020). Enterprise Architecture Complexity: Implications for the Portfolio of Control Mechanisms. The University of St. Gallen.

Schilling, R. D., Haki, K., & Aier, S. (2018). Dynamics of Control Mechanisms in Enterprise Architecture Management: A Sensemaking Perspective.

Schmarzo, B. (2017). "What is Digital Transformation?". Available at <https://www.cio.com/article/230121/what-is-digital-transformation-2.html> [Accessed 3 January 2022].

Schmidhuber, J. (2015). Deep learning in neural networks: An overview. *Neural Networks*, 61, 85-117. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Schmidt, C., & Buxmann, P. (2011). Outcomes and success factors of enterprise IT architecture management: empirical insight from the international financial services industry, *Eur. J. Inf. Syst.* 20 (2) (2011) 168–185.

Schneider, C. Q., & Wagemann, C. (2007). *Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) und Fuzzy Sets: Ein Lehrbuch für Anwender und jene, die es werden wollen*. Barbara Budrich.

Scott, S. V., Zachariadis, M., & Barrett, M. (2013). Methodological implications of critical realism for mixed-methods research. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems* 37(3): 855–879.

Scribbr. (2020). Sample Theoretical Framework of a Dissertation or Thesis. Available at <https://www.scribbr.com/dissertation/theoretical-framework-example/> [Accessed 20 September 2021].

- Seppanen, V., Heikkila, J., & Liimatainen, K. (2009). "Key issues in Enterprise Architecture-implementation: a case study of two Finnish government agencies". Paper presented at the 11th IEEE Conference on Commerce and enterprise computing, Vienna.
- Settles, B. (2012). Active learning. *Synthesis Lectures on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*, 6(1), 1-114. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Shanks, G., Gloet, M., Someh, I. A., Frampton, K., & Tamm, T. (2018). 'Achieving benefits with enterprise architecture', *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*. Elsevier BV, 27(2), pp. 139–156. DOI: 10.1016/j.jsis.2018.03.001.
- Shanks, G., Parr, A., Hu, B., Corbitt, B., Thanasankit, T., & Seddon, P. (2000). Differences in critical success factors in ERP systems implementation in Australia and China: a cultural analysis. In *Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Information Systems*. Vienna, Austria.
- Sharpe, G. (2011). A review of program theory and theory-based evaluations. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research* 1(3): 72–75.
- Shorten, C., & Khoshgoftaar, T. M. (2019). A survey on Image Data Augmentation for Deep Learning. *Journal of Big Data*, 6(1), 60. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Shpilberg, D., Berez, S., Puryear, R., & Shah, S. (2007). "Avoiding the Alignment Trap in IT". *MIT Sloan Management Review*, October 1, 2007. Available at: <https://sloanreview.mit.edu/article/avoiding-the-alignment-trap-in-it/>. Accessed August 15, 2020.
- Sidorova, A., & Kappelman, L. A. (2011). Better Business-IT Alignment Through Enterprise Architecture: An Actor-Network Theory Perspective *Enterprise Architecture*. Available at: www.aejournal.org.
- Silverman, D. (1989). *Qualitative Methodology and Sociology*. Aldershot: Gower Publishing.
- Simon, D., Fischbach, K., & Schoder, D. (2013). An exploration of enterprise architecture research. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 32(1), 1.

- Simons, H. (2004). Utilising evaluation evidence to enhance professional practice. *Evaluation*, 10, 410-429.
- Simons, H. (2009). *Qualitative data analysis: A sourcebook*. London: SAGE.
- Sivarajah, U., Kamal, M. M., Irani, Z., & Weerakkody, V. (2017). Critical analysis of Big Data challenges and analytical methods. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, 263-286. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Smith, R. (2006). Peer review: a flawed process at the heart of science and journals. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 99(4), 178–182. <https://doi.org/10.1258/jrsm.99.4.178>.
- Smolander, K., & Päivärinta, T. (2002). Describing and Communicating Software Architecture in Practice: Observations on Stakeholders and Rationale. In: Banks Pidduck, A. et al. (Eds.), *CAISE*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 117–133.
- Snoek, J., Larochelle, H., & Adams, R. P. (2012). Practical Bayesian optimization of machine learning algorithms. In *Advances in neural information processing systems* (pp. 2951-2959). [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Sobh, R., & Perry, C. (2006). Research design and data analysis in realism research. *European Journal of Marketing* 40(11–12): 1194–1209. DOI: 10.1108/03090560610702777.
- Sorinola, O. O., Thistlethwaite, J., Davies, D., & Peile, E. (2017). “Realist evaluation of faculty development for medical educators: What works for whom and why in the long-term”. *Medical Teacher* 39(4): 422–9.
- Sousa, J. L. R., & Machado, R. J. (2014). 'Sociomaterial Enactment Drive of Business/IT Alignment: From Small Data to Big Impact', *Procedia Technology*. Elsevier BV, 16, pp. 569–582. DOI: 10.1016/j.protcy.2014.10.005.
- Spewak, S. H., & Hill, S. C. (1992). *Enterprise Architecture Planning: Developing a Blueprint for Data, Applications, and Technology*, Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley and Sons.

- Stake, R. E., & Schwandt, T. A. (2006). On discerning quality in evaluation. *The Sage Handbook of Evaluation*, 404-418.
- Stanley, B. G. (2010). 'Why Doesn't the Federal Enterprise Architecture Work?', *Technology Matters, Inc.*
- Stieger, S., & Goritz, A. S. (2006). 'Using instant messaging for internet-based interviews', *CyberPsychology and Behavior*, Vol. 9, No. 5, pp. 552–9.
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1990). *Basics of qualitative research: Grounded theory procedures and techniques*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Sutton, R. S., & Barto, A. G. (2018). *Reinforcement learning: An introduction*. MIT Press. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Svee, E. O., & Zdravkovic, J. (2015). Extending Enterprise Architectures to capture consumer values: The Case of TOGAF. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering Workshops*. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-19243-7_22.
- Sykes, B. L., Verma, A., & Hancock, B. H. (2018). Aligning sampling and case selection in quantitative-qualitative research designs: Establishing generalizability limits in mixed-method studies. *Ethnography*, 19(2), 227–253. doi.org/10.1177/1466138117725341.
- TAFIM. (1996a). *Department of defence technical architecture framework for information management, volume 2: Technical reference model (version 3.0)*. Arlington County, VA: Defense Information Systems Agency.
- Tamm, T., Peter, B. S., Shanks, G., Reynolds, P., & Frampton, K. M. (2015). How an Australian retailer enabled business transformation through Enterprise Architecture, *MIS Q. Executive*. 14 (4) 181–193. Publisher: Indiana University Operations and Decision Technologies Department.
- Tamm, T., Seddon, P. B., Shanks, G., & Reynolds, P. (2011). "How Does Enterprise Architecture Add Value to Organisations?" *Commun. Assoc. Inf. Syst.*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 141–168.

Tavory, I., & Timmermans, S. (2014). *Abductive analysis: Theorizing qualitative research*. University of Chicago Press.

Teece, D. J. (2010). *Handbook of the Economics of Innovation*, Vol. 1.

Teece, D. J. (2014). *The Foundations of Enterprise Performance: Dynamic and Ordinary Capabilities in an (Economic) Theory of Firms*. Available Online at <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2013.0116> [Accessed 20 December 2021].

Teo, H. H., Wei, K. K., & Benbasat, I. (2003). Predicting intention to adopt interorganizational linkages: An institutional perspective. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(1), 19–49.

The Commons Library. (2020). *Insight: "The health and social care workforce gap"*. Available online at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/the-health-and-social-care-workforce-gap/> Accessed on 26 May 2021.

The Interim NHS People Plan. (2019). Accessed online at: https://www.longtermplan.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Interim-NHS-People-Plan_June2019.pdf.

The Open Group. (2001). *The Business Executive's Guide to IT Architecture*. Available at: <http://www.opengroup.org/public/arch/p1/oview/index.htm> [Accessed: August 22, 2020].

The Open Group. (2001b). *The Role of Case Studies*. Available at: http://www.opengroup.org/public/arch/p4/cases/case_intro.htm#NHS. Accessed Date: 6th October 2020].

The Open Group. (2011). *Architecture Deliverables*. Available at <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/togaf91-doc/arch/chap36.html> [Accessed on 11 September 2021].

The Open Group. (2018). *The TOGAF Standard, Version 9.2*. Retrieved from <http://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/togaf9-doc/arch/index.html> [Accessed on August 5, 2020].

The Open Group. (2019). Welcome to Archimate 3.1 Specification, a standard of The Open Group. Available at <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate3-doc/chap14.html> [Accessed 1 January 2022].

The Open Group. (n.d.). The Role of Case Studies. Available at http://www.opengroup.org/public/arch/p4/cases/case_intro.htm [Accessed 10 January 2022].

Thompson, M. (1979). *Rubbish Theory*, London: Routledge.

Tibshirani, R. (1996). Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 58(1), 267-288. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Tietze, S. (2012). "Researching your own organization", in G. Symon and C. Cassell (eds) *Qualitative Organisational Research Core Methods and Current Challenges*. London: Sage, pp. 53–71.

Tilley, N. (1993). *Understanding Car Parks, Crime, and CCTV: Evaluation Lessons from Safer Cities*. Police Research Group Crime Prevention Unit Series Paper No. 42. London: Home Office Police Department.

Tilley, N. (2000). *Realistic Evaluation: An Overview*. The Founding Conference of the Danish Evaluation Society. URL: http://evidence-basedmanagement.com/wp-content/uploads/2011/11/nick_tilley.pdf (accessed 2 October 2015).

Tilson, D., Lyytinen, K., & Sørensen, C. (2010). "Desperately seeking the infrastructure in IS research: Conceptualization of digital convergence as co-evolution of social and technical infrastructures". Paper presented at the HICSS 43, Kauai, HI.

Timmins, P., & Miller, C. (2007). *Making evaluations realistic: the challenge of complexity*. *Support Learn*;22:9–16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9604.2007.00439.x>

TOGAF. (2018). *TOGAF Version 9.2*. Van Haren Publishing.

Tolson, D., McIntosh, J., Loftus, L., & Cormie, P. (2007). Developing a managed clinical network in palliative care: a realistic evaluation. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 44, 183–195.

- Toomela, A. (2009). "How methodology became a toolbox - and how it escapes from that box," in *Dynamic Process Methodology in the Social and Developmental Sciences*, eds J. Valsiner, P. Molenaar, M. Lyra and N. Chaudhary (New York: Springer), pp. 45–66.
- Toomela, A. (2010). 'Quantitative methods in psychology: Inevitable and useless', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 1(JUL), pp. 1–14. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2010.00029.
- Tracy, S. J. (2010). "Qualitative Quality: Eight "Big-Tent" Criteria for Excellent Qualitative Research." *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(10), 837–851.
- Treib, O., Bähr, H., & Falkner, G. (2007). Modes of governance: towards a conceptual clarification. *Journal of European public policy*, 14(1), 1-20.
- Triggle, N. (2022). "BBC News: Government overseen years of decline in NHS – MPs". *Health*. Available at <https://www.bbc.com/news/health-60754227?piano-modal> [Accessed 10th January 2022].
- Trist, E., & Bamforth, K. (1951). Some social and psychological consequences of the long wall method of coal-getting. *Human Relations*, 4(1), 3–38.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/001872675100400101>.
- Tsang, E. W. (2014). Case studies and generalisation in information systems research: A critical realist perspective. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 23(2), pp. 174-186.
- Urbaczewski, L., & Mrdalj, S. (2006). A comparison of Enterprise Architecture frameworks. *Issues in Information Systems*, 7(2), pp. 18 – 23. Available at:
http://ggatz.com/images/SOA_COMPARE.pdf [Accessed August 15, 2020].
- Vaidyam, A. N., Wisniewski, H., Halamka, J. D., Kashavan, M. S., & Torous, J. B. (2019). Chatbots and Conversational Agents in Mental Health: A Review of the Psychiatric Landscape. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 64(7), 456–464. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

- Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H., & Bondas, T. (2013). “Content analysis and thematic analysis: Implications for conducting a qualitative descriptive study”, *Nursing and Health Sciences*, 15(3), pp. 398–405. Doi: 10.1111/nhs.12048.
- Vallerand, J., Lapalme, J., & Moïse, A. (2017). ‘Analysing enterprise architecture maturity models: a learning perspective’, *Enterprise Information Systems*. Taylor and Francis Ltd., 11(6), pp. 859–883. DOI: 10.1080/17517575.2015.1091951.
- van de Wetering, R., Kurnia, S., & Kotusev, S. (2021). ‘The Role of Enterprise Architecture for Digital Transformations’, *Sustainability*, 13(4), p. 2237. Doi: 10.3390/su13042237.
- van den Berg, M., Slot, R., van Steenberghe, M., Faasse, P., & van Vliet, H. (2019). “How enterprise architecture improves the quality of IT investment decisions”, *Journal of Systems and Software*. Elsevier Inc., 152, pp. 134–150. DOI: 10.1016/j.jss.2019.02.053.
- Van der Knaap, L. M., Leeuw, F., Bogaerts, S., & Nijssen, L. T. J. (2008). Combining Campbell standards and the realist evaluation. The best of two worlds? *American Journal of Evaluation*, 29, 48-57.
- Van Der Raadt, B., Bonnet, M., Schouten, S., & Van Vliet, H. (2010). ‘The relation between Enterprise Architecture effectiveness and stakeholder satisfaction. *Journal of Systems and Software*. 83(10), pp. 1954–1969. DOI: 10.1016/j.jss.2010.05.076.
- van der Raadt, B., Schouten, S., & van Vliet, H. (2008). Stakeholder Perception of Enterprise Architecture. In: Morrison R., Balasubramaniam D., Falkner K. (eds) *Software Architecture*. ECSCA 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 5292. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-88030-1_4.
- van Velthoven, M. H., Cordon, C., & Challagalla, G. (2019). ‘Digitization of healthcare organizations: The digital health landscape and information theory’, *International Journal of Medical Informatics*. Elsevier, 124(January), pp. 49–57. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2019.01.007.

- Vargas, A., Boza, A., Patel, S., Patel, D., Cuenca, L., & Ortiz, A. (2016). Inter-enterprise architecture as a tool to empower decision-making in hierarchical collaborative production planning. *Data & Knowledge Engineering*, 105, 5-22.
- Vasileiou, K., Barnett, J., Thorpe, S., & Young, T. (2018). Characterising and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1). doi:10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7.
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., ... & Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. In *Advances in neural information processing systems* (pp. 5998-6008). Retrieved from <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/2017/hash/3f5ee243547dee91fbd053c1c4a845aa-Abstract.html>.
- Vatandsoost, M., & Litkouhi, S. (2019). 'The Future of Healthcare Facilities: How Technology and Medical Advances May Shape Hospitals of the Future', *Hospital Practices and Research*, 4(1), pp. 1–11. DOI: 10.15171/hpr.2019.01.
- Veltman-Van Reekum, E., van Steenbergen, M., van den Berg, M., Bos, R., & Brinkkemper, S. (2006). An instrument for measuring the quality of Enterprise Architecture products. Ingediend voor publicatie bij het Landelijk Architectuur Congres.
- Verstegen, I. (2006). A critical realist perspective on aesthetic value. *Journal of Critical Realism*, 5(2), pp.323-343.
- Vessey, I., & Ward, K. (2013). "The Dynamics of Sustainable IS Alignment: The Case for IS Adaptivity," *Journal of the Association for Information Systems* (14:6), pp. 283-311.
- Vial, G. (2021). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *Managing Digital Transformation*, 13-66.
- Villejoubert, G., & Mandel, D. R. (2002). The inverse fallacy: An account of deviations from Bayes's theorem and the additivity principle. *Mem Cogn* 30, 171–178. Available at <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03195278> [Accessed 12 November 2021].

- Wagter, R., Van den Berg, M., Luijpers, J., & van Steenberg, M. (2005). *Dynamic Enterprise Architecture: How to Make It Work*. John Wiley and Sons.
- Walsham, G. (1995). Interpretive case studies in IS research: Nature and method. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 4 (2), 74–81.
- Walshe, K., Rundall, T. G., & Shortell, S. M. (2011). Evidence-based management: From theory to practice in health care. *The Milbank Quarterly*, 79(3), 429-457. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Wand, Y., & Weber, R. (1995). On the deep structure of information systems. *Information Systems Journal*, 5(3), 203–223.
- Wang, G., Kalra, M., & Orton, C. G. (2017). “Machine learning will transform radiology significantly within the next five years”. *Med Phys*. 44(6):2041-2044. doi:10.1002/mp.12204.
- Wang, P. (2008). Assimilating IT innovation: The longitudinal effects of institutionalization and resource dependence. *ICIS 2008 Proceedings*.
- Weill, P. (2007). *Innovating in Information Systems: What do the most agile firms in the world do?* Sixth e-Business Conference, Barcelona, Spain. Available at: [http://www.scirp.org/\(S\(i43dyn45teexjx455qlt3d2q\)\)/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=382108110](http://www.scirp.org/(S(i43dyn45teexjx455qlt3d2q))/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=382108110) [Accessed 10 December 2021].
- Weiss, C. H. (1997). *Theory-based evaluation: Past, present, and future. New directions for evaluation*. (No. 76). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Wenger, E. (1998). "Communities of Practice: Learning as a Social System", *Systems Thinker*.
- Wenzel, L., & Evans, H. (2019). Clicks and mortar. *Technology and the NHS estate*". Available at <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk › Publications> [Accessed 10th December 2022].
- Wessel, L., Baiyere, A., Ologeanu-Taddei, R., Cha, J., & Jensen, T. (2020). Unpacking the difference between digital transformation and IT-enabled organizational transformation. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems* (Forthcoming).

- Westerman, G., Calmejane, C., Bonnet, D., Ferraris, P., and McAfee, A. (2011). "Digital Transformation: A Roadmap for Billion-Dollar Organizations," MIT Center for Digital Business and Capgemini Consulting, Consulting.
- Westhorp, G. (2014). Realist impact evaluation: an introduction. Research and Policy Development (September). London: Overseas Development Institute.
- Westhorp, G., Prins, E., Kusters, C., Hultink, M., Guijt, I., & Brouwers, J. (2011). Realist Evaluation: An Overview. Report from an Expert Seminar. Wageningen: Wageningen UR Centre for Development Innovation.
- Williams, L. (2013). What Works? A Realist Evaluation of the Role of Intermediaries in Promoting Best Practice in Infection Prevention and Control. Bangor: Bangor University.
- Williams, L., Rycroft-Malone, J., & Burton, C. R. (2017). Bringing critical realism to nursing practice: Roy Bhaskar's contribution. *Nursing Philosophy* 18(2): e12130. DOI: 10.1111/nup.12130.
- Williams, M. (2018). "Making Up Mechanisms in Realist Research." In *Doing Realist Research*, edited by N. Emmel, J. Greenhalgh, A. Manzano, M. Monaghan, and S. Dalkin, 25–40. London: Sage Publications.
- Willmott, R. (2000). The place of culture in organisation theory: introducing the morphogenetic approach. *Organisation* 7(1): 95–128.
- Wimelius, H., Mathiassen, L., Holmstrom, J., & Keil, M. (2021). 'A paradoxical perspective on technology renewal in digital transformation', *Information Systems Journal*, 31(1), pp. 198–225. DOI: 10.1111/isj.12307.
- Winter, R., & Schelp, J. (2008). Enterprise Architecture governance: the need for a business-to-IT approach. Paper presented at the 2008 ACM symposium on applied computing (SAC 2008), Fortaleza.
- Winter, K., Buckl, S., Matthes, F., & Schweda, C. M. (2010). Investigating the state-of-the-art in enterprise architecture management methods in literature and practice.

- Wodak, R., & Meyer, M. (Eds.). (2015). *Methods of critical discourse studies*. Sage.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2020, March 11). WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19 - 11 March 2020. <https://www.who.int/director-general/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19---11-march-2020>. (Accessed 31st May 2023).
- Wolff, J. (1983). *Aesthetics and the Sociology of Art*, Boston: George Allen and Unwin.
- Wong, G., Greenhalgh, T., Westhorp, G., & Pawson, R. (2014). Development of methodological guidance, publication standards and training materials for realist and meta-narrative reviews: the RAMESES (Realist and Meta-narrative Evidence Syntheses - Evolving Standards) project. *Health Serv Deliv Res*. Southampton (UK): NIHR Journals Library.
- Wong, G., Greenhalgh, T., Westhorp, G., Buckingham, J., & Pawson, R. (2013). RAMESES publication standards: Realist syntheses. *BMC Medicine*, 11, 21.
- Wong, G., Westhorp, G., Manzano, A., Greenhalgh, J., Jagosh, J., & Greenhalgh, T. (2016). RAMESES II reporting standards for realist evaluations. *BMC Medicine* 14(1): 96. DOI: 10.1186/s12916-016-0643-1.
- Wong, G., Westhorp, G., Pawson, R., & Greenhalgh, T. (2013b). "Realist synthesis". RAMESES training materials. London: The RAMESES Project.
- Wren, H. (2020). "What is digital transformation? Definition, Examples, Main Areas". Available at <https://www.zendesk.com/blog/digital-transformation/> [Accessed 3 January 2022].
- Wu, R. C. Y., & Lu, J. (2007). "Enterprise Integration Strategy of Interoperability," in *Advances and Innovations in Systems, Computing Sciences and Software Engineering*, K. Elleithy, Ed. Springer Netherlands, pp. 369–374.
- Wynn, Jr. D., & Williams, C. K. (2012). "Principles for conducting critical realist case study research in information systems". *MIS Quarterly* 36(3): 787–810. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijproman.2012.11.012.

- Yang, Y., Loog, M., & Xu, Z. (2018). Active learning using uncertainty information. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, 30(10), 3109-3121. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Yeo, K. T. (2002). Critical failure factors in information system projects. *International Journal of Project Management* 20 (2002) 241–246.
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and methods*. (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Yin, R. K. (2013). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. California: Sage Publications.
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (6th edn.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Ylimaki, T. (2006). Potential critical success factors for Enterprise Architecture. *Journal of Enterprise Architecture*, Vol. (4), pp. 29-40. Available at: https://jyx.jyu.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/41369/1/Article_CSFs_for_EA.pdf [Accessed 10 December 2021].
- Yoo, Y., Henfridsson, O., & Lyytinen, K. (2010). Research commentary—The new organizing logic of digital innovation: An agenda for information systems research. *Information Systems Research*, 21(4), 724–735.
- Yosinski, J., Clune, J., Bengio, Y., & Lipson, H. (2014). How transferable are features in deep neural networks? In *Advances in neural information processing systems* (pp. 3320-3328). [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].
- Zachman, J. A. (1987). “A framework for information systems architecture”. *IBM Syst. J.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 276–292.
- Zeghidour, N., Usunier, N., Kokkinos, I., Synnaeve, G., Liptchinsky, V., & Schatz, T. (2020). End-to-end speech recognition from the raw waveform. In *ICASSP 2020-2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (pp. 6314-6318). IEEE. doi:10.1109/ICASSP40776.2020.9054444.

Zhang, M., Chen, H., & Luo, A. (2018). A Systematic Review of Business-IT Alignment Research with Enterprise Architecture. *IEEE Access*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 6, pp. 18933–18944. Doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2819185.

Zhang, S., Yao, L., Sun, A., & Tay, Y. (2018). Deep learning based recommender system: A survey and new perspectives. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 52(1), 1-38. [Accessed: 20th May, 2023].

Zliobaite, I. (2015). On the relation between accuracy and fairness in binary classification. In *Fairness, accountability, and transparency in machine learning*.

Zliobaite, I., & Custers, B. (2016). Using sensitive personal data may be necessary for avoiding discrimination in data-driven decision models. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 24(2), 183-201.

9 APPENDIX A: ETHICAL APPROVAL FORM

Consent Form for Participation in a Research Study

The University of the West of Scotland

Title of Study: EXPLORING VALUE CREATION MECHANISMS IN ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE: A REALIST EVALUATION OF HEALTHCARE ORGANISATIONS EVIDENCED IN THE UK.

I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.

Description of the research and your participation

The researcher would like to invite you to participate in a research study conducted by Joshua Tadam. This research evaluates EA programmes to suggest critical failure and success factors that may affect their outcomes.

As a professional in technology, I would like to obtain your opinion about the management of Enterprise Architecture. Your role does not have to be Enterprise Architecture but your involvement in technology programme delivery within healthcare.

Your participation will involve taking part in an interview lasting between 35 mins to 60 mins, enabling the researcher to collect first-hand data for this research. The interview aims to obtain your opinion about how the programme was conducted.

Risks and discomforts

There are no known risks associated with this research. Concerning non-maleficence, the researcher will take all the necessary measures to ensure the wording of the research work doesn't in any way cause harm to anyone, group or organisation. And the researcher will continue to review the research work to resolve any aspect of the work that is considered controversial.

Potential benefits

There are no known direct benefits to you that would result from your participation in this research, except that this research will stir up interest in improving technology implementation outcomes. This research may help us to understand corporate compliance better.

Protection of confidentiality

- Your data will be protected under the Data Protection Act 2018. Data collected, including your name and contact details, will be stored on the UWS secure OneDrive account.
- I am bounded by the University of the West of Scotland's code of conduct and Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship. The university has ethically approved this research study.
- The researcher will ensure that every respondent's data is kept confidential, anonymised, and shared only with the researcher's doctoral thesis supervisor. Data collected will be kept digitally under role-based access authentication and authorisation to prevent unauthorised access to the interview.

The researcher will do everything possible to protect your privacy. Your identity will not be revealed in any publication resulting from this study. All information regarding your identity will be anonymised.

Voluntary participation

Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate, and you may withdraw your consent to participate at any time. You will not be affected in any way should you decide not to participate or withdraw from this study.

Contact information

If you have any questions or concerns about this study or if any problems arise, don't hesitate to contact Joshua Tedam at The University of the West of Scotland at B00354904@studentmail.uws.ac.uk or hgeec@hotmail.com. If you have any questions or concerns

about your rights as a research participant, don't hesitate to get in touch with The University of the West of Scotland ethics committee via BCIEthics@uws.ac.uk.

Consent

I have read this consent form and have been given the opportunity to ask questions. I give my consent to participate in this study.

Participant's signature _____ Date: _____

A copy of this consent form should be given to you.

10 APPENDIX B: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Research Participant Information Sheet		<i>The University of the West of Scotland</i>	
Study Title:	EXPLORING VALUE CREATION MECHANISMS IN ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE: A REALIST EVALUATION OF HEALTHCARE ORGANISATIONS EVIDENCED IN THE UK.		
Locality:	UK	Ethics committee ref:	BCIEthics@uws.ac.uk
Lead investigator:	Joshua Tedam	Contact phone number:	+447701312469

You are invited to participate in a study on "*EXPLORING VALUE CREATION MECHANISMS IN ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE: A REALIST EVALUATION OF HEALTHCARE ORGANISATIONS EVIDENCED IN THE UK.*" Whether or not you take part is your choice, and if you do not wish to participate, you do not have to give a reason for your decision. However, if you want to take part now but change your mind later, you can pull out of the study.

This Participant Information Sheet will help you decide if you would like to participate. It sets out why we are doing the study, what your participation would involve, the benefits and risks to you, and what would happen after the study ends. We will go through this information with you and answer any questions. You do not have to decide whether you will participate in this study today. Before you decide, you may want to discuss the study with other people, such as the principal investigator, the research supervisor, or the University ethics committee.

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to sign the Consent Form on the last page of this document. You will be given a copy of the Participant Information Sheet and the Consent Form.

This document is five (5) pages long, including the Consent Form.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

This study will help address the failure of most Enterprise Architecture initiatives to meet organisational expectations. It will help in digital transformation initiatives where Enterprise Architecture practice aligns technology with the organisational strategies, goals and objectives.

- The study aims to explore the critical failure factors and the critical success factors that may influence the outcome of Enterprise Architecture initiatives in healthcare organisations.
- Enterprise Architecture (EA) is a discipline that defines, organises, standardises, and documents the organisation's technology and all essential elements of the respective organisation, covering

relevant domains such as clinical and operational functions, digital application and data, and physical infrastructure or organisational.

EA also defines the relations and interactions between elements that belong to those domains, such as processes, functions, applications, events, data, or technologies.

- It explores how mechanisms within EA programs in context influence the outcomes paying particular attention to how practitioners act, why, by whom, and in what circumstances these outcomes are implemented.
- This business management research is self-funded by the researcher and constitutes a body of work towards a postgraduate research thesis at the University of the West of Scotland.

WHAT WILL MY PARTICIPATION IN THE STUDY INVOLVE?

- The study explores the impact of the Enterprise Architecture body of work on digital transformation in healthcare and requires participants in certain positions to give reliable information on strategic alignment using enterprise architecture within their organisation. Consequently, you have been selected to participate in this study because you fall within the category of participants for the studies because of your experience in technology management/use in your current or previous organisation. Participant profiles include departmental heads, chief information officers, clinicians, experts, Senior managers, Architects, directors, top management staff and those employees engaged in the operational management of technology implementation. For this crucial reason, participants will be selected using purposive sampling.
- Due to Covid-19 restrictions, all meeting interviews will be conducted online via Microsoft Teams or Zoom to eliminate transmission risks. The meeting interview data will be recorded and transcribed. The transcribed data will be coded and analysed using the NVIVO software.
- Your participation in this study will involve taking part in an interview to help obtain reliable data concerning enterprise architecture initiatives in technology programmes. Your nonparticipation limits the researcher's ability to obtain first-hand and reliable data to support this study and improve digital healthcare transformation.
- The interview process will last between 30 minutes to 1 hour. The researcher will send the initial invitation to participants, followed by an appointment to schedule an interview if they choose to participate.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS AND RISKS OF THIS STUDY?

- The researcher will ensure that all data collected from respondents are kept confidential and shared except with the researcher's thesis supervisor. Data collected will be stored on the secure UWS OneDrive to prevent unauthorised access to improve data protection.
- Concerning non-maleficence, the researcher will take all the necessary measures to ensure the wording of the research work does not cause harm to anyone, a group, or an organisation. Furthermore, the researcher will continue to review the research work to resolve any aspect of the work that is considered controversial.

WHO PAYS FOR THE STUDY?

- The participant will not incur any costs; the researcher will bear all costs associated with this study.

WHAT ARE MY RIGHTS?

- The researcher will seek the consent of the participants or respondents. The researcher will ensure that data is not obtained unethically by ensuring that respondents sign the consent form.
- The researcher will also give the respondents the right to withdraw their consent during the research.

WHAT HAPPENS AFTER THE STUDY OR IF I CHANGE MY MIND?

The researcher will inform respondents of the destruction of the document containing raw data collected from participants during the study.

WHOM DO I CONTACT FOR MORE INFORMATION OR IF I HAVE CONCERNS?

If you have any questions, concerns, or complaints about the study at any stage, you can contact:

Name: JOSHUA TEDAM Position: Lead Investigator Telephone number: [REDACTED] Email: [REDACTED]	The university ethics committee: [REDACTED]
--	---

Personal details withheld.

11 APPENDIX C: THE TOGAF ADM ARCHITECTURE DELIVERABLE

source: The Open Group. (2011). Architecture Deliverables. Available at <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/togaf91-doc/arch/chap36.html> [Accessed on 11 September 2021]

Architecture Deliverable	Output from ADM Phase	Input to ADM Phases
Architecture Building Blocks	F, H	A, B, C, D, E
Architecture Contract	-	-
Architecture Definition Document	B, C, D, E, F	C, D, E, F, G, H
Architecture Principles	Preliminary, A, B, C, D	Preliminary, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H
Architecture Repository	Preliminary	Preliminary, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, Requirements Management
Architecture Requirements	B, C, D, E, F, Requirements Management	C, D, Requirements Management
Architecture Roadmap	B, C, D, E, F	B, C, D, E, F
Architecture Vision	A and E	B, C, D, E, F, G, H,
Business Principles, Business Goals, and Business Drivers	Preliminary, A, B	A and B
Capability Assessment	A, E, F, G, H	B, C, D, E, F
Change Request		-
Communications Plan	A	B, C, D, E, F
Compliance Assessment	G	H
Implementation and Migration Plan	E, F	F
Implementation Governance Model	F	G, H
Organizational Model for Enterprise	Preliminary	Preliminary, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, Requirements Management
Request for Architecture Work	Preliminary, F, H	A, G
Requirements Impact Assessment	Requirements Management	Requirements Management
Solution Building Blocks	G	A, B, C, D, E, F, G
Statement of Architecture Work	A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H	B, C, D, E, F, G, H, Requirements Management
Tailored Architecture Framework	Preliminary, A	Preliminary, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, Requirements Management

12 APPENDIX D: TOGAF ARCHITECTURE DELIVERABLES

DESCRIPTIONS

Architecture Deliverable	Descriptions
Architecture Building Blocks	The Architecture documents and models from the enterprise's Architecture Repository serve as architecture building blocks.
Architecture Contract	Architecture contracts are cooperative agreements between development partners and sponsors on an architecture's deliverables, quality, and fitness-for-purpose. Effective architectural governance will ensure the successful execution of these agreements.
Architecture Definition Document	<p>The Architecture Definition Document is the delivery container for the project's key architectural artefacts as well as critical associated information. The Architectural Definition Document covers all architecture domains (business, data, application, and technology) as well as all essential architecture states (baseline, transition, and target).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Transition Architecture depicts the company at a key architectural stage between the Baseline and Target Architectures. Transition Architectures are used to explain transitional Target Architectures that are required for the Target Architecture to be realised effectively. • The Architecture Definition Document works in tandem with the Architecture Requirements Specification to achieve the following goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Architecture Definition Document gives a qualitative assessment of the solution and is intended to explain the architect's objective. ○ The Architectural Requirements Specification gives a quantitative picture of the solution by defining quantifiable requirements that must be satisfied throughout architecture implementation.

<p>Architecture Principles</p>	<p>Principles are broad rules and standards that are meant to be long-lasting and seldom changed, and they influence and support how an organisation goes about completing its objective.</p> <p>Principles, in turn, may be simply one component of an organised collection of concepts that collectively define and lead the company, from values to actions and outcomes.</p>
--------------------------------	--

Architecture Deliverable	Descriptions
<p>Architecture Repository</p>	<p>The Architecture Repository serves as a repository for all architecture-related initiatives inside the organisation. The repository enables projects to manage deliverables, discover reusable components, and disseminate outcomes to stakeholders and other stakeholders.</p>
<p>Architecture Requirements</p>	<p>The Design Requirements Specification contains a series of quantitative assertions outlining what an implementation project must perform to comply with the architecture. Typically, an Architecture Requirements Specification will be a substantial component of an implementation contract or contract for a complete Architecture Definition.</p> <p>As previously stated, the Architecture Requirements Specification is a companion document to the Architecture Definition Document with a similar goal:</p> <p>The Architecture Definition Document conveys the architect's objective by providing a qualitative assessment of the solution.</p> <p>The Architecture Requirements Specification gives a quantitative picture of the solution by outlining quantifiable criteria that must be satisfied throughout architecture implementation.</p>

Architecture Roadmap	The Architecture Roadmap identifies specific work packages that will achieve the Target Architecture and plots them on a timeline to demonstrate the transition from the Baseline Architecture to the Target Architecture. The Architecture Roadmap demonstrates the commercial value of specific work packages at each step. As intermediate phases, transition architectures required to actualize the Target Architecture properly are established. The Architecture Roadmap is produced progressively across Phases E and F, using input from easily recognisable roadmap components from Phases B, C, and D inside the ADM.
Architecture Vision	Early in the ADM cycle, the Architecture Vision is produced. It summarises the changes to the enterprise that will result from the successful implementation of the Target Architecture. The Architecture Vision's goal is to offer key stakeholders an officially agreed-upon conclusion. Early agreement on the result allows architects to concentrate on the details required to verify feasibility. By offering a simplified version of the comprehensive Architecture Definition, an Architecture Vision facilitates stakeholder communication.
Business Principles, Business Goals, and Business Drivers	Business principles, objectives, and motivations give context to architectural work by articulating the enterprise's demands and methods of functioning. Many aspects that are not considered by the architectural discipline may have important ramifications for the way architecture is constructed.

Architecture Deliverable	Descriptions
Capability Assessment	Before commencing a thorough Architecture Definition, it is important to establish the enterprise's baseline and target capability level. This Capability Assessment may be investigated on several levels:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the enterprise's overall capability level? Where does the organisation want to improve or optimise capability? What architectural focal areas will support the enterprise's planned development? • What is the enterprise's IT function's capabilities or maturity level? What are the proper style, degree of formality, and quantity of detail for the architectural project to match the IT organization's culture and capability? What are the most probable consequences of carrying out the architectural project in terms of design governance, operational governance, skills, and organisational structure? • What are the enterprise architecture function's capabilities and maturity? What architectural assets are there currently? Are they up to date and correct? What criteria and reference models must be taken into account? Is it conceivable that there would be possibilities to generate reusable assets throughout the architectural project? • Where capacity gaps exist, how prepared can the firm adapt to achieve the desired competence? What are the risks to change, cultural hurdles, and other factors to consider besides the fundamental capacity gap?
<p>Change Request</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As new facts become known throughout architecture development, it is conceivable that the initial Architecture Definition and requirements are insufficient to finish the construction of a solution. External circumstances, such as market considerations, changes in corporate strategy, and new technological prospects, may also provide chances to expand and modify the design. In these cases, implementation projects must either stray from the recommended architectural approach or obtain scope extensions.

- In these cases, a Change Request may be issued to initiate a new cycle of architectural development.

Architecture Deliverable	Descriptions
Communications Plan	Enterprise designs include massive amounts of complicated and interrelated data. Enterprise design relies on effectively distributing targeted information to the relevant stakeholders at the right time. Creating an architectural communications strategy enables this communication to occur within a planned and regulated procedure.
Compliance Assessment	Once an architecture has been designed, it must be governed through implementation to ensure that the original Architecture Vision is achieved and that any implementation learnings are fed back into the architecture process. Periodic compliance assessments of implementation projects offer a method for reviewing project progress and ensuring that design and implementation are on track to meet strategic and architectural goals.
Implementation and Migration Plan	The Implementation and Migration Plan outlines the tasks that will be undertaken to actualize the Target Architecture. A crucial component of the Implementation and Migration Plan is the Implementation and Migration Strategy, which identifies the approach to change. Executable projects are organised into controlled portfolios and programmes in the Implementation and Migration Plan.
Implementation Governance Model	<p>After defining an architecture, it is vital to outline how the Transition Architecture that implements the architecture will be regulated throughout implementation. A governance framework is likely to be in place within businesses that have established architectural functions, but particular procedures, organisations, roles, responsibilities, and measurements may need to be created on a project-by-project basis.</p> <p>The Implementation Governance Model guarantees that a project moving into implementation also easily moves into proper architectural governance.</p>

Organizational Model for Enterprise	The company's proper organisational structure, roles, and responsibilities must back an effective architectural framework. The establishment of boundaries between distinct enterprise architecture practitioners, as well as the governance connections that bridge these borders, is very important.
-------------------------------------	--

Architecture Deliverable	Descriptions
Request for Architecture Work	The sponsoring organisation sends this document to the architecture organisation to initiate the architecture development cycle. Requests for Architecture Work may be generated due to the Preliminary Phase, authorised architecture Change Requests, or terms of reference for architecture work derived from migration planning. In general, all of the information in this paper should be of the highest quality.
Requirements Impact Assessment	A Requirements Impact Assessment evaluates the current architectural requirements and specifications to determine what modifications should be made and the consequences of those changes. Throughout the ADM, new architectural information is gathered. As this data is collected, new facts may emerge that invalidate current components of the design.
Solution Building Blocks	building elements for execution from the enterprise's Architecture Repository
Statement of Architecture Work	The Statement of Architecture Work defines the scope and methodology utilised to finish an architectural development cycle. The Statement of Architecture Work is generally the document against which the success of the architectural project is judged, and it may serve as the foundation for a

	contractual agreement between the provider and the consumer of architecture services.
Tailored Architecture Framework	<p>TOGAF offers an industry-standard architectural framework that may be employed in various organisations. However, two degrees of customising are required before TOGAF can be utilised successfully in an architectural project.</p> <p>To begin, the TOGAF model must be customised for corporate integration. Integration with project and process management frameworks, terminology customization, presentational style creation, and selection, setup, and deployment of architectural tools are all part of this tailoring. The formality and intricacy of any frameworks used should also be consistent with other business contextual elements such as culture, stakeholders, commercial enterprise architecture models, and the current degree of Architecture Capability.</p> <p>After adapting the framework to the firm, more tailoring is required to design the framework for the individual architectural project. This degree of tailoring will pick relevant deliverables and artefacts to fit the project's and stakeholders' demands.</p>

From: The Open Group. (2011). Architecture Deliverables.

13 APPENDIX E: ADDITIONAL DIAGRAMS

Figure 13.1. Superimposing the Transformational Model of Social Action in EA programme action, the Morphogenetic/static cycle, the Context-Mechanism-Outcome Configuration, The TOGAF ADM and the Strategic Alignment Model.

